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**„The Language of Religious Dissent: Comparative
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Authors)“**

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To my parents

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INTRODUCTION

In a letter written in ca. 846 to Eberhard of Friuli, Hrabanus Maurus asks him to expel Gottschalk from Friuli since he considered his teaching on predestination to be a dangerous one that could possibly provoke scandal, and labelled his brand of predestination a sect (*secta*), opposite to the *recta fides*. This could serve as a starting point and an example demonstrating which circumstances could have led to exile – the potential threat of *scandalum*, caused by this monk keen on novelties and later judged to be a heretic, as observed in this case.

The aim of this thesis is to demonstrate the correlation of the selected and most representative 9th-century Frankish and Byzantine texts constituting pivotal threads in semantic fields knitted around religious dissent. Furthermore, this thesis is threaded around the very notions of heresy, dissent and theological debates in Byzantium and Francia, as opposed to the official Christian doctrine - heralded by the *Ecclesia*, through its quasi generic entanglement with the *imperium* - which were unquestionably related to social *realia* and attempts to reach and preserve social consensus and unity.

From the coronation of Charlemagne, the hymn *Laudes Regiae*, inherited from the Roman times, came into the usage and opened the era of the Carolingian ruler-symbolism through emphasizing the connection between the ruler and the Church. Namely, the acclaimed formula *Christus vincit, Christus regnat, Christus imperat* has thus embodied the impermeable bond holding the two powers, ecclesiastical and royal, intrinsically together. Moreover, theology, history and politics became more enhancingly intertwined: theological debates which arose in the 9th-century were combatted in respect to historical and political contexts, in which they were embedded. The situation was similar in Byzantium likewise: As Patriarch Photius stated in one of his epistles, the patriarch and the emperor represented the heads of the Church and state. These two persons – embodying authorities of the world order – worked cohesively and in harmony, with the patriarch looking after the souls of the people, and the emperor being responsible for the well-being of his subjects. The analogous view, condensed in the Gelasian doctrine – dispatched to Emperor Atanasius I by Pope Gelasius I in 494 – was attested in Francia as well.

The language and terminology became the key associates in conveying this strong message of unity; thus, this tendency was also reflected in texts of 9th-century authors. Among others, symbolism of the body and bodily parts was underlined: the body of believers was contrasted to the body of Antichrist, composed of those who fell out of the union with Church. The heretics

were portrayed with diversified and rich terminological means. The analysis of textual and literary tools employed in describing religious dissent will be presented in the following pages, in attempt to unveil the very language of religious dissent. The questions of how the heretics saw themselves, as well as how they understood the concept of heresy, compared to the views of those who accused them of heresy have been put forward; the repertoire of the authors in dealing with religious dissent was analyzed, as well as the recurrent *topoi*, metaphorical language, and textual patterns.

Therefore, the import of this dissertation is to reposition the study of the 9th-century Carolingian and Byzantine authors in close connection to the philological domain as well as to the historical and theological settings their texts originated in, and to re-enhance its role in medieval scholarly research. The aim of the research is to synthesize threads linking Carolingian and Byzantine theological discourses, and to present them to the international scientific community.

One of my objectives was to position Carolingian and Byzantine perceptions of religious dissent in a philological frame, and incorporate into a cohesive *ensemble* those fragmented elements often treated separately in the fields of history, philology and theology. The further essential aspects of this research imply the coalescence between Carolingian and Byzantine philology and theology, by placing it in the historical context of those times, as well as by analyzing the nuances and resonances of the borderlines and intertwining between heresy and orthodoxy, officially accepted and unaccepted discourse, through terminological and literary analysis in the first place.

As this thesis focuses upon the chosen texts containing topics related to religious dissent, and the terminology used in describing it - in the Frankish lands of the middle of the 9th century, and on the comparative approach with that of the 9th-century Byzantine authors, one of the aims of this thesis is to underline the role of the language as a tool for demarcating *recto-* from the *falso- docti*, while delving into the situations propelled by religious dissent in the 9th-century Francia and Byzantium.

Political nature of Carolingian and Byzantine doctrinal debates is demonstrated through the case-studies presented here which traced contours of these debates and provided “justifications” for different interpretations of doctrines. Namely, this thesis also aims at demonstrating to

which extent the language of the selected and analysed authors was influenced by political and historical events. In specific times marked by intense political shifts characteristic of the mid-9th century, language and terminology of can be observed as a bridge linking theology and politics.

Furthermore, the question arises as to how far the theology of the “dissenting authors” conformed to the theology of their contemporaries. Namely, the perception and conceptualization of hierarchy and dissent, obedience and disobedience, authority and Free Will played a central role in the highly self-reflective discourse of this epoch. Therefore, a close comparison between the chosen texts in respect to semantic environment of *hierarchia*, *auctoritas*, *potestas*, *concordia/discordia*, *unitas*, *consensus/dissensus*, or *oboedientia/disoboedientia* could help clarify one of the deep historical problems of this epoch: the hiatus between the efforts to reform and control the Frankish and Byzantine societies, and the deviations and aberrations that necessarily accompany it.

The Theodosian and Justinian Code convey important information on heresies and attitude toward heretics, as attested in the periods preceding the 9th-century. Numerous and diverse are the names of the heretics, but they share the same deceitfulness, according to the Theodosian Code: *diversa sunt nomina (haereticorum), sed una perfidia*.

For Hincmar, Archbishop of Reims, heretics are those who persist in their erroneous doctrine and resist correction of their pestiferous and deadly teachings. It is in his refutation of the theology of Gottschalk of Orbais, that the core of Hincmar’s narrative on the heretics lay. Gottschalk is seen as a heretic and a liar, who utters perverse words, as is the case with heretics.

Hrabanus Maurus, for example, contrasts the terms *haec secta nefanda* to the concept of *recta fides/incontaminata religio*, whereas in the writings of Gottschalk, the “true religion” is alluded to as *secta vera*.

Jonas of Orléans makes an equation between the Latin word *secta* and Greek *haeresis* (αἵρεσις), by stating that the Latin word *secta* corresponds to the Greek word *haeresis*.

On the other hand, we discover more on Gottschalk’s self-defense and the accusations he directed towards those who were his main opponents. Namely, Gottschalk has designated them as heretics; for him, Hincmar was seen as a heretic, the enemy of truth and friend of falsehood.

Various usages and connotations of the terms and definitions employed for heresies and heretics were widely spread in Byzantine literature likewise. Besides, the recurrence to *topoi* and *clichés*

in portraying heretics has also been attested, as in the Latin texts. The heretics are said to share the same insanity which binds them, and have been portrayed as repulsive and impure.

Throughout his epistles, Theodore the Studite refers to heresy as the greatest sin of all. Theodore equates heresy with impiousness and heterodoxy. Photius, patriarch of Constantinople, equates heresy with error of impiety and sees it as the greatest of all sins.

Another important *facette* which should be underlined, is that heresy has been defined in respect to tradition – reaching back to the Holy Scriptures and the Church Fathers – representing any deviation or non-compliance to it.

The first section of the thesis examines and outlines the basis for the study which then follows. These precepts which constitute the foundation of the entire thesis, are established and developed upon the Early Christian writings, mostly those from the Church Fathers (Irenaeus of Lyon, Augustine of Hippo, Justin Martyr, Gregory the Great, Isidore of Seville). Thus, in the first part of the thesis, the notions such as definition of religious dissent have been laid. The chapters ensue with insights into the early heresiological literature, and with attempts to classify religious dissent. An analysis of the specific language and terminology used in demarcating and structuring religious dissent is presented, notably with the accent put on the metaphorical description of heresies. Thus, the narrative on heresies which follows the criterion related to the language of religious dissent, with the accent placed on the particularities of terminology and its metaphorical aspect, but also in relation to the specificities of literary language employed in describing paganism, as positioned in comparative aspect to the language of heresy, has been put forward.

The second section of this thesis concentrates on the carefully selected texts, pregnant with most representative themes threaded around the semantic field of religious dissent. These have been designed as to encompass some of the pivotal 9th-century Greek and Latin texts, judged as essential in knitting the tissues of the principal topics, which marked the Christian *Oikoumene* of those years. The attempt to structure these themes has yielded results in the form of a “road-map” representing the ascending line of sequences, starting with dissent, and ending with exile, through the intermediary “stepping stones”, constituted of specific descriptive features of religious dissent, given in the frame of metaphorical language employed in delineating religious dissent.

Ensuing after the exposition on the definition of heresy and import of metaphorical language, the remaining intermediary points elucidate the following concepts: “adulterating” the word of God – as presented in Hincmar’s portrayal of Gottschalk as a heretic who falsely interprets the words of Augustine, and, among others, Photius, who accuses the Manichaeans in 871-872 of spiritual adultery towards the word of God; “old-new heresies” – as presented in the account of Photius, referring to the Iconoclasts as the “New Manichaeans”; “innovation: danger of novelties” – as demonstrated in the example of the Byzantines, blaming the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria to have brought innovations into the tradition of the Fathers and the dogma of the procession of the Holy Spirit, during the 860’s; “*rustici* and *simplices*” – epitomized in the danger of heresy for the simple people, as strongly accentuated in the treatise “On the Cult of Images” of Jonas of Orléans, composed in the late 820’s; “danger of scandal” – as shown on numerous occasions in the texts originated in Francia primarily, during the reign of Louis the Pious. The concept of *Nubia Christi* as opposed to the *Meretrix* was significantly insisted upon in the epistles of Pope Nicholas I and Photius, for example; the bodily unity symbolism, including the symbolism of the limbs of the body of the Church constituted yet another potent and frequently present theme in the heated theological debates in both Francia and Byzantium. The issue of repentance, as the last possible remedy preventing severance from the body of the Church, is tackled in the chapter II.11, to be culminated in the final stage analyzing issues related to exile. Apart from the chapter on the importance of reaching and preserving the unity within the Church and state, another chapter of the second segment is dedicated to the exposition on the concept of disobedience, being a key-criterion leading to dissent, and a common denominator of various types of dissent, as observed in the example not directly related to the religious sphere – but to the divorce-cases of Lothar II in Francia, and Constantine VI in Byzantium. The closing chapters are focused upon severance from the body of believers, culminating in exile, epitomizing the most severe form of severance.

The time-scale in which this thesis delves represents a period of a political and social crisis in the Carolingian Empire. The integrative power of the Frankish imperium tended to be fragmented and regionalized. Thus, one can detect intense efforts to enforce cohesive and integrative powers in the 9th century. The Predestination debate sprang out in the years approaching the middle of the century, with its carriers, Gottschalk of Orbais, Hincmar of Reims and Hrabanus Maurus, who came to the forefront of the heated theological confrontations of the epoch. As a consequence, Gottschalk, who did not comply with official theological view, was labelled a heretic upon the Synod of Mainz held in 848. On the other hand, the Iconoclastic crisis severely hit the Byzantine Empire in the first half of the 9th century

and provoked turbulent times as well, echoed in the writings of Patriarch Photius and Theodore the Studite. Thus, the chosen texts and their language have been positioned in the context of social, political and theological situation in the 9th-century Frankish and Byzantine Empires, and explored in the scope of the climate in which the ruling ecclesiastical and political circles considered “outsiders” discourses dangerous. These discourses have thus been observed in the time of social and political instability, through drawing interconnections between history, politics, theology and philology.

Due to the considerable scale of the entire corpus of 9th-century Greek and Latin text, relevant for the scope of the study, I have decided to concentrate only upon the predominant and distinguishing events which have, to a significant extent, shaped theological discourses, but also historical and political debates and aspirations of the given period. Thence, the core issues explored here include the main theological controversies of the 9th century in Byzantium and Francia: the Predestination controversy with its apex from 849-851, Iconoclasm (717-843, but especially the second period of Iconoclastic controversy, from 814 to 842), the Moechian controversy (predominantly the second phase from 806-807 and the culminating point for this thesis, following the Synod of 809), and the *Filioque* controversy, with its peak in the mid-860's.

The Iconoclast controversy over the usage of religious images encompasses two periods in the history of Byzantium: the first one lasted between ca. 726 and 787, whereas the second one occurred between 814 and 842. Iconoclasm started with the removal of the icon of Christ from the Bronze Gate at the entrance to the imperial palace in Constantinople, as ordered by Emperor Leo III, and ended in 867, with the solemn introduction of the Icon of the Virgin in the Hagia Sophia. The second phase of Iconoclasm involved, among others, Photius and Theodore the Studite, but also echoed in the Frankish realms, reflected in the writings of Walahfridus Strabo, Jonas of Orléans, and Claudius of Turin.

The Moechian controversy, named after the Greek term designating adultery, *μοιχεία*, began upon the re-marriage of the emperor Constantine VI in 795, after the expulsion of his legitimate spouse. The priest Joseph performed the ceremony, in spite of the vehement opposition of the monks. The second phase of the controversy, which is of interest for this work, encompassed the period from 806 onwards, when the priest Joseph was rehabilitated. In the years that followed the dispute between patriarch Nicephorus and Theodore the Studite occurred, resulting in Theodore's exile, a so-called “Moechian Synod” of 809 acknowledged

the legitimacy of the second union of Constantine VI. The end of the controversy took place in 812, upon the deposition of the priest Joseph.

The *Filioque* controversy reflected the important dispute between Byzantium and the Latin West, with its climax provoked by the events which occurred at the time of the conversion of the Bulgarians around the year 866. The Byzantines accused the Latins of the introduction of the teaching on the *Filioque* doctrinal question – the procession of the Holy Spirit from Son as well – imposed by the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria. The practices introduced by the Latin missionaries were consequently condemned by a local synod of 867 in Constantinople. The decisions of the Synod aimed at the extirpation of the innovations brought in by the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria. Pope Nicholas I and Photius, Patriarch of Constantinople became involved in this heated debate, which marked the very significant *hiatus* between the Church of Rome and the Church of Constantinople.

The Predestination controversy first appeared at the end of the 4th and in the beginning of the 5th century, with Augustine and Pelagius as the main opponents in this strife over the role of grace and free will. This debate re-emerged and marked mid-9th century Francia, with Gottschalk at its forefront, proclaiming the doctrine of twin predestination. The Synod, presided by Louis the German, which was held in Mainz in 848, condemned Gottschalk as a heretic for his interpretation of divine predestination. According to the synod's decisions, Gottschalk was expelled to the territory under the rule of Charles the Bald, in the archbishopric of Reims. The Synod of Quierzy (849), called by Hincmar, archbishop of Reims, and presided by Charles the Bald, condemned Gottschalk as a heretic. As a consequence, Gottschalk was sent to the abbey of Hautvillers, in the archbishopric of Reims.

At the time when the predestination controversy reached its culmination (849-851), the political crisis was growing stronger in the Carolingian realm. The main protagonists of the controversy included Hincmar of Reims, Hrabanus Maurus, Prudentius of Troyes, Lupus of Ferrières, and Florus of Lyon. The representatives of the official theology found themselves united against Gottschalk. Gottschalk spent the last years of his life in confinement in Hautvillers, but nevertheless had the support of the local monks in the propagation of his writings. Even Eriugena was involved in the controversy (850/1), which later spread to the south of the Carolingian lands as well. Synods were organized in Soissons (853), Valence (855), and Tusey (860), which marked the end of the controversy.

Nevertheless, it is important to stress that these controversies did not represent the main topic of this thesis. In other words, they have been treated only to the extent to which they correspondingly represent the pivotal topics and tendencies I analyze and within the main discursive lines I elaborate, leading towards the more comprehensive aim of this thesis as a whole, and to the desired outcomes – towards the comprehension of what could be framed as the “language of religious dissent”.

Bearing in mind that the scope of this thesis is quite exhaustive, it was necessary to limit my study to selected authors and topics, which are the most relevant and pivotal. I have chosen to concentrate upon the 9th century since, in my opinion, it offers a wide range of insufficiently explored examples pertaining to numerous and various types of contacts between the Byzantine and Frankish Empires. These provide a wealth of materials for confronting the manner in which both the Frankish and Byzantine authors expressed themselves in relation to heresies and, particularly, allow us to see the eventual mutual relations and interconnections between those two *modi*. In the background of these contacts, quite often lie questions relating to the semantic fields of heresy. It is this aspect in particular which has not been sufficiently explored previously.

In the course of my thesis, I employ the term “heresy” mostly when the authors I analyze have themselves resorted to it, or else in the modern sense of the word. In fact, it might be more suitable to use the term “religiously divergent/dissenting – non-conforming to the official definition of doctrine” instead. Nevertheless, due to the concise overview of these, often complex, topics, I have opted to use the option – “religious dissent” and this approach to the problematics. Namely, the notion *haeresis* is moreover a source-based term.

By positioning medieval heresy in the wider spectrum of dissent, it becomes clearly observable that heresy itself was seen as embodying dissent by its very being – dissent, seen as a non-acceptance of the norm, defiance of the authorities proscribing the norm, as well as in a wider sense – dissent in respect to order, convention and tradition. Consequently, in this work, the

accent will be put not only on religious dissent, but rather on a more encompassing examination of the semantic fields and complex notions of dissent which were discursively connected to correct and incorrect expressions of faith. Therefore, the semantic fields threaded around the terms of *haeresis* will be brought forward and interrogated. It is therefore, the more extensive scope of semantic field of dissent that I wish to examine here, and in doing so demonstrate, that it is discursively closely related to the semantic field of erroneous faith.

I DEFINING HERESIES AND RELIGIOUS DISSENT

I.1. DEFINING HERESY AND RELIGIOUS DISSENT in respect to *recta fides*

In the opening chapter, an attempt of defining heresy and religious dissent will be given, in respect to the Early Christian authors in the first place.

Heresy (*ἡ αἵρεσις*), a word of Greek origin, was used by the Latin speakers as well. It originally did not refer to the modern meaning of the word, nor the latter transferal to Latin. It designated a choice, an inclination, a plan, an opinion. The term itself comes from the verb *αἰρέω*, “to choose”. The majority of the terms linked to the semantic field of heresy and orthodoxy has also been taken from the Greek and was likewise applied in Latin. Interestingly, the Latins did not translate the relevant Greek terms into Latin, but rather used them as they appeared in Greek (nevertheless, there are some exceptions: Iconoclasts, Iconophiles, translated from the Greek *οἱ Εἰκονομάχοι, οἱ Εἰκονόφιλοι*).

The term “heresy” connotes, originally and etymologically, both a choice and the thing chosen, the meaning being narrowed to the selection of religious or political doctrines, adherence to parties in Church or State, often indicating the opinion contrary to the one officially acknowledged. The more “actualized” meaning of the word was given by Irenaeus, bishop of Lyon (c. 120/140 – c. 200/203) in his work composed in the 2nd century AD and entitled *Contra Haereses* (“Against Heresies”), with the aim of portraying his opponents in the first centuries of the Christian era. In his tract, Irenaeus opposed the orthodox (from *ὀρθός*, “straight”, and *δόξα*, “belief”) teachings to the doctrine of the Gnostics, whom he treated as heretics¹. The term was also used by other (mainly Christian) authors, such as Josephus, St. Justin, early Christian Apologist (c. 100 – c. 165), St. Thomas, St. Augustine (354 – 430), bishop of Hippo (396 – 430)². Nevertheless, it would be important to underline the fact that, in the course of the centuries, this notion has been often employed in a manner which intertwined with every given particular political and intellectual climate, with the aspirations of the ruling circles to detach

¹ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses Libri Quinque* (ed. J.-P. Migne, *Patrologia Graeca* 7A) 433–1118.

² For more detailed information on heresiologies, see below, in the next chapter (I.2.); Augustine wrote substantially against heresies; therefore, I shall mention only some of his works on this topic: *Contra Donatistas* (ed. Migne, *Patrologia Latina* 43) 107–244; *Adversus Quinque Haereses* (ed. Migne, *Patrologia Latina* 42) 1099–1116; *Contra Epistolam Manichaei* (ed. Migne, *Patrologia Latina* 42) 173–206; *Contra Sermonem Arianorum* (ed. Migne, *Patrologia Latina* 42) 683–708; *De Gestis Pelagi* (ed. Migne, *Patrologia Latina* 44) 319–360; *De Haeresibus* (ed. Migne, *Patrologia Latina* 42) 21–50.

and demarcate themselves from the “others”, considered to be opposed from their “straight” path of correct doctrine, discourse or attitude³.

Augustine provides a definition of heresy: it represents the deviation, opposed to the Christian faith: *...dogmata deviare contraria fidei Christianae, et Christianam nominis obumbratione fallentia*⁴. The heretics are opposed to the truth, and they abound with numerous false doctrines: *...haeretici a veritate dissentiunt...multis falsis dogmatibus pleni sunt*⁵.

The heretical teachings are referred to as poisons, and should be avoided: *...haeretica venena vitemus*⁶.

Augustine enumerates heresies⁷. Furthermore, when opening his exposition on heresies, Augustine mentions *Panarion* (composed between 374 – 377) of Epiphanius, bishop of Salamis (c. 315 – 403), in which the author enumerated 80 heresies, and states that it is difficult to define heresy⁸. He ensues with enlisting the 88 heresies, with shorter descriptions and specifications pertaining to each and every one of them.

While Augustine refers to philosophical schools as sects, he employs the same term, *secta*, for heresies as well. It is important to note, that Augustine equals *secta* to *haeresis*⁹.

The Manichaean doctrine is insane: *insana doctrina; deviantes nomen insaniae*¹⁰. He refers to the Manichaean doctrine as to a sect, *secta*¹¹.

Definitions of heresy are present in Theodosian and Justinian’s Code¹², and debated at the Ecumenical Synods¹³. The heralds of the anti-heretical polemical literature in Byzantium were John of Damascus, a prominent theologian, monk, and a philosopher (c. 675 – 749),

³ Cf. M. Eliade, *Istorija verovanja i religijskih ideja* (Beograd 2003); Original : *Histoire des croyances et des idées religieuses*, 2. De Gantama Bouddha au triomphe du christianisme (Paris 1980); 3. De Mahomet a l’âge des Reformes (Paris 1983); here Eliade, *Histoire des croyances* 2, 310 – 313.

⁴ Augustine of Hippo, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 21.

⁵ Augustine, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 49.

⁶ Augustine, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 50.

⁷ Augustine, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 24–25.

⁸ Augustine, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 23; for a more detailed analysis of *Panarion*, see below, chapter I.2. and I.3.

⁹ Augustine, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 33, 47.

¹⁰ Augustine, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 34.

¹¹ Augustine, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 36.

¹² More in detail on the Justinian’s Code, see below; A. Rigo, *Orthodoxy and heresy in Byzantium: the definition and notion of orthodoxy, and some other studies on the heresies and the no-Christian Religions* (Roma 2010) 13.

¹³ Cf. *The First Seven Ecumenical Councils [History and Canons]*, *Patrologia Latina Conciliaria Oecumenica*, ed. Ph. Schaff, *Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers*, II, 14, Christian Classics Ethereal Library (2009); <http://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf214.toc.html>, 23/08/2017.

Germanus I, Constantinopolitan patriarch (715-730), in his *Synodikon of Orthodoxy*¹⁴, Theodore the Studite, abbot of the Studion monastery and a renowned figure in theological disputes of the end of the 8th and the first decades of the 9th century (759 – 826), as well as the patriarchs of Constantinople – Nicephorus (806 - 815) and Photius (858 – 867; 877 – 886). In Francia, heretical issues were vividly debated on several occasions, when religiously dissenting opinions appeared¹⁵. In the 9th-century theology, the orthodox faith was defended by Hincmar (c. 806 – 882; archbishop of Reims from 845), Hrabanus Maurus (c. 780 – 856; archbishop of Mainz from 847), and others¹⁶. In the Carolingian realm, as well as in Byzantium, the struggle for the correct doctrine and against heresy became the pillar stone of the unity of the Empire¹⁷.

The Theodosian Code (*Codex Theodosianus*), was organized in a form of a compilation of the Roman Law in the fifth century, by Emperor Theodosius II. It included legal precepts related to the propagation of the Christian Creed from the times of Emperor Constantine. Nevertheless, it encompassed laws from earlier times as well. The *Corpus Iuris Civilis* assembled under Emperor Justinian represented a sort of continuation of the Theodosian Code. Both the Theodosian and Justinian Codes had a high impact on medieval policies, laws and theology. One of the most important features these codices brought in, was the officialization of the Christian religion and the dismissal of other religions as being illegal¹⁸.

The importance of the analysis of the Theodosian and Justinian Codes in relation to heresies is manifold in this thesis: it will form the basis for the elaboration of the topics relating to the

¹⁴ J. Gouillard, *Le Synodicon de l'Orthodoxie*. Edition et commentaire, *Travaux et Mémoires* 1967 (2) 1-316, here 53.

¹⁵ Cf. M. de Jong/I. van Renswoude, Introduction: Carolingian cultures of dialogue, debate and disputation, in: *EME* 25,1 (2017) 6–18; I. van Renswoude, The art of disputation: dialogue, dialectic and debate around 800, in: *EME* 25,1 (2017) 38–53; W. Pezé, Doctrinal debate and social control in the Carolingian age: the predestination controversy (840s – 60s), in: *EME* 25, 1 (2017) 85–101.

¹⁶ W. Ullman, *The Carolingian Renaissance and the Idea of Kingship* (London 1969) 140–144, on the difference of the Eastern and Western Christian faith and the authenticity of the Western one; *Opus Caroli Regis Contra Synodum (Libri Carolini)* (ed. A. Freeman, *MGH Conc.* 2, suppl. 1, Hannover 1998) 20.

¹⁷ On the importance of the unity principle in combating heresies, see below, chapter II.10.

¹⁸ I. Gothofredus ed., *Codex Theodosianus cum perpetuis commentariis Jacobi Gothofredi* (Leipzig 1736–1743; Nachdruck 1975); Th. Mommsen/P. Meyer, *Theodosiani libri XVI cum constitutionibus Sirmondianis et leges novellae ad Theodosianum pertinentes* (Berlin 1905; Re-print 1954, 1970); I. Gothofredus, *Codex Theodosianus* 16,8,1–29. Übersetzt und bearbeitet von R. Frohne (Bern/Frankfurt/New York/Paris 1991; *Europäische Hochschulschriften*, III, 453); C. Pharr: *The Theodosian Code. And Novels. And the Sirmondian Constitutions. A Translation with Commentary, Glossary, and Bibliography* (Princeton 1952); J. Harris/I. Wood ed., *The Theodosian Code. Studies in the Imperial Law of Late Antiquity* (London 1993); P. Jörs, *Codex Theodosianus*, in: *Paulys Realencyclopädie der classischen Altertumswissenschaft (RE)*, IV, 1 (Stuttgart 1900) 170–173; I. Kroppenber, *Der gescheiterte Codex: Überlegungen zur Kodifikationsgeschichte des Codex Theodosianus*. In: *Rechtsgeschichte (Rg): Zeitschrift des Max-Planck-Instituts für europäische Rechtsgeschichte* 10 (2007) 112–126.

subject-specific fields of study and to particular case-studies related to the selected 9th-century authors and their texts, which will be scrutinized in the following sections of this work.

The Theodosian Code offers definitions of the notion of heretic. These are described as “those persons who may be discovered to deviate, even in a minor point of doctrine, from the tenets and the path of the Catholic religion are included under the designation of heretics and must be subject to the sanctions which have been issued against them”.

Haereticorum vocabulo continentur et latis adversus eos sanctionibus debent subcumbere, qui vel levi argumento iudicio catholicae religionis et tramite detecti fuerint deviare. Ideoque experientia tua heuresium haereticum nec in numero sanctissimorum antistitum habendum esse cognoscat¹⁹.

Furthermore, the Theodosian Code promulgates one Catholic worship, and one salvation:

...Una sit catholica veneratio, una salus sit, trinitatis par sibi que congruens sanctitas expetatur²⁰.

On the other hand, the heresies are compared to crime: for example, the heresies of Priscillianists and Phrygians shall be considered a public crime, since anything committed against “divine religion redounds to the detriment of all”.

Quid de donatistis sentiremus, nuper ostendimus. Praecipue tamen manichaeos vel frygas sive priscillianistas meritissima severitate persequimur. Huic itaque hominum generi nihil ex moribus, nihil ex legibus sit commune cum ceteris.

Ac primum quidem volumus esse publicum crimen, quia quod in religionem divinam committitur, in omnium fertur iniuriam²¹.

In the Theodosian Code, the heretical doctrines are equaled to crime on more than one occasion:

¹⁹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 864; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.28, 455.

²⁰ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 867; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.38, 456.

²¹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 867–868; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.40, 457.

*Oraculo penitus remoto, quo ad ritus suos haereticae superstitionis obrepserant, sciant omnes sanctae legis inimici plectendos se poena et proscriptionis et sanguinis, si ultra convenire per publicum execranda sceleris sui temeritate temptaverint*²².

The Theodosian Code alludes to the official Christian Church as the “Orthodox sect”. The difference between the heretics and Christians is to be observed in the buildings for the sacred service as well – which means, on the physical plane as well. Namely, the sacred buildings erected by the members of the heretic groups should not be called “churches”:

*Si qua etiam propria eorum nunc extant aedificia, quae non ecclesiae, sed antra debent feralia nominari, venerabilibus ecclesiis orthodoxae sectae cum donariis addicentur*²³.

In the 7th century, the Justinian’s Code²⁴ spoke in different sections against the pagans and Manichaeans²⁵. Justinian Code can be taken as a starting point for definitions of heresies in Byzantium, in respect to the legal precepts. The Justinian Code enhances the opposition between heretical sect and Orthodox religion: *haeretica secta: orthodoxa fides/religio*²⁶, *nefaria secta Nestorii*²⁷, as the opposite to the *venerabilis orthodoxarum secta*²⁸, but also between the foreign sect and Orthodox religion: *aliena secta - orthodoxa religio*²⁹.

The Justinian Code was considerably directed against the heretics. In that aim, the prohibition of the heretical assemblies was underlined – the same as in the *Codex Theodosianus*; only the celebration of the Nicæan credo and the one and only Christian God was permitted:

²² Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 872; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.51, 459.

²³ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 875; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.57, 2, 461.

²⁴ P. Krueger, ed., *Corpus Iuris Civilis*, 2, *Codex Justinianus* (Berlin 1954); G. Härtel/F.-M. Kaufmann, *Codex Justinianus*. Ausgewählt und herausgegeben (Leipzig 1991); C. Humfress, *Law and Legal Practice in the Age of Justinian*, in: *The Cambridge Companion to the Age of Justinian*, ed. M. Maas (Cambridge 2005) 161–184. Here 161, 163; W. Kunkel, *An Introduction to Roman Legal and Constitutional History*, trans. J.M. Kelly (Oxford 1973²) 166; S. L. Sass, *Research in Roman Law; a Guide to the Sources and Their English Translations*, in: *Law Library Journal* 56 (1963) 210–233; Ch. M. Radding/A. Ciaralli, *The Corpus Iuris Civilis in the Middle Ages: Manuscripts and Transmissions from the Sixth Century to the Juristic Revival* (Leiden 2007) 133; B. W. Frier ed., *The Codex of Justinian. A New Annotated Translation, with Parallel Latin and Greek Text* (Cambridge 2016).

²⁵ J. Jarry ed., *Hérésies et factions dans l’Empire byzantine du IVe au VIIe siècle* (Le Caire 1968) 342–343.

²⁶ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.10; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 53.

²⁷ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.6pr; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 51.

²⁸ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.6.1; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 51.

²⁹ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.19; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 58.

*..arceantur cunctorum haereticorum ab illicitis congregationibus turbae: unius et summi dei nomen ubique celebretur: nicaenae fidei dudum a maioribus traditae et divinae religionis testimonio atque adsertione firmatae observantia semper mansura teneatur.*³⁰

As underlined in the Theodosian Code, it is the “cult of the Catholic discipline” which condemns the heresies. Moreover, the heretics are strongly opposed to the “Catholic sect”, which is also referred to as the one and true Catholic faith: ... *unam et veram fidem catholicam, quam recta credulitas confitetur, esse retinendam*³¹. On the contrary, heretics are observed as enemies:

*Eos, qui catholicae sectae sunt inimici, intra palatium militare prohibemus, ut nullus nobis sit aliqua ratione coniunctus, qui a nobis fide et religione discordat*³².

Representing the “vicious doctrine” and “madness of the heretics”, “sect” is referred to both for the heretical, as well as to the Orthodox doctrine. The heresies are condemned by the “sincere faith of the true religion”, and in accordance to the “venerable cult of the Catholic discipline”. The heresies are alluded to “perfidious sects”³³:

*Omnes diversarum perfidarumque sectarum, quos in deum miserae vesania conspirationis exercet, nullum usquam sinantur habere conventum, non inire tractatus, non coetus agere secretos, non nefariae praevaricationis altaria manus impiae officiis impudenter adtollere et mysteriorum simulationem ad iniuriam verae religionis aptare*³⁴.

“The false doctrines” of the heretics are frequently referred to:

*Eunomiani, macedoniani, arriani nec non apollinariani inter sacrae religionis officia pro suis erroribus famosa sunt nomina. Omnes itaque, qui harum professionum vel pontificium sibi vel ministerium vindicarunt, qui se fugati nominis adserunt sacerdotes quique in criminosa religione ministrorum sibi nomen imponunt...*³⁵.

³⁰ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.1.2pr; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 5.

³¹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 905–906; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.11.2, 476.

³² Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 869; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.42, p. 457; see also 16.5.52, 459.

³³ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 859–860; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.12, 452.

³⁴ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 860–861; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.15, 453.

³⁵ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 860; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.13, 453.

The Theodosian Code also offers the list of heresies³⁶, and contains diverse enumerations of the different heresies, which are all opposed to the “reverent sect of the Orthodox”, *venerabilis orthodoxorum secta*³⁷.

The list of the heretics, who are doomed to exile, follows: the Encratites, the Saccophori, the Hydroparastatae, the Tascodrogitae, the Eunomians, the Arians, the Macedonians, the Pneumatomachi, the Manichaeans, the Apotactites, the Apollinarian doctrine; the Montanists³⁸; the Priscillianists, the Phrygians³⁹; the Donatists, the Caelicolists⁴⁰; the Emphytenticaries⁴¹. The enumeration is repeated below as well: *Post alia: manichaei et fryges, quos pepyzitas sive priscillianistas vel alio latentiore vocabulo appellant, arriani itidem macedonianique et eunomiani, novatiani ac sabbatiani ceterique haeretici sciunt universa sibi hac quoque constitutione denegari, quae illis generalium sanctionum interdixit auctoritas, puniendis, qui contra generalium constitutionum interdicta venire temptaverint*⁴².

The Justinian Code also conveys the list of heresies which are forbidden to convene on the Roman soil:

*Ariani et macedoniani, pneumatomachi et apollinariani et novatiani sive sabbatiani, eunomiani, tetraditae sive tessarescaedecatitae, valentiniani, papianistae, montanistae seu priscillianistae vel phryges vel pepuzitae, marcianistae, borboriani, messaliani, eutyctitae sive enthusiastae, donatistae, audiani, hydroparastatae, tascodrogitae, batrachitae, hermeieciiani, photiniani, pauliani, Marcelliani, ophitae, encratitae, apotactitae, saccophori et, qui ad imam usque scelerum nequitiam pervenerant, manichaei nusquam in romano solo conveniendi orandique habeant facultatem*⁴³ ...

Furthermore, the heretics and pagans seem to have fallen in the same aggrupation in respect to the law: *Omnibus videlicet, quae nostrae constitutiones de poenis paganorum et manichaeorum*

³⁶ Cf. Rigo, *Orthodoxy and heresy* 13; K. Parry, *Depicting the World: Byzantine Iconophile Thought of the Eight and Ninth Centuries* (Leiden/Boston 1996) here ch. 14, *Heresies and Church Councils* 133-144; on the canons and acts of the seven Ecumenical councils, see: *The First Seven Ecumenical Councils*, ed. Schaff.

³⁷ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 879–880; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.66, 1, 463.

³⁸ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 866; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 5.34, 455.

³⁹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 867–868; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.40, 457.

⁴⁰ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 869; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.43, 458.

⁴¹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 858–859, 872, 873; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.9, 16.5.10, 16.5.11, 452; 16.5. 52, 53, 459–460.

⁴² Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 876; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.59, 461.

⁴³ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.5pr; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 51.

et borboritarum et samaritarum et montanistarum et tascodrogorum et ophitarum ceterorumque haereticorum causa constituerunt, ex hac nostra lege confirmandis et in perpetuum valituris⁴⁴.

⁴⁴ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.19.4; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 58.

I.2. HERESIOLOGIES: CATALOGUES OF HERESIES

*On the upsurge of the Early Christian heresies*⁴⁵

In this chapter, the overview and the analysis of the Early Christian catalogues of heresies shall be given, in the aim to serve as a basis and lay foundations for the further sections of the thesis.

Heresy, the term understood as an inappropriate and erroneous expression of the Christian faith, comes from Greek in which it designates a choice, as already mentioned above. This term has already been in use in Hellenism, in relation to different philosophical schools, and to the schools of Judaism⁴⁶. In the second century BC, as the definition of Catholic Christianity began to take root, the early Christian authors started to employ the term in order to designate erroneous (religious) choices and inadequate interpretations of that which was habitually accepted by the Catholic Church – first of all in the writings of Hippolytus (c. 170 – c. 235)⁴⁷. The conversion of Constantine the Great and the Council of Nicaea in 325 marked the early beginnings of the endeavors of dogmatic identification and definition of the officially recognized Christian Creed, more amply and minutely modelled during the long centuries thereafter, and particularly at the Ecumenical Councils⁴⁸. It represented an opening of the phase in which a dogmatic distinction between the Christian faith and heresies was to be made, firmly established and officialized⁴⁹. Thus, the second part of this process was to demarcate and define the heresies, and, consequently, designate them as opposed to the official dogma. During the times of Theodosius the Great⁵⁰ (Roman emperor from 379 – 395), attempts to promote Catholic Christianity to the rank of the official religion of the Roman Empire raised Christological issues to the questions inherent to the domain of imperial policy. These attempts continued to be pursued at the Council of Constantinople in 381 likewise, upon which the

⁴⁵ Cf. A. Louth, *Christology and heresy*, in: *A Companion to Byzantium*, ed. L. James (Oxford 2010) 187–198.

⁴⁶ For more information on the derivation of the concept of heresy from Antiquity, and on the relation between heterodoxy and heresy, see: M. Simon, *From Greek haireisis to Christian heresy*, in: *Early Christian Literature and the Classical Intellectual Tradition*. In honorem Robert M. Grant, ed. W. R. Schoedel/R. L. Wilken (Paris 1979) 101–116, especially 111f.

⁴⁷ Cf. Louth, *Christology and heresy* 187–188.

⁴⁸ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the World* 133f.

⁴⁹ Cf. Louth, *Christology and heresy* 189.

⁵⁰ Cf. N. Q. King, *The Emperor Theodosius and the Establishment of Christianity* (London 1961).

Orthodoxy was sought to exemplify the imperial religion⁵¹. Importantly, dissent from official Christianity led to disqualification of citizenship⁵². The apostates, or heretics were, in this respect, therefore, equated with foreigners, or outsiders, as both represented those occupying positions outside of the official currents.

From the earliest times of the Church, therefore, the urge emerged to circumscribe the notion of the correct faith and “protect” it from heresies, by sharply defining them as opposed to the Orthodox faith. Orthodox faith was defined as the faith of the apostles, of the Fathers, of the orthodox believers, faith which reinforces the *Oikoumene* (*Οἰκουμένη* - understood as the inhabited world⁵³), whereas heresy was that which brought divisions into it. Insisting upon the cohesive, reinforcing features of the genuine, true faith has been underlined in the West-European regions as well. Frequently, opposition, doctrinal error, the dangers of the false, misinterpreted creed, or simply the fear of novelties and new interpretative models, incited the proliferation of writings which served to explain and underline the importance of the Orthodox faith. One example of those represent the *florilegia* of patristic quotations, composed during the Iconoclast dispute which were written in the aim of supporting the correct, orthodox doctrinal and interpretative method⁵⁴.

Choosing a criterion according to which one should make differentiation and division of heresies represents a difficult task. Jean Gouillard offered a systemization of heresies in Byzantium⁵⁵. He divided Byzantine heresies according to different categories into the following: (1) Christological heresies, (2) dogmatic deviations in the 12th century, and (3) syncretistic sects. According to him, Byzantine heresies were different in respect to how they were defined, but were deemed to be identical in respect to their structure, discipline, and credo – which also served to make them similar to the official church. Gouillard speaks of the categorization of the heretics as well⁵⁶.

⁵¹ Cf. Louth, *Christology and heresy* 193.

⁵² Cf. Louth, *Christology and heresy* 188.

⁵³ Cf. Louth, *Christology and heresy* 188; on the Byzantine principle of *oikonomia*, seen as the “particularly Byzantine ability to interpret the law arbitrarily to suit political or personal purposes”, see: J. Meyendorff, *Byzantine Theology: Historical Trends and Doctrinal Themes* (New York 1974) 46–50; 58–61; 88–90.

⁵⁴ Parry, *Depicting the world* 146–148.

⁵⁵ J. Gouillard, *L’hérésie dans l’empire byzantin dès origines aux XIIe siècle*, in: *Travaux et Mémoires I* (1965) 299–324.

⁵⁶ Gouillard, *L’hérésie dans l’empire byzantin* 194.

I.2.1. *Florilegia* and heresiologies

The exhaustive research field encompassing medieval heresiologies and heresiologists has been substantially developed over the course of the last century⁵⁷.

The urge to recur to tradition was first observed in the Early Christian times following the outburst of the Christian-Jewish exegetical and polemical theological conflicts. This recurrence to tradition was in wide usage from the 4th century, and often reflected in the form of collections of Biblical quotations, joined by those of the Church Fathers; it represented the strongest and most frequently applied textual tool for combating the opponents of orthodoxy during the Early Middle Ages⁵⁸. Thus, Monothelite and Monophysite *florilegia* were being composed in the 7th century, but were not limited to the doctrinal quarrels with non-Christian groups. *Florilegia* flourished during the Christological and Iconoclast disputes, within the mutually divergent currents which constituted the threads of the Christian belief system.

Heresiological writings fall into the category of catechetical literature, composed for the purpose of distinguishing orthodox credence from erroneous doctrines⁵⁹. Composition of the iconoclastic *florilegia* marked a decisive step in the Byzantine struggle against the veneration of the icons⁶⁰.

The Horos, or the definition of the Iconoclastic council of 754, was issued with a Florilegium composed in the purpose of underlying the Orthodoxy of the Iconoclasm. Another example of

⁵⁷ W. Bauer, *Rechtgläubigkeit und Ketzerei im ältesten Christentum* (Tübingen 1934); H. D. Betz, *Orthodoxy and Heresy in Primitive Christianity*, in: *Interpretation* 19 (Richmond-VA 1965) 299–311; N. Brox, *Häresie*, in: *Reallexicon für Antike und Christentum* 13, ed. Th. Klauser (Stuttgart 1984) 248–297; S. L. Greenslade, *Schism in the Early Church* (London 1953); S. L. Greenslade, *Heresy and Schism in the Later Roman Empire*, in: *Studies in Church History* 9: *Schism, Heresy, and Religious Protest*, ed. D. Baker (Cambridge 1972) 1–20; P. Nautin, *Histoire des dogmes et des sacrements chrétiens*, in: *Problèmes et méthodes d'histoire des religions* (Paris 1968) 177–191; H. Paulsen, *Schisma und Häresie*, *Untersuchungen zu I Kor. II*, 18, 19, in: *Zeitschrift für Theologie und Kirche* 79 (Tübingen 1982) 180–211; H. Schlier, „ἁρέσις“, in: *Theologisches Wörterbuch zum Neuen Testament* I, ed. G. Kittel (Stuttgart 1933, 1957²) 180–183; M. Simon, *From Greek Heresies to Christian Heresy*, in: *Early Christian Literature and the Classical Intellectual Tradition. Mélanges offerts à R. M. Grant*, ed. W. R. Schoedel/R. L. Wilken (Paris 1979) 101–116; H. von Staden, *Hairesis and Heresy: The case of the haireisis iatrikai*, in: *Jewish and Christian Self-Definition*, III, ed. B. F. Meyer/E. P. Sanders (London 1982) 76–100.

⁵⁸ Cf. A. Cameron, *Texts as weapons: Polemics in the Byzantine Dark Ages*, in: *Literacy and Power in the Ancient World*, ed. A. K. Bowman/G. Woolf (Cambridge 1994) 198–215, here 204–206.

⁵⁹ Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 207; Id., *How to Read Heresiology*, in: *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies* 33:3 (2003) 471–92; N. Garsoian, *Byzantine Heresy: a Reinterpretation*, in: *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 25 (1971) 85–113.

⁶⁰ More in detail on the *florilegia*, see below; Cameron, *How to Read Heresiology*; Garsoian, *Byzantine Heresy*; cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 206.

the Iconoclast *florilegia* is the one which was prepared for the Council of 815⁶¹; the Horos was preserved and incorporated in the Acts of the 7th Ecumenical Council of 787⁶². The Iconodules also composed their own *florilegia* with exactly the same purpose of justifying their, Iconophile, position⁶³. In addition to *florilegia*, the catalogues of heresies – known as heresiologies – have also been in use: Germanos I composed the *De Haeresibus et Synodis*, attributed to Patriarch Germanos I of Constantinople, and composed for the 6th Ecumenical Council of 680/81, following the *Panarion* of Epiphanius, dating from the 4th century. In this work, Iconoclasm was accused as being the greatest heresy, and the veneration of the icons justified as being an Orthodox stance, by recurring to the tradition of the Fathers and ecclesiastical councils⁶⁴.

Pictura muta poema

John of Damascus also significantly based his *De Haeresibus* on Epiphanius's *Panarion*. John of Damascus assumed Islam to be a heresy as well⁶⁵. Moreover, he epitomized an apogee of the Byzantine theological spirit, by having insisted upon the systematization of theological thoughts and terminological precision⁶⁶, whereas his topics revolved around the meaning of the true doctrine, definitions of heresy, and on the heresy of the Manicheans as well⁶⁷. Truth is, according to him, knowledge, against which he opposes ignorance, equated with evil and the antonym of being⁶⁸. In his words addressed to the entire Christian church, John of Damascus says that correct (*διόρθωσις*) is only what had been transmitted to the universal church through the apostles, fathers of the church and church councils⁶⁹. The important insights into the nature of the orthodox faith – *fides orthodoxa* - ascribed to Theophanes Confessor, whose writings

⁶¹ Cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 206.

⁶² See, for example, D. Sahas, *Icon and Logos: sources in eighth century iconoclasm* (Toronto 1986).

⁶³ On the misuses of *florilegia* in the Iconoclast strife, cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 205.

⁶⁴ Patriarch Germanos, *De Haeresibus et Synodis* (ed. Migne 98) 40–88, here 80A.

⁶⁵ Cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 207, note 51: John of Damascus counted 100 heresies, whereas Epiphanius counted 87; cf. John of Damascus, *De Haeresibus* (ed. Migne, PG 94) 677–780; cf. V. Baranov, *Theology of Early Iconoclasm as seen in the apologies in defense of images by St. John of Damascus*, *Khristianskij Vostok* 4, 10 (2002) 23–55.

⁶⁶ V. Tatakis, *Vizantijska filosofija. Helenska patristička i vizantijska filosofija* (Beograd/Nikšić 2002) 118–120: in original: B. Tatakis, *La philosophie byzantine*, in: *Histoire de la philosophie*, ed. É. Bréhier fascicule supplémentaire no. II (Paris 1949, 1959).

⁶⁷ B. Kotter ed., *Die Schriften des Johannes von Damaskos*, 3 – *De Fide Orthodoxa* (Berlin 1975), 4- *De Haeresibus* (Berlin 1981); cf. E. Barker, *Social and Political Thought in Byzantium: From Iustinian I to the Last Palaeologus; Passages from Byzantine Writers and Documents* (Oxford 1961) 87.

⁶⁸ John of Damascus, *De Haeresibus*, ed. Migne 1508 AB; cf. Rigo, *Orthodoxy and Heresy in Byzantium* 49.

⁶⁹ John of Damascus, *Contra Imaginum Calumniatores Orationes Tres*, ed. Kotter (Berlin 1975) 72–73.

covered the period of the 8th century, counterbalance the orthodox (correct) faith, bestowed by the fathers (*ἡ ὀρθόδοξος πίστις*), as set against the evil, erroneous doctrine (*ἡ κακοδοξία*)⁷⁰.

John of Damascus cited St. Basil on the equivalence of words and pictures: *Καὶ ὅπερ τοῖς γράμματα μεμνημένοις ἢ βιβλίος, τοῦτο τοῖς ἀραμματοῖς ἢ εἰκόν; καὶ ὅπερ τῇ ἀκοῇ ὁ λόγος, τοῦτο τῇ ὀράσει ἢ εἰκόν,* - “And what the book is for those who are initiated into letters, that is the icon for the illiterate, and what is word for hearing, that is the icon for sight...”⁷¹. As John of Damascus stated while recurring to the words of St. Basil on the equivalence of the expression in words and in pictures, the Orthodox tradition of the Bible and the Fathers is opposed to the “unclean writings of the accursed Manichaeans, Gnostics and the resto of the heretics”⁷².

Other heresiologies

Other heresiological texts included Timothy’s treatise *De Receptione Haereticorum*⁷³, Theodore of Raithu’s *Praeparatio*⁷⁴; the synodical Letter of Sophronius of Jerusalem (from 634) contained a list of anathemas against the individual heretics and 30 sects⁷⁵. In the 7th century, an anonymous author composed a piece of work entitled “Trophies of Damascus”, with a section against the Monophysites, and a list of heresies beginning with Arianism⁷⁶. In the 9th century, Nicephorus composed the *Apologeticus Maior*⁷⁷.

As has already been observed, the heresiologies could be considered as a segment of the catechetical literatures, created with a didactic purpose, and originating out of the necessity for

⁷⁰ Theophanes Confessor, *Chronographia* (ed. Migne, PG 108) 63–1006, here 818; cf. J. S. Codoner, *El periodo del Segundo Iconoclasmo en Theophanes Continuatus* (Amsterdam 1995).

⁷¹ John of Damascus, *Contra imaginum calumniatores*, ed. Kotter 93 (*Apology I*, 17, 1–7); *Ibid.*, *Apology III*, 12, 123; cf. J. Mansi, *Sacrorum Conciliorum nova et amplissima collectio* (Florenze/Venezia 1759-1798) XIII, 249DE; cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 214.

⁷² D. Anderson, *Basil of Caesarea: On the Holy Spirit* (New York 1980) 57, *Oratio* 2:10.

⁷³ Tymotheny, *De Receptione Haereticorum* (ed. Migne, PG 86) 40–45.

⁷⁴ *Praeparatio*, ed. F. Diekamp, *Katolische Dogmatik nach den Grundsätzen des heiligen Thomas* (Aschendorff 1938) I; cited from: Cameron, *Texts as Weapons* 207, note 52.

⁷⁵ (ed. Migne, PG 87) 3189–3192, also included in the Acts of the 6th Ecumenical council, cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 207, note 53; cf. A. Cameron, *The Cost of Orthodoxy*, in: *Church History and Religious Culture* 93 (2013) 339–361.

⁷⁶ ed. N. Bonwetsch, *Grundriß der Dogmageschichte* (München 1909); prologue in *Patrologia Orientalis* 15 (1927) 277 f., cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 207, note 54.

⁷⁷ Nicephorus, *Apologeticus Maior* (ed. Migne, PG 100) 533–831.

a systematization of heresies, produced with the aim of informing the body of believers on the nature of correct and erroneous belief⁷⁸.

The formal end of the Iconoclasm was proclaimed in the homily of Photius delivered in St. Sophia on 29th March 867⁷⁹. A Synodikon of Orthodoxy was read each year on the first Sunday of the Lent, upon the end of the Iconoclast crisis in 843.

I.2.2. Epiphanius's *Panarion*⁸⁰

Epiphanius was born in Palestine between 310 and 320, and died in 403. After having adopted Christianity in his youth, he spent some time in a monastery in Egypt, and returned to his native village where he established a monastery of which he was later to become abbot. He became bishop of Constantia in Cyprus (367)⁸¹. In the role of an active defender of Orthodox Christianity, he composed his *Πανάριον* (*Panarion*). This catalogue of heresies which enumerates 80 sects, was written in 374-376 and contains meticulous information on the Jewish, Gnostic and Christian sects⁸². Epiphanius' criterion in classifying the heresies, or, sects, lies in the following: the pre-Christian sects were established on the foundations of Barbarism, Scythism, Hellenism, Judaism and Samaritanism.

In the composition of his *Panarion*, Epiphanius was led and inspired by earlier sources: mainly by Hippolytus and Irenaeus; nevertheless, as he states in his Introduction, he derived much of his material from his own experience and contacts. *Panarion* was considered to be a standardized treatise on the heresies for the Byzantines of the 4th century, since it offered the first written composition on various heretical teachings. The genealogy started with the Fall of Mankind, and enlisted 80 sects, which equated with the number of king Solomon's concubines, according to the *Song of Songs* 6:8⁸³.

Epiphanius' sources include: St. Basile (epistle 258 on Magusaeans); Clement of Alexandria; Irenaeus' lost treatise *Contra Omnes Haereses*; Hippolytus (I, 28, 33,3): "Chronicle" and

⁷⁸ Cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 207.

⁷⁹ For more information on this text, see: Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 213.

⁸⁰ The *Panarion* of Epiphanius of Salamis, Book I (Sects 1-46), ed. and transl. by F. Williams, (Leiden/Boston 2009²); cf. Parry, *Depicting the World* 149.

⁸¹ On Epiphanius's life, see: A. S. Jacobs, *Epiphanius of Cyprus: A Cultural Biography of Late Antiquity* (Oakland-CA 2016) 1–13.

⁸² For more detailed information on Epiphanius's work, see: Jacobs, *Epiphanius of Cyprus* 13–27.

⁸³ Cf. Louth, *Christology and Heresy* 189.

“Syntagma” (lost); Eusebius (I, 29, 4,1): “Chronicle”, and *Praeparatio Evangelica*; “The Book of Jubilees” (I, 39, 6,1); “The Travels of Peter” (I, 30, 15, 1); “The Ascents of James” (I, 30, 10, 6); a Clementine treatise addressed to elders and virgins (I, 30, 2, 6); the “Gospel according to Hebrews” (I, 30, 13, 1-8); “The Book of Elkasai” (I, 19, 2, 1-4, 9), “The Apostolic Constitutions” (I, 45, 45); Clement of Rome (I, 27, 6, 4)⁸⁴. Besides, an important Gnostic corpus also constituted some of Epiphanius’ sources⁸⁵. Other heresiologies which have been placed in relation to Epiphanius include: Master of Brescia, *Diversarum Haereseon Liber*; Tertullian’s 30th chapter of *Praescriptio Haereticorum*, known as Pseudo-Tertullian; as well as Philaster⁸⁶.

In his Prologue, Epiphanius exposes his objective in composing the *Panarion*: his aim is to enlist the heresies, through the recurrence to the metaphorical language conveying the imagery of poison, wild beasts and illness, with the intention of offering an antidote to those already fallen prey to the heretical grasp.

In his description of the first heretic upon Christ’s arrival, Simon Magus is portrayed as leading those who “do not rightly or lawfully believe in Christ’s name, but who do their dreadful deeds” in accord with the “false corruption” which abides in them (21,1,1). Epiphanius describes the term “heresy” in relation to the term “sect” (21,5,6).

Two proems were composed as the introduction to the *Panarion*: the first one contains Epiphanius’s table of contents, whereas in the second one, the author exposes the intentions of his work in detail. These introductions then end with a description of the Catholic faith – *De Fide*⁸⁷.

The *Panarion* is proven to be of significant importance and relevance for the present study. Namely, the *Panarion* greatly influenced early medieval heresiologists posterior to its composition – authors, who composed their respective works on heresies. In the present work, I shall not deal with descriptions and enumeration of each and every heresy from *Panarion* in detail; I shall rather confine myself to the underlining and explaining the most important sequences in heresiological narrative for this research. It will be demonstrated that the specific sequences analyzed later in the second part of this thesis, are already contained in *Panarion*. This entire section, therefore, serves primarily as a starting point and a basis from which the

⁸⁴ Cf. Epiphanius, *Panarion*, ed. Williams XXV.

⁸⁵ Cf. Epiphanius, *Panarion*, ed. Williams XXVII, XXVIII.

⁸⁶ Cf. Epiphanius, *Panarion*, ed. Williams XXVI, XXVII.

⁸⁷ Cf. Epiphanius, *Panarion*, ed. Williams XXI.

tracing of the road-map of the more ample analysis that will follow in the second part of this thesis. This foundation is set up in the first part of this research; afterwards, the elaboration of the chosen case-studies from the 9th-century texts will unfold.

The *Panarion* by Epiphanius of Salamis represents the most comprehensive specimen of the early Christian heresiologies⁸⁸. The importance of this work lies, among other things, in the fact that thanks to it the previously written material on this topic has been preserved. *Panarion* has been edited or analyzed in numerous recent and earlier works⁸⁹.

⁸⁸ A. Pourkier, *L'Hérésologie chez Épiphane de Salamine* (Paris 1992) 19.

⁸⁹ Ed. Migne, *Patrologia Graeca*, ed. K. Holl, Epiphanius, I. Ancoratus. *Panarion* (haer. 1-33), GCS 25 (Leipzig 1915); *ibid.*, II. *Panarion* (haer. 34-64), GCS 31 (Leipzig 1922; ed. J. Dummer, Berlin 1980²); III. *Panarion* (haer. 65-80). *De Fide*, GCS 37 (Leipzig 1933); *Ibid.*, ed. J. Dummer (Berlin 1985); Pourkier, *L'Hérésologie chez Épiphane*; Epiphanius, *Panarion*, ed. Williams; P. Fraenkel, *Histoire sainte et hérésie chez saint Épiphane de Salamine, d'après le tome I du Panarion*, in: *Revue de Théologie et de Philosophie* 12 (Lausanne 1962) 175–191; E. Moutsoulas, *Der Begriff 'Häresie' bei Epiphanius von Salamis*, in: *Studia Patristica VII, I* (Texte und Untersuchungen zur Geschichte der altchristlichen Literatur. Archiv für die griechisch-christlichen Schriftsteller der ersten drei Jahrhunderte, Leipzig/Berlin 1882 sq.) 92 (Berlin 1966) 362–371; C. Riggi, *Il termine 'Hairesis' nell'accezione di Epifanio di Salamina (Panarion, t. I, De Fide)*, in: *Salesianum* 29 (Turin 1967) 3–27.

I.3. TERMINOLOGY: METAPHORICAL LANGUAGE OF HERESY

In this chapter, the terminology of heresy of the Early Christian times will be put forward and scrutinized. Special attention will be given to the metaphorical language of heresy, deemed to be of the utmost significance for the following sections of this work, due to the fact that it contains the protruding features of the very language of heresy, present in the Early Middle Ages likewise.

I.3.1. Heresiologies before Epiphanius

The heresiological genre originated in the second century BC. The Gnostics and their literature represented a central interest in the earliest heresiologists: Justin Martyr (around the year 145), Irenaeus of Lyon (around 180), Joseph (in ca. 230's), and Hippolytus (in ca. 240's). Irenaeus and Hippolytus included the majority of the gnostic sects in their treatises; however, few of them found their place in *Panarion* only⁹⁰. The four afore-mentioned authors who composed treatises against heresies before Epiphanius' *Panarion* may have influenced to a greater or lesser degree the composition of his work. Saint Justin, known also as Justin Martyr of Justin of Naplouse, composed a now lost treatise against heresies, which he informs his readers of in his *Apologia*⁹¹. It is thanks to his other writings, and to those of other authors⁹², that some information of this lost text of Justin's, entitled "Catalogue of all the heresies which have originated" (*Σύνταγμα κατὰ πασῶν τῶν γεγενημένων αἱρέσεων*) – or, the "Catalogue of all of the heresies that have arisen" according to Geoffrey S. Smith⁹³ - has been preserved. Epiphanius mentions Hippolytus and his *Syntagma* and Irenaeus's *Adversus haereses* among his most valuable sources. He allegedly recurred also to Clement of Alexandria and Eusebius of Caesarea. Nonetheless, the list of the potential sources which he may have drawn upon is far from being definitely discernible⁹⁴.

⁹⁰ cf. Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 31, note 9; Ibid., 32, note 53.

⁹¹ cf. A. Wartelle ed., Justin Martyr. Apologies (Paris 1987).

⁹² Namely Irenaeus, but also Hegesippe, whose fragments Eusebius refers to, cf. Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 54.

⁹³ Cf. G. S. Smith, Guilt by Association: Heresy Catalogues in Early Christianity (Oxford 2015) 20.

⁹⁴ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 93, note 91.

Justin's heresiological language

According to Justin's treatise, the heretics are influenced by the demons and the Devil⁹⁵. This method in describing and approaching the heresies will mark the work of the authors to follow as well, representing a *locus communis* attested in the *modus operandi* of the heresiologies and in the texts dealing with heresies.

Irenaeus's heresiological language and modus operandi

Irenaeus composed a more comprehensive treatise against heresies than Justin. His work was originally written in Greek, but was preserved in its entirety in the Latin copy only⁹⁶. Irenaeus's *Adversus haereses*, or, originally entitled, *Ἐλεγχος καὶ ἀνατροπὴ τῆς ψευδωνύμου γνώσεως* – or “The pseudo-knowledge, unveiled and refuted”⁹⁷. In the first part, or, Book I, Irenaeus exposed the heresies, and he then went on to attempt to refute them in the four remaining books⁹⁸. In his work, Irenaeus employed his knowledge of Justin's treatise, but elaborated it further mainly with reference to the Gnostic sources⁹⁹. His aim was to underline the unity of the Christian ecclesiastical faith through the opposition of the various heretical trends¹⁰⁰. Irenaeus extended Justin's list of heresies by attaching the new ones which had arisen as well¹⁰¹.

The *modus operandi* which Irenaeus applies is the following: he enhances the role of the Apostolic tradition and opposes it to heresies; the permanence and the unaltered truth of the Christian tradition have been underlined in Irenaeus's attempt to demonstrate and demarcate the erroneous heretical doctrines, which are inconsistent with the Truth¹⁰². Furthermore, Irenaeus insists upon the innovation and divergence as the predominant features of error, and

⁹⁵ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 56, note 20: Apol., I, 26; I, 56; I, 58; A. Le Boulluec, La notion d'hérésie dans la littérature grecque (IIe-IIIe siècles), I: De Justin à Irénée; II: Clément d'Alexandrie et Origène (Paris 1985) I, 64–67.

⁹⁶ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 59.

⁹⁷ Irénée de Lyon, Contre les hérésies. Livre I (ed. A. Rousseau/L. Doutreleau, SC 263, 264, Paris 1979); Contre les hérésies. Livre II (ed. A. Rousseau/L. Doutreleau, SC 293, 294, Paris 1982); Contre les hérésies. Livre III (ed. A. Rousseau/L. Doutreleau, SC 210, 211, Paris 1974); Contre les hérésies. Livre IV (ed. A. Rousseau, SC 100, 2, Paris 1965); Contre les hérésies. Livre V (ed. A. Rousseau, SC 152, 153, Paris 1969); cf. A. Benoit, Irénée et l'hérésie. Les conceptions hérésiologiques de l'évêque de Lyon, in: Ecclesia orans. Mélanges offerts au Père A. G. Hamman, Augustinianum 20 (1980) 55–67.

⁹⁸ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 60.

⁹⁹ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 60, note 40: F. Sagnard, La Gnose valentinienne et le témoignage de saint Irénée (Paris 1947).

¹⁰⁰ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 60, *Adversus Haereses*, ed. Rousseau I, 10–22.

¹⁰¹ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 61.

¹⁰² *Adversus Haereses*, ed. Rousseau I, Preface 2.

hence, heresies¹⁰³. It is exactly the theme of innovation, present in heretical theological systems, which constitutes a *locus communis* in discourses on heresies and which would remain present in allusions to heretical trends throughout the entire Early Middle Ages as well.

Irenaeus's language and method in Contra Haereses

In his treatise against heresies, Irenaeus instructs the reader on heresies, heretics and their wicked deeds. He applies similar metaphors, writing in a guise of a doctor, who cannot treat the patient properly with the adjusted medicine, unless he discovers the cause of the illness. Furthermore, Irenaeus alludes to heretical doctrines as pestilence: *...ut sapiens architectus et providus medicus, perfecte nos instruit de haeresibus et haeresiarchus, primum detegens eorum prava dogmata et perverse opera...sicut medicus aegrum curare non potest, nisi causam morbi prius agnoscat, sic necesse fuit eum haereticas pestes, cum suis causis, prius agnoscere, ut postmodum competenti medicina posset eis efficacius contraire*¹⁰⁴. Furthermore, Irenaeus compares heresies to venomous spurs and adulterous planting: *Hoc modo sordidissimis phantasiis haereticae dolositatis solertissime deprehensis, et fidelium oculis patenter expositis, ad ultimum venenosos surculos, adulterina plantatione insertos...*¹⁰⁵. The methodology of Irenaeus' work is not only to point to the errors of the heretics and then correct them, but also to elaborate on related verses from the New Testament, in the aim of defending the true faith: *Eiusdem quoque intentionis occasione non solum quae ab haereticis corrupta sunt corrigit, sed insuper multa de novo Testamento, ad munimentum verae fidei, fideliter...exponit*¹⁰⁶. In spite of the fact that the heretics originate in different places and teach different heretical doctrines, they are nevertheless identical, in teaching blasphemous doctrines against God, lethal to the salvation of men: *Hi enim omnes, quamvis ex differentibus locis egrediantur, et differentia doceant, in idem tamen blasphemiae concurrunt propositum, lethaliter vulnerantes, docendo blasphemiam in Deum factorem et nutritorem nostrum, et derogando salutem hominis*¹⁰⁷.

¹⁰³ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 62, note 49: Adversus Haereses, I, 28, 1 (transl. A. Rousseau, SC 264) 355.

¹⁰⁴ Irenaeus, Contra Haereses, ed. Migne Prologus I, 431–432.

¹⁰⁵ Irenaeus, Contra Haereses, ed. Migne Prologus II, 431–432.

¹⁰⁶ Irenaeus, Contra Haereses, ed. Migne Prologus, II, 431–432.

¹⁰⁷ Irenaeus, Contra Haereses, ed. Migne IV, Prologus 975.

Disobedient – cut from God – alien – serpentine

The images and metaphors Irenaeus employs in portraying sinners, falling out of union with God, are similar to those applied in describing the heretics themselves: those who do not believe in God, do not obey him neither; they are angels and sons of the Devil: *Qui Deo non credunt, ipsique non obediunt, angeli et filii diaboli sunt*¹⁰⁸.

Namely, those who do not obey God, do not represent his people, and become “alien” to him: *...qui non obediunt ei (Deo), abdicati ab eo, desierunt illi ejus esse. Unde nec haereditatem ejus percipere possunt, quemadmodum David ait: ‚Alienati sunt peccatores ab utero: ira eis secundum similitudinem serpentis‘. Et propter hoc Dominus quod sciebat hominum esse progeniem, dixit sic progeniem viperarum, secundum similitudinem horum animalium in varietate ambulantes, et laedentes reliquos*¹⁰⁹. In this manner, the sinners have also been portrayed as a „race of vipers“, as was frequently the case with heretics¹¹⁰. Those who perform the works of the Devil become his children, after having been cut off (through their sins) from God: *Verum quando credunt, et subjecti esse Deo perseverant, et doctrinam ejus custodiunt, filii sunt Dei: cum autem abscesserint, et transgressi fuerint, diabolo ascribuntur principi, ei qui primo sibi, tunc et reliquis causa abscessionis sit factus*¹¹¹.

From disobedient to heretic

Irenaeus gives a thorough account based on the Book of Genesis on the origin of the serpentine metaphor (the serpent being equated to evil) and aligns its symbolism from the first sin due to disobedience to encompass heretics as well: through the fallen angel and his serpentine guise, the sin of disobedience has befallen mankind: *...Et tunc quidem apostata angelus per serpentem inoboedientiam hominum operatus, existimavit latere se Dominum*¹¹². And today, in spite of the fact that the epoch is more recent, Irenaeus adds, the evil has spread among humans, to include not the apostates only, but the heretics likewise: *Nunc autem, quoniam novissima sunt tempora, extenditur malum in homines, non solum apostatas eos faciens, sed et blasphemus in plasmatores instituit multis machinationibus, id est, per omnes haereticos qui praedicti sunt*¹¹³. Obedience is closely linked to discipline, as Irenaeus places it

¹⁰⁸ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 16, 1115.

¹⁰⁹ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 16, 1116, 3.

¹¹⁰ See the following examples in this chapter, as in II.3.

¹¹¹ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 16, 1117.

¹¹² Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, Prologus 975.

¹¹³ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, Prologus 975.

in a close connection to discipline in numerous examples. In the following, both concepts are tightly related to faith: *Hoc genus, quod non obedivit voci Domini, neque recepit disciplinam; defecit fides ex ore ipsorum*¹¹⁴;...*sic et mens per utrorumque experimentum disciplinam boni accipiens, firmior ad conservationem ejus efficitur, oboediens Deo*¹¹⁵.

Schism – danger to the unity of the body of the Church

Irenaeus speaks of the danger of schism and of those inducing it, thus causing disunity and division in the body of the Church. The Truth is equaled to the Church: *Iudicabit autem et eos, qui schismata operantur, qui sunt inanes, non habentes Dei dilectionem, suamque utilitatem potius considerantes quam unitatem Ecclesiae: et propter modicas et quaslibet causas magnum et gloriosum corpus Christi conscindunt et dividunt, et quantum in ipsis est, interficiunt... Iudicabit autem et omnes eos qui sunt extra veritatem, id est qui sunt extra Ecclesiam: ipse autem a nomine iudicabitur*¹¹⁶. The apostolic doctrine represents the true knowledge and the character of the Body of Christ, ascertained through the succession of the bishops: *Agnitio vera est apostolorum doctrina, et antiquus Ecclesiae status, in universo mundo, et character corporis Christi secundum successiones episcoporum, quibus illi eam, quae in unoquoque loco est*¹¹⁷.

Furthermore, the limbs of the body of Christ are joined together and through them, the unity is achieved. Additionally, it is through their joint structure that the entirety of the body is portrayed: *...Cum enim et ipsi (prophetae) membra essent Christi, unusquisque eorum secundum quod erat membrum, secundum hoc et prophetationem manifestabat, omnes et multi unum praeformantes, et ea quae sunt unius annuntiantes. Quomodo enim per nostra membra operatio quidem universi corporis ostenditur; figura autem totius hominis per unum membrum non ostenditur, sed per omnia...*¹¹⁸.

¹¹⁴ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 36, 1095, citing Jerem. VII:25 sqq.

¹¹⁵ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 39, 1110.

¹¹⁶ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 33, 1076.

¹¹⁷ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 33, 1077.

¹¹⁸ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 33, 1079.

According to Irenaeus, subsequent heresiarchs follow the path instigated by Simon, frequently pointed to as the first of all heresiarchs. Thus, the alignment of heresies has been established, as a parallel to that of apostolic succession, embodied in St. Peter. Epiphanius would apply the identical scheme in his *Panarion* as well¹¹⁹. To illustrate this textual practice with a corresponding example, the opening line of the 27th chapter, entitled *De Cerdone et Marcione* of Irenaeus's first book *Against Heresies* is suitable. With regards to the heretic Cerdon, Irenaeus would say that his predecessor was Simon, as he would repeat numerous times below in the same book: *Et Cerdon autem qui iam ab iis qui sunt terga Simonem occasionem accipiens...*¹²⁰. The heretics are successors of Simon, and they are "cheating" on the correct Christian doctrine. The Gnostic sects are the successors of Simon as well: *Super hos autem ex his, qui praedicti sunt Simoniani, multitudo Gnosticorum, Barbelo exsurrexit, et velut a terra fungi manifestati sunt, quorum principales apud eos sententias enarramus*¹²¹. The typical heresiological textual procedure is present in Irenaeus's *Contra Haereses* likewise; he ascribes serpentine qualities to the heresy of Marcion¹²²; and additionally, those who follow heretical doctrines perform an adultery, *vis-à-vis* the truth: *...omnes qui quoquo modo adulterant veritatem, et praeconium Ecclesiae laedunt, Simonis Samaritam Magi discipuli et successors sunt*¹²³. Furthermore, in the continuation of the same passage, the serpentine venom is designated as the defining feature of apostasy: *...Simonis autem impietatem varie introducentes, mortificant multos, per nomen bonum sententiam suam male disperdentes, et per dulcedinem et decorem nominis, amarum et malignum principis apostasiae serpentis venenum porrigentes eis*¹²⁴.

Irenaeus applies the heresiological procedure in logically aligning each of the heresies as if each originated from the previous one. Furthermore, he frequently compares heresiarchs between themselves and finds analogies between their doctrines: *...Similiter atque hi qui a Valentino sunt...similiter ut Marcion et Saturninus, dicens...*¹²⁵. For example, he speaks of innovation as the prominent feature of heretical teachings in the 28th chapter of his first book entitled *De*

¹¹⁹ Cf. see below.

¹²⁰ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 27, 687.

¹²¹ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 29, *De variis Gnosticorum sectis, ac primo de Barbeliotis, seu Borborianis*, 691.

¹²² Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 27, 689.

¹²³ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 27, 689.

¹²⁴ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 27, 689.

¹²⁵ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 28, 691.

*Tatiano, et Continentibus, ac aliis quibusdam: Ab his autem, qui praedicti sunt, jam multae propagines multarum haeresum factae sunt, eo quod multi ex ipsis, imo omnes velint doctores esse, et abscedere quidem ab haeresi in qua fuerunt, aliud autem dogma ab alia sententia, et deinceps alteram ab altera componantes, nove docere insistunt, semetipsos adinventores sententiae, quamcunque compegerint, enarrantes*¹²⁶. Irenaeus's observation of the heretics as being torn apart from the Truth is in line with the semantic field surrounding the concept of bodily parts which are, or should be, cut off from the body of believers: *...non est numerum dicere eorum, qui secundum alterum et alterum modum exciderunt a veritate*¹²⁷.

Namely, the concept according to which the newly-arisen heresies represent a continuation, or a re-appearance of the previous, preceding ones, is frequently attested in heresiological texts and writings related to the field of heresy. The heresy is, hence, seen also as a process, as a transmission of error: thus, not only the heretical comprehension and understanding of the Christian doctrine is erroneous one, but also, the mere process of transmission of heresy and heretical concept is considered contagious. The very process of being in contact with heretical doctrine is seen as analogous to dealing with a disease. Consequently, the close semantical relation between heresy and illness is demonstrated in this aspect of transmission of the nefarious, heretical teaching as well.

*Joseph's "Refutation of all the heresies"*¹²⁸ (*Κατὰ πασῶν αἱρέσεων ἔλεγχος, or, Philosophumena*)

Joseph, the author of the treatise, employs the information given by Irenaeus, but nevertheless, he introduces some new heresies as well¹²⁹. Joseph's model is a lineal one. Additionally, he composes a consecutive arrangement of heresies, and has therein accentuated the relation between philosophical schools, mystery cults, astrology and heresies. Namely, the novelty in the heresiological methodology is the following: in search of the origin of heresies, the author seeks to attribute every heretical movement to a particular philosophical group, mystery cult, or astrological tradition¹³⁰. Thus, in the first part of his text (books I-IV), Joseph

¹²⁶ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 28, 690.

¹²⁷ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne I, 28, 691.

¹²⁸ On the origin and attribution of the work, cf. Pourkier, *L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane* 64–65; Elenchos (ed. P. Wendland, GCS 26, Leipzig 1916).

¹²⁹ Pourkier, *L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane* 68.

¹³⁰ Pourkier, *L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane* 66-67; cf. Elenchos, ed. Wendland, Preface, 8–10, 3, 21–26; transl. A. Siouville, Hippolyte, *Philosophumena*, I (Paris 1928) 105, as cited in Pourkier, *L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane* 67, note 75.

expounds on various pagan systems, each of which is considered to be at the origin of heretical doctrines, whereas in the second part (books V-X), he enlists the heresies and attributes each and every of them to the afore-mentioned philosophical or pagan religious system, as had been previously elaborated¹³¹.

*Hippolytus's Syntagma against all the heresies*¹³²

The bishop Hippolytus, Irenaeus's pupil, of whom Eusebius and Jerome both left accounts¹³³, composed the catalogue of 31 heresies dating from the first half of the 3rd century. This work has been preserved in a fragmented state; the long fragment of *Syntagma* has been a source for Epiphanius' *Panarion*¹³⁴. The *Panarion* of Epiphanius and *Liber de haeresibus* of Philaster of Brescia contain lists of heresies (80 in *Panarion* and 156 in Philaster) which have been aligned in a very similar order; the Latin catalogue of heresies entitled *Adversus omnes haereses*, attributed to Pseudo-Tertullian, is likewise similarly arranged¹³⁵. The common source for the three authors is supposed to be Hippolytus's *Syntagma*¹³⁶.

The composition of the *Syntagma* is the following: after having enlisted and exposed on the different heresies, and having refuted them, the work ends, as other heresiological treatises, with the exposition of the Truth¹³⁷.

Methodology of Hippolytus: omission of Joseph's attribution of heresies to pagan/philosophical currents

In the composition of his catalogue of heresies, Hippolytus based his accounts on heresies written by Joseph and Irenaeus¹³⁸. Hippolytus's approach in the *Syntagma* differs to that of Joseph, with his most significant innovation being overlooking that relationship between heresies and pagan/philosophical currents that Joseph had established. Instead, Hippolytus actively substitutes references to pagan, philosophical, or currents attributed to mystery cults

¹³¹ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 67.

¹³² Hippolytus Werke: III. Refutatio omnium haeresium (ed. Wendland, GCS 26, Leipzig 1916).

¹³³ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 70, notes 87, 88.

¹³⁴ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 70–72.

¹³⁵ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 71.

¹³⁶ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 72.

¹³⁷ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 72.

¹³⁸ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 73.

with heresies found in the Gospels¹³⁹. Hippolytus's principal weapon in refuting the heresies lies in the Scriptural tradition: his approach involves combating the heresies by applying the Biblical passages directly. Irenaeus may well have influenced him in applying this procedure; nevertheless, the first heresiological author who strongly adheres to the Scriptural tradition in the methodology he employed to confront the heresies may well be Hippolytus. His *modus operandi* and recurrence to the Scriptural tradition is twofold: firstly, Hippolytus turns to the Scriptures to refute the erroneous beliefs of the heretics; secondly, his methodological procedures are directed towards demonstrating that the heretical teachings are in fact based on the erroneous interpretation of the Scriptural tradition¹⁴⁰. Epiphanius's main sources for the composition of his *Panarion* included Hippolytus and Irenaeus; Epiphanius adopted Hippolytus's binary methodology: exposition and then refutation, applied to every heresy which he addressed. Namely, Epiphanius was more attracted to elaborating his refutation of the heresies through the application of the Scriptural tradition, than to recurring to the accounts of the various philosophical schools¹⁴¹.

I.3.2. Structure of *Panarion* and Epiphanius's *modus operandi*

As with the procedures already undertaken by heresiologists preceding Epiphanius, and according to heresiological practices, Epiphanius offers information on the heresiarch of the heresy in question at the beginning of the each section on different heresies. The exposition on the heresy ensues, followed by its refutation (by quoting Scriptural passages), and a shorter or longer exposition of the genuine Christian doctrine. Inspired by Hippolytus's treatise, Epiphanius analogously applies the model of refutation divided in two sections: refutation by means of logic, and refutation by means of Scriptural material¹⁴².

Recurrent topoi: innovation, old-new heresies, serpent, venom, illness, madness¹⁴³, crime, scandal, adultery

According to Epiphanius, one of the main defining features through which heresies are contrasted with the official Christian doctrine, is that heresies and deviations from the true path of Christian salvation are many, whereas the truth is only one. In other words, the paths in

¹³⁹ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphanie 73–74.

¹⁴⁰ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphanie 74.

¹⁴¹ Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphanie 74–75.

¹⁴² cf. Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphanie 244.

¹⁴³ cf. *Panarion* 57, I, 2, ed. Holl 344, I (1922), as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphanie 120, note 28.

which erroneous and heretical doctrines develop can be numerous, while the true Christian dogma remains one¹⁴⁴. The heretics follow the spirit of error, Epiphanius ensues: *πνεῦμα γὰρ ἐστὶ πλάνης*, directed against the truth - *κατὰ τῆς ἀληθείας*¹⁴⁵. In *Panarion*, Epiphanius demonstrates on various occasions, when exposing on different heresies, one of the main diversifying criteria between the genuine Christian doctrine and the sects – on the uniqueness of the path of the Christian truth and diversity of heretical errors¹⁴⁶. Each heresy, according to Epiphanius, is far distant from the truth and abides in the darkness: *Πᾶσα δὲ αἵρεσις ἀπὸ τῆς ἀληθείας ἐξοκείλασα ἐν σκότῳ τυφλώττει καὶ μωπάζει, ἕτερα ἀνθ' ἐτέρων διανοουμένη*¹⁴⁷.

Innovation

The Theodosian Code enlists various and different heresies. Heretics are equated with criminals, and heresy with crime. Furthermore, heresies are brought into connection with innovations, which are deemed to be opposed to the Christian doctrine. The heretics are forbidden to erect their churches and should be expelled from the cities, as shown on the example of the Manichaeans:

*Post haec...arrianis quidem, macedonianis et apollinarianis, quorum hoc est facinus, quod nocenti meditatione decepti credunt de veritatis fonte mendacia, intra nullam civitatem ecclesiam habere liceat; novatianis autem et sabbatianis omnis innovationis adimatur licentia, si quam forte temptaverint; ...et qui ad imam usque scelerum nequitiam pervenerunt manichaei nusquam in Romano solo conveniendi orandique habeant facultatem; manichaeis etiam de civitatibus expellendis, quoniam nihil his omnibus relinquendum loci est, in quo ipsis etiam elementis fiat iniuria*¹⁴⁸.

As has been demonstrated above, the connection between heresies and innovation is one of the most pivotal ones in discerning the correct from the incorrect, erroneous belief. Namely, the utmost criterion in demarcating the true belief is the recurrence to tradition, to the Scriptural

¹⁴⁴ e.g. cf. Pourkier, *L'Hérésologie chez Épiphanes* 202.

¹⁴⁵ *Panarion*, 25, 4, 9, ed. Holl 272, 6–7 (1915), as cited from: Pourkier, *L'Hérésologie chez Épiphanes* 323, note 170.

¹⁴⁶ e.g. *Panarion*, 59, 12, 2-3, ed. Holl 377, 9–18 (1922).

¹⁴⁷ *Panarion*, 59, 11, 1, ed. Holl 376, 8–9 (1922), as cited from: Pourkier, *L'Hérésologie chez Épiphanes* 409, note 153.

¹⁴⁸ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri 878–879*; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.65, 2, 462–463.

and the authority of the Church Councils and Church Fathers. The problem of innovation when designating heresies has thus become a fundamental issue. In his account on Noet, Epiphanius underlines on multiple occasions the significance of novelty: no one has before him (Noet), he says, “vomited” such a horrifying and deadly bitterness - *μηδένα πρὸ αὐτοῦ ἐξέμεσαι ταύτην τὴν δεινὴν καὶ ὀλετήριον πικρίαν*¹⁴⁹. The innovation is the key-criterion allowing the ascending developmental line between the earlier and later heresies, as demonstrated (to cite only one example) in Epiphanius’s account on Basilide: the heresiarch attempted to discover a new approach to the interpretation of the mythical material - *...βούλεται δὲ ἐτέρως αὐτὰ μεταχειρίζειν καὶ εἰς ὄγκον μείζονα διηγείσθαι τὰ μυθολογήματα*¹⁵⁰. The role of innovation in the heresiarch’s practices and procedures is of great significance, since it is innovation, which assures the alignment of the given heresy to the affiliation to previous heresies¹⁵¹.

Old-new heresies: The interconnectedness between heresies and their ascending line of development

As Aline Pourkier has observed and thoroughly documented, the practice of assimilation of an older heresy into a more recent one – or inversely – as long as they have been presented as having points in common, was apparently the habitual *modus operandi* in heresiological literature¹⁵². Epiphanius’s account on the heresy of Menander offers a sound illustration of this practice on the example from *Panarion*. Namely, Epiphanius depicts a “sacrament” derived from another heresy (that of Simon), and attributes it to Menander¹⁵³. Hence, the process of “assimilation” of heresies is here taking place. To illustrate this tendency with one example depicting the ascending line in which various heretical doctrines develop, Epiphanius narrates the origins of Menander’s sect, which directly ensues from the heresy of Saturnnil. Through a metaphor in which two serpents exchange their deadly venoms, Epiphanius portrays the heresy of Menander as being closely related to that of Saturnnil, as the two heresiarchs belonged to the same group: *...ἐκ ταύτης δὲ παρελθὼν ἐξῆς τὴν Βασιλείδου τοῦ συσχολαστοῦ τούτου, τοῦ καὶ συνηπατημένου δηλώσω. μετέχουσι γὰρ οὗτοι <τῶν αὐτῶν>, ὡς ἀπ’ ἀλλήλων τὸν ἰὸν δανεισάμενοι κατὰ τὴν ἐναργῆ παροιμίαν, [ὡς] ἄσπις παρ’ ἐχίδνης ἰὸν δανειζομένη. ὁμοῦ γάρ*

¹⁴⁹ *Panarion*, 57, I, 5, ed. Holl 344, 6–8 (1922), as cited from: Pourkier, *L’Hérésologie chez Épiphane* 122, note 41.

¹⁵⁰ *Panarion*, 24, I, 6, ed. Holl 257, 6–8 (1915), as cited from: Pourkier, *L’Hérésologie chez Épiphane* 211, note 38.

¹⁵¹ cf. Pourkier, *L’Hérésologie chez Épiphane* 211, 268.

¹⁵² Pourkier, *L’Hérésologie chez Épiphane* 159.

¹⁵³ Pourkier, *L’Hérésologie chez Épiphane* 165; see also: *Ibid.*, 189.

εἰσι τῆς σχολῆς καὶ συνεδρίου ἀλλήλων, καθ' ἑαυτὸν δὲ ἔστηκεν ἑκάτερος τὴν αἵρεσιν προστησάμενος, καὶ τὴν μὲν κακίαν παρ' ἀλλήλων ἠρανίσαντο, τὴν δὲ διαφωνίαν ἐν αὐτοῖς ἐνεστήσαντο...¹⁵⁴. A similar procedure can be observed in Epiphanius' narrative on Basilid: he was analogously inspired by the preceding heresies of Simon and Satornil: ...ἐναρξάμενος ἡμῖν τὰ δεινὰ τε καὶ ὀλετήρια, ἀλλὰ προφάσεις λαβὼν ἐκ τοῦ Σατορνίλου καὶ Σίμωνος τοῦ προεληλεγμένου¹⁵⁵. Namely, Epiphanius employs the analogous *modus operandi* as Irenaeus in his heresiological treaty, according to which, the more recent heresiarch is brought into connection with his earlier predecessor. In that manner, the line of heresiarchs has been reconstructed, reaching back to the father of all the heretics, Simon. Therefore, Epiphanius establishes a procedure which has been designated by Pourkier as being a “projection rétrospective”¹⁵⁶. The Gnostics, for example, derived from the Nikolaites, which Epiphanius also depicted by means of a serpentine metaphor: οὗτοι δὲ οἱ τούτῳ τῷ Νικολάῳ συνεζευγμένοι, πάλιν ἀπ' αὐτοῦ ὡς ἀπὸ οὐρίου ὧοῦ ὄφεως σκορπίοι ἢ ἐξ ἀσπίδων * γεγεννημένοι¹⁵⁷. This sort of “succession of heresiarchs/heresies” is described in allegorical sense through comparison with illnesses: ...ὥσπερ <γὰρ> δι' ἐγκεντρισμοῦ ἢ ψώρας ἀγρίας ἢ λέπρας ἐξ ἐτέρων σωμάτων ἕτερα σώματα * παραφθείρεσθαι, οὕτως ἀπὸ μέρους <τούτοις> εἰσὶ συνηνωμένοι οἱ λεγόμενοι <Γνωστικοί>, ἐξ αὐτοῦ Νικολάου καὶ τῶν πρὸ αὐτοῦ (Σίμωνος δὲ φημι καὶ τῶν ἄλλων) λαβόντες τὰς προφάσεις...¹⁵⁸.

Deviation/madness/illness

As promulgated by the Theodosian Code, the heresies are forbidden by “both divine and imperial laws and shall forever cease”. The heretical doctrines are referred to as noxious and deceptive:

Omnes vetitae legibus et divinis et imperialibus haereses perpetuo conquiescant...Omnesque perversae istius superstitionis magistri pariter et ministri, seu illi sacerdotali adsumptione

¹⁵⁴ Panarion, 23, 7, 2–3, ed. Holl (1915) 255, 20 – 256, 6, as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 203, note 192.

¹⁵⁵ Panarion, 24, I, 6, ed. Holl (1915) 257, 4–8, as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 211, note 35.

¹⁵⁶ cf. Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 211, 340.

¹⁵⁷ Panarion, 26, 1, ed. Holl (1915) 275, 13–14, as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 334 note 233.

¹⁵⁸ Panarion, 25, 7, ed. Holl (1915) 274, 16–18, as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 334, note 234.

*episcoporum nomen infamant seu, quod proximum est, presbyterorum vocabulo religionem mentiuntur...*¹⁵⁹

The Arians and the Manichaeans are most frequently mentioned among the heretics.

According to the Theodosian Code, the madness of the heretics' minds shall be banished, and the heretics should be expelled outside the city walls; the name of the one and only God, transmitted through the Nicæan faith of the fathers should only be observed; the heresy is alluded to as disease: “the contamination of the Photinian pestilence, the poison of the Arian sacrilege”:

*Arceantur cunctorum haereticorum ab illicitis congregationibus turbae. Unius et summi dei nomen ubique celebretur; nicaenae fidei dudum a maioribus traditae et divinae religionis testimonio atque adsertione firmatae observantia semper mansura teneatur; photiniana labis contaminatio, arriani sacrilegii venenum, eunomianae perfidiae crimen et nefanda monstruosis nominibus auctorum prodigia sectarum ab ipso etiam aboleantur auditu*¹⁶⁰.

The perfidious mind and “religious insanity” of the Eunomian heretics has been put forward, and taken as an example demonstrating the afore-mentioned:

*Eunomianorum vero perfidam mentem et nequissimam sectam speciali commemoratione damnamus statuimusque omnia, quae contra illorum vesaniam decreta sunt...*¹⁶¹

Theodosian Code also speaks on the “polluted contagions of the heretics” which are to be expelled from the villages and cities. The heretics are, hence, seen as polluted: the Theodosian Code speaks on the “polluted” sect of the Donatists or the Montanists: *polluta donatistarum vel montanistarum secta*¹⁶².

Thus has the perversity of the heretics been emphasized, as well as the contagion they diffuse, due to which, their congregations should be prohibited:

¹⁵⁹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 855; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.5, 450.

¹⁶⁰ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 855–856; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.6, 1, 451.

¹⁶¹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 863–864; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.25, 1, 454.

¹⁶² Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 882–883; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.6.5, 465.

*Haereticorum polluta contagia pelli urbibus, vicis proturbari ac nullis penitus iubemus patere conventibus, ne in quoquam loco sacrilega cohors talium hominum colligatur. Nulla eorum perversitati vel publica conventicula vel latentiora erroribus secreta tribuantur*¹⁶³.

The heretics propagate “pestilence and contagion”, which are seen as a threat to the “Catholic sect”. Namely, the aim of the heretics, together with the adherents to the Judaic religion, is to act against the sacraments of the Catholic faith:

*Donatistarum haereticorum iudaeorum nova adque inusitata detexit audacia, quod catholicae fidei velint sacramenta turbare. Quae pestis cave contagione latius emanet ac profluat. In eos igitur, qui aliquid, quod sit catholicae sectae contrarium adversumque, temptaverint, supplicium iustae animadversionis expromi praecipimus*¹⁶⁴.

Heresy is understood as insanity, which is to be suppressed:

*Haereticorum ita est reprimenda insania...*¹⁶⁵

The terminology pertaining to the madness of the heretics was present in the Theodosian Code, as well as in the Justinian Code: *Hanc legem sequentes christianorum catholicorum nomen iubemus amplecti, reliquos vero dementes vesanosque iudicantes haeretici dogmatis infamiam sustinere...*¹⁶⁶ The heretical madness is in the Theodosian Code referred to as *haereticorum vesania*¹⁶⁷, whereas the assemblies of the Eunomians are alluded to as *scelus* and *facinus*¹⁶⁸.

The Theodosian Code insists upon the danger of the “perverse dogma” of the heretics, who are to be banished:

*Ii, qui scaevi dogmatis retinent principatum, hoc est episcopi presbyteri diacones adque lectores et si qui clericatus velamine religioni maculam conantur infligere, sub cuiuslibet haeresis sive erroris nomine constituti...omni modo propellantur*¹⁶⁹.

The “noxious books” of the heresies should be burnt; the heresy is referred to as crime:

¹⁶³ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 862; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.20, 454.

¹⁶⁴ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 870; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.44, 458.

¹⁶⁵ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 878–879; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.65, 462.

¹⁶⁶ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.1.1.1

¹⁶⁷ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 883; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.6.6, 1, 465.

¹⁶⁸ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 883–884; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.6.7, 465.

¹⁶⁹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 862; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.19, 454.

*Codices sane eorum scelerum omnium doctrinam ac materiam continentes summa sagacitate mox quaeri ac prodi exerta auctoritate mandamus sub aspectibus iudicantium incendio mox cremandos. Ex quibus si qui forte aliquid qualibet occasione vel fraude occultasse nec prodidisse convincitur, sciat se velut noxiorum codicum et maleficii crimine conscriptorum retentatorem capite esse plectendum*¹⁷⁰.

The Manichaeans are alluded to as criminals, in need of correction:

*Noxios manichaeos execrabilesque eorum conventus, dudum iusta animadversione damnatos, etiam speciali praeceptione cohiberi decernimus. Quapropter quaesiti adducantur in publicum ac detestati criminosi congrua et severissima emendatione resecentur*¹⁷¹.

Similarly, as stated in the *Panarion*, the heretical spirit is insane, and deviant: ὁ τῆς τῶν ἀνθρώπων πολλῆς φρενοβλαβείας καὶ ἀκατορθώτου λογισμοῦ¹⁷². Epiphanius compares heresy to pest, as was not seldom the case in heresiological literature¹⁷³. Thus, the metaphor of heresy as infectious disease is evident: ...ἐν χρόνοις τοίνυν, ὡς ἔφημεν, Ἀνικήτου ἢ προδεδηλωμένη Μαρκελλίνα ἐν Ρώμῃ γενομένη τὴν λύμην τῆς Καρποκρᾶ διδασκαλίας ἐξεμέσσα πολλοὺς τῶν ἐκεῖσε λυμηνάμενη ἠφάνισε¹⁷⁴. The image of heresies propagating as contagion is here presented, as shown above, in relation to the “succession lineage” of heresies¹⁷⁵. Moreover, this concept of heresy as madness and illness constitute one of the most pronounced and important threads in heresiological treatises.

The concept of heresy as illness in Augustine’s work has been thoroughly analyzed by Jean-Paul Rassinier. Namely, through a thorough scrutiny of, primarily, metaphorical vocabulary in Augustine’s work, the metaphorical language shows one of the aspects related to medicinal terminology¹⁷⁶. Heresy was thus defined by means of metaphorical linguistic tools, some pertaining to medicinal vocabulary. The textual treatment of heretics and pagans has frequently

¹⁷⁰ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 866; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.34, 1, 456.

¹⁷¹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 866; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.35, 456.

¹⁷² *Panarion*, 57, 3, 2–4, ed. Holl (1922) 347, 13–21, as cited from: Pourkier, *L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphanes* 126, note 59.

¹⁷³ *Panarion*, 27, 4, 4–5, ed. Holl (1915) 305, 5–14, as cited from: Pourkier, *L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphanes* 270, note 68.

¹⁷⁴ *Panarion*, 27, 6, 8, ed. Holl (1915) 310, 13, as cited from: Pourkier, *L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphanes* 275, note 83.

¹⁷⁵ cf. above, *Panarion* 25, 7, ed. Holl (1915) 274, 16–18.

¹⁷⁶ J.-P. Rassinier, *L’hérésie comme maladie dans l’œuvre de Saint Augustin*, In: *Mots*, n°26, mars 1991. *Médecine, santé et politique*, 65–83, here 66.

been contained within the semantic field of insanity¹⁷⁷. Apart from this relationship drawn between the semantic fields of heresy and insanity, another interesting and important point has been accentuated: that of the relationship between heresies and contagious illnesses, as it has been observed on numerous occasions in the history of heresiologies¹⁷⁸. The third, huge semantic field is the one of venom and the serpent¹⁷⁹. Thus, this three-fold division is, according to Rassinier, present in Augustine’s opus – corresponding to the distinctive features of heresies, as attested in heresiological literature¹⁸⁰: illness of the soul, contagious illness, and poisoning.

As explained, there was hardly any difference drawn between *insania*, *furor* and *mania* in classical Latin literature¹⁸¹.

Venom

In his Preface, Epiphanius informs the readers that he will expose on the twenty-eight heresies in his three books. The aim of Epiphanius’s work is to unveil the “criminal practices” of the heretics, similar to “the venoms and poisons”. Furthermore, Epiphanius wishes to provide the antidote – designated as a medication for those who have already been infected, and as a prevention for those who are susceptible of falling in to this condition¹⁸²: ...ἐπειδὴ γὰρ μέλλομεν ὑμῖν τὰ τε ὀνόματα τῶν αἱρέσεων δηλοῦν τάς τε παρ’ αὐτοῖς ἀθεμίτους πράξεις ἀνακαλύπτειν, ὥσπερ ἰοὺς καὶ δηλητήρια ὄντα, σὺν αὐτοῖς δὲ ἅμα καὶ ἀντιδότους ἐφαρμόσαι, ἀλεξήτρια τῶν δεδηγμένων καὶ προκαταληπτικὰ τῶν μελλόντων εἰς τοῦτο ἐμπίπτειν, τοῖς φιλοκάλοις διαγράφομεν αὐτὸ τοῦτο τὸ προοίμιον, Πανάριον εἶτ’ οὖν κιβώτιον ἰατρικὸν τῶν θηριοδύκτων ἐρμηνεύοντες, ὅπερ ἐστὶ διὰ βιβλίων τριῶν συγγραφέν, <περι>έχον αἱρέσεις ὀγδοήκοντα, αἵτινες εἰσι θηρίων εἶτ’ οὖν ἐρπετῶν αἰνίγματα. The “antidote” Epiphanius offers is represented in the refutation of every heresy he gives (following his exposition of it), and the *Expositio Fidei* which ends the treatise¹⁸³. The image of illness, contagion and venom employed in the description of heretical doctrines is frequent in heresiological literature in general, and in the *Panarion* likewise. As Aline Pourkier stated, the recurrence to the metaphor of venom is not

¹⁷⁷ Sermon 34, quoted from Rassinier, *L’hérésie comme maladie* 67 – *insania* of the pagans and errors of the heretics.

¹⁷⁸ On heresiologies, see above.

¹⁷⁹ Rassinier, *L’ hérésie comme maladie* 68.

¹⁸⁰ On heresiologies, see above.

¹⁸¹ Rassinier, *L’ hérésie comme maladie* 69–70.

¹⁸² Pourkier, *L’Héresiologie chez Épiphane* 77.

¹⁸³ Pourkier, *L’Héresiologie chez Épiphane* 78.

only present in each chapter of *Panarion* when comparing every heresy to another venomous serpent, but also in other sections of the chapters¹⁸⁴.

Scandal

As Irenaeus has demonstrated, the concept of the danger scandal produces is related to the scriptural tradition: ...*Mittet Filius hominis angelos suos, et colligent de regno ejus omnia scandala, et eos qui faciunt iniquitatem, et mittent eos in clibanum ignis: illic erit fletus et stridor dentium. Tunc justi fulgebunt sicut sol in regno Patris ipsorum*¹⁸⁵.

Epiphanius refers to the heretics related to the concept of scandal, by alluding to Matthew 18:7 - ...ἵνα μὴ μηκύνω τὸν λόγον, «οὐαὶ τῷ κόσμῳ ἀπὸ τῶν σκανδάλων» καὶ «τῶν ἐργαζομένων τὴν ἀνομίαν». πόσοι ἑαυτοῖς σκότος ἠϋρηνται καὶ ἄλλοις τοῖς μετέπειτα τῷ σκότει αὐτῶν πειθομένοις· τοῖς δὲ συνετοῖς φανήσεται ἡ ἀλήθεια, ἡ δὲ Βασιλείου καὶ τῶν τοιούτων πραγματεία πλάνης ἔργον ἐλεγχθήσεται¹⁸⁶. The heretics represent, according to Epiphanius, the danger of scandal for the Christian Church; they scandalize the pagans due to the criminal actions they undertake. Therefore, the pagans turn away from the true Christian doctrine: εἰσὶ δὲ ἐκ τοῦ Σατανᾶ παρεσκευασμένοι καὶ προβεβλημένοι εἰς ὄνειδος καὶ σκάνδαλον τῆς τοῦ θεοῦ ἐκκλησίας. ἐπέθεντο γὰρ ἑαυτοῖς ἐπὶ κλην Χριστιανοί, τοῦτο τοῦ Σατανᾶ παρασκευάσαντος πρὸς τὸ σκανδαλίζεσθαι τὰ ἔθνη δι' αὐτῶν καὶ ἀποστρέφειν τὴν τῆς ἀγίας τοῦ θεοῦ ἐκκλησίας ὠφέλειαν...νομίσαντα καὶ τοὺς τῆς ἀγίας τοῦ θεοῦ ἐκκλησίας τοιούτους εἶναι, ἀποστρέφειν ὡς καὶ προεῖπον τὴν ἀκοήν ἀπὸ τῆς τοῦ θεοῦ κατὰ ἀλήθειαν διδασκαλίας...¹⁸⁷. The heretics therefore represent danger for the feeble souls, whom they seduce with their ill doctrine: Εἰσὶ δὲ ἐν ἀσωτία διατελοῦντες οὗτοι καὶ πᾶν ὅτι οὖν ἐργαζόμενοι πρὸς εὐπάθειαν σωμάτων, ἡμῖν δὲ ὅλως οὐ προσεγγίζοντες, εἰ μὴ τι ἂν πρὸς τὸ δελεάσαι ψυχὰς ἀστηρίκτους τῇ αὐτῶν κακοδιδασκαλίᾳ¹⁸⁸.

¹⁸⁴ cf. Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 488, note 74.

¹⁸⁵ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, ed. Migne IV, 40, 1113, quoting Mt. 13:41.

¹⁸⁶ *Panarion*, 24, 10, 1–4, ed. Holl (1915) 266, 16 – 267, 2, as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 253, note 274.

¹⁸⁷ *Panarion*, 27, 3, 3–4, ed. Holl (1915) 303, 25 – 304, 13, as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 268–269, note 59.

¹⁸⁸ *Panarion*, 27, 4, 1, ed. Holl (1915) 304, 14, as cited from: Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 269, note 62.

Symbolism and metaphor of a serpent in describing heresies

The innovation Epiphanius makes, is to compare every heresy he exposes with a specific serpent, always symbolically related to the heresy in question¹⁸⁹. This tradition of attributing serpentine features to the heretics and the Devil¹⁹⁰, springs from the Bible: the “race of vipers” – ὄφεις, γεννήματα ἐχιδνῶν¹⁹¹. Reference to this metaphor and Biblical passages is found in Irenaeus, Tertullian (2nd half of the 2nd century – first half of the 3rd century), Clement of Alexandria, leader of the Alexandrian school (mid-2nd century – early 3rd century), Hippolytus and Origen – perhaps the most significant theologian of the early Christian period (c. 185 – c. 254)¹⁹². Irenaeus applies these terms in referring to those who are disobedient to the Gospel. It is exactly the attribution of the serpent to the Devil, which explains the application of its metaphor for the heretics as well. The alignment sin – disobedience – serpent implies heresies too, representing sin as a product of disobedience in its primal stance. The theme of the serpent, inherent to that of heresies – and the demonic origin underlying heresies - is present in Christian heresiology in Justin, Irenaeus, Eusebius, bishop of Caesarea and the author of a highly influential *Historia Ecclesiastica* (c. 260-339), to mention only some¹⁹³. The antidote, contained in the *Panarion*, is designed to help the heretics who are thus approached as if they were ill. Namely, this antidote is administered through the refutation of the previously-exposed heresies, followed by the Exposition of Faith at the end of the book – composed of the doctrine of truth, ἡ διδασκαλία τῆς ἀληθείας, and faith of the Holy Catholic Church - representing the only existing truth, transmitted through the teachings of the apostles, ἡ τῶν ἀποστόλων διδασκαλία¹⁹⁴. It is in the Prologue that Epiphanius mentions the scope and aim of his work – summarized in exposing, then refuting the eighty heresies and schisms (αἰρέσεων καὶ σχισμάτων) assembled in the three books, and divided in to seven codices¹⁹⁵.

¹⁸⁹ – or, at times to another wild animal, cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 79, note 13; 80; Pourkier 163.

¹⁹⁰ Apoc. 12:9.

¹⁹¹ Mt. 3:7; 23:33, cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 79, note 15.

¹⁹² Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 79, note 18.

¹⁹³ Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 80, and especially note 25.

¹⁹⁴ Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 81–82.

¹⁹⁵ Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 83, note 36.

Nuptial symbolic

Opposed to numerous heresies lie the one and only doctrine of Truth, and the holy maid which represents Christ's Church: *..μία δὲ μετὰ τὰς ὀγδοήκοντα» ἡ τῆς ἀληθείας βάσις ἅμα καὶ διδασκαλία καὶ σωτήριος πραγματεία καὶ Χριστοῦ «νύμφη ἁγία» ἐκκλησία...*¹⁹⁶ Thus the Church is portrayed as a *fiancée* of Christ; while on the other hand, the heresies represent concubines; this metaphor comes from the Song of Songs, where the concubines amount in number to eighty¹⁹⁷.

The metaphor of adultery/whoredom is found in Ezekiel 23¹⁹⁸, among other, and refers to the reversed nuptial symbolic, related to the Church of God, and to the apostasy of Nubia due to her whoredoms. In the Ezekiel 23, the narrative is, summarily, as follows: the prophet describes the story of two women, daughters of one mother, who committed whoredom in Egypt in their youth. Their names were Aholah and Aholibah; Aholah represents Samaria, whereas Aholibah represents Jerusalem (v. 1-4): *..fili hominis duae mulieres filiae matris unius fuerunt, et fornicatae sunt in Aegypto in adulescentia sua fornicatae sunt ibi subacta sunt ubera earum et fractae sunt mammae pubertatis earum; nomina autem earum Oolla maior et Ooliba soror eius et habui eas et pepererunt filios et filias porro earum nomina Samaria Oolla et Hierusalem Ooliba.*

Aholah (Samaria) committed whoredoms with her neighbours, the Assyrians, and she “defiled herself” with their idols (v. 5-7): *fornicata est igitur Oolla super me et insanivit in amatores suos in Assyrios propinquantes, et dedit fornicationes suas super eos electos filios Assyriorum universos et in omnibus in quos insanivit in inmunditiis eorum polluta est...*

These two sisters were “corrupt” in their “harlot love” towards their neighbours, Babylonians and Chaldeans (v. 14-16, referring to the metaphor of the pagans and idolatry):*...et auxit fornicationes suas cumque vidisset viros depictos in pariete imagines Chaldeorum expressas coloribus, et accinctos balteis renes et tiaras tinctas in capitibus eorum formam ducum omnium similitudinem filiorum Babylonis terraeque Chaldeorum in qua orti sunt, et insanivit super eos concupiscentia oculorum suorum et misit nuntios ad eos in Chaldeam...*

They were “polluted” with them (with their neighbours, v. 17); as a consequence, God alienated himself from them (v. 18): *cumque venissent ad eam filii Babylonis ad cubile mammaram polluerunt eam stupris suis et polluta est ab eis et saturata est anima eius ab illis, denudavit*

¹⁹⁶ Cf. Panarion, Prooemium I, I, 1–4, ed. Holl (1915) 155, 6 – 156, 5.

¹⁹⁷ Song of Songs, 6, 8-9.

¹⁹⁸ Ezek. 23:1–30, cited from King James Version.

quoque fornicationes suas et discoperuit ignominiam suam et recessit anima mea ab ea sicut recesserat anima mea a sorore eius.

Finally, God's anger will bring their enemies against them and vengeance will come through their swords (v. 22-24):...*propterea Ooliba haec dicit Dominus Deus ecce ego suscitabo omnes amatores tuos contra te de quibus satiata est anima tua et congregabo eos adversum te in circuitu filios Babylonis et universos Chaldeos nobiles tyrannosque et principes omnes filios Assyriorum iuvenes forma egregia duces et magistratus universos principes principum et nominatos ascensores equorum, et venient super te instructi curru et rota multitudo populorum lorica et clypeo et galea armabuntur contra te undique et dabo coram eis iudicium et iudicabunt te iudiciis suis.*

The passage ends with the message and the pivotal line which explains the entire concept of whoredoms, symbolically representing the state of alienation from God through the recurrence to idolatry and pagan (foreign, ungodly) practices: "I will do these things unto thee, because thou hast gone a whoring after the heathen, and because thou art polluted with their idols" (v. 29-30): ...*et agent tecum in odio et tollent omnes labores tuos et dimittent te nudam et ignominia plenam revelabitur ignominia fornicationum tuarum scelus tuum et fornicationes tuae fecerunt haec tibi quia fornicata es post gentes inter quas polluta es in idolis eorum*¹⁹⁹.

Thus has the relation between idolatry and adultery in metaphorical sense several times been stressed in the Scriptures²⁰⁰. For example, Jeremiah also speaks on the adultery of Israel and Juda: these have been portrayed as unfaithful, who have made adulteries with the idols²⁰¹.

Development of the concept and construct of heresy: superstition – idolatry – heresy; from δεισδαιμονία to θεοσεβεία

The Greek term *αἵρεσις* was not in the beginning attached to the modern meaning of the word "heresy". It simply designated a "choice", as already mentioned. Thence, the sense of doctrinal choice evolved, and especially, the meaning of "school" - philosophical, literary, political school, or "school of thought"²⁰². The meaning of "religious sect" stemmed out of this interpretation. In the New Testament, the term *αἵρεσις* refers to the "religious sect", or, to the

¹⁹⁹ Ezek. 23:1–30, Vulgata.

²⁰⁰ cf. Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphanes 293.

²⁰¹ Cf. Jeremiah 3:6–10, 13; Id., 5: 7, 19; Id., 13:27, Vulgata.

²⁰² Pourkier, L'Hérésiologie chez Épiphanes 85, notes 41, 42.

discord²⁰³; in other Evangelical examples, the meaning of the word remains attached to the meaning of doctrinal deviation. The idioms such as “dangerous (heretical) doctrines” appear already in the Gospels: *αἱρέσεις ἀπολείας*²⁰⁴. Schisms and heresies appear often in closely-related sense, to designate the divergence in doctrine:

*Primum quidem convenientibus vobis in ecclesiam, audio scissuras esse inter vos, et ex parte credo. Nam oportet et haereses esse, ut et qui probati sunt, manifesti fiant in vobis; - Πρῶτον μὲν γὰρ συνερχομένων ὑμῶν ἐν ἐκκλησίᾳ ἀκούω σχίσματα ἐν ὑμῖν ὑπάρχειν, καὶ μέρος τι πιστεύω. Δεῖ γὰρ καὶ αἱρέσεις ἐν ὑμῖν εἶναι, ἵνα [καὶ] οἱ δόκιμοι φανεροὶ γένωνται ἐν ὑμῖν*²⁰⁵.

In Justin’s writings, the term *αἵρεσις* is implied, on behalf of the Jews, in order to designate Christian sects, to which the meaning of “impious” and erroneous is also ascribed. In Irenaeus’s texts, the same term is employed to designate a Christian sect whose doctrine is foreign to that of the Scriptural Tradition. In Clement of Alexandria, on the other hand, the concept of heresy has a pejorative meaning when it refers to Christian sects, whereas the pejorative meaning is omitted when the term alludes to the philosophical currents or schools²⁰⁶.

Epiphanius opens his list of heresies with that of Adam; in his methodological approach, Epiphanius introduces the term “the mother-heresies and prototype-heresies”, employed for Hellenism and Judaism, as well as for the schools or currents which constitute them²⁰⁷. The “mother-heresies” imply Barbarism, Scythism, Hellenism and Judaism. It is exactly in this instance that the originality in Epiphanius’ approach and method in systematizing heresies noticeable. Barbarism covers the period from Adam to Noah; Scythism, which ensues and encircles the period between the age of Noe to Tharra, Abraham’s father, is referred to as “superstition” (*δεισιδαιμονία*)²⁰⁸. Hellenism is marked by the veneration of the idols, or idolatry. Therefore, referring to Epiphanius, the underlying approach in the veneration process remains the same as in earlier epochs – the one based on superstition, and envelops the Egyptians, the Babylonians, Phrygians and Phoenicians²⁰⁹. The new type of religious observation appears only later, when the first Greek philosophical sects (designated as heresies, *αἵρεσις*) came in to play: at this moment piety, or *θεοσεβεία*, replaced superstition. At this

²⁰³ in the Pauline Epistles, cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 85, notes 45, 46.

²⁰⁴ Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 85, note 47.

²⁰⁵ I Cor. 11:18–19.

²⁰⁶ On the notion of heresy in Justin, Clement of Alexandria, Origen: cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 86–87; Simon, From Greek Heresies to Christian Heresy 101–116.

²⁰⁷ Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 87–88, notes 59 and 60 on page 87.

²⁰⁸ Cf. First Preface, I, 3,3, ed. Holl (1915) 157, 3 – cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 88, note 61.

²⁰⁹ Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 88.

stage, Epiphanius does not attribute negative, pejorative meaning to the term “heresy”. Judaism ensues, a “mother-heresy” encompassing seven Jewish sects. Therefore, Epiphanius makes a distinction between what he considers a “mother-heresy” and a “sect”, in spite of the fact that he employs the same term for both, *αἵρεσις*²¹⁰. Epiphanius apparently drew his concept of “mother-heresies” from the Pauline Epistle (Col. 3:11). Namely, these four are at the origin of all the posterior heresies²¹¹.

Interestingly, Epiphanius implies that the difference between “superstition” and (Greek philosophical) “heresy” lies in the presence or absence of piety, *θεοσεβεία*: while superstitious belief is lacking piety, heresy (in this particular case Epiphanius refers to Greek philosophical heresies) has been endowed with it.

Schism and heresy in Panarion

Epiphanius employs the term schism, *σχίσμα* twice: speaking of heresies number 68 and 70. It may seem, judging by the following example, that he uses these two terms synonymously²¹², since he enlists the schism of the Audiens under the 70th heresy. In his opening words, Epiphanius states that he will present various “heresies and schisms” (*αιρέσεων καὶ σχισμάτων*), which amount to eighty in total²¹³. As Aline Pourkier justly observes, Epiphanius could have been led to this classification by St. Paul²¹⁴ and his statement on schisms and heresies²¹⁵. Nevertheless, in his passage on the heresy of the Audiens, he undoubtedly stresses that this group belongs to the Orthodox Christianity and by no means falls into heresy; however, it does represent a schism²¹⁶. Referring to Aline Pourkier’s conclusion on this segment, the term “heresy”, *αἵρεσις*, designates a “sect”, whereas the term “schism”, *σχίσμα*, alludes to the fragmented isle within heresy²¹⁷.

²¹⁰ Panarion, ed. Holl (1915) 165, I.

²¹¹ cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 95.

²¹² cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 90, 91.

²¹³ Panarion, Prologue I, 3, I, ed. Holl, 156, 28 – 157, 29.

²¹⁴ I Cor. 11:18–19.

²¹⁵ cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 91.

²¹⁶ cf. Panarion, ed. Holl (1915) 22, 2–3.

²¹⁷ cf. Pourkier, L’Hérésiologie chez Épiphane 91.

I.4. HERESY versus PAGANISM

HERESIES ON THE INTERNAL LEVEL versus HERESIES ON THE EXTERNAL PLANE – towards another type of classification of religious dissent²¹⁸

“It is impossible, utterly impossible, for a man who has been fettered and subjugated by intestine enemies, and who has sold himself to his passions, to be able to overcome outside enemies. If we wish to destroy the latter, let us first of all take heed to subjugate our internal foes, let us end their rebellion and strife” - ...*Ἄν οὖν ἐκείνους καθελεῖν ἐθελήσωμεν, πολὺ πρότερον τοὺς ἐντὸς πολεμίους ὑποτάξαι σπουδάσωμεν, τὴν τούτων στάσιν καὶ τὴν ἔριν καταλύσωμεν*²¹⁹.

The aim of this section is an attempt of another subdivision of heresy, or, religious dissent, through defining what we might frame as those at the internal level, that is, related to the interior structures of Christological doctrinal issues, and those lying at the fringes of the core Christian notions²²⁰. In the first aggrupation fall the Christological and Trinitarian debates, which marked the very beginnings of the definitions of the Christian creed, and range from Arianism, Nestorianism, and other incongruities debated at the Ecumenical Synods, to Pelagianism, Adoptionism, and to the Predestination debate, *Filioque* and Iconoclasm which marked the 9th-century theological narratives²²¹. On the other hand, the heresies ascribed to the margins of the Christological disputes encompass paganism, other belief systems, Paulicians, Bogomils, and Manichaeans (to name only some)²²². I shall attempt to detect if there are differences in authors’ narrative, exposition, and discourse when dealing with these subdivisions of heresy/religious dissent.

In this chapter, I shall thus lay the contours of what may be considered another attempt at classifying heretical and divergent religious thought. I shall hereby align with the afore-

²¹⁸ This chapter represents a preliminary stage of a more exhaustive research which will follow.

²¹⁹ C. Mango, *The Homilies of Photius Patriarch of Constantinople* (Cambridge-MA 1958) 107, 4th homily; B. Λαουρδα, *Φωτίου Ὁμιλίαι* (Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda, Thessalonica 1959) 50, l. 7–12.

²²⁰ Another possible terminological framing of these two heretical concepts would be to refer to these notions as to “ento-” and “exo-” heresies; cf. C. C. Ames, *Medieval Heresies: Christianity, Judaism, and Islam* (Cambridge 2015) 113, 126-127.

²²¹ Cf. W. Otten, *The texture of tradition. The role of the Church Fathers in Carolingian Theology*, in: *The Reception of the Church Fathers in the West*, ed. I. Backus I (Leiden/New York/Köln 1997) 3–50.

²²² Cf. C. Ludwig, *The Paulicians and ninth-century Byzantine thought*, in: *Byzantine in the 9th Century: Dead or Alive? Papers from the Thirtieth Spring Symposium of Byzantine Studies*. Birmingham, March 1996, ed. L. Brubaker (Aldershot 1998) 23–36.

mentioned and exposed sequences related to the language of heresy and the classification of heresies; furthermore, I shall expand the overview and perspective by comparing the examples relevant to the textual treatment of heresies with that of paganism. Additionally, the interrelations and comparisons between different heresies in the selected texts will be demonstrated as well, with the intention of reaching possible means of classifying heresies into those pertaining to the inner, inherent Christological structures, and those having emerged on the fringes of Christian Creed. Nonetheless, in this section, the heresies have been positioned in a comparative perspective (from the point of view of the given authors) but rather than being compared thematically (as in the case, for example, of revival of old heresies, presented in the section “old-new heresies” below), these have been contrasted purely on nominative, non-substantial phenomenological grounds. That is to say, the authors’ (intentional or unintentional) demonstrations of interconnectedness between different heresies, between those on the “internal” and “external” plane, and between heresies and paganism will be shown.

The scholarly problematic of this chapter falls in the semantic field of “otherness”. Several recent studies have dealt with the question of “otherness” in relation to the Early Medieval history and religion²²³.

Despite all their divergences and differences, the Christian East and West were, nevertheless, to a certain extent, theoretically and conceptually united against barbarians and foreigners who dwelled beyond their boundaries and waited for convenient moments to invade their territories. Does the need to describe those foreigners as “the others” and heretics spring from that fact? However, the notion of the heresies encompassing the “exterior” and “interior” Christological plane was most likely nuanced in the medieval Christian consciousness²²⁴. Even in the earlier theological disputes, preceding the Iconoclast crisis, religious differences had at times been referred to as heresies.

²²³ Ts. Stepanov, *The Bulgars and the Steppe Empire in the Early Middle Ages. The Problem of the Others* (Leiden/Boston 2010); Id., *Periphery as Universe*, in: *Byzantinoslavica* 59 (1998) fasc. 2, 247–254; Id., *From ‘steppe’ to Christian empire and back: Bulgaria between 800 and 1100*, in: *The Other Europe in the Middle Ages: Avars, Bulgars, Khazars and Cumans*, ed. F. Kurta (Leiden/Boston 2007) 363–378; Id./G. Kazakov ed., *Medieval Christianitas: different regions, “faces”, approaches*, *Mediaevalia Christiana III* (Sofia 2010); E.Iricinschi/H.M.Zellentin, *Making selves and marking others: identity and Late Antique heresiologies*, in: *Introduction to Heresy and Identity in Late Antiquity*, ed. Id. (Tübingen 2008) 1–27; cf. W. Pohl, *Introduction: Strategies of identification. A methodological profile*, in: *Strategies of Identification. Ethnicity and Religion in Early Medieval Europe*, ed. Id./G.Heydemann (Turnhout 2013) 1–64.

²²⁴ Cf. H. Chadwick, *East and West: The Making of a Rift in the Church* (Oxford 2003) 29.

The following two sections analyzes how problematics related to the pagan and heretical “others” were treated: the debates over inherent Christian doctrines, and those situated at the fringes of Christianity.

The Theodosian Code equates the heretics with the pagans in the eyes of law:

*Omnia, quae in donatistas, qui et montenses vocantur, manichaeos sive priscillianistas vel in gentiles a nobis generalium legum auctoritate decreta sunt, non solum manere decernimus, verum in executionem plenissimam effectumque deduci, ita ut aedificia quoque vel horum vel caelicolarum etiam, qui nescio cuius dogmatis novi conventus habent, ecclesiis vindicentur...*²²⁵

Additionally, it is explained why the pagans and the heretics are dangerous and why the Donatists, heretics, and the Jews throw the sacraments of the Catholic faith into confusion.

*Defensorum curialium omniumque officiorum specula custodiat, ne quis intra aliquam civitatem vel ulla territorii parte secreta, qui ab ecclesiae catholico sacerdote dissidet, illicitae coitionis habeat facultatem. Ipsa etiam loca iuri publico sociari seclusa omni excusatione censemus et proscriptos eos in exilium detrudi, qui audent disputare ea et adserere, quae institutio divina condemnat*²²⁶.

Comparison between those abiding in error is emphasized: The Donatists are designated as heretics, and compared to others, who have fallen in error – to the Jews and the gentiles, commonly referred to as pagans.

*Post alia: ne donatistae vel ceterorum vanitas haereticorum aliorumque eorum, quibus catholicae communionis cultus non potest persuaderi, iudaei adque gentiles, quos vulgo paganos appellant, arbitrentur legum ante adversum se datarum constituta tepuisse, noverint iudices universi praeceptis earum fideli devotione parendum et inter praecipua curarum quidquid adversus eos decrevimus non ambigant exsequendum*²²⁷.

The Theodosian Code alludes in analogous manner to the Jews, pagans and heretics, and their “nefarious superstition”:

²²⁵ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri*, 869; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.43, 458.

²²⁶ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri*, 870; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.45, 450.

²²⁷ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri*, 870; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.46, 458.

*Montanistas et priscillianistas et alia huiusmodi genera nefariae superstitionis per multiplicata scita divalia diversa ultionum supplicia contemnentes ad sacramenta quidem militiae, quae nostris obsecundat imperiis, nequaquam admitti censemus...*²²⁸

The Jewish faith is considered to be a *nefaria secta*²²⁹, or *Iudaeorum secta*²³⁰, whereas heresy is equaled to superstition: the heresy of *Caelicolarum* is referred to as *novum crimen superstitionis*, and also as *perversitas iudaica*²³¹

The suppression of the pagan abomination has been encouraged, and of the Judaic, as well as heretical “spirit”:

*Nota sunt adque omnibus divulgata nostra maiorumque decreta, quibus abominandorum paganorum, iudaeorum etiam adque haereticorum spiritum audaciamque compressimus*²³².

The Theodosian Code speaks also against pagan sacrifices:

*Cesset superstitio, sacrificiorum aboleatur insania*²³³, whereas the pagan cult is referred to as a cult of the sheer superstition - *cultus vanae superstitionis*²³⁴.

The pagans – *hoc est gentiles*, who have a vicious mind - *sceleratae mentis paganae*²³⁵ - are polluted by the pagan error, and are to be excluded from the military, administrative and judicial service of the state:

*...qui profano pagani ritus errore seu crimine polluuntur, hoc est gentiles, nec ad militiam admittantur nec administratoris vel iudicis honore decorentur*²³⁶.

Additionally, those who abandon the Catholic faith – thus having ceased to participate in the genuine religion, *rectae religionis participes*²³⁷ - and adhere to the pagan cults, are deprived of the Roman law (testament included):

²²⁸ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 871; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.48, 458–9.

²²⁹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 887; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.8.1, 1, 467.

²³⁰ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 889; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.8.9, 468.

²³¹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 891–892; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.8.19, 469.

²³² Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 894; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.8.26, 470–471.

²³³ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 897; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.10.2, 472.

²³⁴ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 902; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.10.18, 475.

²³⁵ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 905; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.10.25, 476.

²³⁶ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 904; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.10.21, 475–476.

²³⁷ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 896–897; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.9.4, 472.

*Christianis ac fidelibus, qui ad paganos ritus cultusque migrarunt, omnem in quamcumque personam testamenti condendi interdiciamus potestatem, ut sint absque iure Romano*²³⁸.

The Justinian Code delves into descriptions of pagan religions, and, for example, of the Jewish superstition, termed as *iudaica superstitio*, as already mentioned above:

*...sancimus contra orthodoxos quidem litigantes nemini haeretico vel etiam his qui iudaicam superstitionem colunt esse in testimonia communionem, sive utraque pars orthodoxa sit sive altera*²³⁹ ... *Iudaei romano communi iure viventes in his causis, quae tam ad superstitionem eorum quam ad forum et leges ac iura pertinent...*²⁴⁰

The pagan superstition, *pagana superstitio*, is also described; the congregations of the pagans are forbidden, whereas certain heresies are judged similar to one another:

*Inter se autem haeticis vel iudaeis, ubi litigandum existimaverint, concedimus foedus permixtum et dignos litigatoribus etiam testes introduci, exceptis scilicet his, quos vel manichaeus furor (cuius partem et borboritas esse manifestissimum est) vel pagana superstitio detinet, samaritis nihilo minus et qui illis non absimiles sunt, id est montanistis et tascodrogis et ophitis, quibus pro reatus similitudine omnis legitimus actus interdictus est*²⁴¹.

The sacred Christian faith is opposed to the heretical superstition (*sancta fides* versus *haeretica superstitio*); those who betrayed the sacred faith and baptism and exchanged it for heretical superstition are segregated:

*Ii, qui sanctam fidem prodiderint et sanctum baptisma haeretica superstitione profanaverint, a consortio omnium segregati sint, a testimoniis alieni, testamenti, ut ante iam sanximus, non habeant factionem, nulli in hereditate succedant, a nemine scribantur heredes*²⁴².

The Justinian Code oppose Christian religion to the infamous sect – *christiana religio* versus *nefanda secta*:

²³⁸ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 884; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.7.2, 465.

²³⁹ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.21pr.

²⁴⁰ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.9.8pr; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 61.

²⁴¹ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.21.1.

²⁴² Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.7.3pr; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 60.

*Eum, quicumque servum seu ingenuum, invitum vel suasionem plectenda, ex cultu christianae religionis in nefandam sectam ritumve traduxerit, cum dispendio fortunarum capite puniendum censemus*²⁴³; furthermore, the worship of the (Christian) God is opposed to the ferocious sect of the Jews – *feralis secta Iudaeorum vs Dei cultus*:

*Iudaeis et maioribus eorum et patriarchis volumus intimari, quod, si quis post hanc legem aliquem, qui eorum feralem fugerit sectam et ad dei cultum respexerit...*²⁴⁴

Heresy is seen as a new superstitious crime, as opposed to the cult of the Christian God – *novum crimen superstitionis* (Caelicolarum) versus *dei cultus veneratioque christiana*:

*Caelicolarum nomen inauditum quodammodo novum crimen superstitionis vindicavit. Ii, nisi ad dei cultum venerationemque christianam conversi fuerint, his legibus, quibus praecipimus haereticos adstringi, se quoque noverint attinendos*²⁴⁵.

The Justinian Code underlines the interdiction to pagan divinatory practices:

*Ne quis mortalium ita faciendi sacrificii sumat audaciam, ut inspectione iecoris extorumque praesagio vanae spem promissionis accipiat vel, quod est deterius, futura sub execrabili consultatione cognoscat. acerbioris etenim imminet supplicii cruciatus eis, qui contra vetitum praesentium vel futurarum rerum explorare temptaverint veritatem*²⁴⁶; moreover, the pagan superstition - *pagana superstitio* - equals to public crime:

*Nemo ea, quae saepius paganae superstitionis hominibus interdicta sunt, audeat pertemptare, sciens, quod crimen publicum committit qui haec ausus fuerit perpetrare*²⁴⁷.

²⁴³ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.7.5; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 60.

²⁴⁴ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.9.3; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 61.

²⁴⁵ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.9.12pr; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 61.

²⁴⁶ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.11.2; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 62.

²⁴⁷ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.11.8pr; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 63.

I.4.1. Heresies pertaining to the inner structures of Christianity

Internal heresy in Byzantium

The following events which have occurred on the internal plane (if observed through the above-proposed lens) and resulted in theological controversies, shall occupy the predominant place in the ensuing research segment: Iconoclasm (717-843), Moechian heresy (Theodore, the Moechian Synod of 809-811), and the *Filioque* controversy (860's).

The Council of Nicaea II in 787 proclaimed the icon worship Orthodox²⁴⁸. Images of the Holy Trinity and the Saints were considered to fall into the rank of the (unwritten) tradition. Namely, between 786 and 815, a short period marked by the re-introduced veneration of the icons was attested in Byzantium.

As will be demonstrated, the Iconoclasts were brought into connection and compared with the Paulicians on numerous occasions, who would occupy the ranks of the “external” heretics.

When the Byzantine Emperor Leo V the Armenian opened the second era of the Iconoclast strife, Patriarch Nicephorus and Theodore the Studite stood up as the firmest opponents of the Iconoclast position. They presented the Iconophile teaching in its most comprehensive and ample form. Nicephorus underlined the fact that the adoration of the icons did not represent idolatry.

Nicephorus considered Iconoclasm to be a new form of Monophysitism and Monothelitism, reinforced by the Jewish and Arabic influence. In other words, while the Orthodoxy strives to preserve the unity of the divine and human natures in Christ, the heretical concepts attempt to dissociate these two natures²⁴⁹.

According to some authors, the Manicheans and the Iconoclasts seem to have fallen into the analogous aggragation²⁵⁰. It would nevertheless be important to establish if there are grounds to divide different heretical trends into “inner” and “outer”, and to examine if they were treated differently by the sources, following the line of that division, both in Byzantium and in Francia. The connection between the Arabs and the Paulicians was clear to some of the

²⁴⁸ Cf. Mansi XIII, 377 CD.

²⁴⁹ Nicephorus (ed. Migne, PG 100) 201–850, here 528 C–533; Tatakis, *Vizantijska filosofija* 135.

²⁵⁰ For more information on iconoclasm, Persia, and outer enemy, see: J. Pargoire, *L'Église byzantine de 527 à 847* (New York 1971) 272; C. Lagier, *L'Orient Chretien*, 1, *Des apôtres jusqu'à Photius* (de l'an 33 à l'an 850) (Paris 1935²) 409–434.

authors²⁵¹. On the other hand, Theophanes Confessor seems to equate the Manicheans with the Paulicians²⁵².

Due to the fact that the imperial edicts, theological disputes and acts of the Iconoclast councils held in 753-754 and in 815 were destroyed upon the victory of the Iconophile fraction, the Iconoclast literature is confined to the indirect accounts preserved in the texts of the Orthodox theologians. Iconoclast ideas appeared even before the outburst of the Iconoclast crisis, in the writings of Epiphanius of Salamis. The question of the veneration of the icons might also be understood, in effect, as a reflection of Christological disputes.

John of Damascus wrote immensely on the Iconophiles and on the Iconoclasts as well. In his arguments in support of the adoration of images, John of Damascus followed Pseudo-Dionysius's view of the icon as a symbol leading towards God, representing a symbolic expression of the unutterable²⁵³. It has been observed that this Iconoclast crisis influenced also the Bogumils and other 9th-century heretical movements. The curious connection between the dualistic movements and icons has been explored²⁵⁴.

Interestingly, the patriarchs of the 9th century equated Paulicians and Montanists with extreme Iconoclasts²⁵⁵.

The Paulicians were also allying with the Arabs, Byzantine's enemies. There are some accounts in the Byzantine sources witnessing the connection between the Paulicians and Iconoclasts²⁵⁶, and even on the alliance between Joseph, leader of the Manicheans and the Saracenes: namely, Joseph asked for their support and apparently obtained it²⁵⁷. This shows us that the heretics and dissenting groups pertaining to the "interior" and "exterior" plane were in contact and even "collaborated", if we could say so, at some occasions and in particular contexts. Other examples on the contacts and mutual support of the "interior" and "exterior" dissenting movements could be found in case of Thomas the Slav. Namely, Thomas the Slav

²⁵¹ Cf. S. Runciman, *The Medieval Manichee* (Cambridge 1969, 4. ed.) 58.

²⁵² C. Mango/Scott, R. ed., *The Chronicle of Theophanes Confessor. Byzantine and Near Eastern History AD 284 – 813* (Oxford 2006) 679; cf. *Theophane Continuatus* (ed. Migne, PG 118) 801; For more detailed information on the Paulicians, see: Pargoire, *Église byzantine 284–286*; Runciman, *Medieval Manichee* 26–62.

²⁵³ John of Damascus (ed. Migne, PG 94–96) *De Imaginibus Oratio I* (ed. Migne, PG 94) 1231–1283, here 1260B.

²⁵⁴ Cf. A. Avenarius, *The Byzantine Struggle Over the Icon: On the Problem of Eastern European Symbolism* (Bratislava 2005).

²⁵⁵ Cf. Runciman, *Medieval Manichee* 61; John of Damascus, *Letter of the Eastern Patriarchs to Theophilus: Epistola ad Theophilum Imperatorem De Sanctis et Venerandis Imaginibus* (ed. Migne, PG 95) 345–385, here 373–376.

²⁵⁶ Runciman, *Medieval Manichee* 56–58.

²⁵⁷ Cf. Runciman, *Medieval Manichee* 35.

united the Paulicians and the Iconophiles, in a certain way²⁵⁸. Photius, apart from others, is the source and speaks on the Manicheans²⁵⁹. Photius was significantly informed on the Paulicians, and was included in disputes with them, as the representative of Basil I in 869²⁶⁰.

In the early 9th century, Theophanes Confessor accused the Byzantine Empire of being too tolerant towards the heretics, the Tetradiatai, Paulicians, Athingans and Iconoclasts²⁶¹.

Apart from being strongly opposed to the Moechian heresy (from Greek *μοιχεία*, adultery²⁶²), Theodore the Studite was leading monks of the Studion monastery who represented radical opposition to Patriarch Tarasius (784-806) and his punishment of the simoniac bishops upon the Council of Nicaea in 787, which condemned Iconoclasm and allowed those Iconoclast bishops who repented to continue with their functions²⁶³. Theodore provides us with significant amount of information on the Synod of 787, which rehabilitated the Iconoclast bishops²⁶⁴. In the next letter, Theodore explains his urge to fight for the Orthodox faith. The letter was most likely written in 809, during his second exile. The Synod of 809 had, under the pretext of the struggle for the *Oikonomia*, abolished the Gospels. Theodore the Studite labeled it a heresy²⁶⁵.

Theodore's letter 59, written between 821 and 826, is only one of many to refer to the Iconoclast controversy. Besides, Theodore enlists undesirable deeds which are to exist in a monastery: greed, conflict and disobedience²⁶⁶. In contrast to Photius, Theodore did not compare the Iconoclasts to Arians: he, on the other hand, compared the Iconoclasts with the Manichaeans, Montanists, Valentinians and Marcionites²⁶⁷.

²⁵⁸ For more information on Thomas the Slav, see below; P. Lemerle, Thomas le Slave, in: *Travaux et Mémoires I* (1965) 255–297, here 294–6; J. B. Bury, *A History of the Eastern Roman Empire: From the Fall of Irene to the Ascension of Basil I (A.D. 802 – 867)* (London 1912) 109–110; however, Lemerle does not seem to agree: Lemerle, *Thomas le Slave* 267.

²⁵⁹ Cf. Peter of Sicily, *Historia Manichaeorum* (ed. Migne, PG 104) 1240 – 1304.

²⁶⁰ Runciman, *Medieval Manichee* 46–47; on Photius's opinion on the term "Paulicians": Runciman, *Medieval Manichee* 47.

²⁶¹ Mango, *Homilies* 282.

²⁶² For a more ample analysis of the Moechian controversy, see below, II.9; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae I*, Ep. 53. (ed. Migne, PG 99) 1102C–1108B.

²⁶³ Cf. F. Dvornik, *The Photian Schism. History and Legend* (Cambridge 1948, reprinted 1970) 8.

²⁶⁴ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae I*, Ep. 38, ed. Migne 1041BC–1045C.

²⁶⁵ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae I*, Ep. 39, *Corpus Fontium Historiae Byzantinae* 31/I (ed. G. Fatouros, Berlin/New York 1992) 183–4, 112–114.

²⁶⁶ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae I*, Ep. 59, ed. Fatouros 203–204; 170–171.

²⁶⁷ cf. Mango, *Homilies* 239, note 20; Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae I*, Ep. 8, ed. Migne 1132C; *Ibid.*, Ep. 72, ed. Migne 1305A; *Ibid.*, Ep. 81, ed. Migne 1321D; *Ibid.*, Ep. 162, ed. Migne 1513C; *Ibid.*, Ep. 199, ed. Migne 1604C.

Photius refers to Iconoclasm as to a doctrine directed against God - ἡ θεομάχη γνώμη. In his numerous letters, he frequently wrote on Iconoclasts²⁶⁸. In the letter addressed to Boris of Bulgaria, Photius discussed the topics related to the icon worship and to the 7th Ecumenical Council²⁶⁹.

A significant amount of research has been undertaken on the Iconoclasm and the Iconoclast crisis in the scope of the Byzantine historical situation of the 9th century.²⁷⁰ Photius also attacks the Iconoclasts in letters addressed to John Chrysocheir, the leader of the Paulicians in Asia Minor²⁷¹. On such occasions, Photius frequently recurs to quoting verses from St. Paul and John the Chrysostom²⁷².

In his third homily against the Iconoclasts, Photius refers to the impious and wicked doctrines of the Iconoclasts, by frequently comparing them to the Arians.²⁷³

Photius intended his 18th homily to be a general condemnation of all heresies, among which Iconoclasm was accentuated²⁷⁴. Photius's 15th-18th homilies are on Arianism and Iconoclasm. In his 16th homily, Photius compares Arianism with Iconoclasm²⁷⁵. Apart from Photius, Patriarch Nicephorus also compared Iconoclasm and Arianism²⁷⁶.

In 847, an internal conflict (schism) was brought into the clergy ranks upon the enthronement of Patriarch Ignatius, against which Photius had fought²⁷⁷. In his 16th homily, apart from describing more in detail the similarities of the doctrines of the Arians and the Iconoclasts, Photius deducts the common elements of their *modus operandi* between the Arian heresy and

²⁶⁸ ΦΩΤΙΟΥ ΕΠΙΣΤΟΛΑΙ, ed. I. Βαλεττα (Photius, Epistolae, ed. I. Valetta, London 1864): Ep. 43 (338–341), Ep. 76 (400–402), Ep. 56–60 (358–362), Ep. 108 (429–431). See F. Dvornik, The Patriarch Photius and Iconoclasm, *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 7 (1953) 67–98, here 87; F. Dvornik, *The Photian Schism* (Cambridge 1948).

²⁶⁹ Cf. Photius, Epistolae, ed. Valetta 216–219.

²⁷⁰ Meyendorff, *Byzantine Theology* 42.

²⁷¹ Photius, Epistolae, ed. Valetta 358–360 (Ep. 56, 58, 59); cf. Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, in: *Les sources grecques pour l'histoire des Pauliciens d'Asie Mineure*, ed. Ch. Astruc/W. Conus-Wolska/J. Gouillard/P. Lemerle/D. Papachryssanthou/J. Paramelle, in: *Travaux et mémoires* 4 (1970) 99–227, here 96–113; on Chrysocheir, see: P. Lemerle, *L'histoire des Pauliciens d'Asie Mineure d'après les sources grecques*, in: *Travaux et mémoires* (1973) 1–144, here 96–103.

²⁷² D. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios of Constantinople: His Life, Scholarly Contributions, and Correspondence Together with a Translation of Fifty-two of His Letters* (Brookline-MA 1981) 90; Photius, Epistolae, ed. Valetta 360–362 (Ep. 60).

²⁷³ Cf. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios* 91–92; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 155.

²⁷⁴ Cf. Mango, *Homilies* 22.

²⁷⁵ Mango, *Homilies* 264–266; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 154–155.

²⁷⁶ cf. Mango, *Homilies* 239, note 19: cf. Nicephorus, *Anthirrheticis tres adversus Constantinum* (ed. Migne, PG 100) 205–534, here 244 D, 561A–B, 796C.

²⁷⁷ For more information on the *Filioque* controversy, see below; cf. Photius, Epistolae, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 200–248.

Iconoclasm²⁷⁸: under the guise of piety - *κατασηματίζονται τὴν εὐσέβειαν*²⁷⁹, these heretics are imbibed by the poison of heresy, and disobedient - , as they have, Photius argues, a snake for a teacher, who has admixed the deadly venom to the semblance of wisdom and goodly manners: *ἔχουσι γὰρ τὸν ὄφιν διδάσκαλον, ὃς ἐν προνοίας καὶ φιλοφροσύνης προσχίματι τὸν ἰὸν τοῦ θανάτου τῇ παρακοῇ κερασάμενος ...*²⁸⁰. Later, when their audience was already prepared, they used the pure poison of impiety in their speech.

Judging by the written proofs on the dissenting group of *Euchtai*, a sort of transformation of dissenting groups into dualistic ones occurred in 10th-century Bulgaria – which offers testimony of alteration and a shift from “interior” dissenting movements into “exterior” ones²⁸¹.

*Heresies inherent to the inner Christian structures in the West: the echos of the Iconoclast crisis in the West*²⁸²; *the Predestination controversy*

Gottschalk of Orbais (ca. 804-868), a young monk, given as a child oblate to the monastery of Fulda, came in conflict with Hrabanus Maurus, one of the leading theologians of the epoch. This conflict became more intense particularly from the 840ies onwards, when Gottschalk raised a predestinarian controversy induced by his doctrine of twofold predestination. Gottschalk was accused of heresy in 847, at the synod held in Mainz, and spent almost the last twenty years of his life in the prison of Hautvillers.

Potestas and *hierarchia*, orthodoxy and heresy, consensus / dissensus – constituted the cardinal threads of the network Gottschalk found himself navigating in, while operating in the interspace between secular and sacred²⁸³. The controversy about Gottschalk was not just a single, isolated case, but a part of a huge crisis that befell the Carolingian society. In the first half of the 9th century, theology was established as a substantial exercise ground of social discourse and thus a significant marker of social change²⁸⁴.

²⁷⁸ Mango, *Homilies* 264–266, Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 154–156.

²⁷⁹ Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 155, l. 2.

²⁸⁰ Cf. Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 152–163 (16. Homily), here 154.

²⁸¹ Cf. E. Barker, *Social and Political Thought in Byzantium, From Iustinian I to the Last Palaeologus: Passages from Byzantine Authors and Documents* (Oxford 1961) 250.

²⁸² Cf. P. Brown, *A dark-age crisis. Aspects of the Iconoclastic controversy*, in: *Doctrine and Debate in the East Christian World, 300 – 1500*, ed. A. Cameron/R. Hoyland (Farnham 2011) 237–270, and especially 241–245; This topic has been elaborated below, mostly in chapters II.2, and II.5.

²⁸³ Cf. my article, *Gottschalk of Orbais, Eberhard of Friuli and Alfred the Great: supporting the dissident thought, or, yearning for learning?*, in: *Spomenica dr Tibora Živkovića*, ed. I. Cvijanović, Institute for History (Belgrade 2016) 65–75.

²⁸⁴ The majority of the writings of Gottschalk of Orbais was discovered in 1930, edited fifteen years later and only recently translated into English, with substantial and encompassing historical and political overview of the climate

Gottschalk's interpretation of Augustine's doctrine on divine predestination and unconditional preordination to eternal life or eternal death was seen as a great threat to the ruling political and ecclesiastical circles, who were focused upon maintaining the delicately balanced political and moral unity in the Frankish realm²⁸⁵. This controversy, induced by Gottschalk, was also understood as a conflict-struggle over the correct interpretation of Saint Augustine, and over the employment of patristic and biblical authorities in political purposes. The predestination controversy can by all means be observed and comprehended as a re-actualization of the far more ancient debates on heresies, issues concerning divine grace and free will²⁸⁶.

The Synod held in Mainz in 848, which condemned Gottschalk as a heretic, was presided by Louis the German, king of the East Francia (c. 804 – 876). Following the synod's decisions, Gottschalk was expelled to the territory under the rule of Charles the Bald, in the archbishoprics of Reims. The Synod of Quierzy (849) called by Hincmar, archbishop of Reims, and presided by Charles the Bald, condemned Gottschalk as a heretic and guilty of breaking the monastic rules (*stabilitas loci*) and sojourning outside the monastery, as *monachus gyrovagus*. Gottschalk was sent to the abbey of Hautvillers, situated in the archbishoprics of Reims, and spent the last years of his life there. Eriugena got involved in the controversy (850/1), which later spread to the South of the Carolingian lands as well²⁸⁷. The Synods organized in Soissons

in which the Gottschalk's controversy spread: C. Lambot, *Oeuvres théologiques et grammaticales de Godescalc d'Orbais* (Louvain 1945); V. Genke/Gumerlock, F., *Gottschalk and a Medieval Predestination Controversy* (Milwaukee-WI 2010); The most recent works which significantly contribute to the exploration of Gottschalk's controversy and intellectual culture include, among others, the dissertations of Warren Pezé and Matthew Gillis: W. Pezé, *Le virus de l'erreur. Essai d'histoire sociale sur la controverse prédestinatienne à l'époque carolingienne*, PhD Thesis (Paris 2014); Id., *Le virus de l'erreur: la controverse carolingienne sur la double prédestination: essai d'histoire sociale* (Turnhout 2017); M. Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais: A Study of Power and Spirituality in a Ninth-Century Life*, PhD Thesis (Charlottesville-VA 2009); Id., *Heresy and Dissent in the Carolingian Empire: The Case of Gottschalk of Orbais* (Oxford 2017); K. Zechiel-Eckes, *Die Kontroverse um die göttliche Prädestination*, in: *Florus von Lyon als Kirchenpolitiker und Publizist*, ed. Id. (Stuttgart 1999) 77–177.

²⁸⁵ Cf. F. Gumerlock, *Gottschalk of Orbais: A Medieval Predestination*, in: *Kerux* 22:3 (December 2007) 17–34; D. Ganz, *The Debate on Predestination*, in: *Charles the Bald: Court and Kingdom*, ed. M. Gibson/Nelson, J. (Oxford 1981) 283–302.

²⁸⁶ For more extensive information on the topic, see: M. De Jong, *The Penitential State: Authority and Atonement in the Reign of Louis the Pious* (Cambridge 2009); C. Chazelle, *The Crucified God in the Carolingian Era* (Cambridge 2002); N. P. Tanner, *The Councils of the Church* (New York 2001); G. C. Stead, *Doctrine and Philosophy in Early Christianity* (Aldershot 2000); Otten, *The Texture of Tradition*; E. Clark, *The Origenist Controversy. The Cultural Construction of an Early Christian Debate* (Princeton 1992); H. Chadwick, *Heresy and Orthodoxy in the Early Church*, (Aldershot 1991).

²⁸⁷ Eriugena composed his *De Divina Praedestinatione* in 850/851 and got involved in the controversy. Other intellectuals got involved in the controversy as well (Florus of Lyon, Prudentius of Troyes, Lupus of Ferrières). From then on, the controversy spread to the South of the Frankish realm as well, cf. Genke/Gumerlock, *Gottschalk and a Medieval Predestination Controversy* 48-50; Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais* 245; on the more encompassing picture of the controversy, see: Ganz, *The Debate on predestination*; Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais* 265-273.

(853), Valence (855) and Tusey (860) marked the final end of the controversy. Pope Nicholas I (858 – 867) briefly intervened in the dispute²⁸⁸.

I.4.2. Heresies at the fringes of the Christianity: official Christianity versus other belief systems (Paganism and other religions)

Bordering, or, liminal religious phenomena may offer criterion according to which it would be possible to separate and analyze paganism and other religions, since paganism was affected by an outer force of missionary and baptismal endeavors. Namely, paganism as such was often considered by Early Medieval Christian missionaries only as an erroneous state of religious minds, which should be corrected, if not utterly eradicated, and finally transformed into Christianity. The final aim of this formational and transformational process undertaken by Christian missionaries was unambiguous: baptism into the Christian rite²⁸⁹. However, these processes did not flow so smoothly, and the Latin chronicles very frequently describe that, for instance, *Slavi denuo relapsi sunt ad paganismum*, which became almost a *topos* in Latin medieval chronicles. This sentence exactly describes the interspace between the two - the previous, pagan, and the new, Christian grounds: the liminality of such states merits an additional comprehensive study of the kind, which should analyze more in detail the impeding factors which prolonged, or halted the Christianization process, and the facilitating ones, which led to the more swift and stable embracement of Christianity among the pagan populations in question²⁹⁰.

The key-question to be posed is the following: do the authors use identical terms when referring to heresy and paganism, i.e. other religions? In this chapter, the study of the linguistic relics,

²⁸⁸ Pope Nicholas I (858-867) got interested in Gottschalk's view of predestination and the debate in general; he thus asked Hincmar in 863 to present himself and his standpoint at the Synod of Metz in 863, which never occurred. More extensively on this issue: Gillis, Gottschalk of Orbais 332–339; Genke/Gummerlock, Gottschalk and a Medieval Predestination Controversy 53–54.

²⁸⁹ J. Shepard, Spreading the Word: Byzantine Missions, in *The Oxford History of Byzantium*, ed. C.Mango (Oxford 2002) 230–247; Id., Orthodoxy and Northern Peoples: Goods, Gods and Guidelines, in: *A Companion to Byzantium*, ed. L. James (Oxford 2010) 171–186.

²⁹⁰ Ninth century was marked by various contacts, established by Francia, Rome and Byzantium with adherents of religions, others than Christianity. These included first of all the Slavs, the Bulgars, the Danes, the Arabs, the Paulicians, the Bogumils, the Manicheans.

elements and expressions dating from the pagan and antiquity cults may be applied to the Early Medieval heresies, but the scope of the present work does not allow the in-depth scrutiny of this research axis²⁹¹.

It would also be important to decipher the literary styles inherited from the Antiquity, including rhetorical code and strategies – how the classical authors spoke of the members of the other religious groups. Namely, the classical reminiscences have undoubtedly survived in the Early Medieval literary approaches to this thematic: for instance, the topics related to allegorical exile, which will be analyzed in another chapter²⁹².

In the collective consciousness, the particular external enemy of the people in question, was often equated with the Devil (or Evil). This is due to the concept of the foreigner, of the “other” – who bears the traits of a malevolent opponent and at times shares common features with the heretics, enemies, and members of other groups in common.

The concept of the “other” and “otherness” is more clearly and distinctly observable in the example of the notions that Christians had of those belonging to other religious groups²⁹³. It is not so poignant and obvious as in the cases when Christians contrasted themselves to the Christian heretics.

The Christian relation to the pagan, or, polytheistic concept, may be detected through the finely-led logical hypothesis of pivotal theological notions. John of Damascus, for example, develops his ideas on polytheism in the following way: God is one; according to that, the existence of many gods would imply the notion of imperfection. Perfection implies one God only²⁹⁴.

Missionary activities represent an encompassing grounds for performing this study on the contacts between the Byzantines and Franks with foreigners, often labelled as pagans²⁹⁵.

²⁹¹ I plan to consecrate some of further research on this problematic.

²⁹² See below, chapter II.13.; cf. J. Irigoien, *Survie et renouveau de la littérature antique à Constantinople (IXe siècle)*, Cahiers de civilisation médiévale: Xe – XIIe siècle, 5 (1962) 287–302, here 289–290.

²⁹³ Cf. D. Müller, *Our image of ‘Others’ and the own identity*, in: *Iconoclasm and Iconoclasm. Struggle for Religious Identity. Jewish and Christian Perspectives Series 14*, ed. W. v. Asselt/P. v. Geest/D. Müller/Th. Salemink (Leiden/Boston 2007) 107–125; cf. D. C. Smythe, *Insiders and Outsiders*, in: *A Companion to Byzantium*, ed. L. James (Oxford 2010) 67–80.

²⁹⁴ John of Damascus, *Expositio Accurata Fidei Orthodoxae* (ed. Migne, PG 94) 789–1227, here 800–1, V.

²⁹⁵ Cf. J. Shepard, *Byzantine relations with the outside world in the ninth century: and introduction*, in: *Byzantium in the 9th Century: Dead or Alive? Papers from the Thirtieth Spring Symposium of Byzantine Studies*. Birmingham, March 1996, ed. L. Brubaker (Aldershot 1998) 167–180; I. Wood, *Christians and pagans in ninth-century Scandinavia*, in: *The Christianization of Scandinavia*, ed. P. Sawyer/Sawyer B./I. Wood (Alingsås 1987) 36–67.

This nevertheless represents a research field upon which extensive studies have already been undertaken, and it exceeds the scope of the present thesis²⁹⁶.

Numerous accounts on the contacts between Christians and the representatives of other religions, from both the East and West, come from their missionary activities²⁹⁷. Byzantium, in addition to Francia, also organized missionary activities, which epitomized a terrain for the two spheres of influence, Byzantine and Frankish, to strive for their predominance. Nevertheless, the current study will not deal with those missionary activities in detail, since this topic is very vast and spreads beyond the scope of this work. However, some particularities of those missions will be briefly outlined and analyzed to the extent to which they offer useful insights into the aspects of this research based on the contacts and interrelations between Christians and non-Christians, the Franks and the Byzantines²⁹⁸, and the ways in which the key-authors observed and compared the pagans with the heretics.

Heresies at the fringes of Christianity in Byzantium

In the Late Antiquity and in the Middle Ages, the dualist belief systems, or, dualist heresies, spread from the Near-East and reached Europe via the Byzantine Empire²⁹⁹. In the third century AD, when Christianity reached Persia, the Iranian prophet Mani attempted to bring it into connection with the old Persian religion – resulting in the Manichean heresy. The earliest text against the Manichaeans dates from the 3rd century, and is attributed to Alexander of

²⁹⁶ See, for example: P. Brown, *The Rise of Western Christendom. Triumph and Diversity, A.D. 200 – 1000* (Oxford 2003²) 408–489; I. Wood, *Missionaries and the Christian frontier*, in: *The Transformation of Frontiers. From Late Antiquity to the Carolingians*, ed. W. Pohl/I. Wood/H. Reimitz (Leiden 2001) 209–218; J. T. Addison, *The Medieval Missionary: A Study of the Conversion of Northern Europe A.D. 500 – 1300* (Eugene-OR 2009) 3–74; A. Sanmark, *Power and Conversion: A Comparative Study of Christianization in Scandinavia* (Uppsala 2004); A. Winroth, *The Conversion of Scandinavia: Vikings, Merchants and Missionaries in the Remaking of Northern Europe* (Yale-CT 2012).

²⁹⁷ In Francia, the missionary activities in the 9th century were undertaken in nowadays Denmark, in the lands of the Slavs and of the Bulgars. In Byzantium, the missionary activities of the 9th century were concentrated upon the Bulgars, Rus, Khazars, Moravians, and Jews. See: I. Dujčev, *Un episodio dell'attività di Costantino Filosofo in Moravia*, in: *Medioevo bizantino-slavo II* (Roma 1968) 113–121; Cf. I. Wood, *The Missionary Life: Saints and the Evangelization of Europe, 400 – 1050* (Harlow 2001).

²⁹⁸ Cf. C. Wickham, *Ninth-century Byzantium through western eyes*, in: *Byzantium in the Ninth Century: Dead or Alive?*, ed. L. Brubaker (Aldershot/Brookfield/Singapore/Sydney 1998) 245–256.

²⁹⁹ On the dualist and gnostic currents in the Middle Ages, see H. R. Söderberg, *La religion des Cathares, étude sur le gnosticisme de la basse antiquité et du moyen-âge* (Uppsala 1949).

Lycopolis³⁰⁰. Besides, in Alexandria, the center of philosophical thought, Christianity became endowed with philosophical features – which gave birth to the gnostic heresy. Several other heresies spread later, on the basis of the two previously-mentioned. In 7th-century Armenia, the new heresy emerged - named after St. Paul – the Paulicians³⁰¹. In the 8th century, the Byzantine emperor Constantine Copronymus (741-775) settled the colonists from Armenia on the Bulgarian border. The Paulician heresy was thus brought in by the newcomers, only to spread later among the Slavs under the name of Bogomilism, and further to the West – to Italy and France, under the name of the Cathar heresy. In Bulgaria, during the reign of the emperor Peter (927-969), the priest Jeremiah allegedly developed this heresy and called himself Bogumil (“loved by God”)³⁰²; consequently, the sect was named after him. He preached among the Slavs around the year 950 in the regions of Veles and Prilep in nowadays Macedonia. Bogomilism spread from Bulgaria quite rapidly, and reached the areas of the present-day Macedonia, Serbia, and Bosnia³⁰³.

Authors of the 9th-century Byzantium consecrated considerable amount of texts to the dualist heresies.

Photius was among those authors who insisted upon preserving the connection between profane science and theology and were deemed to be meritorious for the renewal of the classical humanism and education³⁰⁴. The ancient, Greek heritage, thus made an inherent part of Byzantine consciousness³⁰⁵. Apart from his exhaustive treatise on the Manichaeans, Photius also wrote on numerous occasions to John Chrysocheir, who was once a Byzantine officer, but

³⁰⁰ A. Villey, *Alexandre de Lycopolis: Contre la doctrine de Mani* (Paris 1985); this text has been mentioned in the IV book of Photius against the Manichaeans; cf. J. Parmelle, *L'Épître dédicatoire du IV^e livre du Contra manichaeos*, in: *Travaux et Mémoires du Centre de recherches d'histoire et de civilisation byzantine* 4 (Paris 1970) 180, cited from A. Villey, *Alexandre de Lycopolis: Contre la doctrine de Mani* (Paris 1985) 13.

³⁰¹ On the Paulician heresy, see: N. Garsoïan, *The Paulician Heresy: A Study of the Origin and Development of Paulicianism in Armenia and the Eastern Provinces of the Byzantine Empire* (The Hague 1967) 28–9.

³⁰² Cf. D. Obolensky, *Bogumili. Studija o balkanskom neomaniheizmu* (Zagreb 2009); Original: *The Bogomils. A Study in Balkan Neo-Manichaeism* (Cambridge 1948) 271–274.

³⁰³ Cf. Eliade, *Histoire des croyances et des idées religieuses*, 3 (1983) 156–159; M. Roquebert, *La religion cathare: Le Bien, le Mal et le Salut dans l'hérésie* (Paris 2009) 19–23 ; for more information concerning also the still debated question of relation between Bogomilism and Cathars, see: B. Hamilton, *Wisdom from the East: the Reception by the Cathars of Eastern Dualist Texts*, in: *Heresy and Literacy, 1000 – 1530*, ed. P. Biller-Hudson (Cambridge 1994) 38–60; P. Koledarov, *On the Initial Hearth and Centre of the Bogomil Teaching*, in: *Byzantinobulgarica* 6 (1980) 237–242.

³⁰⁴ Cf. P. Lemerle, *Le premier humanisme byzantin: Notes et remarques sur enseignement et culture à Byzance des origines aux Xe siècle* (Paris 1971) 177–204.

³⁰⁵ Cf. Tatakis, *Vizantijska filosofija* 136.

then lapsed into the Paulician heresy and became their leader³⁰⁶. Photius's letters were written with the aim of consolidating Chrysocheir in his orthodox faith and of warning him of the dangers of the heretical position he was about to embrace. These mentioned letters include: letter 33³⁰⁷, letter 57, in which Photius gives details of Chrysocheir's orthodoxy put to question, and letter 80, in which Chrysocheir's abandon of the Christian, Orthodox faith becomes apparent and obvious³⁰⁸.

Constantine the Philosopher (c. 827 – 869), Photius's student, renowned for his quasi incessant missionary activities, strived to preach the correct way of confessing the Christian dogmas and to eradicate the heathen traces of the popular belief system – what was also characteristic for the Frankish missionaries who came to Moravia as well. The Frankish missionaries who, prior to the arrival of Constantine and Methodius (c. 815 – 884) performed religious service for the Moravian people in the Latin language, feared that their influence would decrease upon the introduction of the ecclesiastical service in the Slavic language, organized by Constantine and Methodius. They therefore attacked the activities undertaken by the brothers, stating that the religious service, effectuated in the Slavic language, did not come from God, since it had not existed from the beginning. According to the Frankish missionaries, there were only three divine languages: Hebrew, Greek and Latin. Constantine labelled their accusations a heresy³⁰⁹. Apparently, the mutual accusations between the Byzantines and the Franks on the matter of language represented a quarrel of a rather long date: as has been mentioned above, Theodulf of Orléans (750/60-820/1) also accused the Byzantines for their knowledge and usage of Greek³¹⁰. Nevertheless, the Franks were not the only ones to accuse the Byzantines regarding their language use; Michael III and Photius also pointed to certain offences regarding the role of Latin in the letter addressed to Pope Nicholas I in 862 or 863³¹¹. This could confirm the importance of and high esteem assigned to language, attested in the East, as well as West. This

³⁰⁶ Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 9, 19, 26 (ed. Migne, PG 102) 933, 941, 945.

³⁰⁷ Photius, *Epistolae*: Photii patriarchae Constantinopolitani epistulae et amphiloquia I-IV (ed. B. Laourda/L.G. Westernik, Leipzig 1983-1986) 86, but also letters 34–40; Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. Valetta 52–60.

³⁰⁸ For more ample analysis of Photius and the Iconoclast period, see: F. Dvornik *Photian and Byzantine Ecclesiastical Studies* (London 1974) 69–97.

³⁰⁹ T. Lehr-Splawiński ed., *Żywoty Konstantyna i Metodego (obszerne)* (Poznań 1959) XV, 69–71; for more detailed information on this topic, cf.: I. Dujčev, *Il problema delle lingue nazionali nel medio evo e gli Slavi, Medioevo bizantino-slavo II* (Roma 1968) 43–68.

³¹⁰ For more information on Theodulf's opus, see: A. Freeman, *Theodulf of Orleans and the Libri Carolini*, in: *Speculum* 32, 4 (Oct. 1957) 663–705; A. Freeman, *Theodulf of Orleans: Charlemagne's Spokesman against the Second Council of Nicaea* (Ashgate 2003); on the veneration of icons, see: *Libri Carolini*, ed. Freeman Preface 97–102; cf. Freeman, *Theodulf of Orleans* (2003) 102.

³¹¹ Cf. П. Коматина, *Црквена политика Византије од краја иконоборства до смрти цара Василија I* (Београд 2014) 193; Photius, *Epistolae*, I. I, Ep. 8, ed. Migne 627–696.

aspect of the topic reveals the sort of embedment of heresy in a large context, and its development in the East and West, including the very important question of the contacts between the two. Namely, it is important to mention hereby the topic encompassing the evangelization of Pannonia and Great Moravia, and the missionary endeavors on behalf of the Archdiocese of Salzburg, including some conflictualities between the missionary work orchestrated from Salzburg and the one performed by Constantine - Cyril and Methodius³¹².

Speaking of the baptism of Boris the Bulgarian ruler, it is instructive to point to the letter which Photius wrote to him, on the occasion of the baptism of Boris³¹³. This letter represents a sort of *Furstenpiegel*³¹⁴, and also includes the summary of the seven Ecumenical Councils³¹⁵.

Nevertheless, Boris renewed contacts with Rome and Francia: namely, in 866 he asked bishops to be sent from Rome, but also from Louis II³¹⁶.

Photius wrote on the Hellenes, the Jews, Christians, Manichaeans, and the Iconoclasts in one of his letters. According to him, they were ill with the same *mania*, and therefore, he equals paganism with illness; in other words, Photius alludes to them as to those, who have fallen ill - *νοσέσαντες*³¹⁷.

In his 8th homily, Photius expounds on the Jewish faith. Namely, Photius, like others of his fellow compatriots and defenders of the icon-worship, frequently/occasionally compared the

³¹² Cf. H. Wolfram, *Conversio Bagoariorum et Carantanorum. Das Weißbuch der Salzburger Kirche über die erfolgreiche Mission in Karantien und Pannonien mit Zusätzen und Ergänzungen* (Ljubljana/Laibach 2013³) 16–25, 129–132, 319–322; Id., *Salzburg, Bayern, Österreich. Die Conversio Bagoariorum et Carantanorum und die Quellen ihrer Zeit. Mitteilungen des Instituts für Österreichische Geschichtsforschung 31* (Wien/München 1995); F. Lošek, *Philologisches zur Conversio Bagoariorum et Carantanorum*, in: *Die Bayern und ihre Nachbarn. Berichte des Symposiums der Kommission für Frühmittelalterforschung, 1* (Wien 1985) 255–268; Id., *Die Conversio Bagoariorum et Carantanorum und der Brief des Erzbischofs Theotmar von Salzburg. MGH Studien und Texte 15* (Hannover 1997).

³¹³ Cf. F. Curta, *Southeastern Europe in the Middle Ages 500-1250* (Cambridge 2006) 171 sq; F. Dvornik, *Les Slaves, Byzance et Rome au IXe siècle* (Hattiesburg-MS 1970) 184-195.

³¹⁴ Cf. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios 30*; Photius's Epistle to Michael, the Bulgarian ruler: cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. Valetta Ep. 6; Photius, *Epistolae*, I. I, Ep. 8, ed. Migne 627–696, here 665.

³¹⁵ Photius's Epistle to Michael, the Bulgarian ruler: cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. Valetta Ep. 6; Photius, *Epistolae*, I. I, Ep. 8, ed. Migne 627–696; for more detailed information on the Bulgarian issue, see: F. Dvornik, *Byzantine Missions among the Slavs. SS Constantine-Cyril and Methodius* (New Jersey 1970) 126–128; G. Cankova-Petkova, *Contribution au sujet de la conversion des Bulgares*, *Byzantinobulgarica 4* (1973) 21–39; Д. Ангелов, *Понякој въпроси околу покръстването на Българите*, *Исторически Преглед*, 21/3 (София 1965) 38–57.

³¹⁶ On the letter of Pope John VIII to Michael, see: John VIII, *Registrum Iohannis VIII. Papae*, Ep. 192 (ed. E. Caspar, MGH, Epp. VII, Berlin 1928) 154.

³¹⁷ Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 37, ed. Laourda/Westernik 87.

Iconoclasts to Jews. The anti-Jewish polemics and Christian-Jewish discussions marked numerous treatises in 9th-century Byzantium³¹⁸. Photius deplors and hates the perversity of the Jews, who have fallen from the true and divine wisdom: *...τῶν Ἰουδαίων ταλανίζειν καὶ μισεῖν τὴν μοχθίριαν ...τῆς ἀληθινῆς καὶ θείας ὄντως σοφίας ἐξέπεσον*³¹⁹. Jewish teachers, while proclaiming to heal diseases of the souls of their people, have become sick themselves, and inflamed their souls with the disease. Unaware of their sickness, they have willingly turned away from their treatment, not wishing to recognize the Saviour: *...τὸ νοσοῦν τῆς ψυχῆς ἄλλοις θεραπεύειν ἐπηγγελμένοι αὐτοὶ τὴν ἐσχάτην ἐνοσησαν ἄγνοιαν ...οὐδ' ὅτι πάσχουσιν ἐπαισθάνονται ...τὸν σωτήρα καὶ δημιουργὸν ἐπιγνῶναι οὐκ ἠθέλησαν*³²⁰.

Furthermore, Photius continues, the Pharisees are intoxicating the minds of the people with the error of phantasies – blaspheming, not believing – which Photius alludes to as madness, and the soul-destroying diseases, which exist in spite of their knowledge of the Law; we should therefore, as Photius argues, flee from such diseases which are destructive for our souls: *...ἡ ἀπόνοια... τοὺς γὰρ λογισμοὺς τῆ πλάνῃ καὶ ἀπάτῃ τῶν φαντασιῶν ἐκμεθύσκουσα... Τοιοῦτον τὸ νόσημα τῶν φαρισαίων καὶ γραμματέων... Ἡμεῖς δὲ φύγωμεν... τὰ ψυχοφθόρα πάθη ταῦτα*³²¹.

This passage aligns very well with the previously-elaborated sub-chapter on heresy as illness and madness³²². According to this example coming from the hand of Photius, not only the heretics have been portrayed as ill, but the members of other confessional groups likewise.

In the context of the feast of Nativity of the Mother of God, and as a counterbalance to the Christian true faith, Photius speaks of paganism and Greek mythology in his 9th homily. The pagan peoples have preached absurdities, *τὰ ἀτοπώτατα πεπρεσβεύκασι*³²³. In the entire homily, Photius alludes to the pagan tradition and gives examples from pagan authors – with a certain amount of sarcasm; he calls it “tedious nonsense” – *...τοῖς μακροῖς ὕθλοις καὶ μύθοις μακρὰ χάρειν εἰπόντες καὶ τοὺς ἐπτοημένους περὶ ταῦτα τῆς παρανοίας ἐλεοῦντες καὶ μισοῦντες τῆς ἀλαζονείας*³²⁴. Throughout the entire homily the vegetative symbolism is present – whether in the Christian or anti-Christian sense. The feast of the nativity of the Virgin – on which occasion the homily has been produced – may have inspired Photius to open the homily with the praise

³¹⁸ Mango, Homilies 152–153.

³¹⁹ Mango, Homilies, 8th Homily 153–4; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 83, l. 13–14, 17–18.

³²⁰ Mango, Homilies, 8th Homily 154; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 83, l. 21–22, p. 84, l. 2, 7–8.

³²¹ Mango, Homilies, 8th Homily 158; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 87, l. 5–7, 9–10, 19.

³²² Cf. above, I.3.

³²³ Mango, Homilies, 9th Homily 169; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 92, l. 27–28.

³²⁴ Mango, Homilies, 9th Homily 171; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 93, l. 30; *ibid.*, 94, l. 1–2.

of the fruit of her womb. Furthermore, the metaphor of the seed is employed to designate the emergence of sin among humans: the seed of sin came through Adam and Eve: *ἡ τῆς ἀμαρτία σπορά*³²⁵. Again, the symbolism of sin as disease appears in this homily: the disease of the trespass has thus been transmitted from the first transgressors through all men – *τοῦ τῆς παραπτώσεως ἀρρωστήματος μεταρρύντος*³²⁶. In his 17th homily, Photius alludes to the Jewish madness: *ἰουδαϊκὴν κἀνταῦθα παραζήλοῦντες ἀπόνοιαν*³²⁷.

Additionally, Photius aligns heresies to the semantic field of paganism and speaks of the “bacchantes and harpies of the heresies and schisms”, who are, being children of heresy, “filled with corybantic frenzy” – thus comparing the heresies and heretics to the cultic phenomena of the pagan past: *...τὰ τέκνα σου, οὓς αἰρέσεων πάλαι καὶ σχισμάτων βάρκλαι καὶ ἄρπυιαι συναρπάσασαι καὶ πολλῆς κορυβαντίας ἐμπλήσασαι*³²⁸. Photius aligns even the *Filioque* controversy, which achieved its peak at the time of the baptism of the Bulgars, to the field of Greek mythology³²⁹. He elaborates further on this observation on his, by explaining his view according to which it is impossible for the two divine principles to co-exist in the Trinity, but only one. Therefore, the Holy Spirit cannot proceed from two divine principles – from God and the Son – but only from God, representing the one and only divine principle there is. That is exactly why Photius brings into correlation the concept of the Latins to the polytheism³³⁰.

In one of his letters³³¹ which speaks of Arius and his heresy, Photius compares the heresy with the Jewish and Greek manners of thinking: “...just as it is Jewish and Christ-hating to confound the majesty and monarch of the Trinity in one person, so it is Greek and polytheistic to divide the simple Godhead, which exceeds being and nature, into unequal and dissimilar beings.” - *...ὥσπερ τὸ εἰς ἓν συγκλείειν πρόσωπον τὴν Τριαδικὴν μοναρχίαν καὶ κυριότητα Ἰουδαϊκὸν ἐστὶ καὶ μισόχριστον, οὕτω καὶ τὸ κατατέμνειν εἰς ἀνίσους φύσεις καὶ ἀνομοίους οὐσίας τὴν ὑπερούσιον καὶ ὑπερφυῆ καὶ ἐνιαίαν Θεότητα Ἑλληνικὸν ὑπάρχει καὶ πολύθεον.*

This comparison made by Photius clearly means that he finds the narrow strand separating some of the pagan contemplation practices and procedures from the Christian heretical ones. So, in

³²⁵ Mango, Homilies, 9th Homily 171; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 94, l. 12.

³²⁶ Mango, Homilies, 9th homily 171; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 94, l. 16.

³²⁷ Mango, Homilies 291; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 168, l. 3–4.

³²⁸ Mango, Homilies 310; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 176, l. 11–13.

³²⁹ Mango, Homilies 304; cf. Photius, Liber de Spiritu S. mystagogia, ed. J. Hergenröther (Regensburg 1857) 14, 15, 36, 37, 109.

³³⁰ Photius, De Spiritu Sancti Mystagogia (ed. Migne, PG 102) 263–542, here 291; for a detailed analysis of this treatise, cf. T. M. Kolbaba, *Inventing Latin Heretics. Byzantines and the Filioque in the Ninth Century* (Kalamazoo-MI 2008) 76–103.

³³¹ Cf. Stratoudaki White, Patriarch Photios 71; Photius, Epistolae, ed. Valetta, Ep. 6, 206.

this letter, Photius undoubtedly compares the heresy of Arianism to the Hellenic religion and polytheism, as well as with the Jewish religion. During his second exile, Photius allegedly composed a lengthy treatise entitled “The Mystagogia of The Holy Spirit”³³² in which he exposed his view of the doctrinal matter and the position of the Eastern Church on the *Filioque* controversy. Even this dispute, according to Photius, could be placed in the line of older heresies, since he esteemed it comparable to the heresies of Sabellius and Macedonius³³³.

In his *De Spiritus Sancti Mystagogia*, Photius condemns the Filioque doctrine of the Latins: By adding that the Holy Spirit proceeds from the Son also, they made it a polytheistic dogma, which is, therefore, also atheistic; it falls in the genre of impious tales, and represents a pagan superstition under the guise of Christianity. Namely, by doing so, they support the existence of the two divine principles, instead of only one, and that is why Photius brings it into connection with polytheism: τὸ τῆς πολυθείας ἄθεον...ἐν προσχήματι χριστιανισμοῦ ἢ δεισιδαιμονία τῆς Ἑλληνικῆς πλάνης...³³⁴

In the Encyclical letter to the Patriarch of the East, composed in 861, Photius mainly focuses on condemning the “false doctrines” imposed on the Bulgarian people by the Frankish missionaries in Bulgaria³³⁵, whom he considered to be impious men – ἄνδρες δυσσεβεῖς³³⁶.

Photius also wrote on the missionary activities, undertaken by the Byzantines, in the region of the Black Sea³³⁷. More precisely, Photius dedicated two of his homilies on the attack – the siege of Constantinople – by the Russians. Interestingly, these two homilies offer some glimpses and instructive material into how Photius perceived the foreign enemy – who is simultaneously pagan – in comparison to how he addresses the enemy of Christianity - heresies and heretics.

Photius refers to the Russians, coming from the sea to invade Constantinople, as “the hail-storm of barbarians”³³⁸, or simply as an inhuman, barbarous tribe³³⁹. He asks himself, whether the inhabitants of Constantinople deserved it as a consequence of their sins³⁴⁰. Curiously, but not completely unexpectedly, Photius refers to the Russians as to the incumbrent plague – ἡ

³³² Upon a thoroughly conducted analysis, Tia M. Kolbaba doubts the authorship of Photius, cf.: Kolbaba, *Inventing Latin Heretics* 87.

³³³ Mango, *Homilies* 304; cf. Photius, *De Spiritus S. mystagogia*, ed. Hergenröther 14, 15, 36, 37, 109.

³³⁴ Photius, *De Spiritu Sancti Mystagogia*, ed. Migne 292B.

³³⁵ Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 4 (Encyclical Letter to the Eastern Patriarchs), ed. Valetta 165–181, here 168.

³³⁶ Photius, *Encyclical Letter to the Eastern Patriarchs*, ed. Valetta 168.

³³⁷ Cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, I. II, Ep. 13, ed. Migne 828D–829B; Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 239, ed. Valetta.

³³⁸ Mango, *Homilies*, 3rd homily 82; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 29, l. 5.

³³⁹ Mango, *Homilies*, 4th homily 96; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 40, l. 15–16.

³⁴⁰ Mango, *Homilies*, 3rd homily 83; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 29, l. 12–13.

παροῦσα θραῦσις – employing the same collocation as in instances when he was referring to heretics³⁴¹. The same expression designating illness is used to describe the disaster provoked by the aggressors: the “plague of war” – *ἡ θραῦσις ἐξήπλωτο καὶ ὁ τοῦ πολέμου λοιμός*³⁴²,

Apart from being a fertile field for intertwined missionary activities, directed from Francia, as well as Byzantium, Bulgaria also offers an excellent case-study for the relationship between Christians and non-Christians, since it is in this area that paganism, and Paulicianism have mingled³⁴³. And, also, because it was the meeting point between missionaries from Rome and from Constantinople.

Besides, the cases in which Christian heretics were compared to the pagans/representatives of other religions also existed: in a letter addressed to John the Grammarian, Theodore the Studite alludes to iconoclasts as the “(new) pagans” – because they wish to demonstrate that the Iconocules worship the creation, and not the Creator only. He also calls the iconoclasts the “Arians of impiety” – *...Ἀρεινῶν ἐλάτους κατὰ ἀσέβειαν*³⁴⁴. At times, one can grasp the impression that all of these denominations were similar, independently of whether the uttered words were related to the “inner-Christian” heretics, or to those at the fringes of Christianity – i.e. the Pagans, Jews, Arabs or Slavs.

Namely, adherents to the extremist party, vehemently opposed to the Iconoclast figures in the middle of the 9th-century were numerous among the Studite monks. They often despised the newly awoken interest in classical knowledge attested by the moderate circles (which counted, among others, Leo the Philosopher and the former Patriarch John the Grammarian, and shared some Iconoclast sympathies) since they saw it as being related to pagan thought. They were consequently against the renewal of a pagan learned culture³⁴⁵.

Some authors enlisted Islam amongst the heresies³⁴⁶. A certain hermit alluded to Arabs as villains – *αἰσχιστοί*³⁴⁷. In the account on Thomas the Slav, the idiom “*pagani et alienigenae*”

³⁴¹ Mango, Homilies, 3rd homily 85, 92; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 31, l. 27–28, 36, l. 24.

³⁴² Mango, Homilies, 4th homily 99; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 43, l. 10–11.

³⁴³ The recently-published work of Tsvetelin Stepanov delves exhaustively into this aspect of the pagan residues in medieval Bulgaria: Ц. Степанов, Религии в езическа България (София 2017).

³⁴⁴ V. Grumel, Jean Grammaticos et saint Théodore Studite, in: *Échos d’Orient* 36 (1937) 181–189, here 188; original: Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne 1640D; Lemerle, *Le premier humanisme byzantin* 135–146.

³⁴⁵ Dvornik, *The Photian schism* 12–13; F. Dvornik, *Les Légendes de Constantin et de Methode, vues de Byzance, Byzantino-Slavica, Supplementa* (Prague 1933) 27–31.

³⁴⁶ cf. Rigo, *Orthodoxy and heresy* 50.

³⁴⁷ F. Halkin, *Saints moines d’Orient* (London 1973) 389.

– was used³⁴⁸. A connection or a semantic field between the heretics and pagans possibly existed in the mind-set of medieval Christian authors.

³⁴⁸ Lemerle, *Thomas le Slave* 256–7.

Heresies at the fringes of Christianity in the Latin West

According to Professor Chadwick's observation, Augustine speaks of how the Christians consider their "separated brethren as heathen outsiders"³⁴⁹. The pagans pursue with disregarding and diffamating the Christian belief, through blasphemies and contempt towards the Trinitarian doctrine. Moreover, Augustine continues, they impiously prefer mocking the accounts on the Son of God or the Holy Spirit, than taking part in the Christian society: ...*Nam et Pagani qui appellantur, etiam nunc totam nostram religionem...maledictis contumeliisque insectantur: et quidquid de ipsa Trinitate dicimus, negando et blasphemando contemunt...Multo magis ergo quod de Filio Dei, vel de Spiritu sancto dicimus, suo impio more deridere, quam nostra pia societate colere maluerunt*³⁵⁰. Augustine also mentioned that the newly-baptized Christians preserved some of the old, pagan beliefs – which was a frequently-attested and quite expected phenomena among many peoples who came to embrace Christianity³⁵¹.

As already mentioned, numerous contacts, which occurred during the Frankish missionary activities throughout pagan Europe, have left their trace in the written records of the Frankish authors. For example, on the occasion of the mission undertaken by Ebbo to the Danes, Ermold the Black wrote against the worshiping of the statues by the pagan inhabitants³⁵². In 815/6, Agobard of Lyon composed "On Hail and Thunder" on the pagan rituals³⁵³, as many other Medieval Latin authors did³⁵⁴. The bishops who gathered together at the Council of Paris in 829 informed Louis the Pious on that issue³⁵⁵.

In his exposition on the earliest days of human religious practices, Walahfridus sees *libri paganorum* as *inutiles fabulae*³⁵⁶, and counter balances the *veri dei cultores* to the *daemorum*

³⁴⁹ Cf. H. Chadwick, Augustine on pagans and Christians: reflections on religious and social change, in: Id., *Heresy and Orthodoxy in the Early Church* (Aldershot 1991) 14–27, here 27.

³⁵⁰ Augustine, *Epistolae ad Romanos Inchoata Expositio* (ed. Migne 35) 2087–2106, here I, c. 15, 2098–2099.

³⁵¹ Cf. Chadwick, *Heresy and Orthodoxy* 24–27.

³⁵² Cf. Th. Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians* (Philadelphia-PA 2009) 363; Ermold the Black, *Carmina*, In honorem Hludowici, l. IV (ed. E. Dümmler, MGH PLAC II, Berlin 1884) 3–79, 68–70.

³⁵³ Agobard of Lyon, *Agobardi Lugdunensis Opera Omnia* (ed. L. Van Acker, CCCM 52, Turnhout 1981).

³⁵⁴ Cf. J. Palmer, *Defining paganism in the Carolingian world*, in: *EME* 15, 4 (2007) 402–425.

³⁵⁵ Cf. Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians* 363; cf. Council of Paris, a. 829, m. Iunio (ed. A. Worminghoff, MGH Conc. II, 2, Hannover/Leipzig 1908) 650–679.

³⁵⁶ Walahfridus Strabo, *Libellus de exordiis et incrementis quarundam in observationibus ecclesiasticis rerum* (MGH, Capit. II, ed. A. Boretius/V. Krause, Hannover 1897) 473–516, here 476, l. 9.

*veneratores*³⁵⁷. The pagan religion was characterized by the filth - *idolum squalor* – semantically related to notions of disease³⁵⁸.

Numerous descriptions and references to the pagans are found in the account of the Frankish missionaries to the Danes³⁵⁹, which began in the first half of the 9th century. The fear of pagans, once baptized, falling again into paganism, designated as “pristine errors, induced by the devil”, is present in this narrative, just as it is in the Latin chronicles’ account of the baptism of the Slavs: *...qui simul baptizati fuerant pia exhortatione, ne ad pristinus reducerentur diabolo instigante errores*³⁶⁰.

The missionaries were bringing the Christian religion to the Danes, referred to as “the way of the truth” – *...ad viam veritatis monere*³⁶¹, or, as *vera religio*, the true religion³⁶². The Danish pagan religion is referred to as diabolical error - *...diabolico ...errore...*³⁶³ The new, Christian religion, is said to have come in the land of many gods: *Multi...ibi sunt dii potentes et magni...et cultura Christi a multis ibi Christianis excolitur, qui fortissimus est deorum*³⁶⁴. The pagan religion is described as a “culture of superstition”, and idolatry: *Nolite ultra culturam superstitiosam quaerere et inani sacrificio idola vobis placare*³⁶⁵. The danger of the pagan religion is that it brings error and disturbance to the hearts of the people: *...error nimius ac perturbatio corda hominum confuderat*³⁶⁶.

³⁵⁷ Walahfridus, Libellus, ed. Boretius/Krause 476, l. 10–11.

³⁵⁸ Walahfridus, Libellus, ed. Boretius/Krause 478, l. 13. The scholarly contributions on the topic of ritual impurity are numerous, cf: R. Meens, Ritual purity and the influence of Gregory the Great in the Early Middle Ages, in: *Studies in Church History* 32 (1996) 31–43; M. de Jong, ‘Imitatio Morum’. The cloister and clerical purity in the Carolingina world, in: *Medieval Purity and Piety. Essays on Medieval Clerical Celibacy and Religious Reform*, ed. M. Frassetto (New York 1998) 49–80; A. Angenendt, Pollutio: Die ‘Kultische Reinheit’ in Religion und Liturgie, in: *Archiv für Liturgiewissenschaft* 52 (2010) 52–92; D. Müller, Heresy as impurity, in: *Sanctifying Texts, Transforming Rituals: Encounters in Liturgical Studies. Essays in Honour of Gerard A. M. Rouwhorst*, ed. P. van Geest/M. Poorthuis/E. Rose (Leiden/Boston 2017) 366–385.

³⁵⁹ *Vita Anskarii* (ed. G. Waith, MGH SSRG LV, Hannover 1988).

³⁶⁰ *Vita Anskarii*, ed. Waitz 29.

³⁶¹ *Vita Anskarii*, ed. Waitz 30.

³⁶² *Vita Anskarii*, ed. Waitz 51.

³⁶³ *Vita Anskarii*, ed. Waitz 35; cf. 51.

³⁶⁴ *Vita Anskarii*, ed. Waitz 43.

³⁶⁵ *Vita Anskarii*, ed. Waitz 43.

³⁶⁶ *Vita Anskarii*, ed. Waitz 56.

Another interesting account which offers a helpful insight into the narrative and textual treatment of the representatives of other religions is the one on the conversion of the Frankish deacon at the court of Louis the Pious to Judaism, during the third decade of the 9th century³⁶⁷.

The most of the account of Bodo is found in the second part of the *Annales Bertiniani*³⁶⁸.

In the record for the year 839, a mention of Bodo's conversion was registered. According to the Annals, Bodo the deacon, Aleman by birth, who was since his earliest childhood imbibed in Christian education and divine, as well as human erudition,has deplorably abandoned Christianity and converted himself to Judaism, incited by the enemy of the mankind. In this account, the "enemy of the mankind", that is, the Devil, is presented as the main cause of Bodo's conversion to Judaism. The accent was put on Bodo's Aleman origin, as well as on his life-long dedication to Christian education and erudition.

*Interea lacrimabile nimiumque cunctis Catholicae ecclesiae filiis ingemiscendum, fama perferente, innotuit. Bodo diaconus, Alamannica gente progenitus, et ab ipsis pene cunabulis in christiana religione palatinis eruditionibus divinis humanisque litteris aliquatenus imbutus, qui anno praecedente Romam orationis gratia properandi licentiam ab Augustis poposcerat, multisque donariis muneratus impetraverat, humani generis hoste pellectus, relicta Christianitate ad Iudaismum sese convertit*³⁶⁹.

The account ensues: the outer signs of Bodo's conversion have been put forward, the change in his appearance, which made him become "an alien" to the Christian flock, as suggested by Frank Riess³⁷⁰. Namely, the accent was put on the change in Bodo's body: he got circumcised, grew his hair and beard longer and took on – or "usurped" the other name, that of Eleazar. Furthermore, he married a Jewish woman and even influenced his cousin to convert to Judaism as well:

Et primum quidem consilio prodicionis atque perditionis suae cum Iudaeis inito, quos secum adduxerat paganis vendendos callide machinari non timuit; quibus distractis, uno tantummodo secum, qui nepos eius ferebatur, retento, abnegata – quod lacrimabiliter dicimus – Christi fide, sese Iudaeum professus est. Sicque circumcises capillisque ac barba crescentibus, et mutato

³⁶⁷ F. Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus: the journey of Deacon Bodo (823-876), in: EME 13 (2005) 2, 131–157; cf. Amolo, Amulo Lugdunensis Episcopus, Epistola Seu Liber Contra Iudaeos (ed. Migne, PL 116) 0141–0184.

³⁶⁸ *Annales Bertiniani* (ed. G. H. Pertz, MGH SS I, *Annales et chronica aevi Carolini*, Hannover 1826) 419–515; the second part, composed by Prudentius and encircling the period between the years 835 and 861, 429–454.

³⁶⁹ *Annales Bertiniani*, ed. Pertz 433, l. 4–20.

³⁷⁰ Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus 137.

*potiusque usurpato Eleazari nomine, acciutus etiam cingulo militari, cuiusdam Iudaei filiam sibi matrimonio copulavit, coacto memorato nepote suo similiter ad iudaismum translato, tandemque cum Iudaeis, miserrima cupiditate devinctus, Caesaraugustam, urbem Hispaniae, mediante Augusto mense ingressus est. Quod quantum Augustis cunctisque christianae fidei gratia redemptis luctuosum extiterit, difficultas, qua imperatori id facile credendum persuaderi non potuit, patenter omnibus indicavit*³⁷¹.

As observed by Riess, the description of the change from Christianity to Judaism was, in the account of Bodo's conversion, connected to the changes in bodily and outer image – with the aim of portraying Bodo as alienated³⁷². This event is brought into connection with the sins which had befallen the empire, similarly as portrayed in the letter of Michael II to Louis the Pious on the rebellion of Thomas the Slav³⁷³. Thus, the thread linking the (declined) body of the state to the altered bodily image of Bodo was brought forward³⁷⁴.

Another interesting account on the textual treatment of the adherents to other, non-Christian religions in the 9th century is to be found in the written testimony of Eulogio y Álvaro, dated to 9th-century Córdoba. Curiously, this author refers to Islam as *secta diaboli* and *secta impietatis*, and to Muhammad as *pseudopropheta*. Thus is Christianity equaled to *fides* and *religio* and the Muslim faith to *secta*³⁷⁵.

³⁷¹ Annales Bertiniani, ed. Pertz 433, l. 10–20.

³⁷² Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus 137, 149–150.

³⁷³ Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus 137; on Michael's letter, see below, in chapter II.5.

³⁷⁴ Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus 137–138; cf. E. H. Kantorowicz, *The King's Two Bodies: A Study in Mediaeval Political Theology* (Princeton-NJ 1997²), 15–16.

³⁷⁵ Cf. A. Biosca I Bas, Una nueva aportación a los nombres de los Musulmanes en latín medieval, https://rua.ua.es/dspace/bitstream/10045/2545/4/Una_nueva_aportaci%C3%B3n_a_los_nombres_de_los_musulmanes_en_lat%C3%ADn_medieval.pdf, 02/01/2018; on this 9th-century text, see: R. Szpiech, ed., *Medieval Exegesis and Religious Difference: Commentary, Conflict and Community in the Premodern Mediterranean* (New York 2015) 90–91.

II STRUCTURING THE LANGUAGE OF RELIGIOUS DISSENT in the 9th-century

Having opened the most important questions relevant to the entire narrative of this work, it is necessary now to concentrate on the following elements, through the close reading and within a comparative perspective between the selected Frankish and the Byzantine 9th-century authors. The aim is to demonstrate their connectedness, as well as to identify the nature of the “procedure” they traced, in an ascending line and disposition, aligned to each other, and following the “road-map”. Hereby shall the protruding features organized in an aligned and inter-connected sequences be presented, and applied to particularly chosen case-studies. Namely, together they constitute one comprehensive pivotal semantic field in the 9th century narratives through the formation of specific sequences (on the examples related to the Iconoclast controversy, the *Filioque* and Moechian controversies, as well as the to Predestination debate in the first place). Apart from elaborating on the importance of correct wording in defining heresy in 9th-century Francia and Byzantium and the import of the metaphorical language, these include also the following sequences: “old” versus “new” heresies; danger of novelties and innovation; *rustici/simplices*; danger of scandal; the concept of *Nubia Christi* versus *Meretrix*; bodily symbolism; in the quest for unity on internal as well as on the external plane; repentance in order to prevent severance; severance from the body of the Church, and severance in the form of exile. At the same time, these concepts show the developmental line, and indicate the manner in which they were mutually inter-connected.

II. 1. ON THE IMPORTANCE OF WORDS: Words, language, discourse – bearers of heresy

This chapter will, as an opening chapter in the second section of this thesis, focus upon the significance of words, correct wording and terminology applied in demarcating the concept of “true faith” from the notion of erroneous belief.

The importance of the language of the heretics, those who deviate from the Christian dogma has been stressed in the Justinian Code:

*Haereticorum autem vocabulo continentur et latis adversus eos sanctionibus debent succumbere, qui vel levi argumento iudicio catholicae religionis et tramite detecti fuerint deviare.*³⁷⁶

For both the Greek and Latin authors of the Early Middle Ages, the importance of correct wording accompanies the importance of the correct doctrine. Theodulf of Orléans criticized the Greeks for their linguistic errors and misunderstanding of the Bible while analyzing the Greek Acts from the Council of Nicaea. On the other hand, during the “Claudius affair” and the echo of the Iconoclast crisis on the West, Jonas of Orléans (818 – 843) and Dungal (died in 827) criticized Claudius, bishop of Turin (817 – 827) for his linguistic errors³⁷⁷. For the Franks, it is obvious that the correct words and grammar represented a significant instance in the theological quarrels of their day. Furthermore, the significance of constructing a correct interpretation is stressed in the works of Alcuin of York, head of the Palatine school founded by Charlemagne at Aachen (ca. 732 – 804) and Bede the Venerable (672/3 – 735), for example³⁷⁸.

³⁷⁶ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.2.1; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 50.

³⁷⁷ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 331–333.

³⁷⁸ Bede the Venerable, *De Proverbia Salomonis Allegoricae Interpretationis Fragmenta* (ed. Migne PL 91) 1051–1066C; Id., *De Schematis et Tropis Sacrae Scripturae Liber* (ed. Migne, PL 90) 175–186D; (ed. C. W. Jones/C. B. Kendall/M. H. King/F. Lipp, CCSL 123A, Turnhout 1975); G.R. Evans, *Bede the Theologian*, in: *The Medieval Theologians. An Introduction to Theology in the Medieval Period* (Malden-MA 2001) 57–64; Alcuin, *Grammatica* (ed. Migne, PL 101) 849–902; Id., *De dialectica* (ed. Migne, PL 101) 949–976B; Id., *Dialogua De Rethorica et Virtutibus* (ed. Migne, PL 101) 919–949; cf. W.S.Howell ed., *The Rhetoric of Alcuin and Charlemagne* (New York 1965); S. Bruni, ed., *Alcuino de orthographia* (Florence 1997); cf. V. Law, *Late Latin grammars in the earlier Middle Ages: a typological history*, in: *Historiographia Linguistica* 13 (1986) 365–380; Id., *The study of grammar*, in: *Carolingian Culture: Emulation and Innovation*, ed. R. McKitterick (Cambridge 1994) 88–110.

In his theological works, Gottschalk frequently discusses the importance of grammar for the correct wording, indispensable for conveying the correct doctrine³⁷⁹.

As Maximus the Confessor – one of the most influential Byzantine theologians (c. 580 – 662) had earlier stated on the subject of the *Filioque* polemic in his letter to Martin: the Romans cannot reproduce the Byzantine concept of the *Filioque* in Latin, that is, in a foreign language, with foreign words, as they would in their own language. The same would be the case if it were applied to the Greeks (in Latin translation):...*Rogavi autem Romanos secundum jussionem vestram, ut ad cavendas sic ex cuniculis obrepentium fraus dolosque, sua ipsi redderent ac interpretarentur. Verum cum in more positum habeant ut ita faciant ac scribant, nescio an forte obtemperaturi sint. Est praeterea alia ratio, quod non ita possint alia lingua ac idiomate mentem suam exacte exprimere, sicut in sua nativa: uti et jam nos in nostra. Prorsus vero rem et ipsi curabant, qui experimento, quod inde est damnum injuriamque, didicerint.*

... παρακάλεσα τοὺς Ῥωμαίους πλὴν ἔθους κεκρακηκόςτος οὕτω ποιεῖν καὶ στέλλειν, οὐκ οἶδα τυχὸν εἰ πιστεῖεν. Ἄλλως τε καὶ τὸ μὴ οὕτως δύνασθαι διακριβοῦν ἐν ἄλλῃ λέξει σὲ καὶ φωνῇ τὸν ἑαυτῶν νοῦν ὥσπερ ἐν τῇ ἰδίᾳ καὶ θρεψαμένη καθάπερ οὖν καὶ ἡμεῖς ἐν τῇ καθ' ἡμᾶς τὸν ἡμέτερον. Γενήσεται δὲ πάντως αὐτοῖς, πείρα τὴν ἐπήρειαν μαθοῦσι, καὶ ἡ περὶ τούτου φροντίς³⁸⁰.

In his sermon on the 53rd Psalm, Augustine underlines the importance of words, silence and praise when combined with good actions, as well as the strong impact the words can have – either in a good, or in a bad sense. It is the word of diffamation that brings scandal³⁸¹. Augustine thoroughly studied the impact of rhetoric on the correct interpretation of the Scriptures³⁸².

Hicmar, archbishop of Reims (806-882), refers to the first and second chapters of the third book of Augustine's *De doctrina Christiana*, in order to emphasize the importance of words and correct interpretation. When faced with an ambiguous meaning, one should always refer to the doctrine of faith: *Cum verba propria faciunt ambiguum scripturam, primo videndum*

³⁷⁹ Cf. Gillis, Gottschalk of Orbais 245; Gottschalk of Orbais, *Confessio Godescalchi monachi damnati* (*Confessio Brevior*), ed. Lambot 52–54, here 54.

³⁸⁰ Cf. Maximus the Confessor, *Maximi Confessoris Ad Presbyterum Marinum* (ed. Migne, PG 91) 9–286, here 136.

³⁸¹ Augustine, *Sermones Suppositi. Classis I. De Vetero et Novo Testamento, Sermo 53* (ed. Migne PG 39) 1735–1972, here 1845–1848.

³⁸² Cf. Augustine, *De Doctrina Christiana Libri Quattor* (ed. Migne, PL 34) 15–122; especially, liber IV, chapters II, III, V, VI, VII, XXVIII; (ed. K. D. Daur/J. Martin, CCSL 32, Turnhout 1962); Id., *Principia Rhetorices* (ed. Migne, PL 32) 1440–1448; cf. S. Ijsseling, *Rhetoric and Philosophy in Conflict* (The Hague 1976) 41–45 (chapter VI, “Augustine and Rhetoric”).

*est ne male distinxerimus, aut pronuntiaverimus. Cum ergo adhibita intentio incertum esse perviderit, quomodo distinguendum, aut quomodo pronuntiandum sit, consulat regulam fidei, quam de Scripturarum planioribus locis et Ecclesiae auctoritate percepit. Quod si ambae, vel etiam omnes si plures fuerint, partes ambiguitatis secundum fidem sonuerint, textus ipse sermonis a praecedentibus et consequentibus partibus, quae ambiguitatem illam in medio posuerunt, restat consulendus, ut videamus cuinam sententiae de pluribus quae se ostendunt ferat suffragium, eamque sibi contexi patiatur*³⁸³. In his condemnation of Gottschalk's Trinitarian doctrine, Hincmar proceeds from this Augustinian precept, and refers to Athanasius and Ambrose. Moreover, he underlines the importance of grammar³⁸⁴, in the aim of producing the correct teaching. Additionally, Gottschalk frequently recurs to the grammatical explanations in order to support his doctrinal views³⁸⁵. Consequently, Gottschalk considers a heretic, him, who corrupts either the meaning, or the order of words: *Falsus enim testis est, qui in dictis quorumcumque aut sensum aut superficiem corumpit*³⁸⁶. This same method, applied by both Hincmar and Gottschalk, is apparently taken from Augustine, who delved deeply into the topics related to the false and correct interpretation³⁸⁷. For Augustine, every doctrine relates either to things or to signs – *Omnis doctrina vel rerum vel signorum*³⁸⁸. Furthermore, it is the problem of the interpreter if he interprets wrongly; in order to depict this opinion of his better, Augustine refers to the problem of translating from Greek to Latin³⁸⁹. Gottschalk's interpretation was considered to be false, a lie: *...manifestissime claret Gothescalcum in sua interpretatione et in sua expositione mentitum fuisse*³⁹⁰, and similarly he was referred to as a 'liar', *mendax*³⁹¹.

By quoting Athanasius' words on the Trinity, Hincmar opens the narrative on the usage of grammar and philosophical heresy which is opposed to the ancient apostolic sacraments: *Ergo, inquires, postulo a te, qui legis hanc istius scripturae meae fidei catholicae professionem, ne hinc superflua vel profuse verba perquiras; sed strictim capaciter, imo specialiter, cum summo studio dicta ad stylum sacrae Scripturae conferas, et secundum regulae aequitatem*

³⁸³ Hincmar of Reims, *De Una et non Trina Deitate* (ed. Migne, PL 125) 473–618, here 513CD.

³⁸⁴ Cf. Hincmar of Reims, *De Una*, ed. Migne 521CD, when referring to Augustine's *De Trinitate*, book 5, chapter 8, on words; also *Ibid.*, 537A–D.

³⁸⁵ For example, in order to support his views on the twofold predestination in his *De Praedestinatione*, IX, ed. Lambot. and in *De Praedestinatione*, XXIV, ed. Lambot 338–346.

³⁸⁶ Cf. Gottschalk, *Confessio Godescalchi moanchi damnati*, ed. Lambot 54; cf. Genke/Gumerlock, *Gottschalk and a Medieval Predestination Controversy* 73.

³⁸⁷ See, for example: Augustine, *De doctrina Christiana*, ed. Daur/Martin 117, 128, 163, 164, 165.

³⁸⁸ Augustine, *De doctrina Christiana*, ed. Daur/Martin 7.

³⁸⁹ Augustine, *De doctrina Christiana*, ed. Daur/Martin 44–45.

³⁹⁰ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 538A.

³⁹¹ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 551A.

*Justitia moderante perpendas*³⁹². Hence, superfluous words are not required. *Unde jam accipe non diserta sed fortia, neque terrena figmenta, sed vera coelestia documenta, neque philosophorum haeretica prava commenta, sed perfecta apostolica arcana sacramenta, neque grammatica quae superflua est doctrinae sapientiae, sed perfecta apostolica ex evangelicis scripturis super melle et favor dulciora et meliora divina praecepta. Disce itaque quia in hoc sophistae hujus mundi stulti vel muti facti sunt, quoniam sapientiam veram non cognoverunt, et ideo reprobii facti sunt*³⁹³. Hereby, the difference between philosophical and apostolic wisdom is emphasized. Additionally, the opposition between mundane interpretations and genuine “celestial documents” is underlined; and interestingly, the grammar is considered superfluous to the sapiential doctrine. In his narrative, Hincmar focuses on Gottschalk and on the refutation of his Trinitarian doctrine. Curiously, this statement of Hincmar’s on the superfluosity of grammar appears to be in direct opposition to the one of Alcuin, his teacher³⁹⁴.

Namely, Hincmar argues that Gottschalk makes erroneous interpretations, according to the ways of the heretics, that he does not understand the sense well, and that he alters the meaning of words in accordance to his erroneous sense: *...sic et Gothescalcus de his quae hinc legerat, aut in totum dimisit, aut prave interpretando negavit, aut sicut facere solent haeretici, quia malo voto legit quod legit, ex retributione justitiae intelligere bene non valuit, idque ad pravitatem sui sensus inflectens, sicut voluit posuit*³⁹⁵. In this passage, Hincmar introduces the notion of Gottschalk’s own wisdom, inspired not by God, but either by an evil spirit (*a malo spiritu inspirata*), or simply, having turned into stupidity (*a se stulta inventa*), as an antonym to the previously-mentioned ‘true wisdom’ (*sapientia vera*, see above): *Cum primo referimus, quia secundum suam sapientiam, non sibi a Deo datam, sed vel a malo spiritu sibi inspiratam, vel a se stultam inventam, debuerat cognoscere differentiam esse inter ternam et trinam, sed dicens se esse sapientem stultus factus est*³⁹⁶. Gottschalk’s words are ridicule, and equated with fraudulent, fantastic tales: *Scriptis et alia multa ridicula, quae apud fautores suos, quibus ea servanda fraudulenter donavit...aniles fabulas, hic inserere superfluum duximus neniae*³⁹⁷. The erroneous interpretation, furthermore, lies in the core of heresy, whereas the devil is designated

³⁹² Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 565AB.

³⁹³ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 565BC.

³⁹⁴ Cf. Alcuin, De Rhetorica et virtutibus (ed. Migne, PL 101) 919–946; M. Alberi, The „Mystery of the Incarnation” and Wisdom’s House (Prov. 9.1) in Alcuin’s „Disputatio de vera philosophia”, in: Journal of Theological Studies 48 (1997) 505–516; M. Diesenberger/H. Wolfram, Arn und Alcuin 790 bis 804. Zwei Freunde und ihre Schriften, in: Erzbischof Arn von Salzburg, ed. M. Niederkorn-Bruck/A. Scharer, in Veröffentlichungen des Instituts für österreichische Geschichtsforschung 40 (Wien/München 2004) 81–106.

³⁹⁵ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 565BC.

³⁹⁶ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 565D.

³⁹⁷ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 613BC.

as a wicked interpreter: *...perversus interpretis diabolus*³⁹⁸. According to Hincmar, Gottschalk is a bad interpreter of the Bible; either because he does not understand its sense, or due to his purposeful lying: *Et vel non intellegens vel scienter mendaciter interpretans ex scripturis quod bene et vere dictum est*³⁹⁹. Just a few lines below, Hincmar calls Gottschalk a liar, as already mentioned above: *Gotescalcus mendax*⁴⁰⁰.

On the other hand, Gottschalk employs the identical arsenal of heretical accusations as his opponents do, by equating those who do not share his point of view with heretics, enemies of the truth and friends of falsehood⁴⁰¹. Consequently, we can conclude that the identical phraseological means have been applied in the textual struggle against the opponents, only in different settings and situations, depending upon the given contexts. The aim was to prevent those judged as the enemies of truth – meaning, of tradition – from interpolating certain parts, introducing novelties, interpreting according to their own liking instead of aligning with the interpretations of the fathers, thus interfering with ancient dogmatic precepts and altering tradition. Likewise, in his letter addressed to Pope Nicholas, Hincmar accuses Gottschalk of vehemently twisting the meaning of the Scriptures, and of lacerating the words of the Fathers: *...non solum scripturas ad suam sensum violenter inflexas, sed et catholicorum dicta detruncata...praevalent...decantare*⁴⁰².

Analogous image of the devil being the source of every erroneous interpretation of the truth is to be found in *De imagine Tetrici*, a poem in a dialogue form, written by Walafridus Strabo in 829⁴⁰³. Here, the author writes on the statue of Theodoric the Great, king of the Ostrogoths (454 – 526), which became a symbol and the warning of the danger of heresy. Namely, Arianism – heresy of Theodoric - was hereby only recurred to as a symbol of the struggle for the preservation of the Christian faith within the Carolingian realm, which found itself surrounded by threats to its unity at those years⁴⁰⁴. Walafridus's message therein aligns to the aspirations of the Carolingian state with one of the main aims to re-affirm its stronghold

³⁹⁸ Hincmar, *Epistolae* (ed. E. Perels, MGH Epp. VIII, Berlin 1939) 113, l. 7–8.

³⁹⁹ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 188, ed. Perels 198, l. 12–25.

⁴⁰⁰ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 188, ed. Perels 198, l. 37.

⁴⁰¹ Hincmar, *De Una et non Trina Deitate* (ed. Migne, PL 125) 473–618, here 613–614; Gottschalk, *Confessio Prolixior*, ed. Lambot 66.

⁴⁰² Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 162.

⁴⁰³ Cf. Walafridus, *De imagine Tetrici*, PLAC II (ed. E. Dümmler, Berlin 1884) 370–378; M. W. Herren, 'The *De imagine Tetrici*' of Walafrid Strabo: Edition and Translation, in: *The Journal of Medieval Latin* 1 (1991) 118–139.

⁴⁰⁴ Cf. Walafridus, *De imagine Tetrici*, ed. Dümmler 378.

in the unity of the Christian faith, being one of the principal pillars which were to strengthen the balance in the realm. Thence, the line between wicked interpretation and falsity has been traced, with the devil as the source.

In the 9th-century Byzantium, the significance of words in delineating correct from the incorrect doctrine, as a means in demarcating the right from the erroneous approach to it, has also been emphasized. In his treatise against the Manichaeans composed at the very end of the 860's, Peter of Sicily stresses several times that the Manichaeans recur to allegory and twist the interpretation in the aim of fulfilling their plans: ...τὴν ἐρμηνείαν πρὸς τὸ οἰκεῖον βούλημα διαστρέψαι⁴⁰⁵; they use allegory illicitly: Ἀλληγοροῦντες ἀθέσμως...⁴⁰⁶. Similarly, Peter the Hegoumen, the author of another important account on the Paulicians originated in ca. 870, addressed the Manichaeans' recurrence to allegory and their employment of metaphorical language likewise: Ταῦτα πάντα καὶ πλείω τούτων...ἀλληγοροῦσιν⁴⁰⁷.

Theodore the Studite accentuates the importance of the faculty of expression and practice, in order to defend the correct faith and to oppose those who hold erroneous beliefs: Δεῖ γὰρ καὶ τῆς ἐν λόγῳ δυνάμεως καὶ πείρας μετέχειν τὸν ὀρθοδόξιας ἀντεχόμενον, καὶ ἀντιφέρεσθαι τοῖς κακοδόξοις βουλόμενον⁴⁰⁸. And furthermore, the Iconoclasts were characterized by their "alien", foreign way of thinking, as Theodore observes - ἀλλόφυλος νοῦς - which was to be fought by means of 'correct understanding' - μετ' ὀρθοῦ λόγου⁴⁰⁹. Theodore's reference to language should be brought into connection with Gottschalk's attitude to correct grammar. The fault of the Iconoclasts, to have led the faithful astray was expressed in Germanus's *De Haeresibus et Synodis*: τῆς ἀληθείας διαμαρτάνουσι⁴¹⁰.

Additionally, the concept of adultery, applied to committing forgery with the word of God, also frames the research axis relevant to correct wording⁴¹¹. According to Theodore the Studite, who

⁴⁰⁵ Peter of Sicily, Pierre de Sicile. *Histoire des Pauliciens*, in: *Les sources grecques pour l'histoire des Pauliciens d'Asie Mineure*, ed. Ch. Astruc/W. Conus-Wolska/J. Gouillard/P. Lemerle/D. Papachryssanthou/J. Paramelle, in: *Travaux et mémoires* 4 (1970) 3–67, here 37, 81.

⁴⁰⁶ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al., 11, 14.

⁴⁰⁷ Peter the Hegoumen, Pierre l'Higoumène. *Précis sur les Pauliciens*, in: *Les sources grecques pour l'histoire des Pauliciens d'Asie Mineure*, ed. Ch. Astruc/W. Conus-Wolska/J. Gouillard/P. Lemerle/D. Papachryssanthou/J. Paramelle, in: *Travaux et mémoires* 4 (1970) 69–92, here 89, 17.

⁴⁰⁸ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 49, ed. Migne 1084C.

⁴⁰⁹ cf. Parry, *Depicting the world* 144; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Antirrhetici tres adversus iconomachus*, III *Antirrheticus* (ed. Migne, PG 99) 327–436, here 389A; English translation: C. P. Roth, *St. Theodore the Studite on the Holy Icons* (New York 1981).

⁴¹⁰ Parry, *Depicting the world* 137; cf. Germanus, *De Haeresibus et Synodis*, ed. A. Mai et al. 61.

⁴¹¹ Cf. below, chapter II.4.

takes part in adultery with the adulterers (alluding to the Moechian controversy), also becomes an adulterer; consequently, those who are with those who destroy the Gospel, jointly participate in the destruction of the Gospel: *...ὅπερ αὐτοὶ ὁμοιώθησαν, τῷ μοιχῷ συμμοιχεύσαντες, τῷ μοιχοζεύκτη συζεύξαντες, τῷ θεοκατηγόρῳ συνθεοκατηγορήσαντες, τῷ εὐαγγελιολύτῃ συνευαγγελιολυττήσαντες*⁴¹². Thus, the second, or, adulterous marriage⁴¹³, is in Theodore's understanding compared to the evil-doing against the words of the Scriptures. In the course of his narrative, Theodore compares the fraudulent heretical practices to the story-tales, designed in the aim of seducing the souls of the simple: *...οὕτω ψευδοεποῦσι μυθαρνεύμενοι, ὅπως θηρεύσωσι ψυχὰς ἀφελότητι πορευομένας*⁴¹⁴. The words, according to Nichephorus, Patriarch of Constantinople, during the second outburst of the Iconoclast crisis, lead the spirit of the faithful towards the understanding of the phenomena in an indirect way, by means of reasoning, whereas the icons direct the faithful to grasp the knowledge in a direct way⁴¹⁵.

The word of the truth is always the same, Theodore argues; only that that which is unchangeable can be true – the statement which is to be compared to the one of Gottschalk, above mentioned. The falsehood, therefore, is subordinate to the laws of change⁴¹⁶. Furthermore, not only which words have been uttered is relevant, but in which manner and order. As we can read in Photius's 15th homily, the heretic (namely Arius) pays the penalty for his “licentious tongue” - *τῆς ἀκολάστου γλώσσης ὁ δυσμενῆς τὰς δίκας ἐδίδου*⁴¹⁷. The Arians' tongue is venomous: *τὸν ἰὸν τῆς γλώσσης ἐκπτύουσι*⁴¹⁸ – and Photius may well be comparing it to the snake, the Devil's advocate, in this passage. The speech of the heretics is ambiguous – *ἐπαμφοτεριζούσαις ταῖς λέξεσι τὸ τῆς βλασφημίας ἀναιδῆς ἐπικρυπτόμενοι*⁴¹⁹. The heretics – the enemies of the Spirit⁴²⁰ – have also a bold tongue – *ἡ τολμηρὰ τῶν αἵρετιζόντων γλῶσσα*⁴²¹.

⁴¹² Theodore, *Epistolae*, Ep. 49, ed. Migne 1088CD.

⁴¹³ Cf. below, chapter II.9.

⁴¹⁴ Theodore, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 49, ed. Migne 1088D.

⁴¹⁵ Cf. Nichephorus, *Antirrhethici*, ed. Migne 381C.

⁴¹⁶ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the World* 142–144; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Antirrhethici*, ed. Migne 352C, as mentioned by Parry, 143, note 58.

⁴¹⁷ Cf. Mango, *Homilies* 244; Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. Valetta 139, l. 11–12.

⁴¹⁸ Mango, *Homilies* 248; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 142, l. 11.

⁴¹⁹ Photius, 16th homily, Mango 264, l. 3–4; Photius, ed. Laourda 155.

⁴²⁰ 16th homily, Mango 275; Photius, ed. Laourda 161.

⁴²¹ Photius, *Homilies*, 16th homily, ed. Mango 274; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 160, l. 18–19.

II. 2. DEFINING HERESY/RELIGIOUS DISSENT

in 9th century Francia and Byzantium

In this chapter, the attempt of defining, framing and naming of heretics and heresies in 9th-century Francia and Byzantium will be undertaken, including their defining features, and modes of appearance. The analysis will be conducted according to the selected examples contained in the most representative textual material.

Numerous and diverse are the names of the heretics, but they share one deceitfulness, as attested in the Theodosian Code: *...diversa sunt nomina (haereticorum), sed una perfidia*, against which our fore-fathers have established the precepts (the role of tradition); the heretical madness apparently makes a constituent trait of a definition of heretic:

*De haereticis omnibus, quorum et errorem execramur et nomen, hoc est de eunomianis arrianis macedonianis ceterisque omnibus, quorum sectas piissimae sanctioni taedet inserere, quibus cunctis diversa sunt nomina, sed una perfidia, illa praecipimus debere servari, quae divi avus et pater nostrae clementiae constituerunt, scituris universis, quod, si in eodem furore permanserint, interminatae poenae erunt obnoxii*⁴²².

The Theodosian Code enhances the objective to correct the false doctrine and return to the true faith⁴²³. The enemies of the Catholic faith should be eradicated, which is conveyed on the example on the Donatists, as presented in the following section of the Theodosian Code. The sect of the Donatist should be destroyed; this sect preferred the appellation of schism, in order not to be called a heresy. Thus, in the case of the Donatists, the heresy originated from schism. Namely, the Donatists are designated as those who committed criminal and lawless actions by performing the second baptism: moreover, they are accused of having infected others. In this case, a heresy was born from a schism. The heresy of the Donatists is referred to as perversity and depravity, in contradiction with tradition:

Adversarios catholicae fidei extirpare huius decreti auctoritate prospeximus. Ideoque intercidendam specialiter eam sectam nova constitutione censuimus, quae, ne haeresis vocaretur, appellationem schismatis praeferebat. In tantum enim sceleris progressi dicuntur hi, quos donatistas vocant, ut baptismum sacrosanctum mysteriis recalcatis temeritate noxia

⁴²² Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri*, 876; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.60, 462.

⁴²³ Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16, 6, 3, 464.

iterarint et homines semel, ut traditum est, munere divinitatis ablutos contagione profanae repetitionis infecerint. Ita contigit, ut haeresis ex schismate nasceretur. Inde male credulas mentes ad spem secundae indulgentiae blandus error invitat...Quare hac lege sancimus, ut quisquis post haec fuerit rebaptizasse detectus...poenam, qua in perpetuum afficiatur, expendat...⁴²⁴.

In 9th-century Francia, various authors have dealt with numerous attempts to define heretics. Hincmar of Reims opens his treatise on predestination with an elucidation of the term “heretic”⁴²⁵. Hincmar considers heretics to be those who persist in their erroneous doctrine and resist correction of their pestiferous and deadly teachings: *Qui ergo in Ecclesia Christi morbidum aliquid pravumque sentiunt, si correpti ut sanum rectumque sapient, resistunt contumaciter, suaque pestifera ac mortifera dogmata emendare nolunt, sed defensare persistent, haeretici fiunt...* Furthermore, heretics are not inspired by the spirit of wisdom, but of impatience, and perturb the peace of the saintly: *Genus hominum callidum non spiritu sapientiae, sed impatientiae, quo solent haeticorum fervere primordia, et pacem perturbare sanctorum*. Namely, the actions undertaken by the heretics are alluded to as a crime, *scelus*⁴²⁶. The heretics are equaled to anti-Christ: *...omnes antichristi, id est haeretici*⁴²⁷.

Hincmar enumerates the heretics: Arians, Novatians, Photinus, Manichaeans, Sabbelians, Eunomians, Macedonians, Donatists, and Pelagians. Refutation of the theology of Gottschalk of Orbais, and primarily, of his Trinitarian teaching, is in the core of Hincmar’s narrative⁴²⁸. Gottschalk is seen as a heretic and a liar, and a relationship to the Devil, the father of lies, is evident⁴²⁹. Gottschalk’s statements are wayward, as is the case with heretics: *Igitur Gothescalcus perverse dicit, ut revera haeticus*⁴³⁰. On several occasions, Hincmar enlists heretical teachings in his treatise: *...plures convincuntur haeretici, Manichaei videlicet, Sabelliani, Ariani, Nestoriani, Eutychiani, Macedoniani; Eudoxiani...*⁴³¹

Hincmar brings Gottschalk into relation with other heretics, heralds of the erroneously-interpreted Trinitarian doctrine, and to other opponents of the Nicæan creed, who were

⁴²⁴ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 881–882; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.6.4, 464.

⁴²⁵ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 481CD.

⁴²⁶ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 501C.

⁴²⁷ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 500C.

⁴²⁸ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 482AC.

⁴²⁹ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 553CD, 576CD.

⁴³⁰ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 602D.

⁴³¹ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 603D–604A.

condemned: *Fugiamus turbulentes et coenosos fallaciae rivos, sectas Deum impugnantes, Arianico furorem, dividendam individuum Trinitatem in quinta synodo scribentes, et sanctus Athanasius in libris suis demonstrat haec quae Gothescalcus didicit, videlicet quia sicut Deus personaliter est trinus, sic deitas personaliter est trina, sensisse praefatum Arium et complices ejus in sacra Nicaena synodo damnatos: quos cum omnibus qui contra symbolum Nicaenum sentire praesumunt, omnia concilia catholica damnaverunt et damnant*⁴³². Hincmar alludes to Pope Gelasius (492-496) on the topic related to heresies. The Pope compares heresies to a plague, which reaches the hearts of the simple: *Nam si limitibus etiam praefixis positarum semel synodalium regularum, non cessant elisae pestes resumtis certaminibus contra fundamentum sese veritatis attollere, et simplicia quaeque corda percutere, quid fieret si subinde fas esset perfidis inire concilium?*⁴³³

The decisions of the ecclesiastical synods are not allowed to be altered, and they condemn the authors of the insanity of error: *Quae majores nostri divina inspiratione cernentes, necessario praecaverunt, ut quod acta semel synodus pro fidei communione, et veritate catholica atque apostolica promulgasset, non sinerent post haec novis retractionibus mutilari, ne pravis occasione praeberetur quae medicinaliter fuerant statuta pulsandi, sed auctore cujuslibet insaniae ac pariter errore damnato sufficere judicarunt...*⁴³⁴ Consequently, the role of the ecclesiastical tradition is highly emphasized in Hincmar's work; the non-compliance to the canons is to be condemned. The role of discipline and negligence is stressed in Hincmar's treatise, when expounding on sin, heresy included: *In factis enim saepe infirmitate, saepe negligentia delinquitur, in studiis vero malitiosa semper intentione peccatur*⁴³⁵. Negligence enables the wicked to join the good in union, and bring impediment to the unity of the good ones⁴³⁶. Discipline is the most effective weapon against sin⁴³⁷. Alluding to Pope Leo, Hincmar underlines the responsibility of the leaders and their negligence in frequently allowing the plague to spread as a result of the sins of those who are situated in the lower ranks: *Aloquin, ut Leo dicit, inferiorum ordinum culpa ad nullos magis sunt referendae quam ad desides negligentisque rectores, qui multam saepe nutriunt pestilentiam, dum necessariam dissimulant adhibere medicinam*⁴³⁸. On the other hand, the role of the ecclesiastical tradition has been

⁴³² Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 497AB.

⁴³³ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 497C.

⁴³⁴ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 497CD.

⁴³⁵ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 504A; more on the importance of negligence and discipline in Hincmar's texts: cf. *Ibid.*, 506B–D.

⁴³⁶ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 507A.

⁴³⁷ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 507AB.

⁴³⁸ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 188, ed. Perels 200, l. 35–38.

stressed. The Synod of Nicaea reflects the divine authority: *Hoc namque sacrum Nicaenum consilium, non ad inventionem humana, sed inspiratione et auctoritate divina constituit*⁴³⁹. Hincmar discredits Gottschalk's theological stance by quoting the Scriptures, as well as the Church Fathers⁴⁴⁰. Gottschalk is accused for not having obeyed the apostolic and ecclesiastical traditions, as conveyed by ecclesiastical synods: *...contraque caeterorum orthodoxorum traditionem sentiens condemnatus est Gothescalcus, vel de omnibus, quae apostolicae sedis et sex generalium synodorum auctoritate diffinita sunt...*⁴⁴¹

In his epistle on Gottschalk's doctrine of double predestination, Hincmar cites Gottschalk's accusation at the Synod of Quierzy (849). Gottschalk is accused for his perverted doctrines, and his irregular usurpation of sacerdotal office, and therefore condemned, castigated and imprisoned. The main charge against Gottschalk was that he acted contrarily to the ecclesiastical and civil affairs: *Frater Goteschalc, sacerdotalis ministerii officium, quod irregulariter usurpasti et in cunctis moribus ac pravis actibus atque perversis doctrinis eo hactenus abuti non pertinuisti...noveris tibi esse...sublatum et, ne ulterius eo fungi praesumas, perpetuo interdictum. Insuper quia et ecclesiastica et civilia negocia contra propositum et nomen monachi conturbare contempnens iura ecclesiastica praesumpsisti, durissimis verberibus te castigari et secundum ecclesiasticas regulas ergastulo retrudi auctoritate episcopali decernimus...*⁴⁴². As the Scriptures warn, the pseudo-prophets and false teachers who negate God are at the origin of sects. They are blaspheming the path of truth and shall encounter damnation: *Fuerunt pseudoprophetae in populo, sicut et in vobis erunt magistri mendaces, qui inducent sectas per[dictionis et eum], qui emit eos, Dominum negantes, superducente sibi celerem perditionem. Et multi sequentur eorum luxurias, per quas via veritatis blasphematur...*⁴⁴³. Gottschalk was teaching wayward doctrines: *...perversae praedicationis*⁴⁴⁴, and had "abused" the teachings of Augustine, when he presented his doctrine of double predestination: *Deo quo dante exemplum beato Augustino male abusus est Goteschalcus*⁴⁴⁵. Gottschalk was thus accused and condemned for having acted against canonical institutions in ecclesiastical and civil undertakings (as already mentioned above), and furthermore that he did

⁴³⁹ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 490B.

⁴⁴⁰ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 504BD.

⁴⁴¹ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 504D.

⁴⁴² Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 12–23, here 23, l. 18–24; on the Synod of Quierzy, cf. Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 12–23, here 23, l. 18–26; Mansi XIV, 921; Hrabanus Maurus, Epistolae, Ep. 43 (ed. E. Dümmler, MGH Epp. V, Berlin 1899) 379–516, here 489, the answer of Hrabanus Maurus.

⁴⁴³ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 13, l. 21–24, quoting 2. Petr. 2:1–3.

⁴⁴⁴ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 38, ed. Perels 13, l. 39.

⁴⁴⁵ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 22, l. 32–33.

not acknowledge his wrongdoings: *...quia contra canonicam institutionem civilia et ecclesiastica negotia perturbare studuit indefessus et se noluit recognoscere vel aliquot modo humiliare profusus, ab episcopis est secundum ecclesiastica iura damnatus*⁴⁴⁶. The difference between correct, true faith – *recta fides*, and a sect – *secta* – has been clearly presented. It is namely this, which discerns the heretic from a true believer – his opposition to the correct doctrine. Hincmar’s labelling of Gottschalk a heretic, a leader of the sect and of his simple followers whom he led into error and away from the body of believers – has thus reflected the real dangers of a false doctrine.⁴⁴⁷ The emphasis is hereby also put onto different interpretations of the term *secta* (negatively employed by Hrabanus), and *secta vera* (positively by Gottschalk).⁴⁴⁸ For example, Hrabanus used the term *incontaminata* to refer to the genuine, Orthodox religion,⁴⁴⁹ which was the opposite of *haec secta nefanda* as used when referring to Gottschalk and his followers.⁴⁵⁰

Heretics are those who recede from the Church by their own judgment, and contemplate on the perverse dogma, according to Hrabanus: *...qui perversum dogma cogitantes, arbitrio suo de Ecclesia recesserunt*⁴⁵¹. The heresies are named after their respective heresiarch⁴⁵². In spite of the fact that heresies differ by various errors the heretics fall into, the common denominator for all of them is the conspiracy against God they undertake under the same name: *...quaedam in multis erroribus diversae invicem sibi dissentiunt, communi tamen nomine adversus Ecclesiam Dei conspirant*⁴⁵³. Hrabanus was clearly inspired by Isidore of Seville (c.

⁴⁴⁶ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 48, ed. Perels 26–30, here 27, l.17 – 28, l. 1–2.

⁴⁴⁷ Hincmar, *De una*, ed. Migne 475–484, 510, 579, 613; Hincmar, *Epistolae*, ed. E. Perels 160–163, 169.

⁴⁴⁸ Cf. Gottschalk’s poem *Ut quid iubes*, in: M.-L. Weber, *Die Gedichte des Gottschalk von Orbais* (Lateinische Sprache und Literatur des Mittelalters 27, Frankfurt 1992) 150.

⁴⁴⁹ Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais* 180.

⁴⁵⁰ Hrabanus, *Epistolae* (ed. E. Dümmler, MGH Epp. V, Berlin 1898-1899) 379–516, here 496–498.

⁴⁵¹ Hrabanus, *De Clericorum Institutione Ad Heistulphum Archiepiscopum Libri Tres* (ed. Migne, PL 107) 293–420A, here l. I, c.31; Id., *De sacramento corporis et sanguinis Domini*, *ibid.*, 316C–321C, here 317BC; cf. Hrabanus Maurus, *De Institutione Clericorum Libri Tres, Über die Unterweisung der Geistlichen I* (ed. D. Zimpel, Turnhout 2006).

⁴⁵² Hrabanus, *De Clericorum Institutione*, ed. Migne l.1, c. 31, 318B.

⁴⁵³ Hrabanus, *De Clericorum Institutione*, ed. Migne l. 2, c. 58; Id., *De haeresibus variis*, *ibid.*, 371B–378B, here 377A-378A.

560 – 636), when composing his list of heresies⁴⁵⁴; nevertheless, the connection to Epiphanius' *Panarion* is obvious likewise⁴⁵⁵.

Furthermore, Hrabanus speaks on *recta fides* in relation to *incontaminata religio*⁴⁵⁶. This would imply the construct of heresy as an argument *a contrario*, therefore related to the contamination and ritual pollution⁴⁵⁷. Namely, in the letter addressed to Louis the Pious (778 – 840; succeeded Charlemagne 814 – 840) dating from 847, Hrabanus refers to Louis the Pious as a determined leader, chief responsible of the true religion and a defender of the holy Church of god: ...*vere religionis strenuissimus rector ac defensor sanctae dei aecclisiae*⁴⁵⁸ which certainly is a *topos*, a common place in the designation of Carolingian rulers⁴⁵⁹. The aim of the Synod held in 847 in Mainz was the discussion on the state of the true religion – *de statu verae religionis*⁴⁶⁰, which is alluded to as a “sane” doctrine, *sana doctrina*⁴⁶¹.

It is with these words that Hrabanus aimed at defending Christianity from the false teachings of Gottschalk at the Synod of Mainz in the year to come⁴⁶². Namely, Gottschalk was accused of heresy and convicted at the Synod of Mainz in 848:...*Gotescalcus, qui dicebatur hereticus...convictus est*⁴⁶³.

Gottschalk's teaching on twin predestination has also been treated as a sect in *Annales Xantenses*⁴⁶⁴:...*secta quaedam in Sinodo episcoporum inlata est a quibusdam monachis de predestinatione omnipotentis Dei...*

⁴⁵⁴ Isidore of Seville compiled his work on the Etymologies between the years 615 and early 630's; cf. Isidore of Seville, *Etymologiarum sive originum libri XX, De Haeresibus Christianorum, VIII (de ecclesiis et sectis), 5* (ed. Migne, PL 82) 73–728C, here 298-305; *The Etymologies of Isidore of Seville*, trans. and ed. S. A. Barney/Lewis, W. J./J.A. Beach/Berghof, O. (Cambridge 2006) 173–190.

⁴⁵⁵ For example, the similar observation on the identical strivings against God all the heretics undertake, albeit their differences.

⁴⁵⁶ Cf. MGH Conc. III, No. 14 [Mainz] (ed. W. Hartmann, Hannover 1984) 159–160.

⁴⁵⁷ The problem of ritual impurity has been very exhaustively dealt with; apart from those works already cited above (in chapter I.4.), I shall name only a few more titles: A. Benoit, *Orthodoxie et hérésies aux premiers siècles*, in: *Aux origines du Christianisme* (Paris 2000) 511–518; R. Moore, *Heresy as Disease*, in: *The Concept of Heresy in the Middle Ages, 11th-13th Century*, *Mediaevalia Lovaniensia*, ed. W. Lourdaux/D. Verhelst (Louvain 1976) 104–143.

⁴⁵⁸ Conc. III, ed. Hartmann 159, l. 25–26.

⁴⁵⁹ Cf., among many other examples: ...*sanctae Dei ecclesiae strenuissimus cultor Karolus*, *Annales Bertiniani* (ed. G. Waitz, MGH SSRG V, Hannover 1883) 36, a. 849.

⁴⁶⁰ Conc. III, ed. Hartmann 160, l. 19.

⁴⁶¹ Conc. III, ed. Hartmann 160, l. 26.

⁴⁶² Cf. Synod of Mainz in: MGH Conc. III, ed. W. Hartmann 179–184.

⁴⁶³ *Annales Fuldenses* (ed. Friedrich Kurze, MGH SSRG VII, Hannover 1891) 37–38.

⁴⁶⁴ Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais 192: Annales Xantenses* (ed. B. von Simson, MGH SSRG XII, Hannover 1909) 16, s.a. 848.

Amolo, archbishop of Lyon (841 – 852), also speaks of Gottschalk’s heresy, in the letter addressed to him. Amolo thus perceives Gottschalk as having been sadly deceived by the spirit of error and arrogance: ...*spiritu erroris et superbiae miserabiliter deceptus*⁴⁶⁵.

Curiously, it is in the letter of Amolo addressed to Gottschalk that we can grasp another case of attribution of the term “heretic” to those who accused Gottschalk of heresy themselves. In other words, we discover more on Gottschalk’s self-defense and the accusations he directed towards those who were his main opponents. Namely, Gottschalk has designated them as heretics, “the Hrabanians”: *Nam inter cetera omnes, qui insaniae sensuum tuorum zelo fidei resistunt, heretiquos appellare non metuis, eos que a bono et erudito atque catholico episcopo Rabanicos nuncupare presumis*⁴⁶⁶. Gottschalk wrote of Hincmar as of a heretic, the enemy of truth and friend of falsehood: ...*haereticus veritatis inimicus falsitatis amicus*⁴⁶⁷.

Jonas of Orléans makes an equation between the Latin word *secta* and Greek *haeresis* (ἁῖρεσις): namely, he states that the Latin word *secta* corresponds to the Greek word *haeresis*: *Sectae igitur Latine, Graece dicuntur haereses*⁴⁶⁸.

In the 860’s, Ratramnus of Corbie, Carolingian monk and theologian, composed his answer to the Greek accusations against the Latins, arisen at the culminating point of the *Filioque* controversy. After having enumerated those points of discord, Ratramnus consecrates his treatise on debating the *Filioque* issue and proving the Latin position correct, according to the testimony from the Scriptures and from the Fathers. He refers to the Greek accusations as false, heretical, superstitious, or impious: *Opposita quibus Michael et Basilius, Graecorum imperatores, Romanam Ecclesiam infamare conantur, vel falsa, vel haeretica, vel superstitiosa, vel irreligiosa fore cognoscuntur*⁴⁶⁹.

Various usages and connotations of the terms and definitions employed for heresies and heretics were widely spread in Byzantine literature likewise. Besides, the recurrence to *topoi* and *clichés* in portraying heretics has also been attested, as in the Latin texts.

⁴⁶⁵ Amolo of Lyon, *Epistolae*, Epistola 2 (ed. Ernst Dümmler, MGH Epp. V, Berlin 1899) 368–378, here 377, l. 3–4.

⁴⁶⁶ Amolo, *Epistola 2*, ed. Dümmler 377, l. 5–7.

⁴⁶⁷ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 613–614; Gottschalk, *Confessio Prolixior*, ed. Lambot 66; cf. Gottschalk, *De Praedestinatione*, ed. Lambot 214, 227.

⁴⁶⁸ Jonas of Orléans, *De Cultu Imaginum Libri Tres* (ed. Migne, PL 106) 305B–388A, here 314D.

⁴⁶⁹ Ratramnus of Corbie, *Contra Graecorum Opposita Romanam Ecclesiam Infamantium Libri Quatuor* (ed. Migne, PL 121) 223–346B, here 225D.

An important treatise affluent with crucial information on heresies and the perception of them in the 8th-century Byzantium⁴⁷⁰, imminently preceding the period, which represents the chronological core of this thesis, was falsely attributed to Patriarch Germanus (713-730), and entitled *Narratio de Synodis et Haeresibus*⁴⁷¹. This text contains the enumeration of capital heresies - *αἱρέσεων κεφαλαί*⁴⁷². Furthermore, it has been noticed, similarly as in the *Panarion*, that the heresies are similar to one another, albeit the differences in their teachings. They share the same insanity which binds them. The heretics are portrayed as repulsive and impure; additionally, they are far from the kingdom of heaven, as well as from the truth: *Γειτονοῦσι δέ πως καὶ ἀγγίθουροι ὡς εἰπεῖν εἰσὶ τινὲς τῶν αἱρετικῶν, ἤγουν ἔν τισι τῶν δογμάτων αὐτῶν βλασφημίαι πρὸς ἀλλήλους οὕτως... ἴση ἄνοια... ἀποτρόπαιοι καὶ μιαιοὶ καὶ τῆς ἄνω βασιλείας ἐξόριστοι*⁴⁷³ ...*τῆς ἀληθείας διαμαρτάνουσι*...⁴⁷⁴.

Even before the 9th century, the Byzantines began to use the term “Manichaean” in reference to the dualists⁴⁷⁵. Throughout his epistles, Theodore the Studite mentions different denominations of heretics⁴⁷⁶, and refers to heresy as the greatest sin of all⁴⁷⁷. In Theodore’s 49th letter, he argues that when combating the heterodox, one must be sure to have good writing skills and capacity⁴⁷⁸: ...*ὅτι μάλιστα καλυνεῖς, ἐὰν τὰ τῆς γραμματικῆς σχόλια δυνήθῃς ἐπιέναι. Δεῖ γὰρ καὶ τῆς ἐν λόγῳ δυνάμεως καὶ πείρας μετέχειν τὸν ὁροδοσίας ἀντεχόμενον, καὶ ἀντιφέρεσθαι τοῦς κακοδόξους βουλόμενον*...⁴⁷⁹. Theodore advises that it is good to avoid communion with heretics - *διαφυγοῦσαι τὴν κοινωνίαν τῶν αἱρετικῶν*⁴⁸⁰. Two other words for heresy which he uses is *ἀσέβεια*, or *ἑτερόδοξοι*⁴⁸¹.

⁴⁷⁰ On the overview of the orthodoxy and dissent in Byzantium, cf. M. Angold, *Church and society: Iconoclasm and After*, in: *The Social History of Byzantium*, ed. J. Haldon (Oxford 2009) 233–256, at 248–250.

⁴⁷¹ Germanus, *Narratio de synodis et haeretibus* (ed. Migne, PG 98) 40–88; Cf. D. M. Gwynn, *From Iconoclasm to Arianism: the construction of Christian tradition in the Iconoclast controversy*, in: *Greek, Roman, and Byzantine Studies* 47 (2007) 225–251, especially 233.

⁴⁷² Cf. Germanus, *De Haeresibus et Synodis*, ed. Mai et al. 64–65.

⁴⁷³ Germanus, *De Haeresibus et Synodis*, ed. Mai et al. 70–71.

⁴⁷⁴ Germanus, *De Haeresibus et Synodis*, ed. Mai et al. 62.

⁴⁷⁵ Cf. Runciman, *The Medieval Manichee* 49.

⁴⁷⁶ Ep. I, 43: Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne 1052 C; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, ed. Fatouros, I, 115, l. 20–25.

⁴⁷⁷ Pargoire, *Église Byzantine* 347; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne 1236–1237.

⁴⁷⁸ For general information on Theodore’s correspondence, see: S. Efthymiadis, *Notes on the Correspondence of Theodore the Studite*, in: *Revue des Études Byzantines* 53 (1995) 141–163.

⁴⁷⁹ Theodore the Studite *Epistolae*, ed. Migne I, Ep. 49, 1084C.

⁴⁸⁰ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 59, ed. Fatouros 170.

⁴⁸¹ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 59, ed. Fatouros 170.

In the course of his narrative of the Moechian controversy⁴⁸², Theodore speaks of the danger of a great schism (*τὸ μέγα σχίσμα*), unless the Patriarch Nicephorus removes priest Joseph from office: ...*ἡ πίστις ὀρθή; ὀρθόδοξοι ἐσμεν κατὰ πάντα: πᾶσαν αἵρεσιν ἀποβαλλόμενοι, καὶ πᾶσαν σύνοδον οἰκουμενικὴν τε καὶ τοπικὴν ἐγκεκριμένην ἀποδεχόμενοι*⁴⁸³; *Τὸ μὲν οὖν δίκαιον καὶ ὅσιον καὶ ἀσκανδάλιστον τοῖς λαοῖς τοῦ Θεοῦ*⁴⁸⁴. Namely, Theodore calls a synod of 809 heretical⁴⁸⁵. He asks the Pope to proclaim this Synod as having been heretical and illegal. In his 34th Epistle, Theodore shows that Joseph's case is a hint indicating that the foundations of Christianity have been disempowered. Theodore concludes, by induction, that the Synod of 809 was basically opposed to the Orthodox faith and therefore contradictory to the Old and New Testament. Theodore's procedure is the following: he supports his claim with Biblical verses, and later says that the decisions of the Synod are contrary to the Bible in the first place, but to the Christian canons as well, which are of equal importance as the Gospels⁴⁸⁶. Theodore's *modus operandi* is expressed in progressively aligning examples, which confirm his claim from the Bible (similar to the approach taken by both Hincmar and Hrabanus in Francia). The heretics did likewise: cited the Bible and interpreted it in their aims and purposes - they did not rarely seek support for their thoughts in the Bible. In the 37th letter, Theodore attempts to prove that the Synod of 809 tackled questions of heresy, and not of *Oikonomia*. Theodore portrayed himself as a defender of the Orthodox faith. The letter was most likely written in 809, during his second exile. The Synod of 809 had, under the pretext of the struggle for the *Oikonomia*, abolished the Gospels. Theodore refers to it as a heresy⁴⁸⁷. Furthermore, Theodore expounds on the difference between the heretics and the schismatics. The schismatics must throw anathema on their heresy and either be anointed or re-baptized. He refers to Epiphanius's book against heresies, and considers the supporters of the Synod of 809 (the "Moechianic synod") to be heretics (the "Moechianic heretics")⁴⁸⁸.

In another letter, Theodor explains that the adulterers are those who transgress God's precepts and break divine canons. They can rightly be called those who perform sacrilege: ...*μοιχεύειν*

⁴⁸² Cf. below, in chapter II.9.

⁴⁸³ Fatouros, Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 30, ed. Fatouros 82, 83; Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne, I, Ep. 30, 1005D.

⁴⁸⁴ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 30, ed. Migne 1008C.

⁴⁸⁵ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 33 (to Pope Leo), ed. Migne 1017B – 1021AB.

⁴⁸⁶ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 36, ed. Fatouros 179, 101–106.

⁴⁸⁷ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 39, ed. Fatouros 112–114, 183–184.

⁴⁸⁸ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 92, ed. Fatouros 184–5, transl. notes 153, 185; 115–120.

*καὶ λύειν τοὺς ἀνιέρους. Πῶς καλέσομεν αὐτοὺς αἰρετικούς; Παραβάτας γὰρ τῶν ἐντολῶν τοῦ Κυρίου, καὶ καταπατητὰς τῶν θείων κανόνων, καὶ ἀνιέρους, δίκαιον*⁴⁸⁹.

John the Grammarian, maybe one of the most learned of the Patriarchs, fell to the error of Iconoclasm after having performed his illustrious ecclesiastical career as an Iconophile in the first place⁴⁹⁰. Theodore the Studite composed rather numerous letters to John the Grammarian⁴⁹¹.

Three of Theodore's letters addressed to John the Grammarian were analysed by Venance Grumel⁴⁹², dating most likely from the period in which John was apparently still imbued in Orthodoxy. Apart from these letters, Theodore the Studite wrote on this subject others, as well⁴⁹³. In the first one analyzed by Grumel, the topic is related to metaphysical issues and terminology, regarding Trinity⁴⁹⁴. In the second letter addressed to John, Theodore opens the topic related to the icon worship. In the third letter, Theodore writes on image and prototype, and introduces grammatical terms to explain the adoration of images⁴⁹⁵. Photius's 15th homily is on John the Grammarian and his resemblance to the Arians⁴⁹⁶.

In his epistle addressed to young Athanasius, the topic of Theodore's narrative is, as in numerous writings of his, the Moechian controversy, or, heresy. Namely, Theodore explains to the young addressee why the Moechian controversy is considered a heresy⁴⁹⁷.

The Moechian issue represents the heaviest of all heresies: *αἵρεσις χαλεπωτάτη*⁴⁹⁸, since it implies impiety: *...διδάσκοντος τοῦ μοιχεύειν καὶ λύειν τοὺς ἀνιέρους*⁴⁹⁹. The persons involved in the Moechian controversy have transgressed God's precepts and divine canons: *Παραβάτας γὰρ τῶν ἐντολῶν τοῦ Κυρίου, καὶ καταπατητὰς τῶν θείων κανόνων*⁵⁰⁰.

⁴⁸⁹ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1072AB.

⁴⁹⁰ L. Brehier, Un patriarche sorcier à Constantinople, in: *Revue d'Orient Chretien* 9 (1904) 261–268.

⁴⁹¹ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, ed. Migne 1201A, 1212B, 1324C; S. Gero, John the Grammarian, the last iconoclastic patriarch of Constantinople: the man and the legend, *Byzantion* 3-4 (1977) 25–35.

⁴⁹² V. Grumel, Jean Grammaticos et saint Théodore Studite, *Echos d'Orient* 36 (1937) 181–190.

⁴⁹³ Cf. Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 30 (to monk Symeon), ed. Migne 1201A; Ep. 36 (to Naucratius), ed. Migne 1211 AB; Ep. 82 (to logothet Demochares), ed. Migne 1324 C.

⁴⁹⁴ Cf. Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 168, ed. Migne 1531.

⁴⁹⁵ Cf. Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 212, ed. Migne 1637–1640.

⁴⁹⁶ Mango, *Homilies* 246; 241, note 31.

⁴⁹⁷ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48 (to young Athanasius), ed. Migne 1069–1084.

⁴⁹⁸ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, ed. Migne, Ep. 48, 1069D.

⁴⁹⁹ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, ed. Migne, Ep. 48, 1072AB.

⁵⁰⁰ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1072AB.

In his homilies, Photius narrates on the subject of the true faith and propagates it among the heretics. The majority of his homilies were composed in the 860's.

Photius composed two of his homilies on heresies (15 and 16). His major works on heresy are, nevertheless, the two treatises against the Manichaeans⁵⁰¹.

In his 16th Homily, Photius defines the Orthodox faith against heresies⁵⁰². In the 17th homily, Photius speaks of the restoration of Orthodoxy, that is, of the restoration of images in St. Sophia. Namely, although the Iconoclast controversy was ended in 843⁵⁰³, the images were only restored in St. Sophia in 867, exactly when this sermon was presented.

Photius convened a Synod in 867 to condemn the practices of the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria together with the *Filioque* doctrine of the Latins⁵⁰⁴. Pope Nicholas was condemned for the Latin practices in Bulgaria, whereas the Latin *Filioque* doctrine was pronounced heretical⁵⁰⁵. Photius composed one of his most influential and discussed letters on his support of the position of the Eastern Church in the *Filioque* controversy with the Latins⁵⁰⁶.

One of the most important pieces of textual evidence for the actual mind-set of the Byzantine clergy in regard to heresies and the Orthodox credo is portrayed in detail and picturesquely by Photius in his 18th homily⁵⁰⁷. In this literary composition, the refutation of all heresies takes the predominant place, since this homily depicts the events of the Council of 867⁵⁰⁸. It proclaimed triumph over all heresies, and proclamation and glorification of the Orthodox credo, uttered by both Emperors, Michael III (842 – 867) and Basil I (867 – 886). In a panegyric tone, Photius proclaims the destruction not of one, but of all the heresies, effectuated by Michael III. Photius extolls the work of the Emperors in combatting heresy: theirs was the struggle, which reflected the state endeavors. Photius proceeds by enumerating all heresies fought against upon each of the seven Ecumenical councils: he starts with the Arian heresy, followed by the heresy of Macedonius, of Nestorius, the Monophysite one, the heresy

⁵⁰¹ Cf. Photius, *Contra Manichaeos* (ed. Migne, PG 102) 15–264; see also H. Grégoire, *Les sources de l'histoire des Pauliciens*, *Bulletin de la Classe des Lettres de l'Académie Royale de Belgique* 22 (1936) 95–114; F. Scheidweiler, *Paulikianer-probleme*, *Byzantinische Zeitschrift* 43 (1950) 10–39; Garsoian, *The Paulician Heresy*.

⁵⁰² Mango, *Homilies* 21.

⁵⁰³ Mango, *Homilies* 279.

⁵⁰⁴ Cf. below, chapter II.6.

⁵⁰⁵ Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios* 32–34; cf. the Latin version in: Wolfram, *Conversio Bagoariorum et Carantanorum* 58–83, 217, 226–227.

⁵⁰⁶ Cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 200 sq.

⁵⁰⁷ For more detailed information on the date of composition of this homily, see Mango, *Homilies* 297–299; Chadwick, *East and West* 158–161.

⁵⁰⁸ For more detailed information on this Council, cf. Mango, *Homilies* 299–305.

of Eutyches, of the Monothelites, of the Origenistic doctrines, to conclude his list of annihilated heresies with Iconoclasm⁵⁰⁹. Photius's main theme through the entire homily is the praise of the Emperor's faith and his struggle with the heresies, as well as his triumph over them⁵¹⁰. The enemy of the Church, embodied in heresies, has finally been suppressed by the hand of the Emperor, together with their devices and leaders - ...*ἅμα πάσας τὰς φάλαγγας τοῦ ἐχθροῦ αὐτοῖς ἡγεμόσι καὶ αὐτοῖς τεχνάσμασι καὶ βουλαῖς μιᾶ καὶ τῇ αὐτῇ πληγῇ τῆς βασιλικῆς δεξιᾶς νεκροῦς καὶ ἐσκυλευμένους παρεστήσατο*⁵¹¹.

The Council of 867, called by Emperor Michael, sought to put an end to every heresy. Photius's 18th homily speaks of that event: ...repulsed every schismatic and heretical error⁵¹².

For Photius, heresy is the greatest sin of all⁵¹³. Photius refers to heresy as an "error of impiety" – *ἡ τῆς δυσσεβείας πλάνη*⁵¹⁴. He refers to heresy as "the heretical gang", and "the schismatic infamy":...*αἰρετικὴ συμμορία...σχισματικὴ πονηρία*⁵¹⁵. Furthermore, Photius exposes his narration on the Paulicians, and their impious acts, with recurring to the terms *τὸ βδελυκτὸν*, and similarly *ἡ βδालυρία*⁵¹⁶, and their infamous deed - *τῆς λύμης ...ἔργον*⁵¹⁷, in a chronological manner. The Paulician doctrine is understood as an impious religion - *ἡ ἄθεος θρισκεία*⁵¹⁸. Analogously, Peter of Sicily opens his treatise on the "infamous heresy of the Manichaeans" and their insanity, which led to apostasy, by equating them with the Paulicians: ...*ἐπὶ ταύτην ἤλασε μανιωδῶς τὴν ἀποστασίαν*⁵¹⁹.

⁵⁰⁹ Cf. Mango, Homilies, 18th homily 310; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 176.

⁵¹⁰ Mango, Homilies, 18th homily 308, Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 174–175.

⁵¹¹ Mango, Homilies, 18th homily 310, Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 176, l. 8–10.

⁵¹² Mango, Homilies, 18th homily 306 sq.; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 173 sq.

⁵¹³ Photius, Amphilochia (Cum ordine Rerum) (ed. Migne, PG 101) 37–1190, XX, 145.

⁵¹⁴ Cf. 16th homily, in: Mango, Homilies 260, Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 152, l. 6.

⁵¹⁵ Photius, 16th homily, in: Mango, Homilies 276; cf. Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 162, l. 3–4.

⁵¹⁶ Photius, Contra Manichaeos, ed. Migne 16A, 21B.

⁵¹⁷ Photius, Contra Manichaeos, ed. Migne 61A.

⁵¹⁸ Photius, Contra Manichaeos, ed. Migne 61B.

⁵¹⁹ Peter of Sicily, Histoire des Pauliciens, ed. Astruc et al., 7, 9, 1–2.

II. 3. METAPHORICAL LANGUAGE OF HERESY

Floral and faunal symbolism: historical journey of meaning

In this chapter, the import of metaphorical language will be accentuated. Consequently, the protruding features of the metaphorical language of heresy and religious dissent in the 9th-century Francia and Byzantium will be put forward and analyzed, bearing in mind its high relevance and significance for the present study, as well as the possible analogies between its employment in the here-presented Latin and Greek textual sections.

In the New Testament, the metaphor of the seed is often employed: the word of God sown in the thorns alludes to those, who listen to it, but the concerns of this world and the deceit of riches make it barren, fruitless: ... *καὶ οὗτοί εἰσιν οἱ εἰς τὰς ἀκάνθας σπειρόμενοι, οἱ τὸν λόγον ἀκούοντες, καὶ αἱ μέριμναι τοῦ αἰῶνος τούτου καὶ ἡ ἀπάτη τοῦ πλούτου καὶ αἱ περὶ τὰ λοιπὰ ἐπιθυμίαι εἰσπορευόμεναι συμπνίγουσι τὸν λόγον, καὶ ἄκαρπος γίνεται*⁵²⁰. In general, the floral and faunal symbolism, which mainly came from the Scriptural tradition, flourished in the theological discourse of the Middle Ages. The Biblical symbolism dated, in effect, from an era of agricultural societies (which became predominant after the era marked by the nomadic way of life and was potentially linked to fertility cults) – and was preserved until the Middle Ages. In the medieval period, it was utilized in the purpose of designating semantic fields related to faith and heresies likewise⁵²¹. Some of the numerous New Testamental examples include: branch, fruit, harvest, sheep, lion, wine, weed (John 15:1-8; I Petr. 1:24; I Petr. 2:9; I Petr. 2:25; I Petr. 5:2; I Petr. 5:8). This same pattern, vegetative and floral symbolism in respect to Christian representations – remained active in the medieval consciousness as well – only because even when the old belief systems based on agricultural cults were long gone, the semantic field remained the same. Namely, the schematic representations almost automatically followed the already existing, or, pre-existing pattern common to the same semantic field. In other words, speaking of the transferal of the semantic code, the Early Medieval concept of heresy has been “planted” upon the already existing semantic fields, which were inherited from the Bible. Thus, these semantic fields/terms are much more ancient than the Early Middle Ages,

⁵²⁰ Mark 4:18–19.

⁵²¹ Cf. N. Frye, *The Great Code: The Bible and Literature* (New York 2002); A. Assmann, *Zur Metaphorik der Erinnerung*, in: *Mnemosyne, Formen und Funktionen der kulturellen Erinnerung*, ed. A. Assmann/D. Harth (Frankfurt a. M. 1991) 13–35; M. Sandl, *Historizität der Erinnerung/Reflexivität des Historischen. Die Herausforderung der Geschichtswissenschaft durch die kulturwissenschaftliche Gedächtnisforschung*, in: *Erinnerung, Gedächtnis, Wissen: Studien zur kulturwissenschaftlichen Gedächtnisforschung*, ed. G. Oesterle (Göttingen 2005) 89–120.

the epoch in which we are analyzing and dealing with these particular notions; they originated in a more remote times which did not share analogous social and cultural patterns with the Early Middle Ages. Nevertheless, it was due to the semantic kinship, that these patterns were transposed and transferred into a new epoch and frame. We might say that this has led to the certain “petrification” of particular semantic codes and fields.

Additionally, heresies have also very often been compared to “spurs”, growing out of the ground, as Photius implied: *...τῆς τοῦ Ἀρείου πονηρᾶς σπορᾶς τὰ γεννήματα*⁵²². It may well be that the relation to sowing and adherence to this semantic field comes directly from the Gospels. For example, in the Gospel of Matthew, the heretics are referred to as venomous snakes: “O generation of vipers, how can ye, being evil, speak good things? For out of the abundance of the heart the mouth speaketh”: *...progenies viperarum quomodo potestis bona loqui cum sitis mali ex abundantia enim cordis os loquitur*⁵²³. Heretics have received the “seed of impiety” – *τὸ σπέρμα δυσσεβείας*⁵²⁴. In the same homily, Photius compares the heretic to a wolf and communion with him to consuming a snake’s poison – *ὁ ἰὸν ὄφεως*⁵²⁵. The heretics have the serpent for a teacher⁵²⁶: this faunal symbolism comes from the Bible and the concept that the Devil represent an old snake, deceiver of humanity⁵²⁷. The heretic is not a shepherd, but a wolf⁵²⁸. It is by their fruits that the people shall recognize them and consequently, avoid their company. Namely, the heretics have received a seed of impiety in their souls – *τὸ σπέρμα ἀσεβείας; τῆς ἀσεβείας σπέρματα*⁵²⁹. The correct faith is presented by means of vegetative symbolism - as a beautiful fruit, *ὁ καρπὸς ὠραῖος*, which is sown, which has taken root and blossomed due to the endeavor of the Emperors through their Christian zeal⁵³⁰.

The account of Photius perhaps hides the semantic line of development starting with “seed” and ending in “battle against God”: the term here applied for heretics is *ἡ ἐπίσπορα* (a

⁵²² Cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 206.

⁵²³ Cf. Mt. 12:34 King James Version; *Ibid.*, *Vulgata*.

⁵²⁴ Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily, 258; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 149.

⁵²⁵ Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily, 258; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 149.

⁵²⁶ Photius, 16th homily, in: Mango, *Homilies*, 264, Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 154, l. 30–31.

⁵²⁷ This aligns to the above-mentioned petrification of particular semantic fields. As this research axis exceeds the scope of this thesis. The examples pertaining to this are rather numerous, and I shall indicate only some: the usual portrayal of the enemy as a snake, or foreigner (usually dressed in black clothing); some summarial observation in this respect on the Slavic populations has already been given in Procopius.

⁵²⁸ Photius, 15th homily, in: Mango, *Homilies* 258; homily 16th, Mango, *Homilies* 260; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 149; *Ibid.*, 152.

⁵²⁹ Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily, 258; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 149, l. 12; 16th homily, Mango, *Homilies* 262, Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 153, l. 16.

⁵³⁰ Mango, *Homilies*, 17th homily, 287, Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 165, l. 1–8.

composite term, of *ὁ σπόρος*, and *ἡ σπορά* designating sowing, crops, and fruit)⁵³¹. Additionally, the heresy is alluded to as error, *ἡ πλάνη*; and finally, the narrative on heretics expands to the war directed against God - *ἡ θεομαχία* - bore by the root of bitterness⁵³². Furthermore, the semantic field of sowing is very often employed for the words (some of which fall on the thorny ground, as already mentioned), just as it was in the New Testament⁵³³.

Hence, Photius opens his treatise on the origin of the Paulician group in Siria, and explains their erroneous doctrine from its early beginnings. Namely, as a frequently-employed image in heresiological texts, the Paulicians also propagate their doctrine by spreading the seed of impiety - *τῆς ἀσεβείας σπέρματα*⁵³⁴. The heresy in question is represented as being an infamous and dangerous seed: ...*Ἐκ ταύτης οὖν τῆς πονηρᾶς καὶ ὀλεθρίου σπορᾶς*⁵³⁵. The grains of impiety spring out of the root of acerbity: ...*τῆς πικρίας ρίζα βλαστοῦς ἀνέδωκετῆς θεομαχίας*⁵³⁶. The dangerous seed of the Manichaean heresy has spread and given its lethal fruit, states Peter of Sicily: ...*τῆς κακίστης σπορᾶς ἡ ρίζα βλαστήσασα καρποῦ θανασίμου τοῖς πολλοῖς μετέδωκεν*⁵³⁷.

Plague/illness/virus/madness/serpent/beast

Heresy was compared to disease and contagion from the dawn of Christian doctrine. As shown on manifold examples in the Theodosian Code, the heresies or schismatics are detrimental to the mankind, due to their criminal contagion; they should be removed from communion, so that they do not corrupt others. Furthermore, the Manichaeans, the heretics and every sect which is considered to represent the enemy of the Catholic faith shall be exiled from the city of Rome:

Manichaeos haereticos schismaticos sive mathematicos omnemque sectam catholicis inimicam ab ipso aspectu urbis Romae exterminari praecipimus, ut nec praesentiae criminorum contagione foedetur. Circa hos autem maxime exercenda commonitio est, qui pravis

⁵³¹ The term *ἐπισπείρω* was attested in the Gospel of Matthew (Mt. 13:25), and was also employed by John Chrysostom and Clement of Alexandria – designating the actions of the Devil (*ὁ ἐπισπορεύς*) to sow a second crop (*τὸ ἐπισπόριον*), compared to the introduction of heresies in the Church; cf. G. W. H. Lampe, ed., *A Patristic Greek Lexicon* (Oxford 1961) 534.

⁵³² Cf. Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne; cf.: *Les sources grecques pour l’histoire des Pauliciens d’Asie Mineure: texte critique et traduction par Ch. Astruc/Conus-Wolska, W./J. Guillard/Lemerle, P./D. Papachryssanthou/Paramelle, J., Travaux et memoires 4 (1970) 1–227, here 172.*

⁵³³ Photius, referring to Luke, 8:5–6: Mango, *Homilies*, 3rd homily, 87; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 33, l. 3–5.

⁵³⁴ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 17A, 180 AB.

⁵³⁵ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 68B.

⁵³⁶ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 83BC.

⁵³⁷ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al., 37, 84.

*suasionibus a venerabilis papae sese communione suspendunt, quorum schismate plebs etiam reliqua vitiatur*⁵³⁸.

Heresy is equaled to the virus of the impious discipline, pertaining to those who abandoned the Church: *virus impiae disciplinae*⁵³⁹.

This tendency continued throughout the centuries which followed, and metaphorical representation of heresies through the imagery of illness and contagion was also widely attested in the 9th-century Greek and Latin texts.

The first appearance of the heresiological stereotypes in the Carolingian times stems from the Adoptionist controversy⁵⁴⁰.

Before expanding on Gottschalk's views on the Trinity, Hincmar endows Gottschalk's teachings with venom and virus-like features, by means of which he tried to seduce the simple ones. Additionally, as in other heresiological procedures, Gottschalk is here portrayed as having acted in a covert heretical manner from the beginning, which is henceforth continued in the following sections, in which Hincmar compares Gottschalk to a wolf in a guise of a sheep: *Sicut venefici et sortiariae mel ad os vasculi virus celantis ponere solent, sic Gothescalcus in initio suprascriptae suae compilationis haereticorum errores proponit, et verbotenus respuit, ut credibilius se catholicum mentiens, simplicibus illudere et se commendabilem reddere possit, et haereticus loquens contra haereticos, lupus ovis pelle palliare se volens dicit...* The heretical knowledge is referred to as bitter: *...amara haereticorum Scientia*⁵⁴¹.

The multiplicity of heretical erroneous doctrines is being pointed to: the heretics do not possess the knowledge of the true faith and are compared to the leprotics. Consequently, the falseness of Gottschalk is mixed with the truth, as the outward signs of leprosy appear in different colors: *...falsitas Gothescalci, quam inordinate permiscuit veritati, tanquam leprosus in uno corpore diversos habens permistos colores. Ut enim tradunt magistri Ecclesiae, leprosi haereticos non absurde significant, scientiam verae fidei non habentes, et varias erroris doctrinas*

⁵³⁸ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 877; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.62, 462.

⁵³⁹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 880–881; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.6.2, 1, 464.

⁵⁴⁰ Cf. Pez, *Le virus de l'erreur* (Paris 2014) 524–525; on the transmission of the heresiological stereotypes, cf. Pez, *Le virus de l'erreur* (Paris 2014) 590–597.

⁵⁴¹ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 162, l. 13–14.

*proferentes*⁵⁴². Gottschalk's doctrine is wicked, *perversa*⁵⁴³, dangerous and opposite to catholic faith: *pernitiosa et catholicae fidei contraria*⁵⁴⁴.

The believers should be aware of the heretics who are often dressed in sheep clothing, Hincmar continues; they should be cautious not to be deceived by them. Gottschalk, for example, took on the false appearance of wisdom, until the church doctors had revealed his true intentions: *Sed necesse est Ecclesiae praepositis, ei cunctis fidelibus, ut non modo fortiter hostibus Christi apertis resistant, verum et prudenter lupos rapaces se ovinis pellibus contegentes attendant et vitent, ne eos fallere possint, sicut his Gothescalcus, qui non solum religioso habitu monachi, sed et falsi nominis scientia aliquandiu se contegens plures deceptit, donec quod corde confoverat erupit aperte in regulum. Cujus pellem ovinam, quia se inde non bene contexit, doctores catholici detrahentes, nudum lupum, apertumque hostem ovilis Dominici, quod est Ecclesia, eumesse demonstrant*⁵⁴⁵. The heretics have a tongue of a serpent; and this feature came into prominence with Gottschalk: *Haec autem numquam per nullius haeretici linguam serpentem antiquum sibilasse, nisi per os Gothescalci, audivimus*⁵⁴⁶. After having enumerated several heresies, Hincmar alludes to various heretics as to a plague: ... *caeteraeque pestes...catholicae fidei*⁵⁴⁷. Gottschalk's words are similar to crazy man's aberrations: ...*frivola...ut revera deliramenta maniatici*⁵⁴⁸. Hincmar classifies Gottschalk either as demonic, or insane; nevertheless, he adds, insanity is frequently connected to a demonic force: ...*quia pro certo talia dicit et talia facit, in quibus et de quibus evidenter congoscitur aut daemoniacus esse aut maniaticus; et scitis, quoniam mania esse non solet absque daemone*⁵⁴⁹. Gottschalk was infusing horrifying venom into the hearts of people: ...*venena pessima auditibus simul et cordibus vestris infudit*⁵⁵⁰ - since the confusion and controversy Gottschalk introduced is compared to venom: ...*frater Gotescalcus ex praedestinationis et praescientiae confusione venena sua usquequaque diffudit*⁵⁵¹. Additionally, men were created good, but the illness came from the devil; sins are equated with illness, whereas the successful treatment comes through obedience, Hincmar argues: ...*sed a diabolo inventus est morbus ...homo bonus a Deo factus, sed a diabolo per malum inorbatus, sicut per prophetam Dominus dicit: Peccata*

⁵⁴² Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 485CD.

⁵⁴³ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 187, ed. Perels 195, l.1.

⁵⁴⁴ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 187, ed. Perels 195, l. 37.

⁵⁴⁵ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne, 485D – 486A.

⁵⁴⁶ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 589CD.

⁵⁴⁷ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 604A.

⁵⁴⁸ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 613BC.

⁵⁴⁹ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 187, ed. Perels 196, l. 21–23.

⁵⁵⁰ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 14, l. 2–3.

⁵⁵¹ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 27, ed. Perels 17, l. 11–12.

*separant inter me et vos, id est morbus sanitatis. Quapropter si tollitur morbus gratia medici et oboedientia aegroti ut omnia, quae medicus proposuerit, oboedienter suscipiat, recepta sanitate aegrotus laetabitur...*⁵⁵². Gottschalk's writings are lethal – *mortifera capitula*⁵⁵³.

Gottschalk's words are distorted and poisonous: *Ceterum multiplices ac tortuosas et venenatas sententias Gothescalci*⁵⁵⁴; the doctrine of Gottschalk and his followers is plague-inducing: *...licet pestilens eorum doctrina...*⁵⁵⁵; *pestiferi Gotescalci verba loetifera...*⁵⁵⁶, as Gottschalk is portrayed as a carrier of plague – *pestiferous homo*⁵⁵⁷. As Hincmar explains, this doctrine was spread in numerous regions of the realm: *Sciebant namque idem venerabilis catholici et docti viri, quia in multis regionibus ac provinciis haec pestifera erat recommenta doctrina*⁵⁵⁸. Hence, Gottschalk divulged this pestiferous and deadly poison of his doctrine to those who rejoiced to novelties and were open to receive them: *Cum aliis pestiferis, magis autem mortiferis venenis, quae Gotescalcus sanam doctrinam non sustinentibus vocumque novitate delectantibus et prurientes aures habentibus...bibendi proponit*⁵⁵⁹. Hereby Hincmar makes a decisive, sharp distinction between sanity embodied in the official teaching of the church, the *sana doctrina*, and Gottschalk's peste-inducing heresy, opposite to it. Hincmar and other ecclesiastics are clearly demarcated as those endowed with *sana fides*, with Gottschalk described as their adversary: *Sunt et alia, quae et ipse et alii plures in istis partibus dicunt, quae nobis sanae fidei adversari videntur*⁵⁶⁰. The deadly virus of heresy is, Hincmar emphasizes, a mother of idolatry: *Quod haereseos mortiferum virus, idolatriae scilicet matris...*⁵⁶¹. The hearts of Gottschalk and other heretics burst with insanity of the perverted sense: *...etsi eorum corda in insania perversi sensus ebullient*⁵⁶².

Amolo's observation on Gottschalk's insanity, as well as on the instability of his mind and body, fall into the aggrupation of classical *topoi* referring to heretical insanity and madness,

⁵⁵² Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 20, l. 5–11; for more detailed information on the importance of obedience in Hincmar's texts, see my forthcoming article: Hierarchy and Social Cohesion in the Carolingian Era – on the example of Gottschalk's, Hrabanus's and Hincmar's interpretation of St. Paul's Epistle to Romans (13:1–7), in: Social Cohesion and its Limits/Identity and Religion, ed. W. Pohl/A. Fischer (Wien 2018).

⁵⁵³ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 188, ed. Perels 197, l. 17–18.

⁵⁵⁴ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 131, ed. Perels 70, l. 19–20.

⁵⁵⁵ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 131, ed. Perels 70, l. 21–22.

⁵⁵⁶ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 115, l. 10.

⁵⁵⁷ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 160, l. 4.

⁵⁵⁸ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 131, ed. Perels 72, l. 12–13.

⁵⁵⁹ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 109, l. 36–39.

⁵⁶⁰ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 162, l. 7–8.

⁵⁶¹ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 112, l. 13–14.

⁵⁶² Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 162, l. 11.

affluent in Carolingian literature as well⁵⁶³. The analogous conceptual points between heresy and madness are frequently put forward by mediation of semantic field encompassing poisoning, venom, illness. In his letter to Hincmar, Hrabanus designates Gottschalk as a noxious person, who inebriated many with his venomous potion, and directed their minds towards the insanity of error: *...istum noxium virum, hoc est Gotescalcum...sui veneni poculo non paucos inebriavit, et in erroris insaniam vertit*⁵⁶⁴. Similarly, Hincmar alludes to Gottschalk's heresy as a deadly virus of idolatry, *mortiferum virus idololatriae*⁵⁶⁵. On the other hand, Gottschalk used a language laden with highly stylistic means and figures as well, and frequently resorted to similar metaphors while describing his opponents. Besides, Gottschalk relies upon poetical language on many occasions, and employs various figures of style with the aim of accentuating the message he wished to spread⁵⁶⁶. Gottschalk refers to him, who refutes his doctrine, as a rapacious wolf or a shameless goat - *rapax lupus vel procax hircus*, preparing traps for Christ's sheep - *insidiae procacium pertinacium, pervicacium, luporum rapacium*⁵⁶⁷. Therefore, the enemies of God's sheep are identified with shameless, implacable, stubborn and rapacious wolves. Simultaneously, Gottschalk employs the equivalent adjectives in describing Hincmar: *...caecus procax pertinax pervicax haereticus*⁵⁶⁸.

Moreover, Jonas of Orléans, writing on Felix, bishop of Urgell (died in 818), refers to his adoptionist doctrine as insane - *insana...vesana doctrina*, and as the most vicious of errors - *sceleratissimus error*. The doctrine of Felix has, additionally, infected great part of Hispania, according to Jonas: *...Hispaniam magna ex parte infecit*⁵⁶⁹.

In Byzantium, the treatise *De Haeresibus et Synodis*, attributed to Patriarch Germanus, assumes that all heretics are similar to one another; they all share the same features - one of

⁵⁶³ Among numerous examples, I shall hereby name only some authors: Augustine, *De baptismo contra Donatistas libri septem* (ed. Migne, PL 43) 107–244, here II, 3, 128; Jerome, *Commentariorum in Hiezechielem* (ed. F. Glorie, CCSL 75, Turnhout 1964) 306–307; Ambrose, *Explanatio psalmorum xii* (ed. M. Petschenig, CSEL 64, Vienna 1919) 216.

⁵⁶⁴ Hrabanus, *Epistolae*, Ep. 44, ed. Dümmler 496.

⁵⁶⁵ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 479.

⁵⁶⁶ On Gottschalk's poetry and his poetical language, see my article in print: *L'entremêlement des motifs préchrétiens et chrétiens dans les textes de Gottschalk: à la recherche de son répertoire*, in: *La controverse carolingienne sur la prédestination : histoire, textes, manuscrits. Actes du colloque des 11-13 novembre 2013, collection „Haut Moyen Âge“ of Brepols 32* (Paris 2018); For more general information on the heretical stereotypes in Carolingian period, see: Pez, *Le virus de l'erreur* (Paris 2014) 590–597.

⁵⁶⁷ Cf. Gottschalk, *De Praedestinatione*, ed. Lambot 180-258, here 244.

⁵⁶⁸ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 613–614.

⁵⁶⁹ Jonas, *De cultu imaginum*, ed. Migne 308CD.

which is insanity - (*ἴση ἄνοια*); they are all detestable and impure – as already mentioned and cited above⁵⁷⁰.

Photius describes the teachings of the Manichaeans as the “venom of the apostasy”, which the two heresiarchs, Paul and John, have accepted - *τὸν ἰὸν τῆς ἀποστασίας εἰσεδέξαντο*⁵⁷¹. Mani, the heresiarch of the Manichaeans, performed the deeds characteristic of insanity, exactly because he nourished a spirit of error in himself: ...*ὡς ἀληθῶς τῆς μανίας δοχεῖον... ὄλον τὸ τῆς πλάνης πνεῦμα ἐν ἑαυτῷ χωρήσας*⁵⁷². Photius also speaks of the deadly venom of the Manichaean teachings: ...*πολλοῖς τὸν θανατηφόρον ἰὸν τῶν δηλητηρίων αὐτοῦ δοξασμάτων ἐγκεράσαι*⁵⁷³; ... *τὸν θανατηφόρον τῆς ἀποστασίας... ἰὸν*⁵⁷⁴. The heresiarch of the Manichaeans is portrayed as just another horrendous, multiform beast filled with serpentine venom: ...*συναναφέεται τῷ πολυμόρφῳ τοῦτῳ καὶ βδελυρῷ θηρίῳ ἕτερον τι παραπλήσιον δρακοντείου γέμον ἰοῦ*⁵⁷⁵. The faunal symbolism was also significantly employed throughout Middle Ages. For instance, at the time of the Byzantine and Frankish missions to Moravia, the Latin bishops, priests and monks attacked Constantine and Methodius as “the crows”, who would attack “the falcons”⁵⁷⁶.

Heresy of the Manichaeans is equated with the poison of apostasy: ...*τὸν τῆς ἀποστασίας ἰὸν*⁵⁷⁷. In other words, the heresy of the Manichaeans is like a pestilence, provoking destruction among the people: ...*ὡς κοινήν λύμην καὶ φθορὰν τοῦ γένους πρὸς τὸν διὰ ζίφους θάνατον ὑπάγειν*⁵⁷⁸. The concept of serpentine venom is important in relation to the language of heretics as well: ...*ὡ γλώσσης ἰὸν ἀσπίδος προχεούσης*⁵⁷⁹. The venom originates in language (speaking): ... *ἰὸν διὰ τῆς γλώττης ὁμοίως ἀποτίκτουσι. Καὶ γὰρ ἐκχέουσι μὲν τὸν ἰὸν κατὰ τῆς νομοθεσίας...*⁵⁸⁰. Peter of Sicily refers to the heresy of the Manichaeans as a plague, *λοιμῆ*⁵⁸¹, or a pestilence, *λυμώδη*⁵⁸². The teachings of the Manichaeans are alluded to as poison of evil, with a bitter root: ...*τὸν ἰὸν τῆς πονηρίας καὶ τὸ πικρὸν ζιζάνιον τοῦ ἐχθροῦ...*⁵⁸³; or as the most horrendous

⁵⁷⁰ Cf. above, chapter II.2.

⁵⁷¹ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 17A.

⁵⁷² Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 37B.

⁵⁷³ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 45C–48A.

⁵⁷⁴ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 56C.

⁵⁷⁵ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 61C.

⁵⁷⁶ Cf. Lehr-Splawinski, *Żywoty Konstantyna i Metodego* 75.

⁵⁷⁷ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 69B.

⁵⁷⁸ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 77B.

⁵⁷⁹ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 188D.

⁵⁸⁰ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 213C.

⁵⁸¹ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 9, 5.

⁵⁸² Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 25, 49; *Ibid.*, 39, 87.

⁵⁸³ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 37, 86; *Ibid.*, 39, 86.

poison: τὰ...κάκιστα δηλητήρια⁵⁸⁴. Peter of Sicily compares the *modus operandi* of the heretics in spreading their doctrine and eagerness to disguise their wrongdoings to those who pour poisonous potions into food and drink and then mask the taste by adding honey: ὄπος δυνηθῆ δι' αὐτῶν ἐπικαλύψαι τὴν τῆς κακίας βλάβην, ὥσπερ οἱ τὰ δηλητήρια φάρμακα διδόντες πίνειν διὰ μέλιτος ταῦτα ἐπικαλύπτουσιν⁵⁸⁵. The Manichaeans's venom is the venom of evil: ..τῆς κακίας ἰὸν⁵⁸⁶. When referring to the important part of the Christian population among which the Manichaean heresy had spread, Peter of Sicily uses the verb “to get damaged”, “to suffer from decay”, as if he was speaking of disease: ...πολὸν μέρος τῶν χριστιανῶν τοιαύτη αἵρεσις ἐλυμήνατο⁵⁸⁷.

The notions of sin and illness were apparently closely intertwined in medieval theological consciousness. Namely, the Fall occurred as a consequence of man's illness, which came as a result of his sin. It was only the salvation through Christ that could bring remission.

Photius speaks of Arius in his letter, but also in 15th and 16th homilies⁵⁸⁸: an innovator charged of impiety by the Synod - ...ὁ ἱερός...σύλλογος, Ἄρειὸν τινα νεωτεροποιὸν δυσσεβείας δίκας εἰσπραττόμενος⁵⁸⁹. He calls his heresy “the most impious and God-assaulting” - ...τὴν δὲ δυσσεβεστάτην καὶ θεομάχον αὐτοῦ αἵρεσιν τῷ ἀναθέματι καθύπεβαλεν⁵⁹⁰. On the contrary, he refers to orthodoxy as to the “holy and spotless religion” - ...μετὰ τῆς καθαρᾶς καὶ ἀμωμήτου ἡμῶν θρησκείας⁵⁹¹. In another passage above, in the same letter, Photius employs a similar cluster: ἡ καθαρὰ καὶ ἀμώμητος ὁμολογία⁵⁹²: pure and spotless unity/concord. Photius speaks of Arius as of a “wretch” - ὁ δειλαιοῦς⁵⁹³. In his 15th homily, he refers to Arius's doctrine as “madness” - ἡ ἀπόνοια, and to his supporters as to “madmen” - ἀρειομανιτοῖ⁵⁹⁴, whereas a heretic is defined as a man “diseased with Arianism”: τὰ Ἀρείου νοσοῦντα⁵⁹⁵; impiety is thus understood as an illness: ...ἐπὶ τὴν δυσσεβείαν μεταχωρίσαντα καὶ νόσῳ περιπεσόντα⁵⁹⁶. Additionally, heresy is equated with poison as well – “poison of heresy” – αἱρετικὸν ἰὸν⁵⁹⁷. In

⁵⁸⁴ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 39, 90.

⁵⁸⁵ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 41, 96.

⁵⁸⁶ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 53, 138.

⁵⁸⁷ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 65, 175.

⁵⁸⁸ Cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 206.

⁵⁸⁹ Cf. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios 70*; Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 206.

⁵⁹⁰ Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 206.

⁵⁹¹ Cf. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios 71*; Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 224.

⁵⁹² Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 219.

⁵⁹³ Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios 70*; Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 206.

⁵⁹⁴ Mango, *Homilies 247*; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 141, l. 7.

⁵⁹⁵ Mango, *Homilies 246, 257*; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 148, l. 28.

⁵⁹⁶ Mango, *Homilies 246*; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 140, l. 28–29.

⁵⁹⁷ Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily, 248, 258; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 149, l. 25.

his 16th homily, Photius describes heresy as a plague of heretical corruption – *τῆς αἰρετικῆς λύμης ὁ φθόρος*⁵⁹⁸. He writes very frequently on heresy as on illness, and refers to heretics as infested with error of impiety – *...οὐδὲν γὰρ ἢ τῆς δυσσεβείας πλάνη ἐπενέμετο*⁵⁹⁹. Arian heresy is described as madness – “Arian madmen”; “the madness of Arius” – *τῆς ἀρειανῆς λύσσης*⁶⁰⁰, whereas the Iconoclastic madness is opposed to the correct faith: *ἡ εἰκονομαχικὴ αἵρεσις...τὰ τῶν ὀρθῶν δογματῶν*⁶⁰¹. Eutocius, for example, was a heretic who bore the poison of the Arian heresy in his breast, but presented himself as a pious Christian on the exterior. The poison of the snake, the teacher of the heretics - mixed with disobedience, and under the guise of kindness - lead to the fall of Mankind: *ὃς ἐν προνοίας καὶ φιλοφροσύνης προσχήματι τὸν ἰὸν τοῦ θανάτου τῆ παρακοῆς κερασάμενος*⁶⁰². Nevertheless, these heretics simulate piety. The heretics exhibit the pure poison of impiety – *τὸν ἰὸν ὄλον ἄκρατον τῆς ἀσεβείας*⁶⁰³. The enemy of Christ, the “harlot conventicle” – *ἡ πόρνη παρασυναγωγὴ*, nourishes him who “hides the asp’s poison under his lips” – *ἰὸν ἀσπίδος ὑπὸ τὰ χεῖλη κρύπτων*⁶⁰⁴. Orthodoxy is a “true religion” – *τὸ ὀρθὸν δόγμα*⁶⁰⁵. Heresy is often seen as disease: “the plague of heretical corruption” that spread all over East – *τῆς αἰρετικῆς λύμης ὁ φθόρος ἐσκέδαστο*⁶⁰⁶. For this “most distressing illness” of Arianism – *τῆς τοιαύτης χαλεπωτάτης νόσου...οὐδὲν ἐξευρίσκετο ἴαμα* – as Photius says in his 16th homily, the remedy was sought⁶⁰⁷. In his 17th homily, Photius refers to heresy as to a “disease of superstitious prejudice” – *ἐν προλήψει δεισιδαιμονίας τὸ πάθος* - and “sickness” – *ἡ νόσος*⁶⁰⁸. Photius alludes to heresy as *ὁ ὄλεθρος* – endowing it with features of a living being – that is, in metonymic sense – the term broadly applied for destruction, and already in usage in Antiquity, as well as in the Bible. In the same homily, Photius writes on the heretical “truly absurd madness” – *τῆς ἀλεθῶς ἀτόπου φρενοβλαβείας οἰκτείρουσα*⁶⁰⁹.

In his 18th homily, Photius compares heresy with plague, following the identical semantic field of illness, or disease, as already shown above: *ὁ φθόρος*⁶¹⁰.

⁵⁹⁸ Mango, Homilies 260; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 152, 4–5.

⁵⁹⁹ Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 260; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 152, l. 6–7.

⁶⁰⁰ Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 261; 268, 269; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda, 16th homily 152, l. 12.

⁶⁰¹ Mango, Homilies, 17th homily 291; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 168, l. 12–13.

⁶⁰² Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 264; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 154, l. 29–30.

⁶⁰³ Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 264; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 155, l. 6.

⁶⁰⁴ Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 277; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 162, l. 22, 29–30; cf. Ps. 139:4.

⁶⁰⁵ Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 275; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 160, l. 28–29.

⁶⁰⁶ Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 260; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 152, l. 4–5.

⁶⁰⁷ Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 271; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 159, l. 7–8.

⁶⁰⁸ Mango, Homilies, 17th homily 288; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 165, l. 26–27.

⁶⁰⁹ Mango, Homilies, 17th homily 291; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 168, l. 9–10.

⁶¹⁰ Mango, Homilies, 18th homily 314; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 178, l. 30; *Ibid.*, 179, l. 5.

Serpentine symbolic

Photius applies the typical procedure of heresiological literature, and depicts the heretics as being the offspring of serpents. Thus, Paul and John, the two heresiarchs, are portrayed as the offspring of the viper, representing a calamity: *Παῦλον καὶ Ἰωάννην γεννήματα ἐχιδνῶν ἐπ'ὀλέθρῳ τοῦ ἀνθρωπίνου γένους ἀπέτεκε*⁶¹¹. The heresiarch, tortuous serpent alike, calls himself a shepherd and a leader: *Ἐκάλει δ' οὗτος ὁ σκολιὸς ὄφεις ἑαυτὸν καὶ θυρωρὸν καὶ ποιμένα καὶ ὁδηγόν*⁶¹². The heresy is presented as a monstrous and diversified serpentine offspring, which effuses the venom of blasphemy against the Creator: *...ὡσπερ ἐξ ἐχιδνης πολύμορφόν τι καὶ ἀλλόκοτον ἀποτεχθὲν θηρίον καταφαγὸν μὲν σὴν γαστέρα τῆς τεκούσης πλέον δὲ τὸν ἰὸν τῆς βλασφημίας ἀποπτύον κατὰ τοῦ Δημιουργοῦ*⁶¹³. The Savior will bring punishment for the apostates, the preservers of the evil principle, and for their serpentine offspring, as Photius stresses: *Ὁ δὲ ἀγαθὸς καὶ φιλόανθρωπος ἡμῶν Σωτὴρ...ἀλλὰ καὶ τοὺς ἐκείνων παῖδας ὄφεις καὶ γεννήματα ἐχιδνῶν ἀποφαίνων ἄφυκτον αὐτοῖς ἀναμένειν τὴν γέενναν τοῦ πυρὸς προαγγέλλει*⁶¹⁴. Peter of Sicily, warns the simple ones to flee from any conversation with the heretics, as if they were fleeing from a serpent: *...ὡς ἐξ ὄφεως*⁶¹⁵. In the same treatise, the serpent is designated as the father of evil, the most hideous dragon, sower of chaff, founder and source of all iniquity, father of lie: *Ὁ ἀρχέκακος ὄφεις καὶ πονηρότατος δράκων, ὁ τῶν ζιζανίων σπορεὺς καὶ πάσης κακίας ἀρχηγὸς καὶ διδάσκαλος, ὁ τοῦ ψεύδους καθηγεμῶν καὶ πατὴρ αὐτοῦ...*⁶¹⁶. Further on in the same text, the leader of the Maichaeian heresy is referred to as a disciple of evil and a wild beast: *ὁ...τῆς κακίας μαθητὴς...θηρίον*⁶¹⁷. The mother of the two heresiarchs is referred to as a viper, having given birth to two serpents: *...δύο ὄφεις ἢ αὐτῶν γεννήτρια ἐχιδνα*⁶¹⁸. Peter of Sicily speaks of heresiarch Sergius as the biggest of all the wild beasts: *...μεῖζον πάντων τῶν θηρίων*⁶¹⁹.

Similarly, the heretics are compared to serpents and possess a serpentine voice, according to Theodore the Studite. Furthermore, they should be fled from, since they bring peril from generation to generation:

⁶¹¹ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 45A.

⁶¹² Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 72AB.

⁶¹³ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 169CD.

⁶¹⁴ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 253AB.

⁶¹⁵ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 11, 10.

⁶¹⁶ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 13, 18.

⁶¹⁷ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 25, 49–50.

⁶¹⁸ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 37, 84.

⁶¹⁹ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 65, 181.

...ἵνα τὸν ὄφιν καὶ τοὺς ὀφιοφώνους φεύγοιτε, ἐφ' οἷς ὠλέκοντο ὅτι μάλιστα πλεῖστοι ἀπὸ γενεῶν εἰς γενεάς⁶²⁰.

⁶²⁰ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 49, ed. Migne 1088D.

II. 4. *ADULTERATUM ATQUE FALSATUM*: Adulterating the word of God

In this chapter, the basis of the important semantic field encompassing the metaphorical employment of the terms related to the concept of adulterating the word of God has been laid.

The concept of adulterating the word of God is present in the New Testament: *Non enim sumus sicut plurimi, adulterantes verbum Dei, sed ex sinceritate, sed sicut ex Deo, coram Deo, in Christo loquimur*⁶²¹ - “For we are not as many, which corrupt the word of God: but as of sincerity, but as of God, in the sight of God speak we in Christ”⁶²².

*Sed abdicamus occulta dedecoris, non ambulantes in astutia, neque adulterantes verbum Dei, sed in manifestatione veritatis commendantes nosmetipsos ad omnem conscientiam hominum coram Deo*⁶²³. - “But have renounced the hidden things of dishonesty, not walking in craftiness, nor handling the word of God deceitfully; but by manifestation of the truth commending ourselves to every man’s conscience in the sight of God”⁶²⁴.

Hincmar suggests, that the metaphorical adultery is perpetrated upon the word of God on behalf of an erroneous interpretation. Namely, in reference to the erroneous interpretations of the Trinitarian doctrine, Hincmar alludes to Augustine’s words cited shortly before, and adds: *...ista verba, quae hic sunt interposita, ab Augustino non fuisse prolata, sed ab adulterante verbum Dei et catholicam fidem hic per imposituram immissa*⁶²⁵. In arguing against Gottschalk’s Trinitarian doctrine and his allusions to the words of Augustine, Hincmar designates this as adulterous: *Manifestum et manifestatum est ergo compilatum, et adulteratum atque falsatum esse librum beati Augustini contra quinque hostium genera, in quo haec haeretica pravitas a quocunque falsatore interposita comprobatur, sicut in quinta synodo ex catholicorum libris quaedam testimonia ab haereticis ad suam confirmandam pravitatem detruncata, et quaedam falsa catholicis catholicorum verbis interposita fuisse vigilantia catholicorum detexit*⁶²⁶. In this sense, the term *adulteratum* refers to the sacrilegious, illicit and false; it denotes the process of twisting the truth, and is closely related to the sense of *falsatum*. Those heretics, according to Hincmar, starting from Arius and Nestorius and including

⁶²¹ Cf. 2. Cor. 2:17 Vulgata.

⁶²² Cf. 2. Cor. 2:17, King James Version.

⁶²³ Cf. 2. Cor. 4:2, Vulgata.

⁶²⁴ 2. Cor. 4:2, King James Version.

⁶²⁵ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 514BC.

⁶²⁶ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 526CD.

Gottschalk, are accused of twisting the truth, as well as the words of Augustine, as Felix, Bishop of Urgell did likewise. An *adulterator* is a heretic who turns the truth into a lie. Therefore, Hincmar employs the term *adulterator verborum beati Augustini*⁶²⁷: *Sic et iste adulterator verborum beati Augustini, juxta quod scriptum est, “Qui a semetipso loquitur propriam gloriam quaerit”*⁶²⁸, *de proprio mendacium, ut gloriari posset adversus veritatem, veritati inseruit: quomodo Gothescalcus veritatem quantum ex ipso est in mendacium commutavit, trina pro ter vel Trinitatis deitate, in sextae synodi edicto immutans*. Furthermore, referring to Gottschalk’s erroneous translation of the Trinitarian creed from Greek, Hincmar speaks of the difficulties which might occur when translating Greek words into Latin: *Nam et si ita ut ab eo adulteratum credimus, ex Graeca interpretatione in eodem haberetur edicto....quia Graecitas idioma e suae linguae quaedam recte potest effere, quae Latina lingua maxime de his quae pertinent ad fidem non recipit*⁶²⁹.

Gottschalk, a pseudo-monk, and an overt-heretic, in Hincmar’s view, is designated as *fidei sinceræ adulterator et apertus haereticus*⁶³⁰. Those who, according to Judas, kill the flesh, and do not understand the meaning of the Scriptures, are “adulterating”, or, “forging” the word of God and teach with a shameful intent *...nescientes secundum apostolicam scripturam “neque quae loquuntur neque de quibus adfirmant”, “adulterantes verbum Dei” et “docentes” non sincere, sed “turpis lucre gratia”*⁶³¹.

Speaking of Hincmar in ca. 856-857, Gottschalk alludes to him as a heretic, but also as an adulterer: *moechus et caecus procax pertinax pervicax haereticus...*⁶³² Curiously, Gottschalk employs the Greek word for adulterer – *moechus* – which is not so frequently attested in Carolingian sources⁶³³.

Similarly, Eriugena accused Gottschalk of being a lying adulterer – *mendosus adulterator*⁶³⁴. In this sense, adulterer refers to forger of the word of God.

⁶²⁷ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 527BC.

⁶²⁸ Cf. John 7:18.

⁶²⁹ cf. above in chapter II.1 and similar interpretation of Maximus the Confessor.

⁶³⁰ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 615BC.

⁶³¹ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 13, l. 32–35, cf. 2 Cor. 2:17, Tit. 1:11.

⁶³² Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 613–614.

⁶³³ The more common noun would be *adulterator*, or *adulter*. In the Latin Early Medieval sources which have been analyzed here, the term *moechus* is attested with much lesser frequency than the term *adulterator* – and most frequently in the texts of Gottschalk and Pope Nicholas.

⁶³⁴ Cf. John Scottus Eriugena, *Iohannis Scotti de divina praedestinatione liber* (ed. G. Madec, CCCM 50, Turnhout 1978); G. Mathon, *L’utilisation des textes de Saint Augustin par Jean Scot Érigène dans son De Praedestinatione*, in: *Augustinus Magister, Actes du Congrès international augustiniens*, Paris, 21-24 Septembre 1954 (Paris 1955) 519–528; M. Goulven, *L’augustinisme de Jean Scot dans le De predestinatione*, in: Jean Scot

The semantic field of the metaphorical employment of the term “adultery” is present in Photius’ treatise likewise: he inserts his observations on the Gnostics, who perform adulterate actions regarding the interpretation of the Scriptures and their meaning. Compared to them, the Paulicians do not follow the same pattern, Photius argues, but use more subtle ways to spread their erroneous teachings: *...τοῖς ῥήμασι μὲν καὶ ὀνόμασιν οὐδὲν μέγα παραλάττων, οὐδὲ κατακιβδηλεύων τοῦ λόγου τὸ σχῆμα*⁶³⁵. Hence, the concept of heresy is demonstrated as being closely related to that of spiritual adultery: *...οἱ δε μηδὲν ἄδολον μηδ’ ἀκαπήλευτον φιλονεικοῦντες καταλιπεῖν*⁶³⁶. Photius insists upon the symbolism of the adulterous actions: the heretics are alluded to as those who wanted to “adulterate” the word of God: *...οἱ τὸν λόγον τοῦ Θεοῦ καπηλεύειν ἐθέλοντες*⁶³⁷. The same verb, *καπηλεύειν*, is employed by Peter of Sicily as well, in his account on the Manichaeans. Photius explains how heretics (and in this particular case, Chrysocheres, the heresiarch of the Manichaeans) adulterated the word of God: they did likewise, in order to dissimulate their own sentences under the guise of the interpretation of the Holy Scriptures: *...τίνες δὲ τῆς ἀποστασίας αἱ καλούμεναι Ἐκκλησίαι καὶ πόσαι, καὶ τίνες ἔσχε διδασκάλους, ὅπως τε τὰς ἱερὰς κατακιβδηλεύουσι φωνὰς, καὶ οἷς αὐτῶν τὸ δυσσεβὲς ἐπισκιάζουσι φρόνημα*⁶³⁸. The same verb, *καπηλεύειν*, is used in the treatise of Peter of Sicily as well, designating the “merchandizing” or “black-marketeering”, “forging” of the word of God by heretical priests, who conceal the evangelical mysteries: *...οἱ ἱερεῖς ὑμῶν καπηλεύονται τὸν τοῦ θεοῦ λόγον καὶ τὰ ἐν εὐαγγελίοις μυστήρια ἀποκρύβουσιν*⁶³⁹. Moreover, in his Encyclical letter to the Oriental Patriarchs, written in the peak of the *Filioque* controversy (860’s), Photius clearly exposes and summarizes the wrongdoings of the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria, opposed to the ecclesiastical tradition. Furthermore, it is thanks to their audacity that they attempted to “adulterate” the liturgical practices. Photius refers to their evil concepts, according to which they introduced novelties by claiming that the Holy Spirit proceeds not only from the Father, but from the Son, as well: *...θράσους ὑπερβολή, κιβδηλεύειν ἐπεχείρησαν: ὃ τῶν τοῦ πονηροῦ*

Érigène et l’histoire de la philosophie, Colloques internationaux du CNRS, 561, ed. R. Roques (Paris 1977) 183–190.

⁶³⁵ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos* 20A.

⁶³⁶ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos* 21C.

⁶³⁷ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos* 65AB.

⁶³⁸ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos* 84C.

⁶³⁹ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 53, 139; cf. II Tim. 4:4.

μηχανιμάτων! τὸ πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον οὐκ ἐκ τοῦ Πατρὸς μόνον, ἀλλὰ γε καὶ ἐκ τοῦ Υἱοῦ ἐκπορεύεσθαι καινολογήσατε⁶⁴⁰.

On the other hand, regarding the inner policy of the Constantinopolitan Patriarchate, Pope Nicholas condemned the enthronement of Photius and the deposition of the former Patriarch Ignatius - and referred to Photius as an adulterer and intruder into the Constantinopolitan Church, as well as as a neophyte – certainly alluding to his rapid ascension to the patriarchal rank (...*quia Photii adulteri et inuasoris ecclesiae Constantinopolitanae atque neophiti*⁶⁴¹). Photius is also referred to as *moechus* – a Greek word that gives the identical indication of him being an adulterer⁶⁴², and the Pope resorts to it quite frequently: ...*in consecratione Photii moechi et ecclesiae inuasoris et contra statuta nostra, sed et adversum sedem principis apostolorum Petri*⁶⁴³. This cluster is always related to Photius – the neophyte, adulterer, or assailant (“intruder”): *neophito et moecho et Constantinopolitanorum ecclesiae invasori Photio olim iusteque damnato* – or simply, as *invasor ecclesiae*⁶⁴⁴. Interestingly, even Pope Hadrian II (867-872) – Pope Nicholas’s successor - uses the same word, in the same context, to accuse Photius: ...*de schismatico et moecho Photio...Photium tyrannum...adversum tyrannum vel moechum*⁶⁴⁵, or simply alludes to him as *Photius moechus*⁶⁴⁶. Even more curiously, Pope Nicholas does not apply this word in its literal sense – designating an adulterer – in his numerous letters gathered in the same volume in which he expounds on Lothar II and his re-marriage: instead, this term seems to be reserved for Photius and is employed in the metaphorical sense only – apparently implying Photius’s “shift” from lay to ecclesiastical status⁶⁴⁷. The key to this interpretation is given in the ensuing Pope Nicholas’s words: *invasori ac moecho ac laico Photio*⁶⁴⁸, and *moechum* (sc. Photium) *irregulariter in sede Constantinopolitanae firmatum*⁶⁴⁹. The term *moechus* – employed to designate Photius - is counterbalanced to *legitimus* – in reference to Ignatius: *si potest ecclesiae*

⁶⁴⁰ Photius, Encyclica Epistola (Encyclical letter), Epistolarum Liber I, ed. Migne 725CD; cf. on the Encyclical letter, see: Kolbaba, *Inventing Latin Heresies* 57–75.

⁶⁴¹ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 601, l. 18–19; 497, l. 10–11; 549, l. 16–17.

⁶⁴² Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 602, l. 5.

⁶⁴³ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 553–565, here 562, l. 36–37; 563, l. 1.

⁶⁴⁴ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 605, l. 18.

⁶⁴⁵ referring to Photius, Pope Hadrian II, Hadrianus II Papa, Epistolae (ed. E. Perels, MGH VI) 691–765, here 751, l. 6, 18; 752, l. 8.

⁶⁴⁶ Hadrian, Epistolae, ed. Perels 756, l. 4.

⁶⁴⁷ See below, chapter II.9, on the second marriage of Lothar II.

⁶⁴⁸ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 556, l. 25.

⁶⁴⁹ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 602, l. 5–6.

*Dei subveniens pro repellendo moechno et revocando legitimo dare operam*⁶⁵⁰. Additionally, the attribution of the term adulterer to Photius might also have been used with the aim of portraying the Church as the bride, who was assaulted by an intruder, adulterer – the new Patriarch Photius. Nevertheless, the term in a feminine form has also been used by Pope Nicholas to designate Waldrada, Lothar’s mistress. If that be the case, then we are witnessing a transferal of meaning from one semantic field to another. Or could it be the reflection of the similar episode having taken place in Byzantium, when, only a few decades earlier, the imperial second marriage had shaken the intellectual scene and provoked sharp disputes – with Theodore the Studite as the representative of the faction demanding the strict observance of the ecclesiastical canons?⁶⁵¹

Furthermore, the Pope did not acknowledge Photius as a patriarch due to the fact that he, Photius, had not established the service of communion in the Constantinopolitan Church in “our letters”: *...quippe quem non litterarum nostrarum communionem in ecclesia Constantinopolitana stabiliendum, sed nostrae sententiae iam mucrone percussus ab ea penitus decreveramus tamquam adulterum propellendum*⁶⁵². To summarize Pope’s words, the Greeks, in their accusations, recur to blasphemies: *plectrum linguae in derogationes et blasphemias acuerunt*⁶⁵³. And Photius was to be expelled as an adulterer. The Pope saw this act of Photius’s enthronement as *pervresitas* and *tenebrarum opera*⁶⁵⁴.

At the same time, Patriarch Ignatius (847 – 858; 868 – 877) enjoyed the full support of the Pope: he is referred to as the Pope’s brother and co-minister (*...fratris scilicet et comministri nostri*⁶⁵⁵; *...in depositione fratris nostri et consacerdotis Ignatii*⁶⁵⁶) – the statement which perhaps assigns to the Patriarch Ignatius an equivocal status to the papal one.

To conclude, Pope Nicholas repeatedly employs the *locus communis* in his description of Photius as an adulterer, intruder to the Church and a neophyte - *...Photio adultero ac ecclesiae invasore atque neophyto*⁶⁵⁷, sometimes alternated with *moechnus* and *laicus*⁶⁵⁸, or *adultero, praevaricatore ac pervasore sedis Constantinopolitanae*⁶⁵⁹. It is in this letter that the key to Pope’s portrayal of Photius as an adulterer has been given: it is due to the fact that Photius had

⁶⁵⁰ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 98 ed. Perels 553, l. 4–5.

⁶⁵¹ Cf. below, II.9.

⁶⁵² Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 606, l. 26–28.

⁶⁵³ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 607, l. 35.

⁶⁵⁴ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 607, l. 19, 23; cf. Rom. 13:12.

⁶⁵⁵ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 601, l. 20–21.

⁶⁵⁶ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 562, l. 36.

⁶⁵⁷ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 554, l. 41–42.

⁶⁵⁸ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 556, l. 25.

⁶⁵⁹ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 559, l. 19–20.

come from the laity rank and so swiftly become a patriarch after having removed the legitimate patriarch Ignatius from the office; he thus “invaded” the Patriarchal See – the “Bride” of Christ - in a robber-like mode, like a violent and rapacious adulterer: *Photius, qui ex schismaticorum et se a sanctae communionis participatione avertentium parte esse dinoscitur, et ex saeculari administratione atque militia et ex foro subito tonsoratus a Gregorio, Syracusano dudum episcopo a synodo damnato et ab apostolica sede vincto, episcopus ordinatus est et vivente ac superstite consacerdote nostro Ignatio, sanctae ecclesiae Constantinopolitanae patriarcha, sedem ipsius invasit et sponsam, quam a Christo sponso immaculatam custodiendam veluti amicus sponsi perceperat, non per ostium, quod Christus est, sed aliunde ex adverso in ovile dominicum more furis atque latronis ingrediens acsi violentus, rapax et scelestus adulter irrupit*⁶⁶⁰.

⁶⁶⁰ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 557, l. 20–28.

II. 5. "OLD" - "NEW" HERESIES:

new heresy in view of the old one/new heresy as the old heresy revisited⁶⁶¹.

In this chapter, the concept of the newly-emerged heresies viewed as the old ones revisited will be presented, as conveyed by the selected 9th-century Greek and Latin texts.

Knitting the thread of narratives related to religious dissenting thought and its developmental pattern constitute a sort of "disobedience process" in Byzantium and Francia, and can be observed through graded sequences, as explained in the opening lines of the second segment of this thesis.

The heretics were accused of innovation – the "survived" past threads have been re-actualized ("*revisités*", revisited) in the new contexts: the "new Predestinarians" (Augustine and Pelagianism revived) in the 9th-century Francia; Maximus the Confessor and Monothelism revived in the 9th-century Byzantium – always in particular contexts (often political) which incited the reference to the preceding heresies⁶⁶². In Byzantium, on the other hand, Photius frequently referred to Iconoclasts as the "new Manichaeans" and compared them to the earlier heresies, for example to the Arian heresy. This paradox of the innovation and revisiting the earlier heretical trends represents a curious feature which will be more thoroughly demonstrated in the following pages.

Positioned in this perspective, the heresies have thus been seen as the enemies of tradition, and therefore, the role of the Church was to protect the tradition of the fathers and to combat its enemies.

The ultimate aim, according to the Theodosian Code, is thus to preserve the tradition of the religious authority, pertaining to the catholic law, and conserve it entire and unviolated if a new (religious) superstition arises. The following passage stresses the importance of tradition, transmitted through the fore-fathers, and reflecting the religious authority, as well the urge to protect the Catholic faith from the religious novelties.

⁶⁶¹ On earlier doctrinal tendencies and strives, which nonetheless influence the course of events in the 9th century as well, see: J. Meyendorff, *Imperial Unity and Christian Divisions: The Church 450 – 680 A.D. The Church in history*, 2 (New York 1989); A. J. Ekonomou, *Byzantine Rome and the Greek Popes: Eastern influences on Rome and the papacy from Gregory the Great to Zacharias, A.D. 590 – 752* (Lanham-MD 2007); A. E. Siecienski, *The Filioque: History of a Doctrinal Controversy* (Oxford 2010).

⁶⁶² Cf. Rigo, *Orthodoxy and heresy* 14–15.

*Ea, quae circa catholicam legem vel olim ordinavit antiquitas vel parentum nostrorum auctoritas religiosa constituit vel nostra serenitas roboravit, novella superstitione submota integra et inviolata custodiri praecipimus*⁶⁶³.

In the first centuries of Christianity, Christian heresies have often been related to Christological concepts, opposite to the established conciliar tradition. Nevertheless, in the 4th century, some earlier gnostic heresies reappeared in the form of Manichaean teachings. At the Council held in Nicaea in 787, convoked with the aim of combating Iconoclasm which had been seen as another Christological dispute, the amount of heretical sequences related to Christian dogma decreased, since the dogmatic tradition had already become firmly established⁶⁶⁴. In the later periods, namely the Middle and Late Byzantine period, the main heretical trends were reflected in the dualist teachings of the Paulicians and Bogomils, which was led by a motivation for the revival of the allegedly pristine apostolic tradition and the undermining of the legitimacy, hierarchy and liturgy of the official Christian Church⁶⁶⁵. Furthermore, heretical tendencies related to the territories lying outside the Byzantine realm emerged, such as in the Armenian Church, or in the Western Latin Church, where a schism related to the procession of the Holy Spirit, known as *Filioque* erupted to the fullest during the missionary episode in Bulgaria⁶⁶⁶.

The question regarding the procession of the Holy Spirit was mentioned in the Scriptures and continued to be present in the writings of the holy fathers from then onwards. Nevertheless, the disputes it induced were strongly related to the Christological issues dating from the dawn of the officialization of the Christian creed. John the Chrysostom mentioned the Greek and Latin terminological differences in denoting the complex theological question of the procession of the Holy Spirit⁶⁶⁷. In a way, this was a linguistic debate as well⁶⁶⁸. It might seem that some

⁶⁶³ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 906; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.11.3, 476.

⁶⁶⁴ Louth, *Christology and Heresy* 196.

⁶⁶⁵ Louth, *Christology and Heresy* 196–197.

⁶⁶⁶ Louth, *Christology and Heresy* 197.

⁶⁶⁷ The summarized analysis containing the most relevant information on the *Filioque* controversy in the Middle Ages is proposed by Siecienski, *The Filioque*.

⁶⁶⁸ Cf. Ş. Barbu, *Language, Philosophy and Politics in the Development of the Filioque Clause*, in: *Theologia Orthodoxa* 2010 (1) 257–271.

pertinent ecclesiastical disputes have in fact never entirely perished, but only submerged and re-emerged respectively at different epochs, with more or less altered causes of apparition⁶⁶⁹.

The role of tradition, conveyed through textual authorities, is clearly observable in all of the 9th-century narratives focused on divergent religious thought. The question of tradition underlines the here-presented sequences. Namely, the Iconodules have, in their struggle against the Iconoclasts, often alluded to their adversaries as falling into the ranks of earlier heresies: the aim was to show that the orthodox, Iconodules, had tradition as their strongest ally on their side of the battlefield, as well as to demonstrate that the Iconoclasts were guilty of innovation⁶⁷⁰. Theodore the Studite composes a list of heresies; in his first *Antirrheticos*, he similarly refers to earlier heresies when condemning Iconoclasm⁶⁷¹. Iconoclasm refers to two periods in the history of the Byzantine Empire when the use of religious images was opposed by religious and imperial authorities within the Eastern Church and the imperial hierarchy. The “First Iconoclasm”, as it is sometimes called, lasted between about 726 and 787. The second period of Iconoclasm took place between the years 814 and 842.

Hence, before exposing the facts and events of the 9th century, it is important to turn to the earlier heresies which marked the Byzantine soil. The aim of this section, but also of other segments of this work – in the Latin West likewise - is in highlighting the ascending chronological line and interconnectedness between the earlier and the later forms of religious dissent, first of all in their framing and defining: namely, heresies and divergences in religious concepts and dogmas which appeared in the 9th century not seldom represented the continuation of the earlier threads, or, they have often been referred to as the survival of earlier heretical doctrines.

Thus, in Byzantium of the earlier centuries, heretical discordances often provoked debates, ranging from Monothelism, to the reference to the Arians, Novatians, Marcionites and others in theological conflicts. Namely, in 691, the Byzantine episcopate found it necessary to renew the canon, which the Fathers of the second Ecumenical Council issued against the Arians, Macedonians, Novatians, Quatrodecimans, Apollinarists, Eunomians, Montanists and Sabellians, who wished to accept the Orthodox teaching. This canon included also the notion

⁶⁶⁹ Chadwick, *East and West* 93; On Maximus the Confessor and the Filioque controversy, see: G.C.Berthold, *Maximus the Confessor and the Filioque*, *Studia Patristica* 18/1 (1985) 113–117.

⁶⁷⁰ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the world* 142.

⁶⁷¹ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the world* 142–144; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Antirrheticos*, ed. Migne.

of Mani, Valentinus, Nestorius and others⁶⁷². Namely, these earlier heresies were still present in some areas of the 7th-century Byzantium. The new heresy, related to the Manichaeans, which would mark the centuries that followed, originated in the 7th century under the name of Paulicianism⁶⁷³.

The practice of debating Iconoclasm was previously prepared by the means employed during the dogmatic and textual struggle over Monothelitism in the 7th century⁶⁷⁴ – and by the recurrence to the model according to which those patterns of collecting and systematizing polemical and anti-Monothelist material have been used. The Monophysitism, on the other hand, has been considered to have potentially influenced the Iconoclasm, which has not been proved grounded in reality⁶⁷⁵. Nevertheless, it has been suggested that some Monophysite arguments have been similar to those employed by the Patriarch Germanus⁶⁷⁶.

Photius intended his 18th homily to prepresent a general condemnation of all heresies, among which the Iconoclasm was enlisted as well⁶⁷⁷. Photius's 15th–18th homilies were composed on the topics related to Arianism and Iconoclasm. In his 16th homily, Photius compares Arianism with Iconoclasm⁶⁷⁸. Apart from Photius, Nicephorus also compared Iconoclasm and Arianism⁶⁷⁹. Theodore's letter 59, written between 821 and 826, regards the Iconoclast controversy: it is desirable to avoid contacts with heretics, in his opinion⁶⁸⁰. Differently to Photius, Theodore did not compare Iconoclasts to Arians: he, on the other hand, compared the Iconoclasts with the Manichaeans, Montanists, Valentinians and Marcionites⁶⁸¹.

Thus have the Iconodules, in their struggle against the Iconoclasts, ascribed their doctrine to the rank of previous heresies⁶⁸². On the other hand, we witness an exactly identical *modus operandi*, employed by Michael II (820 – 829) in his portrayal of the Iconodules, in the letter he addressed to Louis the Pious on the rebellion of Thomas the Slav. Thomas the Slav,

⁶⁷² Cf. W. Hartmann/Pennington, K. ed., *The History of Byzantine and Eastern Canon Law to 1500* (Washington 2012) 1–23, on the formation of ecclesiastical law in the Early Church; 24–114, on the sources of the Greek Canon Law to the Quinisext Council (691/2); 115–169 on the Byzantine Church law to 1100.

⁶⁷³ Peter of Sicily, *Historia manichaeorum* (ed. Mansi, PG 104) 1240–1304.

⁶⁷⁴ Cf. Cameron, *Texts as weapons* 212–214.

⁶⁷⁵ S. Brock, *Iconoclasm and the Monophysites*, in: *Iconoclasm: Papers Given at the Ninth Spring Symposium of Byzantine Studies*, University of Birmingham, March 1975, ed. A. Bryer/J. Herrin (Birmingham 1977) 53–58.

⁶⁷⁶ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the World* 9, note 56; Pargoire, *Église byzantine* 179–182.

⁶⁷⁷ Cf. Mango, *Homilies* 22.

⁶⁷⁸ Mango, *Homilies* 264–266, Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 154–155.

⁶⁷⁹ cf. Mango, *Homilies* 239, note 19: cf. PG 100, 244 D, 561A-B, 796C.

⁶⁸⁰ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 59, ed. Fatouros 203–204; 170–171.

⁶⁸¹ cf. Mango, *Homilies* 239, note 20: ed. Migne, 388D; 452 C; 461C; 481A; 1132C; 1305A; 1321D; 1513C; 1604C.

⁶⁸² Cf. Parry, *Depicting the world* 142.

the “disciple of the Devil”, was the commander of five themes of Asia Minor, later promoted into the rank of the *turmarch* of the federates by Leo the Armenian (813-820)⁶⁸³. The account on Thomas’s rebellion offers an example of combatting the common enemy who allied East and West in diplomatic purposes. Namely, Michael II addressed the letter to Louis the Pious with the aim of assessing and improving diplomatic relations, in which he explains his coming to power and demanded Louis’s support through the lens of his victory over Thomas. Although apparently Thomas was not an Iconodule, Michael addressed Thomas as such in order to equalize Iconodules with an imminent danger. Michael politically used the moment of Iconoclasm to ask the West for support and portrayed Thomas as an Iconodule in political purposes. By all means, Michael painted Thomas in black additionally due to his relations with the Saracens. The political use of Iconoclasm can be observed in Michael’s statement that his predecessor was deposed because he could not deal with Thomas. Hereby has the use of Iconoclasm in political purposes and as an impetus for the contacts between East and West, with Christian religion allying them been attested. Thomas the Slav has apparently joined the Paulicians and the Iconophiles⁶⁸⁴. After having exposed on Thomas’s rebellion in the first half of his letter, Michael continues on the Iconodule’s adoration practices in Byzantium. The question remains, if the rebellion and the Iconoclast crisis of Michael’s time were related. Michael II described the Iconodules as comprising of the ecclesiastics or the laics, distant from the apostolic tradition, who are not acting as guardians of the paternal borders: *...multi de ecclesiasticis seu de laicis viris, alieni de apostolicis traditionibus facti et neque paternos terminos custodientes*⁶⁸⁵.

Theodore compared Iconoclasts with other heresies: Valentinians, Marcionites, Manicheans and Montanists⁶⁸⁶.

The Iconoclast controversy stirred up debates in the West as well⁶⁸⁷. On that occasion, Claudius of Turin and Jonas of Orléans composed their respective texts for Louis the Pious on

⁶⁸³ Lemerle, Thomas le Slave 255–297; W. Treadgold, *The Byzantine Revival 780-842* (Stanford 1988) 196, 198; cf. Т. Живковић, *Јужни Словени под византијском влашћу 600-1025* (Београд 2007?) 237-239.

⁶⁸⁴ Efthymiadis, *Correspondence of Theodore the Studite* 153; Treadgold, *Revival* 234–244; on more information against the Iconophiles: Lemerle, *Thomas le Slave* 260.

⁶⁸⁵ *Michaelis et Theophili imperatorum Constantinopolitanorum epistola ad Hludovicum imperatorem directa* 824 m. Aprili, (ed. A. Werminghoff, *MGH, Conc. II* (819-842), Hannover/Leipzig 1908) 475–480, here 478, l. 36–38.

⁶⁸⁶ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne 1132C, 1305A, 1321D, 1513C, 1604C.

⁶⁸⁷ Cf. Th. Ertl, *Byzantinischer Bilderstreit und fränkische Nomentheorie. Imperiales Handeln und dialektisches Denken im Umfeld der Kaiserkrönung Karls des Großen*, in: *Frühmittelalterliche Studien* 40 (Berlin/New York 2006) 13–42; for a more generalized overview of how the 9th-century in Byzantium was perceived in the West, see: C. Wickham, *Ninth-century Byzantium through western eyes*, in: *Byzantium in the 9th Century: Dead or*

the question of the veneration of the icons, as will be discussed more in detail below. Jonas attacked Claudius and brought his view into connection with earlier heresies: Montanists, Priscilians, Manichaeans, Novatians, and he perceives him as the enemy of the Catholic Church⁶⁸⁸. Hincmar labeled Gottschalk as the “modern Predestinarian”⁶⁸⁹. As Walahfridus stated in his work on the images, the novelties and misunderstandings had provoked a dispute in the 8th century⁶⁹⁰.

Not only had the echo of the Iconoclast controversy stirred debates in the West. Few decades later, Ratramnus of Corbie (died in 870), the renowned Carolingian monk and theologian, refuted the Byzantine accusations against the Westerners, arisen during the *Filioque* controversy in the 860’s. Therein, he compared the Greeks with the Arians: *Ario assimilantur Graeci*⁶⁹¹.

In 9th-century Francia, the Predestinarian controversy arisen by Gottschalk represented, in fact, the struggle for the correct interpretation of Augustine. Namely, the development line and occurrence of controversy reached back to the debate between Augustine and Pelagius⁶⁹²; then continued in the form of Semi-pelagianism with Fulgentius of Ruspe⁶⁹³, only to take up the appearance of Adoptionism with Felix of Urgell⁶⁹⁴, leading to the Predestination controversy. The pivotal questions of Free Will, God’s Grace and predestination remained dominant in all of these heresies.

When speaking of Gottschalk, Hincmar makes allusion to Arius: they have both fallen in error, in spite of the fact that their words are different: *Ambo errore pares, quanquam diversa loquantur*⁶⁹⁵. In the argumentation against Gottschalk’s interpretation of the Trinitarian doctrine, Hincmar recurs to Biblical and patristic quotations. Furthermore, he refers to Athanasius’ words against the Arians and Sabelians on Trinitarian issues. Thus is Trinity put in context with preceding Christological disputes⁶⁹⁶. Hincmar compares Gottschalk to Arius:

Alive? Papers from the Thirtieth Spring Symposium of Byzantine Studies. Birminghnam, March 1996, ed. L. Brubaker (Aldershot 1998) 245–256.

⁶⁸⁸ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 301.

⁶⁸⁹ Hincmar, *De Praedestinatione Dei et Libero Arbitrio* (ed. Migne, PL 125) 65–474.

⁶⁹⁰ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 330.

⁶⁹¹ Ratramnus, *Contra Graecorum Opposita*, ed. Migne 229A.

⁶⁹² Cf. Augustine, *De Gestis Pelagi* (ed. Migne, PL 44) 319–360; M. Levering, *Predestination: Biblical and Theological Paths* (New York 2011) 37–50; 69–75; H. Chadwick, *The Early Church* (London 1993) 230–235.

⁶⁹³ Cf. Fulgentius of Ruspa, *Liber de Praedestinatione et Gratia* (ed. Migne, PL 65) 843B–854C.

⁶⁹⁴ Cf. Felix of Urgell, *Confessio Fidei* (ed. Migne, PL 96) 882–888B.

⁶⁹⁵ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 530CD.

⁶⁹⁶ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 551A-C.

...cuius inspiratione Gotescalcus Arrium sensu sequens⁶⁹⁷, and even calls him the “son of Arius”: ...Arrii...filium Gotescalcum⁶⁹⁸. Hincmar positions Gottschalk to the rank of earlier Predestinarian heretics (*veteres Praedestinatiani*), alluding to him as their successor⁶⁹⁹. Differently to them, Gottschalk’s words are more audacious and dangerous - *audacius ita et perniciosius dicit*, since he also erroneously interprets the Trinitarian doctrine through his employment of the idiom *deitas trina*⁷⁰⁰.

Alcuin also compared newly-arisen heresies with previous ones: thus, he compared Felix of Urgell to Nestorius. Consequently, Alcuin clearly pointed to the Christological disputes as a common denominator of both, earlier and more recent heresies⁷⁰¹. Hence, old heresies were frequently recurred to and brought into connection with newer ones. For example, at the peak of the Trinitarian controversy in 850’s, Gottschalk aligned those disagreeing with his interpretation of the Greek term *tritheiotheia* (τριθειοθεΐα) as *trina deitas* – to the line of previous heresies, comparing them to the Arians, Sabellians and Patripassians⁷⁰².

⁶⁹⁷ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 112, l. 31.

⁶⁹⁸ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 112, l. 34.

⁶⁹⁹ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 161, l. 14.

⁷⁰⁰ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 162, l. 6–7.

⁷⁰¹ Cf. Alcuin, *Liber contra haeresim Felicis* (ed. G. Blumenshine, *Studi e testi* 285, Vatican City 1980) 2, 55–56.

⁷⁰² Cf. Gottschalk, *Schedula*, ed. Lambot 21–22; Gottschalk, *De Trina Deitate*, ed. Lambot 81–130, here 98; cf. Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais* 296–297.

II. 6. INNOVATION: DANGER OF NOVELTIES

In this chapter, aligning to the previous one and representing its continuation, the theme relevant to the danger of innovation and novelites has been researched on the basis of the selected sources, and put deservedly at the forefront of the textual treatment of religious dissent.

The Theodosian Code contains precepts against the innovations. Namely, the ancient ecclesiastical practices should be observed and all innovations should cease (in the provinces of Illyricum). The synod of priests should deal with any uncertain issues:

*Omni innovatione cessante vetustatem et canones pristinos ecclesiasticos, qui nunc usque tenuerunt, per omnes Illyrici provincias servari praecipimus. Tum si quid dubietatis emerit, id oporteat non absque scientia viri reverentissimi sacrosanctae legis antistitis urbis Constantinopolitanae, quae Romae veteris praerogativa laetatur, conventui sacerdotali sanctoque iudicio reservari*⁷⁰³.

The Justinian Code contains incentives against the introduction of the innovations into the Christian doctrine, as does the Theodosian Code:

*Omni innovatione cessante vetustatem et canones pristinos ecclesiasticos, qui nunc usque tenuerunt, et per omnes illyrici provincias servari praecipimus...*⁷⁰⁴

During the process of the baptism of the Bulgarians and the emerging *Filioque* dispute in 860's, the Byzantine missionaries complained that the Latin ones brought innovations into the liturgy and sacraments, which were later to constitute the differences between the East and West Christian rite, including the *Filioque* question on the procession of the Holy Spirit which was dealt with differently in the West and East churches⁷⁰⁵. Namely, the Third Ecumenical

⁷⁰³ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 852; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.2.45, 449.

⁷⁰⁴ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.2.6; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 13.

⁷⁰⁵ Cf. T. M. Kolbaba, *Byzantine perceptions of Latin religious 'errors'*, in: *Doctrine and Debate in the East Christian World, 300 – 1500*, ed. A. Cameron/R. Hoyland (Farnham 2011) 293–319, at 295–297.

Synod of Ephesos (431) and the Fourth in Chalcedon (451) have already forbidden the import of additions (or, innovations) to the Nicæan-Constantinopolitan creed⁷⁰⁶.

In his letter on Thomas's rebellion, Michael II portrays the Iconodules as the ones who bring offence and defamation to the church, and distort the true religion: *iniuriam et calumniam ecclesiae inferentes et verae religioni detrahentes*⁷⁰⁷. Addressing the Iconoclast crisis, the emperor aligns the Iconodules in the line of inventors of the evil things⁷⁰⁸: *...facti sunt inventores malarum rerum*⁷⁰⁹.

The *Filioque* controversy between East and West⁷¹⁰ had its 9th-century peak during the events related to the Frankish and Byzantine missionary activities in Bulgaria in 866⁷¹¹. The accusations followed on the behalf of the Byzantines, according to which the *Filioque*, introduced by the Latin bishops in Bulgaria was similar to the older heresies, as well as to the tales of Greek mythology. The work of the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria had been condemned by a local synod in Constantinople, held in 867. The Council asked the innovations brought in by the Latin missionaries to be extirpated. Nicholas I got excommunicated by the Council. On this occasion, Photius directed a letter to the Oriental Patriarchs, in which he condemns the liturgical practices introduced by the Latin missionaries in Bulgaria – which was officially expressed upon a Council of Constantinople, held in 867⁷¹². It was upon this Council that the Pope Nicholas I got excommunicated⁷¹³.

Therefore, the innovations and novelties can also represent danger for the traditions of the fathers. During the theological disputes between the Byzantines and the Latins, the Greek accusations were particularly ponderous, since they pertained to the old tradition of the Fathers,

⁷⁰⁶ Cf. Stratoudaki White, Patriarch Photios 31–32; Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers, ed. Ph. Schaff (Buffalo-NY 1886-1900) 16:163 – on the *Filioque* proceeding from the Father, as stated in Nicaea 325; on the forbidden additions: *Ibid.*, 231, 265.

⁷⁰⁷ Michael, *Epistola*, ed. Werminghoff 479, l. 23–24.

⁷⁰⁸ Michael, *Epistola*, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 36–38.

⁷⁰⁹ Michael, *Epistola*, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 36–38.

⁷¹⁰ Cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta.

⁷¹¹ Dvornik, The Photian Schism 91–131, esp. 122; Stratoudaki White, Patriarch Photios 32; Photius, *De Spiritus S. mystagogia*, ed. Hergenröther 14, 15, 36, 37 109; more on Hergenröther's edition, see: G. Glockmann ed., *Texte und Untersuchungen zur Geschichte der altchristlichen Literatur* (Berlin 1967) Vol. 83, 95, note 5; Photius's Encyclical Letter to the Oriental Patriarchs, in: Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 4, ed. Valetta, 165–181; *Ibid.*, ed. Migne 721–741; Kolbaba, *Inventing Latin Heretics* 49–75.

⁷¹² On the summary on the particularities of the Latin liturgy which provoked the condemnation, cf. Mango, *Homilies* 300; the Encyclical Letter to the Oriental Patriarchs, cf. Photius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 4, ed. Valetta, 165–181; *Ibid.*, ed. Migne 721–741.

⁷¹³ Cf. Mansi, *Sacrorum Conciliorum collectio*, XVI, 174C, 405C; Nicetas David Paphlago, *Vita Archiepiscopi Ignatii Constantinopolitani sive Certamen* (ed. Migne, PG 105) 487–574, here 541; cf. Wolfram, *Conversio Bagoariorum et Carantanorum* 58–83, 217, 226–227.

according to the Pope Nicholas: *ridiculum est enim et satis abominabile dedecus, ut... eas traditiones, quas antiquitus a patribus nostris suscepimus, pro libitu semper errantium infringere patiamur*⁷¹⁴.

Thus have the Byzantines, propelled by envy - as has already been pointed to - pertained to eradicate ecclesiastical tradition, according to Pope Nicholas: *zelo invidentiae perculsi, ecclesiae lacerare traditiones anhebant*⁷¹⁵. They have, therefore, undertaken actions against God's regulations and ecclesiastical traditions: *adversus ordinationes Dei et ecclesiae traditiones*⁷¹⁶; *traditionibus paternis divinis testimoniis roboratis detrahere curaverunt*⁷¹⁷. Having deposed Ignatius and instituted Photius, the Byzantines have proceeded against the ecclesiastical canons and tradition of the Apostolical See: *contra statuta seu traditiones apostolicae sedis*⁷¹⁸. Consequently, the Pope replies to the Greek accusations with the following words, expressing his disbelief that they, the Greeks, label them (the Latins) inventors of some novelties and heretics: *Numquid nos alicuius novitatis inventores extitimus? Numquid alia, nisi quae ad salutem ipsorum et ad communem ecclesiae statum pertinebant, transmisimus? Numquid nos haeretici aliquando fuimus? Nam licet nos peccatores quidem esse non denegemus, quorumlibet tamen eorum faece pollutes Deo gratias minime recognoscimus, quemadmodum illi, qui numquam sine scismate numquam prorsus ab errore reperiuntur extranei*⁷¹⁹. It is important, hortatively proclaims the Pope, while employing the belligerent tone, as well as language, to be united against those defamations and oppose to those false weapons with the sword of truth: *...ut eorum conatibus resistamus et falsis illorum iaculis veritatis clipeum opponamus*⁷²⁰.

Strange as it may seem, the term “enemy” is hereby employed to designate the Byzantines, against whose accusations the Pope demands Hincmar to take action and consolidate the joint stand of the Frankish bishops, rather than against some foreign invader – differently to the message addressed to Louis the Pious by Michael the II, as shown above. The Latins wage their struggle against the inventors of lies and artisans of perverse dogmas, shielded by the true claims and the words of the Fathers: *...ita ut Christo duce una mente et ore ac brachio quasi strenui propugnatores phalanges hostium premere ac debellare communi studio reperiamur*

⁷¹⁴Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 604, l. 14–16.

⁷¹⁵Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 605, l. 10–11, 30.

⁷¹⁶Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 607, l. 13–14; cf. Rom. 13:2.

⁷¹⁷Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 607, l. 37–38.

⁷¹⁸Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 608, l. 12–13.

⁷¹⁹Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 606, l. 12–17.

⁷²⁰Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 604, l. 17–18.

*eorumque perniciosam factionem ipso auxiliante socia concertatione funditus interrupisse comperiamur et tam inventores mendaciorum quam fabricatores perversorum dogmatum paternis diffinitionibus ac veracium assertionum clipeis in nomine domini nostri Iesu Christi unanimiter triumphare ac superare per omnia dinoscamur*⁷²¹. Here, hence, urge and invective to unite, through joint forces, minds, mouths and hands – take the prominent place, at the closure of this rather long letter, and is expressed in a solemn, exhortative tone, albeit militant. Beyond any doubt, the language and style of the letter bear reminiscences of a belligerently styled Old-Testamentary literary stamina. Similar exhortative tone and topic – joint struggle against the pagans in this case - is employed in another letter, directed to Lothar II, in 860: *Regnum quoque nobis divina pietate commissum ab omni paganorum infestatione aliorumque inimicorum depraedatione, dextera omnipotentis Dei pro nobis pugnante et auxiliantibus meritis beati Petri apostoli vestrisque precibus almifluis suffragantibus, hactenus cum omni integritate tutum manere cognoscite*⁷²². To conclude, the “line of defense” remains the same, whether the Latins are combatting the Greek accusations, or the pagans, under the aegis of the apostolic tradition.

In his 15th and 16th homily, Photius compared the Iconoclasts to the Arians, saying that the Iconoclasts use the same device as the Arians. Namely, Arius simulated piety, and invented fictions, which led to many evils and scandals. In his first homily, delivered in Hagia Sophia on the subject of icons, Photius compares the attitude of the Patriarch Nicephorus towards the iconoclastic Patriarch John the Grammarian, and that of the Patriarch Alexander of old times towards Arius⁷²³:...*Ἄρειον πλαττόμενον ὑποκρινόμενον τὴν εὐσέβειαν... ἀπὸ τῶν πολλῶν κακῶν καὶ σκανδάλων*⁷²⁴. Already at the opening of the 15th homily, Photius compares Arius with John the Grammarian mostly judging by the fact that both have repented from their error of heresy, but did return to it afterwards⁷²⁵. These two sermons most likely date from the period of Photius’s first patriarchate⁷²⁶.

As it has already been mentioned, in his 15th and 16th homilies, Photius makes a comparison between the 4th-century Arianism and 9th-century Iconoclasm, that is, between the heresies and heretics of the 4th- and the 9th-century Byzantium⁷²⁷. This comparison is perhaps not dogmatic,

⁷²¹Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 608, l. 28–33.

⁷²² *Epistolae ad divortium Lotharii*, Ep. 1, ed. Dümmler 209–210, here 209, l. 26–29.

⁷²³ Cf. Dvornik, *Patriarch Photius* 86.

⁷²⁴ Cf. Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily 244; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 139, l. 2–5.

⁷²⁵ Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily 246–247; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 146–147.

⁷²⁶ Cf. Mango, *Homilies* 264.

⁷²⁷ Cf. Mango, *Homilies* 237 f.

but it shows that every heresy is an enemy of Christianity. Theodore compared Iconoclasts with other heresies: Valentinians, Marcionites, Manicheans and Montanists⁷²⁸.

Even the *Filioque* dispute, according to Photius, could be placed to the line of older heresies, since he sees it comparable to the heresies of Sabellius and Macedonius⁷²⁹.

In his 6th letter⁷³⁰, Photius depicts Arius as an innovator who was accused at the first Council of Nicaea (325) for impiety.

Analogously, innovation was also spoken of with contempt on the Western part of the European continent, some years later during the same century when Gottschalk was accused of novelties likewise.

In Francia, according to Hincmar, Gottschalk was delighted by the novelty of words and he used them to corrupt the minds of the simple.

Namely, by quoting the acts of the Sixth Ecumenical Synod held in 680/681, Hincmar continues with an explanation of the anathema: those who alter the symbol of faith and who induce novelties, are to be expelled and anathematized⁷³¹: *...aut qui novitatem vocis vel dictionis adinventionem ad subversionem eorum quae nunc a nobis determinata sunt introducere; hos...alienos esse...anathematizari eos*. Gottschalk was always delighted with bringing up novelties in the realm of theology, which, in Hincmar's opinion, only gave him the allure of the wise man, while ignoring the simplicity of faith: *More suo novitates vocum, quibus semper delectatus est, et exquisivit ut sapiens videatur ad eludendam fidei simplicitatem*⁷³². Heretics induce novelties, which are false: Hincmar underlines this by quoting Augustine's words on Julianus, which could be put forward as the core-defining feature of the heretics: *Mira stupemus, nova cavemus, falsa convincimus*⁷³³. The heretics strive to be considered wise, and are therefore keen on novelties: Gottschalk, likewise, wishing to appear wise, introduces new words, which were inexistent in the writings of the Fathers, Hincmar argues: *Non igitur, ut blasphemat Gothescalcus, inde dicitur in Deo persona, quod per se sit una, more suo, videlicet haeticorum more, profanas vocum novitates exquirens. Qui, ut beatus dicit Gregorius, dum laudari tanquam de excellenti ingenio cupiunt, quasi nova quaedam proferunt, quae in*

⁷²⁸ Cf. Mango, Homilies 239.

⁷²⁹ Cf. Mango, Homilies 304; cf. Photius, De Spiritus S. mystagogia, ed. Hergenröther 14, 15, 36, 37, 109.

⁷³⁰ Photius, Epistolae, Ep. 6, ed. Valetta 206.

⁷³¹ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 528AB.

⁷³² Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 554AB.

⁷³³ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 554BC.

*antiquorum Patrum libris veteribus non tenentur*⁷³⁴. Gottschalk is always aspiring to novelty, and likewise to originality, and thus earning his fame in that way: ...*semper vocum novitates exquisivit, et adhuc semper inquiri, quatenus talia dicens quae nemo aliud dicit, innotesci et sinon de bonis vel de pessimis possit*⁷³⁵.

In his letter, Hincmar observes that novelty is a characteristic of inducing those in error, who do not wish to be disciples of the truth: ...*novitates vocum semper equirunt, prurientes auribus, errantes et in errorem inducentes, qui, quoniam discipuli veritatis esse noluerint, magistri erroris fiunt*⁷³⁶. Hincmar often refers in his opus to Pope Celestine I (422 – 432). In his narrative on Gottschalk's heretical doctrine, Hincmar alludes to Pope Celestine's warning against novelties: ...*universalis Ecclesia quacumque novitate pulsatur*⁷³⁷. Gottschalk, a pseudo-monk, *Orbacensis monasterii Remensis ecclesiae pseudomonachus*, brought in novelties, in his interpretation of the Trinitarian doctrine as well⁷³⁸:...*more suo, qui nova et antea inaudita canaque orthodoxorum intellegentiae contraria adinvenire...*⁷³⁹. He uttered his heretical doctrine first covertly, and then overtly: ...*primum latenter, deinde...aperte*⁷⁴⁰. Gottschalk spread his heresy to those who rejoiced to the voices of novelty – *vocumque novitate delectantibus*⁷⁴¹. Gottschalk is in the guise of a monk, with a bestial mind, delighted with the novelty of words and extremely dangerous due to his doctrine: ...*habitu monachus, mente ferinus, quietis impatiens et vocum novitate delectans ac inter suos mobilitate noxia singularis, de omnibus, quae in his regionibus perverse tunc temporis sensa cognoverat...*⁷⁴².

Hrabanus was, following the concept of his teacher Alcuin, equating novelty with heresy. Namely, at the times marked with Adoptionist controversy, Alcuin took up the role of defender of the Christian tradition, thus aligning the heresy with novelties, opposed to the apostolic tradition⁷⁴³. It is in his letter to Eberhard, marchgrave of Frioul, that Hrabanus offered

⁷³⁴ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 585CD.

⁷³⁵ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 588D.

⁷³⁶ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 37, ed. Perels 13, l. 30–31.

⁷³⁷ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 133, ed. Perels 75, l. 21, quoting Caelestinus I, *Epistolae et Decreta*, *Epistula ad episcopos Galliarum* (ed. Migne, PL 50) II, 530.

⁷³⁸ by having interpreted Greek term *tritheotheia* as *trina deitas*, cf. above; Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 110–112 on Gottschalk's heretical teachings.

⁷³⁹ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 109, l. 4–9.

⁷⁴⁰ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 109, l. 9.

⁷⁴¹ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 141, ed. Perels 109, l. 37.

⁷⁴² Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 160, l. 15–17.

⁷⁴³ Cf. Alcuin, *Contra Felicem Urgellitanum Episcopum Libri Septem* (ed. Migne, PL 101) 119–230, here 129, 154.

his views on novelty as dangerous for the body of believers, since it can produce scandal⁷⁴⁴. Hrabanus quotes firstly the excerpt from *Moralia in Iob*, composed by Gregory the Great (590-604), and then continues further on. Hincmar's accusation of Gottschalk was not restricted to the Predestinarian debate, as was also the case with his accusations of Gottschalk having introduced novelties into the dogma. Namely, during the Trinitarian controversy which arose in the 850's⁷⁴⁵, Hincmar also accused Gottschalk of introducing novelties into the ecclesiastical dogma, having uttered new words, contrary to tradition: *...canaeque orthodoxorum intelligentiae contraria adinvenire...*⁷⁴⁶

Dangerous novelties are associated with the additions brought into tradition. Moreover, it is by adding certain teachings that heretical doctrine is being developed: Gottschalk was accused of introducing precepts which made his doctrine destructive. Gottschalk is judged as being too haughty in respect to his knowledge, prizing superstitions, and uttering his pestiferous words, orally or in the writing: *Godescalcus Gallus quidam, monasterii Orbacensis parrochiae suessonicae monachus et presbyter, scientia tumidus, quibusdam superstitionibus deditus...quaedam nostrae saluti valde contraria, praecipue sub nomine praedestinationis, pestiferis dictis et scriptis adstruens...*⁷⁴⁷ Amolo also speaks on the danger of novelties, and warns not to fall prey to them, after having founded his warning in the Pauline Epistle to Timothy: *...ne vel ad audiendas vel ad loquendas novitates promti et faciles sumus*⁷⁴⁸.

On the other hand, Gottschalk himself recurs to the identical *modus operandi* when exposing on his enemies: during a Reims Antiphonary controversy⁷⁴⁹, Gottschalk attacks Hincmar for having introduced dangerous novelties into the traditional text of the antiphonary, which lead to error⁷⁵⁰. Namely, Gottschalk himself respected and considered st. Paul's advice against introducing novelties in dogma noteworthy⁷⁵¹.

⁷⁴⁴ Hrabanus, Epistolae, Ep. 42, ed. Dümmler 486–487, referring to Gregory the Great, *Moralia in Iob*, l. XVII, c. 26.

⁷⁴⁵ Cf. G. Tavard, Trina Deitas: The Controversy Between Hincmar and Gottschalk (Milwaukee-WI 1996); Gillis, Gottschalk of Orbais 295–299.

⁷⁴⁶ Cf. Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 475.

⁷⁴⁷ Annales Bertiniani, ed. Waitz 36, a. 849.

⁷⁴⁸ Amolo, Epistola 2, ed. Dümmler 370, l. 14–15, referring to 2.Tim. 4:3 and 1. Tim. 6:20.

⁷⁴⁹ For more information on the Reims Antiphonary Controversy, see: Gillis, Gottschalk of Orbais 340–353.

⁷⁵⁰ Gottschalk, Adversaria in Librum responsalem, ed. Lambot 427–459; Gottschalk, Opusculum primum, ed. Lambot 380–381.

⁷⁵¹ Gottschalk, Opusculum primum, ed. Lambot 380–381: *...nam magnopere nobis apostolus iubet vitare novitates vocum* (cf. 1 Tim. 6:20).

The danger of novelties and of introducing innovations into ecclesiastical tradition has been brought into connection with heretical doctrines in Byzantium as well.

Photius describes Constantine the heresiarch as the new legislator, the head of the apostasy, who represents a danger: *...καινὸς νομοθέτης...δυσσεβείας δόγματα τεκῶν, ἀποστασίας ὀδηγὸς καὶ προστάτης τοῖς πειθόμενοις ἐσχάτης ἀπολείας ἀναδείκνυται*⁷⁵². The Manichaean heresy is described as a new apostate insolence against God: *Τοιαύτη τῆς ἀποστασίας ἡ νέα καὶ πρόσφατος κατὰ τοῦ Δημιουργοῦ τῶν ὄλων τυραννίς*⁷⁵³. Moreover, Peter of Sicily narrates how Constantine, the new heresiarch of the Manichaeans, was led by the desire to give a new form to the heretical teachings: *...θέλων αὐθις ἀνανεώσασθαι τὸ κακόν*⁷⁵⁴.

The epistle addressed by Theodore the Studite to young Athanasius ends with a warning to the addressee, not to find delight in novelties, but in preserving the inheritance of the fathers instead: *...οὐ τὸ χαῖρον καινοτομία, ἀλλὰ τὸ φυλάσσειν πατρῶαν κληρονομίαν*⁷⁵⁵.

Theodore's epistle to young Naucratius evolves around the identical topic as in the letter to Athanasius: the Moechian heresy. The Moechians – supporters of the decisions taken upon the Moechian synod - are referred to as the infamous ones: *δυσώνυμοι Μοιχειανοί*⁷⁵⁶. Moreover, during the crisis provoked by the Moechian Synod, Theodore addresses another letter to Pope Leo III (795 – 816). After having exposed on the events related to the afore-mentioned Synod, Theodore states that this was a heretical synod; furthermore, Theodore says, all the heretical novelties which were introduced to the Church on behalf of those who had withdrawn from the truth, are to be submitted to (the authority of) Saint Peter, i.e., to his successor. *Πρὸς Πέτρον ἦτοι τὸν αὐτοῦ διάδοχον, ὅτι οὖν καινοτομούμενον ἐν τῇ καθολικῇ Ἐκκλησίᾳ παρὰ τῶν ἀποσφαλλομένων τῆς ἀληθείας, ἀναγκαῖον ἀναφέρεσθαι*. Moreover, Theodore ensues, this act introduced upon the Moechian Synod (the re-marriage of Constantine VI) is a novelty against the law and against the evangelical canons: *...διὰ τῆς νομικῆς...διὰ τῆς εὐαγγελικῆς παραβάσεως*⁷⁵⁷.

⁷⁵² Photius, *Contra Manichaeos* 48B.

⁷⁵³ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos* 169CD.

⁷⁵⁴ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 41, 96.

⁷⁵⁵ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1069C–1084B, here 1084AB.

⁷⁵⁶ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 49, ed. Migne 1084–1089, here 1084D.

⁷⁵⁷ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 33, ed. Migne 1017B–1021B.

II. 7. *RUSTICI AND SIMPLICES*

In this chapter, the danger of heresy for the simple people has been demonstrated, as conveyed through the chosen narratives.

*UT DIXERUNT, HERESIS*⁷⁵⁸ – *The echos of the Iconoclast crisis in the West*

As already mentioned above, the Iconoclast crisis had its echo in the West. In 731, the Roman Synod rejected heresy and restored the image worship. Afterwards, Claudius revoked the Iconoclast debate in the West. Therefore, in the period encompassing the 820's and the 830's, the Iconoclast crisis provoked vehement reactions on the Latin West. Einhard (c. 770 – 840)⁷⁵⁹, Walahfridus Strabo (808/9 – 849), and Agobard of Lyon (779-840), Dungal, Claudius of Turin, Jonas of Orléans wrote on this issue. Namely, it was the so-called “Claudius affair” which sprang out of the reactions to the Iconoclast controversy in the Latin West that provoked additional debates on this problematic. At that particular moment, the envoys with the *Corpus Areopagiticum* reached the West from Byzantium⁷⁶⁰. For some of the Latin authors, the Iconoclasts were considered heretics. Walahfridus composed his “On the Origins and Developments of Some Aspects of the Liturgy” in respect to the Iconoclast controversy⁷⁶¹. It is worth saying that the first translation of the acts of Nicaea II was replaced by Anastasius Bibliothecarius (c. 810 – c. 878). Gregory the Great influenced the position that the Latin West held on the adoration of the icons⁷⁶².

In his “On the cult of images”⁷⁶³, designed as a response to the Apology of Claudius of Turin composed in ca. 825⁷⁶⁴, Jonas of Orléans states that the people who were content in their simplicity have always represented a target to the enemies of the church. It is specifically to the simple people that the icon worship can be beneficial. Claudius considered the adoration of the icons erroneous and compared it to the idol-worshippers. Similarly, writing on the worshippers

⁷⁵⁸ Cf. Walahfridus, Libellus ed. Boretius/Krause 482, l. 38.

⁷⁵⁹ Cf. Einhard, Quaestio de adoranda cruce (ed. K. Hampe, MGH Epp. V, Berlin 1899) 146–149.

⁷⁶⁰ On the *Corpus Areopagiticum* and its reception in Francia, see below, in chapter II.10.

⁷⁶¹ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 307, 313.

⁷⁶² See: C. Chazelle, Memory, Instruction, Worship: ‘Gregory’s’ Influence on Early Medieval Doctrines of the Artistic Image, in: J. Cavadini, ed., Gregory the Great. A Symposium. Notre Dame Studies in Theology, 2 (Notre Dame-IN 1995) 181–215.

⁷⁶³ Jonas, De Cultu Imaginum, ed. Migne 0305B – 0388A.

⁷⁶⁴ Claudius of Turin, Apologeticum atque rescriptum Claudii episcopi adversus Theutmirum abbatem (ed. Migne, PL 105) 459–464. A translation of the original text appeared in: G. McCracken/A. Cabaniss ed., Early Medieval Theology (Philadelphia-PA 1957) 241-248.

of the holy cross, Claudius alludes to them as worshipers of the superstition and false religion: *...isti falsae religionis atque superstitionis cultores*, and refers to them as impious men, Jews, or the pagans: *...impii homines, sive Iudaei sive pagani*⁷⁶⁵.

Dungal Scott (ca. 760 – ca. 860), the head of the teaching unit in Pavia, on the other hand, vehemently accused Claudius for his stance in support of the Iconoclasts. In ca. 827, Dungal composed his *Responsa contra Perversas Claudii Tauronensis Episcopi Sententias*, in which he referred to the Claudius's view as an insane doctrine, wicked views and fantasies, which he is combatting: *Dungalus doctrinam insanam Claudii Taurinensis episcopi de cultu imaginum impugnat...contra perversas sententias...naenias*⁷⁶⁶. The icons are useful for the uneducated and unlearned people, writes Dungal, while quoting Pope Gregory the Great⁷⁶⁷.

Walahfridus Strabo, abbot of Reichenau and a prolific prose and poetic writer who without any doubt left his mark upon the intellectual circles of the first half of the 9th century, summarily narrates on the outburst of the Iconoclast crisis in Byzantium, and on its impact among the Carolingian intellectuals of the time⁷⁶⁸.

Walahfridus composed a chapter “On Picture and Images” on the iconoclast issue during his exile between 840 and 842. He mentions the “*insipientes*”. According to Walahfridus's explanation - the simple people, those who are not influenced by the force of the word, are influenced and attracted by the depicted expression, that is, image⁷⁶⁹. Similarly, John of Damascus said on the veneration of the icons: “And what the book is for those who are initiated into letters, that is the icon for the illiterate, and what is word for hearing, that is the icon for

⁷⁶⁵ The excerpts from Claudius's Apology are contained in his epistles: Claudius, *Epistolae, Excerpta de imaginum cultu*, Ep. 12 (ed. E. Dümmler, Epp. IV, Berlin 1895) 605–613, here 611; cf. P. Boulhol, *Claude de Turin. Un évêque iconoclaste dans l'Occident carolingien. Étude suivie de l'édition du Commentaire sur Josué* (Paris 2002) 325–330; cf. Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians* 304.

⁷⁶⁶ Dungal Scott, *Responsa contra Perversas Claudii Tauronensis Episcopi Sententias* (ed. Migne, PL 105) 465–530A; Dungal's *Responsa* are contained in his letters, and edited in the MGH: Dungal Scott, *Epistolae* (ed. E. Dümmler, MGH Epp. IV, Berlin 1895) 568–585, here 583.

⁷⁶⁷ Cf. Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians* 307.

⁷⁶⁸ Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause ch. 8, *De imaginibus* 482–484; cf. R. Corradini, *Das Zeitbuch des Walahfrid Strabo. Langzeitperspektiven und Nachhaltigkeitskonzepte*, in: *Zur Verschränkung von Weltdeutung und Zeitwahrnehmung, 750–1350*, ed. M. Czock/A. Rathmann-Lutz (Köln/Weimar/Wien 2016) 39–62; Id., *Historiographie als Zeitdiagnose. Studien zum Kompendium des Walahfrid Strabo* (St. Gallen, Stiftsbibliothek 878) (MGH Studien und Texte, in Vorbereitung 2018).

⁷⁶⁹ Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 482, l. 24–26; Cf. Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians* 327.

sight...’’⁷⁷⁰. It has been pointed to the danger for the simple ones, who would be scandalized by the conduct of Claudius, bishop of Turin⁷⁷¹. Apparently, the connection between the simple and scandal is to be emphasized.

In the 32 chapters of his *Libellus*, Walafridus examines various questions, many of them relevant to religious practices not only from the dawn of Christianity but also inherent to other, pagan belief systems. His major topics range from baptism and temple building, to various liturgical practices⁷⁷².

Walafridus is not strictly opposed to the veneration of icons. Nevertheless, he enumerates certain errors that it can induce, particularly among the unwise people. Namely, Walafridus is against the cult of the icons if the icons are being worshipped as divinities; they should not be endowed with an added value – since the spiritual realm should not be transposed to the corporeal level. They should not become objects of worship such as idols, since only God should be worshipped. The cult of the icons is particularly dangerous for the simple people, as it has already been stressed, because it can resemble idolatry: *ut quasdam idolatriae species respuunt et praesumptionis fastu simplicium corda scandalizant*⁷⁷³. The cult of the icon is appealing to the *insipientes*: *...ars pictorum...propter artis decorum et convenientiam ad cultum sui inliciant insipientes*⁷⁷⁴.

The strife which arose in respect to the icon worship and which stirred up Byzantium was labelled in the East a heresy, “as they put it”, according to Walafridus: *Huius rei questio apud Graecos saepe tantas contentiones excitavit, ut sub Gregorio papa iuniore Constantinus imperator*⁷⁷⁵ *apud Constantinopolim omnes imagines deposuerit et sub Gregorio tertio Romae synodus sit facta contra supradictam, ut dixerunt, heresim, in qua firmatum est, ut sanctorum imagines secundum priscum catholicae ecclesiae usum restituerentur*⁷⁷⁶.

The Byzantine Iconoclast controversy is perceived by Walafridus as *ipsa querela Graecorum* which reached Francia during the reign of Louis the Pious and was disputed at the Council of

⁷⁷⁰ John of Damascus, *Contra imaginum calumniatores*, ed. Kotter 93 (Apology I, 17, 1–7); *Ibid.*, Apology III, 12, 123; cf. J. Mansi, *Sacrorum Conciliorum nova et amplissima collectio* (Florenze/Venezia 1759-1798) XIII, 249DE.

⁷⁷¹ Cf. Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians* 331.

⁷⁷² Cf. A. L. Harting-Correa, *Walafrid Strabo’s Libellus de exordiis et incrementis quarundam in observationibus ecclesiasticis rerum: A Translation and Liturgical Commentary*. *Mittelateinische Studien und Texte* 19 (Leiden 1996).

⁷⁷³ Walafridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 482, l. 33–34.

⁷⁷⁴ Walafridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 482, l. 24–26.

⁷⁷⁵ Constantinus V (741-775).

⁷⁷⁶ The Synod held in Rome, in 731; cf. Walafridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause notes 79-82, 482, l. 34–38; 483, l. 1.

Paris held in 825. Walahfridus expounds briefly on the conflict which had arisen between Claudius of Turin and Jonas of Orléans, as a reflection of the Iconoclast crisis in the Frankish realm⁷⁷⁷.

The didactic role of the icons is hereby stressed, as they can lead the uneducated individuals towards the worship of the unseen, spiritual reality of the Christian God: *...sicque poterit evenire, ut, dum cavemus...ubi insipientium mens possit errare, nihil paene habeamus, quo vel devotionem nostram exerceamus vel simplices et ingaros ad amorem invisibilium trahere valeamus*⁷⁷⁸ – because the image is equated with literature for those who cannot read: *...pictura est quaedam litteratura inlitterato, adeo ut quidam priorum legatur ex picturis didicisse antiquorum historias*⁷⁷⁹. The usefulness of the image worship is not to be underestimated – its role is thus to draw those simple people who cannot be attracted by words to the worship of the Christian God: *Et videmus aliquando simplices et idiotas, qui verbis vix ad fidem gestorum possunt perducī, ex pictura passionis dominicae vel aliorum mirabilium ita compungi, ut lacrimis testentur exteriores figuras cordi suo quasi lituris impressas*⁷⁸⁰.

Later during the same century, in the 860's, Pope Nicholas wrote numerous letters pregnant with criticism, aimed at the Byzantine rulers. The conversion of the Bulgars represented the meeting-point between Latin and Greek missionaries, and brought in numerous points of incomprehension which would later result in a schism⁷⁸¹. In this particular letter, the Pope focused upon the metaphorical description of heresies and brought them into connection with the simple people, to whom they represented an imminent danger. The Pope criticized the carriers of Byzantine political power through claims that Emperor Michael had subjugated the Bulgarians only under the pretext of baptismal pretensions⁷⁸², and that he (Michael III) had accused the members of the Latin clergy to had been covered with the filth of various heresies: *nos quasi noxios et diversarum hereseon squaloribus respersos*⁷⁸³. The Byzantines condemned the Latin liturgical practices as having been uttered by a filthy mouth – *accusare et blasphemare ore polluto*⁷⁸⁴. On the other hand, the Latin ecclesiastics resisted the Greek accusations, and were supported by the authority of the apostolic See and ancient customs: *nos apostolicae sedis*

⁷⁷⁷ Walahfridus, Libellus, ed. Boretius/Krause 483, l. 1–9.

⁷⁷⁸ Walahfridus, Libellus, ed. Boretius/Krause 483, l. 34–36.

⁷⁷⁹ Walahfridus, Libellus, ed. Boretius/Krause 484, l. 1–3.

⁷⁸⁰ Walahfridus, Libellus, ed. Boretius/Krause 484, l. 5–8.

⁷⁸¹ Cf. Dvornik, *The Photian Schism* 91–131.

⁷⁸² Nicholas, Ep. 100 (Nicolaus capitulis 106 ad Bulgarorum consulta respondet), ed. Perels 601, l. 22–30.

⁷⁸³ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 601, l. 28–29.

⁷⁸⁴ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 608, l. 1; cf. with ritual purity and impurity, of which was spoken above (in chapter I.4.).

*auctoritatem Deo gratias non ignorantes...more prisco muniti constantia summa repressimus*⁷⁸⁵. The Pope saw Constantinople as a city ruled by heretical rulers: *prafatae urbis (cf. Constantinopolitanae) heretici principes*⁷⁸⁶. The Pope accused the Greeks of insane action and blasphemy⁷⁸⁷. In the same key, the Pope spoke of the insanity of the Greeks and their malice: *...quatenus id nos quoque adversus eorum vesaniam cum ceteris assertionibus nostris deinde mittere valeamus*⁷⁸⁸; *Quanto autem livore quantaque vecordia iam designati Graecorum principes eorumque satellites adversus nos pro eo, quod suis noluimus parere inclicitis animositatibus, armati sint*⁷⁸⁹; *fulti auctoritatibus istorum oppido sanum respondere possemus insaniae*⁷⁹⁰. The language of heresy and erroneous belief applies to this passage of the Pope's letter likewise – which thus falls in line with other written testimonials on this problematic, as discussed previously in this study. Thus, the Pope alludes to the metaphor of the venomous seeds, which the Byzantines plan to disperse all around the world, and which are particularly dangerous for the hearts of the simple: *...ut haec sua venenosi graminis semina per alias mundi partes dispergant et simpliciorum quorumque fidelium corda suis inclicitis votis incurvent*⁷⁹¹.

In an analogous manner, Ratramnus of Corbie wrote on the simple people, which are in danger of scandal. Hence, *...simplicibus minusque capacibus scandalum laesionis inferre*⁷⁹²... - argues Ratramnus, in the opening passage of his treatise composed in response to the Greek accusations pointed towards the Latins during the *Filioque* dispute.

In Hincmar's exposition on the heretics, they are described as those who damage the hearts of "the small ones" through their wicked preaching, and erase them with the sword of error: *...quoniam nimirum haeretici mentes fidelium...perverse praedicatione perimunt, et scientiae sibi nomen extendunt. Parvulorum corda, iam de verbi conceptione gravida, erroris gladio scindunt...*⁷⁹³. Gottschalk's blasphemies represent danger for the simple⁷⁹⁴. Gottschalk is dangerous for the simple people, receptive to his teachings, to whom he imposes himself as their teacher, while simulating religiosity: *...ut novitiate vocum innotesci valeret utque simplicium et devotorum sensus pervertere et magistri sibi nomen usurpando post se discipulos*

⁷⁸⁵Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 608, l. 4–6.

⁷⁸⁶Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 603, l. 15.

⁷⁸⁷Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 604, l. 3, 13.

⁷⁸⁸Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels l. 27–28; 608, l. 22.

⁷⁸⁹Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 605, l. 4–6.

⁷⁹⁰Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 605, l. 17–18; 608, l. 23.

⁷⁹¹Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 608, l. 7–9.

⁷⁹²Ratramnus, Contra Graecorum Opposita, ed. Migne 225D–226D.

⁷⁹³Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 502BC.

⁷⁹⁴Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 510CD.

*trahere illisque, qui ad sua vota auribus prurientes magistros sibi coacervare decertant, quaerere indebite, quoniam legitime non poterat, simulatione vitae religiosae et doctrina praeesse*⁷⁹⁵. Nevertheless, not only did the ignorant people find Gottschalk's teachings attractive: even those with more knowledge, and the imprudent ones, were also among his followers: *Unde non solum idiotas in admirationem sui abducere, verum et sciolos et incautos...*⁷⁹⁶.

Gottschalk was seen as a threat to the Church and to the simple ones: Hincmar equals Gottschalk's followers as *scioli*⁷⁹⁷ – the quasi-learned people – whom we can bring into connection with *insipientes*, but also with *rustici*⁷⁹⁸.

In his letter to Hincmar, Hrabanus informs him on the imminent danger of a wandering monk named Gottschalk, who spreads new superstitions and perilous doctrine of predestination, and thence, leads people into error: *Notum sit dilectione vestrae, quod quidam gyrovagus monachus nomine Goteschalc, qui se asserit sacerdotem in vestra parrochia ordinatum, de Italia venit ad nos Moguntiam novas superstitiones et noxiam doctrinam de praedestinatione dei introducens et populos in errorem mittens*⁷⁹⁹. After having presented the main points of Gottschalk's doctrine, Hrabanus argues that his teachings are dangerous, and that he should be prohibited of spreading the error and seducing the Christian people, as he had already done and seduced many; he should stay secluded in Hincmar's parish of Reims: *...decrevimus eum cum perniciose sua doctrina damnatum mittere ad vos. Quatenus eum recludatis in vestra parochia, unde primum inordinate recessit et non sinatis eum amplius errorem docere et seducere populum Christianum, quia iam multos seductos, ut audivi, habet et minus devotos erga suam salutem...*⁸⁰⁰

In Byzantium, Photius alludes to “the simple ones” (*οἱ ἀπλούστεροι*), who are induced to sin by the Paulicians⁸⁰¹. In his 16th homily, he also refers to the simple-minded people, who are seduced by the Iconoclast heresy: *...οἱ εἰκονομάχοι τὴν τῶν εἰκόνων περίγειον καὶ κάτω γραφὴν αἰτίαν πλάνης τοῖς ἀπλουστέροις ἀπήρξαντο λέγειν*⁸⁰². Theodore the Studite also writes

⁷⁹⁵ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 160, l. 17–21.

⁷⁹⁶ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 169, ed. Perels 162, l. 35.

⁷⁹⁷ Hincmar, Epistolae, ed. E. Perels, Ep. 169, 162–163.

⁷⁹⁸ Cf. Hincmar, Ad reclusos et simplices (ed. W. Gundlach, Zwei Schriften des Erzbischofs Hincmar von Reims II, Zeitschrift für Kirchengeschichte 10 [1889] 258–310).

⁷⁹⁹ Cf. MGH Conc. III, ed. Hartmann 184, l. 6–9.

⁸⁰⁰ Cf. MGH Conc. III, ed. Hartmann 184, l. 15–19.

⁸⁰¹ Photius, Contra Manichaeos, ed. Astruc et al., 129.

⁸⁰² Mango, Homilies, 16th homily 265, Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 155, l. 14–16.

on the rusticity of the heretics: *Si qui autem sunt viri ac mulieres e laicis, qui vel ob rusticitatem, vel ob innatam haeresim sint haeretici: Ἐὰν δέ εἰσιν ἄνδρες τε καὶ γυναῖκες, λαϊκοὶ, αἰρετικοὶ εἴτε ἀπὸ χωρικίας, εἴτε ἔμφυτος ἔχοντες τὴν αἴρεσιν...* The heresy emerges either out of the evil mind, or out of ignorance: they originate either *ex animi pravitate*, or *ex ignorantia*: *εἰ ἐκ κακονοίας εἰσὶν αἰρετικοὶ ... εἰ ἐξ ἀμαθίας*⁸⁰³.

In Photius's treatise against the Manichaeans, composed in 871-872, the heresiarch is portrayed as a seducer of the simple: *...ὁ πλάνος...παγιδεύων τὰς τῶν ἀπλουστέρων...ψυχὰς*⁸⁰⁴. Analogously, the best advice Peter of Sicily has for the simple ones, is to flee the society of the heretics, as if they were repulsive, and to avoid any conversation with them, because even entering into discussion with them could lead the simple people into danger: *Ἀρίστη γὰρ αὕτη μηχανὴ τοῖς ἀπλουστέροις τὸ τοῦς μιαινοῦς ἐκείνους ἀποτρέπεσθαι μὲν καὶ βδελύττεσθαι, μὴ πειρᾶσθαι δὲ ταῖς αὐτῶν πεύσεσιν ἀνταποκρίνεσθαι...μήποτε καὶ κινδυνεύσωσιν οἱ ἀπείρως πρὸς αὐτοῦς διαλεγόμενοι*⁸⁰⁵. According to Peter of Sicily, the aims of the heretics are depicted by the image of a wolf in a sheepskin, and directed towards the accusation of the truth and leading the unlearned and simple people into error: *...κατηγορεῖν τῆς ἀληθείας καὶ ἐξαπατᾶν τοὺς ἀμαθεῖς καὶ ἰδιώτας...ὡς ἐν κωδίῳ προβάτου λύκον περικαλύψαι*⁸⁰⁶. It is to the unlearned population that the Manichaeans spread their poison of evil, and the bitter root of the enemy: *...Οἱ...τοῦς...ἀμαθεῖς...τὸν ἰὸν τῆς πονηρίας καὶ τὸ πικρὸν ζιζάνιον τοῦ ἐχθροῦ ἐνέσπειραν*⁸⁰⁷. Writing on the Paulician heresy, Peter the Hegoumen exposed on some people among the Paulicians who secretly enter the Christian churches and take part in communion, in the aim of deceiving the simple ones more effortlessly: *Ἐτεροὶ δὲ εἰσερχόμενοι ἐν τῇ ἐκκλησίᾳ τῇ ἡμετέρᾳ τῶν ὀρθοδόξων λεληθότως τῶν θείων μυστηρίων μεταλαμβάνουσι, πρὸς πλείονα ἐξαπάτην τῶν ἀπλουστέρων*⁸⁰⁸.

Not only those referred to as the “simple” ones were in danger of heretical doctrines. Interestingly, in *Chronographia*, a collection of historical writings preserved under the name of Theophanus Continuatus, the Iconoclast emperors were alluded to as uncultured and unlearned,

⁸⁰³ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, *Interrogatio-Responsio* 17, ed. Migne 1665CD.

⁸⁰⁴ Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Migne 69CD.

⁸⁰⁵ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 11, 10, 12.

⁸⁰⁶ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 37, 80–81.

⁸⁰⁷ Peter of Sicily, *Histoire des Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 37, 86; 39, 86.

⁸⁰⁸ Peter the Hegoumen, *Précis sur les Pauliciens*, ed. Astruc et al. 92, 23.

in the early 9th century:...τῶν κρατησάντων ἀγροικία καὶ ἀμαθία; *humaniores literae imperatorum barbarie ac inscitia obsolevissent*⁸⁰⁹.

⁸⁰⁹ Theophanes Continuatus, in: Theophanes Continuatus, Ioannes Cameniata, Symeon Magister, Georgius Monachus, ed. I. Bekker (Bonn 1838) 3–431, here 185.

II. 8. DANGER OF SCANDAL

*...vae mundo ab scandalis necesse est enim ut veniant scandala verumtamen vae homini per quem scandalum venit*⁸¹⁰

In this chapter, the ascending line in textual treatment of religious dissent ensues: after having elaborated on “old – new” heresies, and the danger of novelties for the simple, the danger of scandal aligns as forthcoming and represents the following thread in the narratives knitted around religious dissent in 9th-century Francia and Byzantium.

At the time when the Iconoclast crisis also provoked disturbance in the West, Jonas spoke of the danger of introducing scandal⁸¹¹. Namely, scandal is closely related to heresy, and, according to Jonas’s words, he, who induces the minds of people into scandal, is estimated to be the author of schisms and superstitions: *Ille namque qui irrationabiliter subjectarum sibi plebium mentes scandalizare traditionesque ecclesiasticas tam impudenter reprehendere, et tot tantisque sanae fidei sincerissimis cultoribus abominationum nomina non metuit ascribere, nequaquam compressor, sed potius erector et auctor schismatum ac superstitionum iudicandus est*⁸¹². The semantic field of “scandal” is closely linked to the semantic field of negligence in the 9th-century Frankish narratives. The problem of negligence was addressed at the Council of Paris in 829; besides, these were crucial notions in the accusations against Louis the Pious in 833. In the *Libellus* (from the council of Paris, held in 825) the possibility of scandal arising out of the disordered situation was emphasised⁸¹³. The quarrel emerged over the question of whether the image worship could lead to scandal, according to Jonas and Walahfrid⁸¹⁴. Claudius also wrote on the danger of scandal, and of the dire consequences for him, who had led the Christians into scandal⁸¹⁵. In his answer to Theutmir’s accusations that he, Claudius, forbade believers to travel to Rome on pilgrimage, Claudius states: *Nullum scandalum maius est quam hominem illam prohibere pergere viam, per quam possit ad gaudia pergere sempiterna*⁸¹⁶.

⁸¹⁰ Cf. Mt. 18:7.

⁸¹¹ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 301; cf. Jonas, De cultu imaginum, ed. Migne 373–375B.

⁸¹² Jonas, De Cultu Imaginum, ed. Migne 314D–315A.

⁸¹³ Cf. Libellus Synodalis Parisiensis, a. 825, m. Novembri (ed. A. Werminghoff, MGH Conc. II,2, Hannover/Leipzig 1908) 473-551, here 499, 528; Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 331.

⁸¹⁴ Jonas: the image quarrel can lead to scandal, alluding to Claudius, cf. Jonas, De cultu imaginum, ed. Migne 311A, 373D-375A; Walahfridus, Libellus, ed. Boretius/Krause 483.

⁸¹⁵ By quoting Mt. 18:6.

⁸¹⁶ Cf. Claudius, Epistolae, ed. Dümmler 611; cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 304.

The sway and significance of scandal was put forward at the council of 829⁸¹⁷ – designating sin, which “disrupts a divinely sanctioned social order”⁸¹⁸. The restoration of the order implied a sharpening of the distinctions between the orders. The “dualist” order was composed of the two complementary segments – sacerdotal and royal – which were both contained in the *ecclesia*, representing the Christian polity⁸¹⁹. The “political sins” in 8th century Francia were seen as the sins which affected the entire community, related to scandal, and denoting public sins⁸²⁰.

The understanding and notion of scandal as a “public sin offensive to God and people”, followed by *correctio*, appears within a Biblical context⁸²¹. Nevertheless, the concept of *admonitio* and *negligentia* (representing the “sin of omission”) is often alluded to in the writings of the Fathers⁸²². The importance of *negligentia* is stressed in the Capitularies of Charlemagne, indicating the negligence of the office performed by the *missi*⁸²³. *Negligentia*, especially when referring to the ecclesiastical rank, represented a part of the reforms undertaken in 813⁸²⁴. Negligence of office was thus unambiguously related to scandal⁸²⁵, leading to a requirement for public penance. Negligence of leaders, for example, was referred to as *desidia*, and could have been, as with the example of the Danish king Harald, closely related to God’s punishment for the sins of the people, as a consequence of the incorrectly handled pagan incursion, occurred in 827⁸²⁶.

In his letter to Eberhard, Hrabanus says that Gottschalk’s teaching is a scandal to many in those regions. During the time Gottschalk spent on Eberhard’s court, the danger of scandal was imminent – according to Hrabanus. Namely, Hrabanus writes to Eberhard in order to help him understand that a scandal might occur in regions under Eberhard’s jurisdiction. Hrabanus warns Eberhard that he should forbid any teachings contrary to the correct faith, which may spread in those areas, so that he may leave that “sect”; the preaching of the kind might hinder

⁸¹⁷ Cf. Council of 829, ed. Werminghoff, MGH Conc. II,2, 596–597.

⁸¹⁸ Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 182; Cf. Hludowici et Hlotharii Epistola generalis, a. 828, m. Decembri (ed. Werminghoff, MGH Conc. II/2) 597–600, here 599–601.

⁸¹⁹ Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 182.

⁸²⁰ De Jong, Penitential State 232.

⁸²¹ De Jong, Penitential State 121, cf. Ezek. 14:3–4, 14:7 in King James Version, as cited in Ibid., 121, note 35, where scandal (*scandalum*) is translated as a “stumblingblock”.

⁸²² Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 121.

⁸²³ Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 121, note 36, pointing to the specific sections of the following capitularies: *Capitulare de villis*, *Capitula a missis dominicis ad comites directa* (801-813), *Capitulare missorum* (802-813), *Capitulare de latronibus* (804-813).

⁸²⁴ Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 121, note 37, referring to the Councils of Chalon, Mainz, Arles, and Tours.

⁸²⁵ De Jong, Penitential State 152.

⁸²⁶ De Jong, Penitential State 150.

the feeble ones. Hrabanus makes an appeal to Eberhard's consciousness of a Christian, underlining that it is his responsibility if he does not prohibit this doctrine of spreading, and if he stays in communion with those opposite to the Gospel, instead of supporting that which pertains to human salvation:

*Haec ergo, amice karissime, ideo tibi scripsi, ut cognosceres, quale scandalum de illis partibus opinio veniens in hoc populo generarit, et si quis iuxta te manens impudenter docet quae recte fidei sunt contraria, prohibeas eum, ut cesset ab hac secta, dicasque ei: Vide, frater, ne hac licentia tua in predicando offendiculum fiat infirmis, et tuo dogmate ne perdas eum, pro quo Christus mortuus est, quia sanguis eius requiretur de manu tua*⁸²⁷.

Nevertheless, Amolo of Lyon quotes the Scriptural verse according to which the scandal ought to occur, but woe unto the man through whom it occurs: *...necesse est ut veniant scandala, veruntamen ve homini illi, per quem scandalum venit*⁸²⁸.

In his exposition of the genuine Trinitarian credo, Hincmar refers to the ways in which heretical wording related to this issue could cause scandal, purposefully or unintentionally: *...ubi a quibusdam cantatur, vel potius blasphematur, "Te trina deitas", aut scienter aut nescienteer scandalum in Ecclesia moveant, quae aliis multis perturbationibus concutitur et vexatur: scientes quid mercatur, qui suo vitio unum scandalizaverit de pusillis credentibus, docente Paulo: "Sic autem peccantes in fratres, et percutientes conscientiam eorum infirmam, in Christum peccatis"*⁸²⁹. Therefore, Hincmar alludes to the words of St. Paul, according to which, he who scandalizes the small ones by his vice, does indeed commit sin against Christ.

Hrabanus underlines the importance of words in creating scandal: *...per verba eius scandalum...capiat*⁸³⁰. According to Amolo, the heretic's mouth is filled with bitterness – as a symbolical representation of the erroneous, sacrilegious words he utters: *Sed adhuc insuper os tuum maledictio et amaritudine plenum est*⁸³¹... Furthermore, altering words and terminology can lead to heresy. The Trinitarian Controversy demonstrate this to the fullest. The controversy was stirred up by Gottschalk's rendering of the Greek term *tritheiotheia* in Latin as *trina deitas*,

⁸²⁷ Gillis, Gottschalk of Orbais 192: *Annales Xantenses*, s.a. 848 (ed. B. von Simson, MGH SSRG XII, Hannover 1909) 16, s.a. 848; Hrabanus, *Epistolae*, Ep. 42, ed. E. Dümmler 487, l. 17–22.

⁸²⁸ Amolo, *Epistolae*, Epistola 2, ed. Dümmler 370, l. 12–13, referring to Mt. 18:7.

⁸²⁹ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 498D, cf. 1 Cor. 8:12.

⁸³⁰ Hrabanus, *Epistolae*, ed. Dümmler, Ep. 42, 487, l. 3–4, referring to Gregory the Great, *Moralia in Iob*, l. XVII, c. 26.

⁸³¹ Amolo, *Epistola* 2, ed. Dümmler 377, l. 13, referring to Rom. 3:14.

after having supported his view as orthodox by recurring to the Acts of the 6th Ecumenical Synod of Constantinople (689/681)⁸³², upon which the Monothelism had been condemned.

Additionally, the holy authority of the canons is to be acknowledged and revered; if not, such negligence represents an act against faith, which leads to scandal, Hincmar argues:

*...praesertim quia ipsa sacra auctoritas canonum, Spiritu Dei condita, et totius mundi reverentia consecrata, in Africano concilio ducentorum octo episcoporum, capite septuagesimo primo praecipit ut non preces aliae celebrentur, nisi illae quae in concilio cum prudentioribus collectae fuerint, ne forte contra fidem, quod absit, in eisdem precibus, quibus fidelis quisque debet Deo conciliari, ab aliquot proferatur, ut audientibus scandalum fiat*⁸³³.

Scandal emerges on the account of heretics: for example, in the course of the Trinitarian controversy. Furthermore, the words themselves can be bearers of the scandal in this case, Hincmar continues: *Et quia de his verbis, quae catholice a catholicis et intelliguntur et proferentur, ab haereticis, sicut et de pluribus sanctae Scripturae verbis, visa seri sunt scandala...*⁸³⁴. Those who do not believe in the word of God and Christ, prepare their own damnation; for as the incarnation, predication, miracles and death of Christ represent salvation and honor for the believers, and thence, the stone of displeasure and the pillar of scandal to the non-believers: *Qui eutem non credunt, ipsi sibi damnationem adquirunt. Nam sicut incarnatio, praedicatio, miracula, ita et mors Christi salus et honor est credentibus, non credentibus autem lapis offensionis et petra scandali*⁸³⁵.

Nevertheless, not only did dissident religious thought lead to scandal, the re-marriage of Lothar II has also provoked it: the Pope incited clerics to acknowledge the vices provoked by Lothar's affair: *recognoscite contra vitia ministerium vestrum, ipsum, per quem tantum ecclesia Dei scandalum patitur, Hlotarium scilicet regem*⁸³⁶. In the course of his narrative, the pope compares the actions of Lothar, *qui utcumque nostris studuit oboedire decretis*⁸³⁷ with *scelus*, and *crimen*⁸³⁸.

⁸³² Cf. Gottschalk, *Schedula et fragmenta* i-xi, ed. Lambot 19–36, here 23–24.

⁸³³ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 499A.

⁸³⁴ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 517BC.

⁸³⁵ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 188, ed. Perels 199, l. 19–23.

⁸³⁶ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 53, ed. Perels 349, l. 15; for more detailed analysis of the remarriage of Lothar II, see below, chapter II.9.

⁸³⁷ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 53, ed. Perels 351, l. 14–16.

⁸³⁸ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 53, ed. Perels 351, l. 21–24.

The context of scandal could also have emerged during the conflictual issues outside any given territorial domain (as shown above in respect to the case of Francia). Namely, it could have been related to the bi-lateral relations between Francia and Byzantium. During a Photian schism, which provoked conflicts between Byzantium and Rome due to the enthronement of Photius in the 860's, a set of circumstances which could have potentially led to scandal and exile was addressed, in the new political and situational context. Pope Nicholas' letter containing the indispensable information on those troubled times was written in the autumn of 866 and addressed to the bishops of the East⁸³⁹. Appeals to the *sana doctrina* of the Christian Church were made in the very title of the letter; further on, Pope Nicholas explained and enlisted events related to the condemned enthronement of Photius and claims for Ignatius's restitution. The Pope referred to Photius as a heretical patriarch: *Constantinopolitani heretici patriarchae*⁸⁴⁰, whose ecclesiastical practice and service were to be condemned, and labelled a schismatic: *ad damnatorum et schismaticorum comunem*⁸⁴¹. Photius is referred to as adulterer and invader who had banished the bishops, opposed to his enthronement and consequently, with the official policy of the Church and state: *Postremo episcopos, qui ei tamquam adultero et pervasori communicare noluerunt, exilio religavit*⁸⁴².

The cause leading to exile is hereby clearly demonstrated as a noncompliance with the official policy. In its opening chapter, the letter unambiguously presents the grounds why Photius was referred to as adulterer, as repeatedly stated on many occasions in other letters as well, and explains which occurrences can lead to scandal: led by envy and arrogance, the Byzantine ecclesiastics removed Patriarch Ignatius, *nostrum Ignatium, sanctissimum praefatae Urbis antistitem*, from patriarchal office, and enthroned Photius against the sacred canons, who came from the secular rang, which induced scandal: *...Photium quondam, ex foro ac saeculari militia et habitu atque a palatinis aedibus eductum ac subito tonsoratum, eidem contra sacros kanones ecclesiae praefecerunt, tunc coepit scandalum et schisma*⁸⁴³. Emperor Michael sent legates to Rome asking for an embassy from Rome to reach Constantinople, in order to find a solution to the schism: *...qui scandala illa sedarent et schismata dissiparent*⁸⁴⁴. The Apostolic

⁸³⁹Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 553–565.

⁸⁴⁰Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 558, l. 4.

⁸⁴¹Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 558, l. 6–7.

⁸⁴²Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 558, l. 9–11.

⁸⁴³Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 554, l. 6–12.

⁸⁴⁴Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 554, l. 15–18.

See considered its role to look after its flock, and therefore dispatched Rhadoaldus and Zaccharius to investigate the Constantinopolitan issue.

Theodore wrote in numerous epistles on scandals provoked by priest Joseph and the “Moechian Synod”⁸⁴⁵.

⁸⁴⁵ More in detail on this issue below, in chapter II.9; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 30–31, ed. Migne 1005D–1013D.

II.9. DISOBEDIENCE - A KEY CRITERION IN DEMARCATING *RECTO-* FROM THE *FALSO-DOCTI*

The remarriage of Emperor Constantine VI (780 – 797) and Lothar II (c. 835 – 869; king of Lotharingia from 855): a case in-between

In this chapter, a specific case-study of disobedience indirectly related to the textual procedures in the 9th-century Greek and Latin narratives of religious dissented is presented. The aim of this chapter is to demonstrate that disobedience represents a key-word in cases of remarriage, which have been presented here, as well as in textual treatment of the concept of religious dissent.

The divorce of Constantine VI occurred in 795⁸⁴⁶, and provoked dissent and opposition between the official church and the faction led by Theodore the Studite, thanks to whom we have the majority of the information on this issue at our disposition. The topic of the Moechian synod has been significantly discussed in the scholarship⁸⁴⁷.

The second marriage of Constantine VI has attracted scientific attention likewise⁸⁴⁸. One of the most important sources on remarriage of Constantine VI comprises numerous letters dedicated to that particular set of circumstances, written by Theodore the Studite⁸⁴⁹. It has been debated whether positions on the issue of remarriage taken in the Eastern and Western churches were analogous⁸⁵⁰. The question of divorce and re-marriage in the medieval Christian church falls into the field of canonical right, amongst other⁸⁵¹. Nevertheless, the divorce of Constantine VI is relevant to this study due to the fact that it stirred up a theological debate in Byzantium, referred to as “the Moechian controversy”, and since it offers insights into the incongruities of the hierarchical structure of the Empire. After Theodore vehemently opposed himself to the

⁸⁴⁶ cf. Theofanes, *Chronographia*, ed. Migne 943A, 946A, 946 B, 947B.

⁸⁴⁷ Cf. R. Devreesse, *Une lettre de S. Théodore Studite relative au synode moechien (809)*, in: *Analecta Bollandiana* 68 (1950) 44–57; P. Henry, *The Moechian controversy and the Constantinopolitan Synod of January A.D. 809*, in: *The Journal of Theological Studies* 20, 2 (1. October 1969) 495–522.

⁸⁴⁸ For a summary, see Dvornik, *Photian Schism* 9–12.

⁸⁴⁹ Theodore the Studite, I, Ep. 25, note 98 ed. Fatouros 167; Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 31, ed. Migne 1009A–1013D; cf. J. A. Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI y la doctrina matrimonial de San Teodoro Estudita* (Pamplona 1984) 148; Cf. Theodore the Studite, I, *Epistolae*, Ep. 28, ed. Migne 997B–1004C; on the summary of the different views on the marital unions of the time and the insolubility of marriage, cf. P. Adnes, *De indissolubilitate matrimonii apud Patres*, in: *Periodica de re morali canonica liturgica* 61 (1972) 195–223.

⁸⁵⁰ On the doctrine of the Fathers regarding the insolubility of marriage, see: Adnes, *De indissolubilitate matrimonii*; for an overview of this complex topic, see: J. Meyendorff, *Marriage: An Orthodox Perspective* (New York 2000) 16–18 (on the early church and Roman law); 44–47 (on successive marriages); 54–58 (on divorce).

⁸⁵¹ cf. Rincón, *La doctrina sobre la indisolubilidad del matrimonio en el primero milenio Cristiano*, *Ius Canonicum* 25 (1973) 91–136, cited from: Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 174, note 86.

divorce and re-marriage of Constantine VI at the very beginning of the controversy and was exiled in 797, he made peace with Constantine VI by means of mediation undertaken by his mother Irene, and then took up the positions of abbot at the monastery of Saccudion in the same year. Nevertheless, in 799, they fled the Arab incursion and came back to Constantinople and the monastery of Studion in 799, where Theodore began his flourishing activities on monastic reform and discipline⁸⁵². Furthermore, the reinforcement of monastic discipline sought to strengthen the Christian doctrine in general, in the world outside monastery as well – and there perhaps lay the seed of Theodore’s insistence upon the respect of the ecclesiastical canons in view of the remarriage of Constantine VI.

In 802, Nicephorus I (802-811) came to the Byzantine throne. Theodore proclaimed Nicephorus the new patriarch in 806. In the same year, the former priest Joseph with whose benediction the new union of Constantine VI was sealed – got rehabilitated⁸⁵³. The rehabilitation of Joseph was seen as a sign of support to the adulterous marriage. Nevertheless, Theodore undoubtedly states that his protest was not directed against emperors or the Patriarch, but, against the priest Joseph who had consecrated the adulterous union of Constantine VI and Theodote.⁸⁵⁴ Early in 809, a Synod was convened which confirmed the decisions taken at the first one in 806, and anathematized those who were against it. Consequently, Theodore and other Studites were exiled⁸⁵⁵. Theodore was exiled for two years, until 811, for being strongly opposed to the decisions taken by the Synod and the acceptance on behalf of the official church of the second marriage of Constantine VI. The controversy that arose due to this issue is called “Moechian”, as already mentioned above. Theodore returned once again to the Studion monastery upon the coronation of the new emperor, Michael I (811 – 813), which marked the end of Theodore’s second exile⁸⁵⁶. Under Michael I, the interior dispute tearing the ecclesiastical structures apart was annulled, since the Emperor definitively condemned priest Joseph and thereby established a concord between the Studites and the patriarch. Nevertheless, in 813, Michael retreated from the political scene due to the military putsch in which Leo V the Armenian was pronounced emperor.

Leo V (813 – 820) renewed the iconoclast controversy once more, and as consequence Theodore was banished again in 816, and this time for four years. When the newly-proclaimed

⁸⁵² cf. *Vita Theodori* (ed. Migne, PG 99) 114–327, here 142B, 146B.

⁸⁵³ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 30, ed. Migne 1006–1007; Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 194–195.

⁸⁵⁴ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 31, ed. Migne 1010 B.

⁸⁵⁵ *Vita Theodori*, ed. Migne 159C.

⁸⁵⁶ Theofanes, *Chronographia*, ed. Migne 990C.

emperor, Michael II, came to power in 820, he did not continue the practice of persecuting the Iconoclasts, alike his predecessor, but maintained a moderate position.

Theodore and other Iconophile monks returned from exile in 820. Therefore, it can be seen that the Moechian controversy occupied two distinct periods in the life of Theodore and the history of Byzantine church: the first period, from 795 to 797, and the second, from 806 to 811. Theodore's epistles represent one of the principle sources for the reconstruction of the divorce and re-marriage of Costantine VI. In 795, when Constantine VI sent his former spouse to a convent and re-married a new one, Patriarch Tarasius clearly stated his non-approval of the royal choice, referring to the Gospel: *Qui dimittit uxorem suam, praeterquam propter fornicationem moechatur*⁸⁵⁷ – and thereby equated the second marriage with adultery. Theodore, writing on this issue, simply describes it as being directed against the Gospels; and he, who is proceeding against the Gospels, is also acting against God: ...*ὅτι μοιχός ἐστιν, οὐδέ ὁ ἀντιπίπτων, ὅτι μὴ οὐχὶ θεομαχεῖ*⁸⁵⁸. Theodore also agrees to the words uttered by the patriarch, that the second union cannot represent more than an adultery. Theodore was opposed to the priest Joseph, as already stated, who had presided over the marital service, and to the fact that Joseph performed the Eucharist⁸⁵⁹. But also, and primarily, Theodore was in fact opposed to the transgression of the canon law, and of the evangelic precepts. It was in no way possible, according to Theodore, that this second union id considered licit⁸⁶⁰.

According to the ecclesiastical canon, the clerics who have erred against the canons, are allowed one year only during which they shall undergo excommunication to prove their innocence: *“Rursus constitutum est ut, quoties clericis convictis et confessis in aliquot crimine vel propter eorum quorum verecundiae parcitur vel propter ecclesiae opprobrium aut insolentem insultationem haereticorum atque gentilium, si forte causae suae adesse voluerint et innocentiam suam asserere, intra annum excommunicationis hoc faciant. Si vero intra annum causam suam purgare contemserit, nulla eorum vox postea penitus audiatur”*⁸⁶¹. Theodore was vehemently opposed to the impeacher of the canon law. He strived to preserve the sanctity of the ecclesiastical marriage and sought for a public penance to be undertaken by the guilty priest⁸⁶².

⁸⁵⁷ Mt. 5:32; Vita Tarasii (ed. Migne, PG 98) 1405–1910, here 1407A.

⁸⁵⁸ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 218, ed. Migne 1657 CD.

⁸⁵⁹ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 32, ed. Migne 1015C.

⁸⁶⁰ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 22, ed. Migne 978A.

⁸⁶¹ Council of Cartago, an. 401, sept., canon 79 (Concilia Africae, CCSL, ed. Ch. Munier (Turnhout 1974) 149, 203, cited from: Fuente Alonso, El divorcio de Constantino VI 155–156, note 24.

⁸⁶² Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 32, ed. Migne 1015A.

In the Greek Church, the second marriage was prohibited; nevertheless, it seems that the situation was different in the Roman West⁸⁶³. Not all the Eastern Fathers were radical and ostensibly intolerant to the issue of the second marriage. They mainly attempted to follow the precepts that had been proscribed by the Apostle Paul in his first Epistle to the Corinthians⁸⁶⁴. Penance was sometimes excluded from the usual proceedings in these cases, but at times, it included the prohibition of the Eucharist, or the communion with the church⁸⁶⁵. However, Theodore aligns with the opinion of St. Basil and even directly quotes him. According to this view and the penance it proscribes, the participants in the second marriage are prohibited from taking the Eucharist for one year. The penance changes, or, is augmented, for the third or the last marriage. In this case, the exception from the ecclesiastical rites is proscribed for the period of two years, compared to one year in case of the second marriage⁸⁶⁶. Nevertheless, Theodore adheres to the words of St. Paul, according to which the second marriage is not desirable, but tolerable⁸⁶⁷.

Nonetheless, Theodore is considerably strict and underlines the words of the Synods and the Fathers, which are opposed to the second marriage⁸⁶⁸. In fact, maybe one of the main problems which could have provoked divergent opinions posed the fact, that the second and other successive marriages in Constantinople appeared to have obtained sacerdotal benediction from the second half of the 8th century⁸⁶⁹. And it was that point precisely which constituted the principle line of Theodore's incessant counter-reaction and disagreement, making him one of the most arduous opponents of the practice of the second-marriage. However, it is important to emphasise the fact that, in the theological writings produced in Byzantium, a difference between the second or successive marriage and adulterous marriages did exist, in spite of the fact that this conceptual differentiation has not always clearly been explained in the sources⁸⁷⁰.

⁸⁶³ R. Guiland, *Les noces plurales à Byzance*, *Études Byzantines* (Paris 1959) 233–261; on the ecclesiastical regulations on marriage from the 8th to the mid-9th century, see: K. Heidecker, *The Divorce of Lothar II: Christian Marriage and Political Power in the Carolingian World*, transl. from the Dutch, Tanis M. Guest (New York 2010) 11–35.

⁸⁶⁴ chapter 7; on the brief outline of the position of the Byzantine authors, as well as of the councils, on that issue, see: Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 160–164.

⁸⁶⁵ Cf. on this canon, see: P. E. Joannou, *Fontes* (Roma 1962) I, 2, 130, cited from: Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 160, note 44.

⁸⁶⁶ Fuentes Alonso, *El Divorcio de Constantino VI* 167; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 21, ed. Migne 1091CD; Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 50, ed. Migne 1093B.

⁸⁶⁷ Cf. I Cor. 7, 7–9; Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 161, see esp. note 46.

⁸⁶⁸ Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI*, 167; cf. Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 50, ed. Migne 1092CD.

⁸⁶⁹ cf. K. Ritzer, *Le mariage dans les Églises Chrétiennes* (Paris 1970) 210, cited from: Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 165, note 64.

⁸⁷⁰ Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 171–172.

Numerous letters in which Theodore thoroughly addresses the question of the second marriage have been preserved⁸⁷¹. Basically, Theodore adheres to the Bible and the canonical tradition, and promulgates this precept⁸⁷². The third and fourth marriages were prohibited by the law⁸⁷³.

The fathers of the church were slightly divided on the issue of the second marriage: some proscribed it vehemently, while others did not find it desirable, but, nevertheless, did not condemn it neither. Penance was installed, in view of the second marriage, although it differed slightly from canon to canon (cf. the Council of Laodicea in 380, which acknowledged the second marriage, under condition that it had been performed according to the canons, and only after a certain amount of time had elapsed⁸⁷⁴). Some canons proposed a middle ground between views considered too strict, or too lax: a moderate penitence was to be undertaken by those who concluded the second marriage⁸⁷⁵. Theodore, nevertheless, supports a rather strict option, including penance as well⁸⁷⁶. Despite this, the official stance on remarriage underwent considerable changes in the 6th century, when the practice of remarrying came to be accepted⁸⁷⁷. On what concerns the divergences in this respect – of the matrimonial doctrine between the Eastern and Western churches, these can be dated to the 9th century, according to some authors⁸⁷⁸.

In order to examine the practice itself of re-marriage and to conclude who had the authority over marriage and remarriage, Theodore refers mostly to the Prophets and to the Gospels in the first place, by citing examples according to which God's words are opposed to the dissolution of marriage and to the remarriage⁸⁷⁹. It is important to say, that Theodore's aspirations to delve into this problem emerged out of the particular case of the re-marriage of Constantine VI, who, having expelled the legitimate spouse, has welcomed the adulterous one - *legitima ejecta, moecham induxit* - ...ἐπὶ τῇ ἐκβολῇ τῆς νομίμου, καὶ εἰσοικίσει τῆς μοιχαλίδος⁸⁸⁰. It was exactly by referring to the Scriptural truth that Theodore prepared his opposition upon the Synod of

⁸⁷¹ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne, 903–1679, here: Ep. I 50, 1090–1095; II 191, 1581; II 201, 1616.

⁸⁷² Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 21, ed. Migne 1091A.

⁸⁷³ Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 172–173.

⁸⁷⁴ Cf. Canon 1, *Fontes*, t. 1, 2, 130, cited from: Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 160, note 44.

⁸⁷⁵ Cf. L. Godefroy, *Dictionnaire de Théologie Catholique* 9 (Paris 1909 -) Mariage, 2096–2098, here 2096, cited from: Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 161, note 45.

⁸⁷⁶ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 22, ed. Migne 978A.

⁸⁷⁷ P. Adnes, *Le mariage* 66, cited from: Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI* 174–175, note 89.

⁸⁷⁸ Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI*, 174–5.

⁸⁷⁹ Fuentes Alonso, *El divorcio de Constantino VI*, 177; Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 196, ed. Migne 1595A.

⁸⁸⁰ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 34, ed. Migne 1024B.

809, which supported the dissolution of the first Constantine's marriage⁸⁸¹. According to St. Basil's canon, as referred to by Theodore, the sin of adultery is equal to that of homicide: *adulteriumque sit grave peccatum homicidae par* - ...μοιχεία δὲ τὸ χαλεπὸν ἀμάρτημα, καὶ ἰσοδύναμον φονέως⁸⁸².

The divorce-case and the remarriage of Lothar II in the West was preserved in exhaustive source material, and written testimonies of Hincmar of Reims and Pope Nicholas I. This event occurred in the Frankish realm has awakened interest in recent scholarship, just as it did in the late-ninth century when it occurred⁸⁸³.

Numerous epistles written by Pope Nicholas dealt with remarriage of Lothar II and issues directly or indirectly related to it, or provoked by it: from the excommunication of the two archbishops, to act of disobedience and disrespect towards the ecclesiastical canons⁸⁸⁴.

Similarly to the request of Theodore the Studite, according to which the priest Joseph should be excommunicated due to the fact that he had blessed the illicit union of Constantine VI with his new spouse, Pope Nicholas I ordered the archbishops Guntharius and Theutgaudus, to be expelled from Church, together with other clerics who had participated in the unlawful remarriage of Lothar II in the West⁸⁸⁵. It was at the same time that the Pope had to tackle the Ignatian issue as well – at the Synod held in Rome in November, when Photius, considered by the Annales as *quidam laicus attonsus*, replaced Ignatius on the patriarchal throne⁸⁸⁶.

As already mentioned, Pope Nicholas composed many letters directly or indirectly related to the divorce of Lothar II⁸⁸⁷. The key argument the Pope wished to underline in his letters was the importance of discipline in questions regarding the insolubility of marriage – and even before the case of Lothar II came to pass. Namely, Ingiltrud, wife of count Boso, had abandoned her husband for another; the Pope ordered the bishops in the realm of Charles the

⁸⁸¹ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 34, ed. Migne 1022D–1023A.

⁸⁸² Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 31, ed. Migne 1012CD.

⁸⁸³ Heidecker, *The Divorce of Lothar II*, 36–50; 63–99; S. Airlie, *Private bodies and the body politic in the divorce case of Lothar II*, in: *Past and Present* (1/11/1998) 161 (1) 3–38; R. Stone/Ch. West, trans & ed., *The Divorce of King Lothar and Queen Theutberga: Hincmar of Rheims's De divortio* (Manchester 2016).

⁸⁸⁴ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 29, ed. Perels 295–297 (an. 864); *Annales Bertiniani*, ed. G. Waitz 73–74.

⁸⁸⁵ *Annales Bertiniani*, ed. Waitz 74.

⁸⁸⁶ *Annales Bertiniani*, ed. Waitz 73–74; on the excommunication of the archbishops of Trier and Metz, see: *Annales Fuldenses*, a. 863, ed. Kurze 58–61.

⁸⁸⁷ To mention only some: Nicholas, *Epistolae*, ed. Perels, Ep. 9, 10, 13, 14, 20–32, 35, 37–39, 41, 42, 45–49, 51–53; cf. Heidecker, *The Divorce of Lothar II* 149–172.

Bald (king of the West Francia 843 – 877) to excommunicate her. The pope had divergences in opinion with bishops of Lotharingia regarding the insolubility of marriage. A short time afterwards, King Lothar II broke his marital union with his legitimate wife Teutberga in order to marry Waldrada⁸⁸⁸. The dispute between the Pope and the bishops arose when the bishops of Lotharingia, at the Synod of Aachen in 862, approved of this union – even if it was clearly opposed to the ecclesiastical canons, similarly to the situation in Byzantium emerged upon the remarriage of Constantine VI and the priest Joseph who blessed this new, albeit illicit union. However, at the Synod in Metz held the next year, Theutberga was condemned. The two archbishops, Guntharius of Cologne and Theutgaudus of Trier, were also condemned and removed from office at the Lateran Synod of 863⁸⁸⁹. Nevertheless, they retook their functions at the order of Lothar II.

In Lothar's case, Hincmar and Pope Nicholas protected the interests of Theutberga and were opposed to Lothar's planned divorce. In his effort to obtain divorce from Theutberga, Lothar accused her of having had an incestuous relationship with Hugobert. After having sought and obtained the support of Charles the Bald, and after having proven her innocence, Lothar was obliged to take her back; nevertheless, he imprisoned her, and finally it was Theutberga who asked to be divorced from Lothar, in order to be accepted into the monastery. Hincmar continued to defend Theutberga's case and to accuse Lothar vehemently. In 862, a synod called by Lothar annulled the marriage. Lothar consequently married Waldrada. The synod held in the following year proclaimed Lothar's union with Waldrada lawful. The marriage with Theutberga has thus become invalid. Pope Nicholas objected to Lothar's remarriage and convoked a Lateran Synod, which annulled the decisions taken upon the synods called by Lothar; the bishops who were present were deposed, and Lothar was demanded to renew his union with Theutberga. Lothar acted in accordance with the decrees of Pope Nicholas in 865. Lothar continued to plead his case and desire to dissolve this union; the Pope remained firm and sustained that Lothar could not have remarried even if Theutberga had entered into the convent. The case did not end in Lothar's favor, who died in 869, without having succeeded in his intentions.

In his letters pertaining to the questions threaded around Lothar's remarriage, Pope Nicholas expounded on Theutberga and Waldrada, underlining the sanctity of marriage by alluding to the relevant Biblical passages, as well as to both Jerome and to Pope Gregory the

⁸⁸⁸ Cf. Heidecker, *The Divorce of Lothar II*, 100–148.

⁸⁸⁹ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 29, ed. Perels 295–297.

Great⁸⁹⁰. Lothar had been called to rectify his actions on numerous occasions, and to reunite with Theutberga⁸⁹¹. The important point to note is that some of the key-words of the Pope's letters revolving around Lothar's re-marriage are closely linked to the semantic field of (dis)obedience.

In his 30th letter, dating from the autumn of 864, and addressed to the bishop of Tongres⁸⁹², Pope Nicholas writes of disobedience, and of the limbs of "the Prostitute", which should be cut off. The Pope opens his narrative with an event from the past, dating to the time of Pope Leo, in which the performer of the scandal was "amputated"⁸⁹³. Pope Nicholas continues further on, and relates information regarding the archbishop Guntharius, who was disobedient: *...apostolicis institutis inoboediens erat*⁸⁹⁴. He ends his letter with the hortative formula, advising the bishop to cut off his flesh, and the limb of the *meretrix*, if necessary: *Quod aegre nullatenus potestis, nisi carnem suam, quam odio habens contra apostolum a se proicit, reciso membro meretricis nostro et vestro iudicio hortatus etsi non sponte, saltem invitus receperit*. We can clearly observe the identical language employed in the Latin passages, as well as in Photius's texts: the Deceiver, or "the Prostitute"; the limbs/members of the body which should be cut off – as Hincmar states likewise. This metaphor, contained in both, Latin and Greek texts, represents an excerpt from the New Testament⁸⁹⁵. Furthermore, the Pope continues, Lothar should repent; otherwise, he would be excommunicated⁸⁹⁶: *Quodsi venire distulerit et a praesentia se synodali praesentibus legatis nostris subduxerit et ad poenitentiam ac satisfactionem repedare minime curaverit, ita ut praesentialiter ad synodum coram missis nostris satisfactorius et a scelere recessurus occurrat, illum de cetero excommunicatum reddemus et, quamdiu in hoc permanserit, a totius ecclesiae consortio faciemus exortem*⁸⁹⁷. This topic is a recurrent one in Pope Nicholas's letters, since he was one of the principle characters included in Lothar's case. Lothar's divorce and remarriage falls into the vast field of issues related to obedience and disobedience to ecclesiastical canons: it was according to the church rite and authority that Lothar II had married his first wife – *secundum canonicam*

⁸⁹⁰ e.g. Nicholas, *Epistolae*, ed. Perels, Ep. 42, 315–316; Ep. 45, 319–322; Ep. 46, 322–325; cf. 1 Cor. 7:4; Mt. 19:16.

⁸⁹¹ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, ed. Perels, Ep. 48, 329–322; Ep. 49, 332–334; Ep. 51, 334–338; Ep. 53, 340–351.

⁸⁹² *Franconus Tungrensus*, cf. Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 30, ed. Perels 297–298; *Annales Bertiniani*, ed. Waitz 73–74, an. 864.

⁸⁹³ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 30, ed. Perels 298, l. 6.

⁸⁹⁴ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 30, ed. Perels 298, l. 12–13.

⁸⁹⁵ Eph. 5:29.

⁸⁹⁶ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 6, ed. Perels 275–6.

⁸⁹⁷ Nicholas, *Nicolai I Papae epistolae de rebus Franciae*, Ep. 10, 276, l. 14–18, in: *Epistolae ad Divortium Lotharii II regis pertinentes* (ed. E. Dümmler, MGH, Epp. VI) 207–240.

*auctoritatem*⁸⁹⁸. Analogously, the topic of the observance of the canons is often the axis of Theodore's letters as well, especially those relevant to the Moechian Synod, as already demonstrated above.

The importance of disobedience is stressed in the following pages: Cleric Hilduin took the administration of the church of Cambrai (*Camaracensis ecclesia*), in spite of the fact that it lay in Hincmar's jurisdiction. The Pope was severely opposed to this act: *Nam si hanc nostram praeceptionem apostolicam contempseritis, scitote vos pro inoboedientia et pro consilii pestiferi veneno, quo iam fatum regem saepe inflicitis, a nostra communione penitus submovendos*⁸⁹⁹. Those who abide by Hildouin and his decision, against the ecclesiastical canons, should be excommunicated from the ecclesiastical unity and communion⁹⁰⁰. He, who adheres to those who are against God, tears apart the limbs of Christ and transform them into the limbs of the *meretrix: qui dissociatur a Deo et carnem suam odio habens tollit membra Christi et facit ea membra meretricis*⁹⁰¹. He who acts against the ecclesiastical decrees, should not participate in the church communion⁹⁰². The same semantic pattern is employed here as in Photius's letters (homilies): the both ecclesiastics cite Biblical verses⁹⁰³ referring to "the Prostitute".

The symbolism of the limbs/members of the body of the Church reappears again in this narrative on Lothar's divorce, with allusion to New Testament verses⁹⁰⁴: *qui dissociatur a Deo et carnem suam odio habens tollit membra Christi et facit ea membra meretricis*⁹⁰⁵. It is unambiguously implied that the roots of this disassociation of God's body lay in Lothar's disobedience to the rules: *...normae iustitiae non oboedierit*⁹⁰⁶. Furthermore, if Lothar fails to act according to Pope's precepts – *contra decreta nostra* - he should be deprived of communion⁹⁰⁷. The narrative on the limbs of the body, *membra*, and the *caput*, continues further on – through the allusion to Isaiah 9:14,15⁹⁰⁸. The question of obedience seem to re-emerge repeatedly; speaking of Lothar's case, the Pope refers to the words of the apostle which instruct

⁸⁹⁸ Nicholas, *Epistolae de rebus Franciae*, Ep. 11, ed. Dümmler 277, l. 22.

⁸⁹⁹ Nicholas, *Epistolae de rebus Franciae*, Ep. 13, ed. Dümmler 280, l. 8–10.

⁹⁰⁰ Nicholas, *Epistolae de rebus Franciae*, Ep. 13, ed. Dümmler 280, l. 16.

⁹⁰¹ Nicholas, *Epistolae de rebus Franciae*, Ep. 26, ed. Dümmler 290, l. 6–7.

⁹⁰² Nicholas, *Epistolae de rebus Franciae*, Ep. 26, ed. Dümmler 290, l. 30–33.

⁹⁰³ 1 Cor. 6:15.

⁹⁰⁴ Eph. 5:29 and 1. Cor. 6:15.

⁹⁰⁵ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 26, ed. Perels 291, l. 6–7.

⁹⁰⁶ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 26, ed. Perels 291, l. 8.

⁹⁰⁷ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 26, ed. Perels 291, l. 30–33.

⁹⁰⁸ Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 53, ed. Perels 347, l. 8–17.

a person to avoid him, who does not obey the word of the epistle: *...si quis, inquit, non oboedierit verbo nostro per epistolam, hunc notate et non commisceamini cum eo*⁹⁰⁹.

The Pope clearly demands from Lothar to repent and show obedience⁹¹⁰. Lothar is called *ad correctionem et oboedientiam*⁹¹¹. The disobedience represents immense evil, similar to the crime of idolatry, the Pope says: *Nam inoboedientia tam horrendum malum est, ut idolatriae merito comparetur dicente Samuhele: “Quasi peccatum ariolandi est repugnare et quasi scelus idolatriae nolle acquiescere, unde merito apostolus ait: ‘In promptu habentes ulcisci omnem inoboedientiam’*⁹¹².

Pope Nicholas expounds also on the topic of the obedience to the king, on several occasions: *...quid ei prodest regnum terrenum, qui perdit aetherium*⁹¹³.

Second marriages of Lothar II and Constantine VI in relation to dissenting practice

The discussion of these two events, related to the second marriage of Lothar II in Francia and the other to that of Constantine VI in Byzantium during the 9th century, undoubtedly indicates that each falls within a narrative of (dis)obedience (in both cases, to the ecclesiastical canons). Unlike the example in Francia, the remarriage of Constantine VI in Byzantium has been labeled a heresy, having led to the strong opposition in the ranks of the church, under the lead of Theodore the Studite. On the other hand, from the above-cited and analyzed extracts, there is no suggestion to indicate that the Pope labelled Lothar II a heretic. That also represents one of the important differences between these divorce cases in Francia and in Byzantium: namely, the divorce case in Byzantium was labelled a heresy, but the similar situation in Francia was not.

Moreover, the ruler's part is significant in maintaining discipline - by means of presenting a sound model for his subjects⁹¹⁴. Namely, this act of remarriage was considered devious, and it

⁹⁰⁹ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 35, ed. Perels 306, l. 36–37, alluding to 2. Thes. 3:14.

⁹¹⁰ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 38, ed. Perels 311, l. 19–30.

⁹¹¹ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 53, ed. Perels 340–351.

⁹¹² in alluding to 1. Reg. 15:23, and 2. Cor. 10:6, Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 53, ed. Perels 344, l. 18-21.

⁹¹³ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 26, ed. Perels 291, l. 4–5; Ep. 31, ed. Perels 299.

⁹¹⁴ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 31, ed. Migne 1014A.

was for that reason that this act of Constantine VI was considered dangerous – since it offered a bad model to his subjects.

Nevertheless, in both cases we witness to the requests for excommunication of the priests who had presided over the respective second marital unions. The rulers who performed the second marriages against the canonical practices did not suffer consequences in person; on the other hand, it was the priests involved in these cases who were excommunicated⁹¹⁵. Furthermore, the Pope criticizes the afore-mentioned Guntharius and Theutgaudius due to the affair including Waldrada and Theutberga⁹¹⁶. Pope Nicholas I strived to excommunicate archbishops Theutgaudus and Guntharius, who were involved in the irregular marriage – in a manner that was similar to Theodore’s demand for the excommunication of the priest Joseph who performed the illicit union of Constantine VI.

Are we witnessing here to the sort of “transferral” of sin of disobedience from the rulers - who were the ones actually disobedient - to the ecclesiastics who presided over the *secundae nuptiae*? Moreover, the very important point to observe is that in the accounts knitted around the events related to the the remarriages of the two rulers, the same pattern prevails: disobedience, reflected in these factual practices of remarriage leads to scandal and to the severance of the limbs of the church.

⁹¹⁵ for example, Pope Nicholas forbids Louis the German to reconstitute Guntharius and Theutgaudus: Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 52, ed. Perels 338–339, who acted *contra sacras canones et praecipue Nicenos*, cf. Id., Ep. 53, ed. Perels 342, l. 25.

⁹¹⁶Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 53, ed. Perels 347.

II.10. IN THE QUEST FOR UNITY

In this chapter, the analysis of the bodily symbolism ensues, and knitting of threads intertwined in the research segment here-presented – this time with the chosen narratives in Greek and Latin, pertaining to the unity symbolism (mainly those relevant to the domain of Church and state). Likewise, the pivotal semantic fields encompassing the employment of the metaphor for the Church as the Bride of Christ will be analyzed and put forward.

II.10.1. *Nubia Christi* versus *Meretrix*: The bodily unity symbolism on the internal plane

*...Solliciti servare unitatem spiritus in vinculo pacis / unum corpus et unus spiritus sicut vocati estis in una spe vocationis vestrae / unus Dominus una fides unum baptismum / unus Deus et Pater omnium qui super omnes et per omnia et in omnibus nobis*⁹¹⁷.

According to Isidore of Seville, the believers represent the limbs of Christ's body: *Membra quippe Christi fideles sunt populi, quos, dum ea potestate quam accipiunt optime regunt, bonam utique vicissitudinem Deo largitori restituunt*⁹¹⁸.

Augustine's reference to Biblical quotations, given in the aim of expressing and underlining the bodily symbolism, has significantly influenced the Carolingian thinkers.

Augustine refers to the Scriptures, in his narrative on the constructing of the body of Christ, through the unity in faith, with Christ representing the head of the body. According to the apostolic doctrine, the church represents Christ's body, Augustine ensues⁹¹⁹. The entire body is joined in unity. The perfect man is, hence, contained in all his limbs and head; thus is the church

⁹¹⁷ Ephes. 4:3–6, Vulgata; “Endeavouring to keep the unity of the Spirit in the bond of peace. / There is one body, and one Spirit, even as ye are called in one hope of your calling; / One Lord, one faith, one baptism, / one God and Father of all, who is above all, and through all, and in you all”, King James Version. Numerous Scriptural verses point to the bodily unity symbolism, e.g. Mt. 18:12, Luke 15:4, Rom. 12:5, 1. Cor. 8:6; 2 Cor. 11:4.

⁹¹⁸ Isidore of Seville, *Sententiarum Libri Tres* (ed. Migne, PL 83) 537–738, here 721.

⁹¹⁹ Augustine, *De doctrina Christiana*, ed. Daur/Martin 15.

being constructed. It is through Christ that the entire body is conjoined, through the activity of each and every limb⁹²⁰.

The construct of unity, achieved through the limbs of the body, is opposed to the notion of the heretics, which are torn from the body of believers. He, who is in the unity of the body of Christ, is among the Christian believers, by having assured his participation in the sacraments – namely, in partaking of Christ’s blood and body. Nonetheless, the heretics and schismatics are severed from this bodily unity.

*Qui ergo est in eius corporis unitate, id est, in Christianorum compage membrorum, cuius corporis sacramentum fideles communicantes de altari sumere consuerunt, ipse vere dicendus est manducare corpus Christi et bibere sanguinem Christi. Ac per hoc haeretici et schismatici ab huius unitate corporis separati possunt idem percipere sacramentum, sed non sibi utile, immo vero etiam noxium, quo iudicentur gravius, quam vel tardius liberentur. Non sunt quippe in eo vinculo pacis, quod illo exprimitur sacramento*⁹²¹.

The sin is greater for him, Augustine argues, who had once been in the church and deserted it, than for him, who had never been a part of it. Those who have fallen either in heresy or in the pagan superstition, have fallen out of the body of Christ. Heresiarchs are those who were the founders of impious heresies, having stepped out of the Church.

*Sed rursus etiam isti, qui recte intellegunt, non dicendum esse manducare corpus Christi, qui in corpore non est Christi, non recte promittunt eis, qui vel in haeresim vel etiam in gentilium superstitionem ex illius corporis unitate labuntur...qui haereses impias condiderunt exeuntes de catholica Ecclesia et facti sunt haesiarchae...cum peior sit utique desertor fidei et ex desertore oppugnator eius effectus quam ille, qui non deseruit quod numquam tenuit*⁹²².

According to Augustine, the limbs of Christ or the limbs of a prostitute: one cannot participate in both. He, who partakes of Christ’s flesh and blood, remains in him, as the Apostle says. Therefore, those who become the limbs of the prostitute, do not represent limbs of Christ, unless they repent:

⁹²⁰ Augustine, *De Civitate Dei* (ed. Migne, PL 41) 13–804, here XXII, 779; Id., *De Civitate Dei XI-XXII* (ed. B. Dombart/A. Kalb, CCSL 48, Turnhout 1955) XXII, 837.

⁹²¹ Augustine, *De Civitate Dei*, XXI, ed. Migne 741; Id., ed. Dombart/Kalb 794.

⁹²² Augustine, *De Civitate Dei*, XXI, ed. Migne 741–742; ed. Dombart/Kalb 794–796.

*Ut enim alia taceam, non possunt simul esse et membra Christi et membra meretricis-(1 Cor. 6:15)...corpus Christi manducare et eius sanguinem bibere; hoc est enim in Christo manere, ut in illo maneat et Christus...Non itaque manent in Christo, qui non sunt membra eius. Non sunt autem membra Christi, qui se faciunt membra meretricis, nisi malum illud paenitendo esse destiterint et ad hoc bonum reconciliatione redierint*⁹²³.

The body of Church is opposed to the devil and his body, Augustine underlines. The devil represents the head of the impious ones, who constitute his body, and are doomed to the eternal fire; on the other hand, the image of Christ, who is the head of the Church, leads those who shall enter in the heavenly glory: *Est enim et ipse caput impiorum, qui sunt eius quodam modo corpus, ituri cum illo in suplicium ignis aeterni, sicut Christus caput est ecclesiae, quod est corpus eius futurum cum illo in regno et gloria sempiterna*⁹²⁴.

Walahfridus translates *basilica* as *domus regia*, because therein is the service to the king of kings is performed, and because the kings and priests, designating the limbs of the Most Holy king and priest, who govern the motions of the limbs and offer spiritual sacrifices to God, are regenerated therein by water and spirit and nurtured with salvific dogma: *...regi regum in ea servitur, vel quia reges et sacerdotes, id est summi regis et sacerdotis membra, qui motibus corporis imperant et spiritalis hostias immolant Deo, ibi regenerantur ex aqua et spiritu et salutari nutriuntur doctrina*⁹²⁵. Walahfridus presented a more detailed outlook on the symbolism of bodily parts in the 32nd chapter of his *Libellus*. This passage explores the parallelism of the *officia*, ecclesiastical and lay. Walahfridus finishes the 32nd chapter on a high note, as the bearer of a strong message on the unity of the orders, metaphorically seen as the limbs of the body – which compose the *domus Dei* from the opening chapter of his *Libellus*:

*Ceterum ex utriusque ordinis coniunctione et dilectione una domus Dei contruitur, unum corpus Christi efficitur cunctis membris officiorum suorum fructus mutuae utilitati conferentibus...et cetera in ceteris, ut non sit scisma in corpore*⁹²⁶, *sed si gloriatur unum membrum, congaudeant omnia membra; si contristatur unum, cuncta condoleant. Ista convenientia eo usque tenenda est, donec occurramus omnes in virum perfectum*⁹²⁷, *ut sit Deus*

⁹²³ Augustine, *De Civitate Dei*, XXI, ed. Migne 742–743; *Ibid.*, ed. Dombart/Kalb 795–797.

⁹²⁴ Augustine, *De doctrina Christiana*, ed. Daur/Martin 114.

⁹²⁵ Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 479, l. 6–9.

⁹²⁶ Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 516, l. 16–25; Cf. 1 Cor. 12:25–27.

⁹²⁷ Cf. Ephes. 4:13.

*omnia in omnibus*⁹²⁸. In this concluding and very effective passage, Walahfridus unambiguously insists upon the unity of the members (limbs): *una domus – unum corpus Christi* which is achieved by the joint structure of the limbs of the offices – *cunctis membris officiorum suorum*, functioning in the aim of mutual utility – *fructus mutuae utilitati conferentibus*. Nevertheless, the question of whether Walahfridus alluded to the Unitarian aspirations of the Carolingian realms of the time has been debated⁹²⁹. Analogously, the question of the ecclesiastical and secular hierarchies of office has been enhanced in another work of this prominent Carolingian writer and theologian, entitled *De exordiis et incrementis quarundam in observationibus ecclesiasticis rerum*, composed between the years 840 and 842⁹³⁰.

With the words on the schism taken from the Pauline Epistle⁹³¹, one may grasp the idea that the meaning of the term in this context is not exclusively related to the theological, namely heretical issues, but that it rather pertains to every dividing element.

Apart from the 8th chapter of his *Libellus de exordiis et incrementis quarundam in observationibus ecclesiasticis rerum*, expounding on the echoes that the Iconoclast crisis had had in the Frankish West, the most important section for this work is undoubtedly his 32nd chapter, on the comparison between the *ordines ecclesiasticorum* and *saeculorum*. In this chapter, Walahfridus offers a view of a graded, ordered social universe which surrounded him – of secular and ecclesiastical *dignitates, ordines, officia* or *potestates*⁹³² – and one may assume that these terms were used as synonyms. He opens his narrative by expressing his intention to compare these two domains, in respect to their relevant sub-structures as knitted by their inherent *ordines*, in the aim of *ut ostendamus ordinationes mundanae sapientiae in spiritalem ecclesiae...commutatas in similitudinem antiquae hystoriae*⁹³³. Walahfridus begins with referring to the examples from the Old Testament and to the events which had occurred in Egypt, then continues with the Roman period. He smoothly aligns the threads of the narrative on the *summus pontifex* and on the Carolingian times: *...ita summus pontifex in sede Romana vicem beati Petri gerens totius ecclesiae apice sublimatur*⁹³⁴. Walahfridus enlists the two other most important ecclesiastical Sees, the Antiochene and the Alexandrian one. Together with the

⁹²⁸ Cf. 1 Cor. 15:28.

⁹²⁹ S. Airlie, The aristocracy in the service of the state in the Carolingian period, in: Staat im frühen Mittelalter, ed. W. Pohl/H. Reimitz/S. Airlie (Wien 2006) 93–111.

⁹³⁰ Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause, translation in: Harting-Correa, Walahfrid Strabo's *Libellus de exordiis*; Cf. Airlie, Aristocracy in the service of the state, 97–100.

⁹³¹ Cf. 1 Cor. 12:25–27.

⁹³² Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 514, l. 21–24.

⁹³³ Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 514, l. 31–33.

⁹³⁴ Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 515, l. 3–5.

Church of Rome, these two have been elected by the Nicaean Council as the preeminent ones. Walahfridus continues and exposes on the hierarchical structure of the ecclesia and the state, in a descending line. Similarly, in his *De Institutione Regia*, Jonas of Orléans elaborates on the sacerdotal and royal functions⁹³⁵.

Jonas also writes on the limbs of the devil, which are constituted by those who have fallen out of the ecclesiastical authority, after having recurred to heresy, schism, or other error, pointing also to the offenders and aggressors, who are, like the unbelievers – the Jews, or demons - led by the impure spirit: *...potius diaboli membra vocandi sint, utrumne illi qui nec haeresi, nec schismate, nec alio quolibet errore ab ecclesiastica auctoritate scinduntur....Insultatores, imo impugnatores, merito diaboli membra appellari, alteri hujusmodi erroribus subactae...more infidelium Judaeorum, daemoniacum, quod utique illorum proprium est, eorumque qui spiritu agitantur immundo*⁹³⁶...

During the peak of the Iconoclast controversy in the Carolingian realm, Claudius defends his view against the icon veneration in 825, and denies that he is a leader of some new sect, arisen against the Catholic church. Furthermore, Claudius suggests, that those who constitute the very limbs of the devil themselves – with the devil as their head - may well be the ones who accuse him of that: *...quasi ego sectam quandam novam praedicaverim contra regulam fidei catholicae. Nec mirum est, sit de me ista dixerunt diaboli membra, qui ipsum caput nostrum et seductorem et daemoniacum proclamaverunt*⁹³⁷.

Dungal Scott, in his *Responsa* against the Iconoclast stance of Claudius, written in 827, equally mentions the head – more precisely, of the head of a viper, to which Felix of Urgell is metaphorically compared to. Moreover, Dungal compares Claudius to the impiety of Felix⁹³⁸.

Hincmar also emphasizes the importance of unity: unity of the church, as well as of the empire – since there is only one faith, one baptism, one kingdom, one church, one Christian law.⁹³⁹

⁹³⁵ Cf. Jonas, *De Institutione Regia*, I (ed. Migne, PL 106) 279C–306A, at 285B; on the concept of social order, see: G. Constable, *Three Studies in Medieval Religious and Social Thought: The Interpretation of Mary and Marthe; The Ideal of the Imitation of Christ; The Orders of Society* (Cambridge 1998) 249–360, and especially 256–276.

⁹³⁶ Jonas, *De Cultu Imaginum*, ed. Migne 313CD.

⁹³⁷ Claudius, *Epistolae*, Ep. 12, ed. Dümmler 610.

⁹³⁸ Dungal Scott, *Epistolae*, Ep. 3, ed. Dümmler 584.

⁹³⁹ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii Regis et Theutbergae Reginae* (ed. L. Böhringer, MGH Conc.4, Suppl.1, Hannover 1992) 99–261, here 236: *...unus dominus, una fides, unum baptisma, unus deus et pater omnium...unum regnum, una Christi columba, videlicet sancta ecclesia, unius Christianitatis lege, regni unius et unius ecclesiae.*

By citing the words of St. Cyprian, Hincmar glorifies ecclesiastical discipline, which is compared to a tunic covering Christ's body, whose head is the head of the Church.⁹⁴⁰ Discipline signifies, for Hincmar, the binding power of social cohesion among the *populus Christianus*, with the emphasis on the role of the king to correct injustice.⁹⁴¹ The importance then lies in correcting erroneous authority and preserving those, who are just.⁹⁴² God abides above every ruler.⁹⁴³ The king is subjected only to God and to His laws, who provided for him to become a ruler,⁹⁴⁴ whereas only God can judge the king, and not the bishops, since he is subjected to God only; the king's heart is in God's hand and God directs it.⁹⁴⁵ Hincmar then continues his narrative by alluding to the Old Testament verse, according to which the king should obey the sacerdotal authorities (and he implies that it is of higher importance than the royal one⁹⁴⁶) – since the members of the sacerdotal authority are responsible for the king's soul before God.⁹⁴⁷ However, interestingly, Hincmar implies that it is through the ecclesiastics that God recognizes justice.⁹⁴⁸ He refers to Augustine when speaking of erroneous action: the negligence of the discipline is therein crucial.⁹⁴⁹ Hincmar's "triad" is: the authority of order – the dignity of power – the strength of virtue.⁹⁵⁰ The people are lacking discipline, as a result of actions undertaken by a neglectful bishop, and people are lacking laws, due to the viciousness of an unrighteous king.⁹⁵¹ For Hincmar, the episcopal authority and royal dignity are pivotal:

⁹⁴⁰ Hincmar, *De regis persona* (ed. Migne, PL 125) 833–856, here 850: *Sicut enim tunica totum corpus tegitur praeter caput, ita disciplina omnis Ecclesia, praeter Christum, quia Ecclesia et sub disciplina eius proteritur et ornatur. Ipsa vero tunica contexta desuper fuerat per totum, quia eidem Ecclesiae disciplina a Domino de coelo tribuitur et integratur. Tunica enim corporis Christi disciplina Ecclesiae est.*

⁹⁴¹ On discipline, authority and royal power, cf. Isidore, *Sententiae* 3, ed. Migne 42.1, 711: *Qui praeficitur ad regimen, taliter erga disciplinam subditorum praestare se debet ut non solum auctoritate, uerum etiam humilitate clarescat. Sed tamen ita erit in eo uirtus humilitatis, ne dissoluatur uita subditorum in uitii; atque ita auctoritas aderit potestatis, ne per tumorem cordis seueritas existat inmoderationis.*

⁹⁴² Hincmar, *De regis persona*, ed. Migne 850, 25 : *Qui autem extra disciplinam est, alienus a corpore Christi est.*

⁹⁴³ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 189: *...si illi super alios sunt, super illos deus est... Et si prave egerint et se non correxerint, tanto grauius iudicabuntur, quanto in throno regni ceteris celsius praeponitur. Reges enim et sacerdotes subditorum prave acta corrigunt, sed obliuisci non debent, quia illorum mala per ipsum dominum iudicabuntur.*

⁹⁴⁴ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 246: *...quia iste princeps rex est et nullorum legibus vel iudiciis subiacet nisi solius dei, qui eum in regno, quod suus pater illi dimisit, regem constituit...*

⁹⁴⁵ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 246: *...solius dei principatui debet subici, a quo solo potuit in principatu constitui ; Cor regis in manu dei, quocumque voluerit, vertet illus (Prov. 21 :1).*

⁹⁴⁶ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 247: *pontificalis auctoritas et regia dignitas* – according to pope Gelasius.

⁹⁴⁷ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 247: *Qui autem superbierit nolens oboedire sacerdotis imperio...moriatur homo ille...(Deut. 17:8–13).*

⁹⁴⁸ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 248: *...qui sunt throni dei in quibus Deus sedet et per quos sua decernit iustitia.*

⁹⁴⁹ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 252: *...si sequeretur negligentia disciplinae...nolite consentire...nolite laudare, nolite approbare.*

⁹⁵⁰ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 257: *auctoritas ordinis – dignitas potestatis – fortitudo virtutis.*

⁹⁵¹ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 261 (according to St. Cyprianus): *plebs uidelicet sine disciplina, quod ad negligentis episcopi reatum, populus sine lege, quod ad regis iniqui prauitatem non dubium est pertinere.*

episcopalis auctoritas et regia dignitas.⁹⁵² The holy Roman church is the mother of all the churches;⁹⁵³ sacred authority⁹⁵⁴ is also put forward. Hincmar insists on obedience to the ecclesiastical canons and on discipline⁹⁵⁵. Hincmar's warning is clear: those who despise divine sayings and laws should be cut off, like the putrid body part from the rest of the healthy body.⁹⁵⁶ Therefore, the wicked should be separated from the good, so that the good should not suffer due to the wicked ones.⁹⁵⁷

Similarly to Hincmar, Hrabanus also condemned Gottschalk's doctrine as being new and perverted; he sees him as a heretic, representing a threat. Hrabanus underlines that the body of the believers represents *membra corporis Christi*, who should stay jointly bound.⁹⁵⁸ Gottschalk, on the other hand, also alluded to his enemies as heretics.⁹⁵⁹ In an analogous approach to that of Hincmar, who used a metaphor of a putrid body part for a heretic, Amolo of Lyon stated in his letter accusing Gottschalk to have been cut off from the body of the church.⁹⁶⁰ Gottschalk, reciprocally, referred to the damned as *membra Antichristi*.⁹⁶¹

The symbolic of the unity of the body of Christ is reflected in the Eucharist: Hrabanus wrote on the importance of abiding in the body of Church. According to a passage from his *De Institutione Clericorum*, those who make part of Christ's body shall live; one must stay alert not to be separated from it, since those who are, shall remain alienated to salvation: *Manifestum est enim eos vivere, qui corpus ejus attingunt, unde timendum est, ne dum diu quis separator a Christi corpore, alienus remaneat a salute*⁹⁶². Contrary to the body of believers, the sinners are

⁹⁵² Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 261.

⁹⁵³ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 107: *...sancta Romana ecclesia ut omnium ecclesiarum mater et magistra, nutrix ac doctrix est consulenda*.

⁹⁵⁴ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 127: *sacra auctoritate docente*.

⁹⁵⁵ Cf. Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 241, 247: *apprehendite disciplinam*.

⁹⁵⁶ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 261: *eos autem, qui divina dicta et legum scita contemnunt ut membrum putridum a sanis abscindere*.

⁹⁵⁷ Hincmar, *De divortio Lotharii*, ed. Böhringer 140; cf. Eccl. 7:16; 1 Petr. 3:18; cf. my forthcoming article, *Hierarchy and Social Cohesion in the Carolingian Era*.

⁹⁵⁸ Cf. Hrabanus, *Epistolae*, Dümmler 481–487: *fides recta vs haec secta*; Gottschalk's doctrine incited disobedience directed towards the spreading of Gospel and induced others into error – leading to the scandal which arose in those areas. For more detailed information on heresies in the Middle Ages, cf. *Heresy in Transition: Transforming Ideas of Heresy in Medieval and Early Modern Europe*. Catholic Christendom 1300 – 1700, ed. J.C. Laursen/I. Hunter/C. Nederman (Aldershot 2005); C. C. Ames, *Medieval Heresies. Christianity, Judaism, and Islam* (Cambridge 2015).

⁹⁵⁹ Cf. Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais* 214.

⁹⁶⁰ Cf. Amolo, *Epistolae*, ed. Dümmler 370–371: *...a corpore ecclesiae iustae severitatis dampnatione precisus atque omni bonorum contubernio ac solatio defraudatus remansisti velus stirps inutilis et palmes aridus igni destinatus*; cf. Gillis, 238 – 239.

⁹⁶¹ Cf. Gillis, *Gottschalk of Orbais* 304; Gottschalk, *De Praedestinatione*, ed. Lambot 180–258, here 189, 203, 226.

⁹⁶² Hrabanus, *De Clericorum Institutione*, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, *De sacramento corporis* 321C.

referred to as the limbs of sinners, at the image of Judas: ...*peccatoribus, membris videlicet suis*⁹⁶³.

The Eucharist represents the eternal food and drink and community constituted by the head and its limbs: ...*aeternam societatem capitis membrorumque suorum significat*...⁹⁶⁴ Whoever participates in it, will represent a limb of Christ the head, in the heavenly kingdom: *Quicumque enim ejus particeps fuerit, id est, Christo capiti membrum associatus fuerit in regno coelesti*⁹⁶⁵... Namely, it is through the sacraments that all the limbs become fused and attached with the head. We get transformed in the body of Christ, adds Hrabanus, if we live in piety and obedience: *In virtute enim sacramenti omnia membra capiti suo conjuncta et coadunata...nos in corpus Christi convertimur dum oboedienter et pie vivimus*⁹⁶⁶. The principle of obedience is shown as a ligature, attaching the limbs of the body of the Church together in unity.

In the letter addressed to Gottschalk in 851/852, Amolo of Lyon reprehends him for having abandoned the mother-Church and fallen out of unity with it. In other words, those who disrespect the ecclesiastical doctrine and precepts, are severed from the ecclesiastical unity, having ceased to represent its alive and sane limbs, but become putrid limbs instead, and become meritoriously severed: *Cuius doctrinae et sensibus te, quasi devotum et pium filium, inrefragabiliter optemperate oportet, si cupis in eius corporis unitate vivum et sanum membrum inveniri, et non cum putribus et emortuis iustae severitatis iudicio abscisionem mereri*⁹⁶⁷. Amolo continues on the importance of constituting part of the body of Christ for Christians: *Nam quomodo est Christianus, qui non pertinent ad corpus Christi, qui non est membrum Christi?* Referring to the Pauline Epistle, the elaboration ensues: “your bodies are the limbs of Christ. Otherwise, they become the limbs of the prostitute; you represent the temple of God and God’s spirits abides in you; therefore, God will destroy him who outrages God’s temple: *‘Nescitis, inquit, quia corpora vestra membra Christi sunt? Tollens ergo membra Christi faciam membra meretricis? Absit’*. *Et iterum: ‘Nescitis, quia templum Dei estis et Spiritus sanctus habitat in vobis? Si quis autem templum Dei violaverit, disperdet illum Deus’, et cetera*⁹⁶⁸? Gottschalk has, Amolo explains, been justly cut off for years from the body of the Church, as a futile root and a withered branch, destined to be thrown into fire: *Nec doles, quod ecce tot annis a corpore aeclesiae iustae severitatis dampnatione precisus...remansisti velut*

⁹⁶³ Hrabanus, De Clericorum Institutione, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, De sacramento corporis 319D.

⁹⁶⁴ Hrabanus, De Clericorum Institutione, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, De sacramento corporis 317AB.

⁹⁶⁵ Hrabanus, De Clericorum Institutione, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, De sacramento corporis 317D.

⁹⁶⁶ Hrabanus, De Clericorum Institutione, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, De sacramento corporis 318A.

⁹⁶⁷ Amolo, Epistola 2, ed. Dümmler 370, l. 35–38.

⁹⁶⁸ Amolo, Epistola 2, ed. Dümmler 372, l. 15–22; the reference are made to 1 Cor. 6:5 and 1 Cor. 3:16,17.

*stirps inutilis et palmes aridus igni destinatus*⁹⁶⁹...Having shown disdain towards his mother, the holy Church, and her representatives, his fathers, in his sacrilegious temerity, Gottschalk has directed his actions against God: ...*aecclesiam matrem tuam eiusque presules patres tuos sacrilega audacia contempnans, adversus Dominum iacularis*⁹⁷⁰.

Gottschalk, on the other hand, designates his enemies, and the enemies of his doctrine of predestination as the limbs of the Antichrist, *membra Antichristi*, thus constituting the body of Antichrist – being the opposite to the body of Christ: *Siquidem duo corpora sunt: unum Christi alterum Antichristi, et unumquodque constat integritate, sive plenitudine membrorum suorum*⁹⁷¹.

Another important testimony on the unity of the body of believers and its limbs originates from a manuscript containing homilies from North of France, dating from 810-820's. The story of David and his combat with Goliath ensues. As an aftermath of David's victory over Goliath, the message of unity follows in a solemn tone: *Hoc significat fratres quia nos, qui baptizati sumus et membra sumus veri David id est Christi, superbos ereticos, qui sanctas scripturas cum superbia discutunt et superbe maledicunt, de ipsis suis verbis eos vincimus et quasi superbum goliath de suo gladio truncamus*. In this account, the haughty heretics are compared to Goliath, and will be smitten by the believers, who constitute one body of Christ⁹⁷².

In Byzantium, the equivalent semantic field of bodily unity has also been related to the severance of the heretics from the body of believers, in order to strengthen the unity.

In his *Contra manichaeos*, Photius insists upon the fact, that the most wicked of all will be the one who brings the body and blood of Christ to defamation, and who does not participate in them; he is to be anathematized: *Ὁ δὲ τρισαλιτήριοις πάλιν τὸν τε ἀτιμίαις ὑπάγοντα τὸ σῶμα καὶ αἷμα Χριστοῦ τοῦ θεοῦ ἡμῶν καὶ τὸν τῆς μετοχῆς αὐτῶν ἔξω διαμένοντα τῷ ἀναθέματι παρετίθετο*⁹⁷³.

⁹⁶⁹ Amolo, Epistola 2, ed. Dümmler 377, l. 10–13.

⁹⁷⁰ Amolo, Epistola 2, ed. Dümmler 377, l. 14–16.

⁹⁷¹ Gottschalk, De Praedestinatione, ed. Lambot, IX, 3, 203, 226.

⁹⁷² Cf. Pezè, Le virus de l'erreur (Paris 2014) 2, Annexe 23: Cycle de catéchèses du Nord de la France, 152–169, here 160–161.

⁹⁷³ Photius, Contra Manichaeos 56AB.

Photius elaborates his understanding of the unity in the body of the Church and of the severance of the limbs, which have been torn apart from it: *...τὸ δὲ κοινὸν τῆς Ἐκκλησίας, ἐφ' ᾧ γε παρὰ κεκλήμεθα⁹⁷⁴ ...ἀφηρέθως μέλος...ἀφιέρωται⁹⁷⁵.*

In his letter to Naucratus, Theodore the Studite equally depicts heretics as severed from the body of Christ: *...that they are separated from the body of Christ, and from the throne of Christ, where Christ has deposited the keys of faith: ...ἐαυτοὺς ἀπέρρηξαν τοῦ σώματος τοῦ Χριστοῦ, τοῦ κορυφιακοῦ θρόνου, ἐν ᾧ Χριστὸς ἔθετο τὰς κλεῖς τῆς πίστεως⁹⁷⁶.*

⁹⁷⁴ Photius, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 34 ed. Migne 848B.

⁹⁷⁵ Photius, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 34, ep. Migne 848A.

⁹⁷⁶ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 53, ed. Migne, 1281–1284, here 1281A.

II.10.2. *Summi regis et sacerdotis membra*⁹⁷⁷ – ecclesiastical authority and imperial power

The Church was considered one body, whose head was Christ⁹⁷⁸. The secular and clerical spheres were not distinctly differentiated in 9th-century Francia; the hierarchical orders within the church and state were intended to function towards a cohesive goal. Therefore, the policy was designed according to the Church – Christ was the head of the body of believers, just as the emperor (Louis the Pious in this particular case) was the head of different orders of the polity, which represented the limbs of society.

In Byzantium, the doctrine of ecclesiastical policy in relation to the policy of the state was quite different to the one in Francia⁹⁷⁹: the church and state have been viewed in Byzantium as organisms with two, equally important, rulers at their heads: the Emperor and the Patriarch.

Nevertheless, the role of the bishop was pivotal: bishops should, according the precepts contained in the Theodosian Code, intervene in the questions pertaining to religion; in other cases, which concern the public jurisprudence, the authority of the law should be observed:

*Quoties de religione agitur, episcopus convenit agitare; ceteras vero causas, quae ad ordinarios cognitores vel ad usum publici iuris pertinent, legibus oportet audiri*⁹⁸⁰.

Some of the central themes in Augustine's opus are related to the questions of obedience and human responsibility.⁹⁸¹ Namely, the thorough comprehension of the medieval theological frame of mind is rooted in Augustine's thought and its ensuing reception – which came to be

⁹⁷⁷ cf. 1 Cor. 12:25–27.

⁹⁷⁸ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 358.

⁹⁷⁹ Stratoudaki White, Patriarch Photius 139–155, 193–194; Photius, Epistolae, I, Ep. 14, ed. Migne 742D – 764D, here 764AD.

⁹⁸⁰ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri, p. 905; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.11.1, 476.

⁹⁸¹ On the mark Augustine's notion of the will has left, cf. Ch. H. Kahn, Discovering the Will: From Aristotle to Augustine, in: The Question of „Ecclecticism“: Studies in Later Greek Philosophy, ed. J. M. Dillon/A. A. Long (Berkeley 1988) 234–260; A. Dihle, The Theory of the Will in Classical Antiquity (Berkeley 1982) 132–144; W. Otten, The Reception of Augustine in the Early Middle Ages (700–1200): Presence, Absence, Reverence, and Other Modes of Appropriation, in: The Oxford Guide to the Historical Reception of Augustine, ed. K. Pollmann/W. Otten 1-3, 1 (Oxford 2013) 23–39; for more information on the concept of obedience and social cohesion in Hrabanus's, Hincmar's and Gottschalk's texts, see my forthcoming article: Hierarchy and Social Cohesion in the Carolingian Era.

called “political Augustinism”⁹⁸², particularly underlining the fact that Augustine considered obedience as one of the highest virtues.⁹⁸³ *Potestates* are seen as the constituent parts of the *ordo*.⁹⁸⁴ In his *Sermo* 62, Augustine elucidates the interrelation between king and God.⁹⁸⁵ *Mala potestas* is a power, misused by the evil, bad ruler. However, God allows it to exist due to the sinful actions of the people.⁹⁸⁶

A long tradition of Carolingian representations of the ruler-cult and topics relevant to obedience to worldly powers stem not only from the Bible and the early Christian concepts, but also from more ancient models as well.⁹⁸⁷ The concept of the earthly and heavenly king reaches further back to the more remote times and encompasses other traditions likewise: moreover, the highly mystical aspect of this concept, developed within a specific literary tradition based on the measurements of the God’s body parts (known as *schuur koma*), has been elaborated in speculations on earthly and heavenly king in the Jewish mystical tradition⁹⁸⁸.

In order to grasp a fuller understanding of the “ruler theology” in 9th-century Francia⁹⁸⁹, a glimpse into the events which marked the preceding century may be useful: at the Synod of Frankfurt, held in 794, the king was officially elevated above the pope by the formula *Laudes regiae*: heresy was deemed to be the primal enemy of the Frankish state. On this synod,

⁹⁸² For more extensive information, see: K. Froehlich, *Biblical Interpretation from the Church Fathers to the Reformation*, *Variorum Collected Studies Series CS 951* (Farnham 2010) 239–260; H.-X. Arquillière, *L’augustinisme politique. Essai sur la formation des théories politiques au Moyen Âge* (Paris 1955²).

⁹⁸³ Augustine, *De civitate Dei*, ed. Dombart/Kalb 14, 12, 434.

⁹⁸⁴ *Ibid.*, 85–90; on medieval concepts of Christ-centered kingship, cf. Kantorowicz, *The Kings’s Two Bodies* 42–86.

⁹⁸⁵ cf. Augustine, *Enarrationes in Psalmos*, 55 (ed. Migne, PL 36) 67–1028, here 646–661, at 647: *alius rex terrenus, alius rex caelestis: rex terrenus sub rege caelesti, rex caelestis super omnia*.

⁹⁸⁶ For more extensive information on Augustine’s view of God as *dominus*, see: B. Studer, *Deus, Pater et Dominus bei Augustinus von Hippo*, in: *Essays in Tribute to G.C. Stead*, ed. L. Wickham/C. Bammel (Leiden 1993) 190–212; G. Madec, *Le Dieu d’Augustin* (Paris 1998).

⁹⁸⁷ E. H. Kantorowitz, *The King’s Two Bodies. A Study in Mediaeval Political Theology* (Princeton 1957) 89, 262; W. Affeldt, *Die weltliche Gewalt in der Paulusexegese. Röm. 13, 1–7 in den Römerbriefkommentaren der lateinischen Kirche bis zum Ende des 13. Jahrhunderts* (Göttingen 1969) 63, 71, 72; on the image of the king as a ruler in Carolingian times, cf. P. Kershaw, *Peaceful Kings. Peace, Power and The Early Medieval Political Imagination* (Oxford 2011) 180–189; W. Ullmann, *Die Carolingian Renaissance and The Idea Of Kingship* (London 1969) 35–55; on the Indo-European ruler-archetype, cf. G. Dumézil, *Mitra-Varuna. An Essay on Two Indo-European Representations of Sovereignty*, trans. D. Coltman (New York 1988) 21–33 (on the division between *regnum* and *flaminium*, on the example of the Roman *rex*); M. Eliade, *Le “dieu lieur” et le symbolisme des noeuds*, in: *Revue de l’histoire des religions* 134 (1947) 1, 5–36.

⁹⁸⁸ These theological and literary inclinations were originally inherent to the intellectual circle gathered around Rabbi Yohanan ben Zakkai, cf. G. Scholem, *Die jüdische Mystik in ihren Hauptströmungen* (Frankfurt 1980) 68–72, 44–55, cited from C. Bötttrich, *Weltweisheit, Menschheitsethik, Urkult. Studien zum slavischen Henochbuch* (Tübingen 1992) 113–114; on the concept of the body politic and mystical body, cf. Kantorowicz, *King’s Two Bodies* 15–16.

⁹⁸⁹ Cf. J. L. Nelson, *Religion in the age of Charlemagne*, in: *The Oxford Handbook of Medieval Christianity*, ed. J. Arnold (Oxford 2014) 490–514; W. Ullmann, *The Carolingian Renaissance and the Idea of Kingship* (London 1969) at 43–70.

Charlemagne was acclaimed as *rex et sacerdos*.⁹⁹⁰ This couplet king-bishop was inherited from the Merovingian, if not Late Antique, tradition.⁹⁹¹ The letter of Pope Gelasius, which was read on that occasion (although originally composed in 494), became an axis in the debates encircling the sacerdotal *auctoritas* and imperial *potestas*. The negligence of a bishop was a pillar-stone in understanding the limits of social cohesion, since it could lead to scandal (seen as an offence to God which disrupts social order), due to the fact that bishops had a predominant role in mediating between God and the ruler.⁹⁹²

Consequently, in Francia, the foundations for medieval political theory were established at the Council of Paris in 829. On this occasion, the letter of Pope Gelasius addressed to the Byzantine emperor Anastasius I (491 – 518) in 494 was read again. This text, in fact, lay the basis for the later elaborations on the relationship between the ruler and the Pope, which would often be referred to throughout the entire Early Medieval period⁹⁹³: *Duo quippe sunt, imperator auguste, quibus principaliter mundus hic regitur: auctoritas sacrata pontificum et regalis potestas, in quibus tanto gravius est pondus sacerdotum, quanto etiam pro ipsis regibus hominum in divino reddituri sunt examine rationem*. In 829, Francia had to tackle a different set of complex and intertwined issues, relating to the internal struggles: Pope Gelasius's letter, containing this doctrine and conveying such a strong message, represented the first clear portrayal of the bishops who wished to raise their *sacerdotum* above the *imperium*⁹⁹⁴. The king was the preserver of the orders within the realm⁹⁹⁵.

⁹⁹⁰Cf. Pez, *Le virus de l'erreur* (Paris 2014) 237–238.

⁹⁹¹ Pez, *Le virus de l'erreur* (Paris 2014) 241.

⁹⁹² De Jong, *Penitential State* 176–183, 153–170, 195–205; cf. M. Diesenberger, *Predigt und Politik im frhmittelalterlichen Bayern*. Arn von Salzburg, Karl der Groe und die Salzburger Sermones-Sammlung (Millennium-Studien, Berlin/New York 2015); S. Patzold, *Episcopus: Wissen ber Bischfe im Frankreich des spten 8. bis frhen 10. Jahrhunderts* (Mittelalter-Forschungen 25, Ostfildern 2008).

⁹⁹³ Cf. Pope Gelasius, *Epistolae*, 12, 2, cited from: De Jong, *Penitential State* 176, note 134; cf. Pope Gelasius, in: *Concordantium Discordantium Canonum Seu Decretum Gratiani* (ed. Migne, PL 187) 9–1870, here 458D–459B; B. Neil/P. Allen, *The Letters of Gelasius I (492-496): Pastor and Micro-Manager of the Church of Rome* (Turnhout 2014) 73–80; D. Rutherford, *Gratian's DECRETUM as a source of patristic knowledge in the Italian Renaissance: The Example of Timoteo Maffei's In Sanctam Rusticitatem* (1454), in: *The Reception of the Church Fathers in the West. From the Carolingians to the Maurists*, ed. I. Backus, 2 (Boston/Leiden 2001) 511–535.

⁹⁹⁴ Cf. Ullman, *Carolingian Renaissance* 56–7; cf. R. L. Benson, *The Gelasian Doctrine: Uses and Transformations*, in: *La notion d'autorit au Moyen ge: Islam, Byzance, Occident* (Colloques internationaux de la Napoule: Session des 23-26. Octobre 1978), ed. G. Makdisi, a.o. (Paris 1982) 13–44.

⁹⁹⁵ Cf. De Jong, *Penitential State* 129–130, on the discussion on the secular and sacerdotal roles in *Historia tripartita*.

According to the *Admonitio ad omnes regni ordines* issued by Louis the Pious in 825⁹⁹⁶, God had given to Louis (as well as to his ancestors) the charge of the church and kingdom, i.e. of the *imperium Christianum* (for which a parallel can be drawn with the Biblical king Melchisedech).⁹⁹⁷ The importance of the obedience principle was underlined even then.⁹⁹⁸ Cohesion between the orders of the realm depended upon a king; the ruler should not be negligent of his office – as was also underlined by Hincmar⁹⁹⁹ – since he would be held accountable to God.¹⁰⁰⁰ Hrabanus likewise underlined the unity of the believers and the just disposition of the offices.¹⁰⁰¹ It was precisely that safeguarding of the ecclesiastical unity which served as a basis for social cohesion and royal unity.¹⁰⁰² The importance of obedience in maintaining the principle of order within the realm was also contained in the 4th Capitulary, issued by Charles the Bald in 856.¹⁰⁰³

In exposing his view on imperial power and ecclesiastical authority¹⁰⁰⁴, and their correlation, Hincmar quotes the letter sent by Pope Gelasius to Anasthasius, referring to the words of Sts. Paul and Peter, that every soul should be subjected to higher powers ... “*omnia anima*”, *id est omnis homo*, “*potestatibus sublimioribus subdita sit; non est enim potestas nisi a Deo*”; *et iterum dicit: “Subjecti estote omni humanae creaturae propter Deum sive regi tamquam praecellenti”*¹⁰⁰⁵. He continues further and paraphrases Pope Gelasius’s words, according to which there are two powers which govern the world – the imperial power and ecclesiastical authority.

Nevertheless, the weight of sacerdotal power is more important, argues Hincmar, since the ecclesiastics must account for the kings before God: ...*ut et pontificalis auctoritates regiae dignitati cum omni pietas officio se submittat, sicut sanctus Gelasius in decretali epistola ad Anastasium imperatorem ostendit dicens: Duo sunt quippe, imperator auguste, quibus principaliter mundus hic regitur: auctoritas sacra pontificum et regalis potestas; in quibus*

⁹⁹⁶ *Admonitio ad omnes regni ordines*, Capit. I (ed. A. Boretius, Hannover 1883) 303–307.

⁹⁹⁷ Cf. Gen. 14:18–19.

⁹⁹⁸ *oboedientia vel concordia populi*, cf. Additamenta ad Hludowici Pii capitularia 14, MGH Capit. II (ed. A. Boretius/V. Krause, Hannover 1897) 50–51, n. 196–197.

⁹⁹⁹ See above, in this chapter.

¹⁰⁰⁰ Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 37, 83, 152–155, 166.

¹⁰⁰¹ Cf. Hrabanus, *Epistolae*, ed. Dümler 436: *Convenit autem quibusque fidelibus et membris corporis Christi...unanimis omnes sint*; *Ibid.*, 434–435: *Et ideo cuique ordine iuxta mesuram suam officium delegavit, ut per studium humilitatis et dilectionis pax christiana et concordia in populo Die perseveraret.*

¹⁰⁰² Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 27–28.

¹⁰⁰³ The Capitulary was in great part composed by Hincmar, who from those years approximately became the prominent councilor of Charles the Bald, cf. Pez, *Virus de l’erreur* (Paris 2014) 314; 341–343; cf. my forthcoming article, *Hierarchy and Social Cohesion in the Carolingian Era*.

¹⁰⁰⁴ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 108, ed. Perels 53–54.

¹⁰⁰⁵ Hincmar, *Epistolae*, Ep. 108, ed. Perels 53, l. 10–12, cf. Rom. 13:1, 1. Petr. 2:13.

*tanto gravius pondus est sacerdotum, quanto etiam pro ipsis regibus hominum in divino reddituri sunt examine rationem*¹⁰⁰⁶. Thus, ecclesiastics should not interfere in mundane affairs and vice versa: ...*quatenus spiritualis actio a carnalibus distaret incursibus et ideo militans Deo minime se negotiis saecularibus implicaret, ac vicissim non ille rebus divinis praesidere videretur, qui esset negotiis saecularibus implacatus*¹⁰⁰⁷. Namely, it was Christ who had sharply delimited different functions, ecclesiastical and royal: *Quoniam sic Christus....sic actionibus propriis dignitatibusque distinctis officia potestatis utriusque discrevit*¹⁰⁰⁸. Therefore, Hincmar quotes Augustine and underlines, that the king should be revered¹⁰⁰⁹, through obedience: *Oboediendum ergo nobis est regibus pietatis cultui et religione et iure et solatio servientibus*¹⁰¹⁰.

Hincmar acknowledges the train of thought according to which God, who is king and priest at the same time,¹⁰¹¹ permits even bad rulers to govern, frequently as a cause of human sinful actions.¹⁰¹² In his texts, Hincmar also writes on power and good rule,¹⁰¹³ and quotes Gregory the Great.¹⁰¹⁴ He aligns with Hrabanus and underlines the impact of obedience, accomplished by means of discipline as a tool for preserving the rightful hierarchy. Gottschalk, on the other hand, promotes the concept according to which obedience at any price should not be adhered to; moreover, when authority is deemed wrong, it should be opposed.

If a ruler is not good, a trial befalls his subjects - a *virtutis examen*. Hincmar's message is that subjects ought to stay subjected.¹⁰¹⁵

¹⁰⁰⁶ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 108, ed. Perels 53, l. 14–20; on interpretation of Gelasius' view cf. J. Canning, A History of Medieval Political Thought: 300 – 1450 (London/New York 1996) 36–39.

¹⁰⁰⁷ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 108, ed. Perels 53, l. 26–28.

¹⁰⁰⁸ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 108, ed. Perels 53, l. 22–24.

¹⁰⁰⁹ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 108, ed. Perels 53, l. 30–34, p. 54, l. 1–2; cf. 1. Petr. 2:17.

¹⁰¹⁰ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 108, ed. Perels 54, l. 11–12.

¹⁰¹¹ Cf. Hincmar, De divortio Lotharii, ed. Böhringer 259: *rex scilicet et sacerdos*.

¹⁰¹² Hincmar, De regis persona, ed. Migne 835 :...*quia quos permittendo tolerat, profecto per iudicium reprobationis ignorat*; cf. Isidore, Sententiarum Libri Tres, ed. Migne 3 :48, 11, 720 : *Reges quando boni sunt, muneris esse Dei ; quando vero mali, sceleris esse populi*.

¹⁰¹³ Hincmar, De regis persona, ed. Migne 836, 3: *Magnae potentiae argumenta est recte administratio*; cf. Isidore, Sententiae 3: 48.7, 719: *Reges a recte agendo vocati sunt, ideoque recte faciendo regis nomen tenentur, peccando amittitur*.

¹⁰¹⁴ Hincmar, De regis persona, ed. Migne 836, referring to Gregory the Great: *Magna est... potentia temporalis....Igitur bene hanc exercet, qui et retinere illam noverit, et impugnare. Bene hanc exercet, qui scit per illam super culpas erigi, et scit cum illa caeteris aequalitate componi*.

¹⁰¹⁵ Ibid.: *Malorum vero regnum magis regnantibus nocet, qui suos animos vastant scelerum maiore licentia: his autem, qui eis serviendo subduntur, non nocet nisi iniquitas propria. Nam quidquid malorum ab iniquis dominis irrogatur, non est poena criminis, sed virtutis examen. Proinde bonus etiam si serviat, liber est: malus autem etiamsi regnet, servus est; nec unius hominis, sed, quod est gravius, tot dominorum quot vitiorum....Remota itaque iustitia, quid sunt regna, nisi mala latrocinia?*

Hrabanus Maurus, on the other hand, in his letter addressed to Louis the Pious, states that one should render to Caesar what is Caesar's, and to God what is God's, and refers to the words of St. Peter, according to which one should be obedient to every authority. This opinion is quite opposite to Gottschalk's, who underlines the importance of obedience, but not at all costs - only in case when the higher authority in question is itself obedient to God.¹⁰¹⁶ Hrabanus concludes that a disciple should not exceed his teacher,¹⁰¹⁷ thus stressing the importance of preserving the right order, hierarchy, and orderly structure.

Therefore, the concepts of hierarchy and order in Hincmar's, Hrabanus's and Gottschalk's writings have echoed the place they held in the patterns and frames of mind of their authors. Consequently, Hincmar's accusations put forward against Gottschalk as a heretic, thus echoed the imminent and factual danger which a false doctrine can induce by resulting in severance from the body of believers.¹⁰¹⁸

¹⁰¹⁶ Hrabanus, *Epistolae*, ed. Dümmler 417, cf. 1 Petr. 2:13.14: *Subiecti estote omni humanae creaturae propter Deum, sive regi quasi precellenti, sive ducibus tamquam ab eo missis ad vindictam malefactorum, laudem vero bonorum.*

¹⁰¹⁷ *Ibid.*, 417, Mt. 10: 24.25: *Non est discipulus super magistrum, nec servus super dominum suum. Sufficit enim discipulo, ut sit sicut magister eius.*

¹⁰¹⁸ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 475–484, 510, 579, 613; Hincmar, *Epistolae*, ed. E. Perels 160–163, 169.

II.10.3. *Sicut unius eiusdemque fidei et religionis cultoribus facere oportet*¹⁰¹⁹: in the quest for unity on the external plane - through contacts and mediators between East and West

When speaking of the unity symbolism, it is important to delve into another aspect of it. Namely, instead of focusing upon the internal unity of the Frankish or Byzantine empires, and the unity symbolism echoed in the axis of internal unity as accomplished through the joint performances of ecclesiastical and imperial powers, it is necessary to depict and analyze the picture of unity portrayed on a more global plane: the external unity, or, concord, which has often been sought for between the representatives of Byzantium and Francia in terms of their underlying theology and intellectual threads.

Much has been written on theological disputes, and consequently on contacts in this respect between Byzantium and the Latin West of the 9th century¹⁰²⁰. Therefore, this section of my study will not deal with these issues in detail, but will nevertheless try to depict those contacts in terms of exchange, by enhancing the significant role of the mediators which served as a binding tissue in certain events. Furthermore, it is important to emphasize that only the contacts judged most representative for the field of this study will be analyzed. The main lines tracing the conflictual issues between Rome and Byzantium in the middle of the 9th century therefore include: the ecclesiastical tradition of the fathers; the respect of the ecclesiastical canons, and the doctrinal and liturgical practices¹⁰²¹. It seems particularly interesting and important in light of the objectives of this work to analyze how these diverge from a literary and linguistic perspective.

Throughout this century, which was rather turbulent in view of ecclesiastical disputes - some of which reached Rome – the Byzantine rulers and Patriarchs came into contact with the Frankish emperors and the Roman Pontiff on numerous occasions. Analysis of the exchanges between the Latin West and the Byzantine East in the field of ecclesiastical disputes which

¹⁰¹⁹ Cf. Michael, *Epistola*, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 11.

¹⁰²⁰ Cf. Dvornik, *Les Slaves, Byzance et Rome*; Id., *Byzantium and the Roman Primacy* (New York 1966); Noble, *Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians*; Th. Ertl, *Byzantinischer Bilderstreit und fränkische Nomentheorie* (Berlin/New York 2006); Kolbaba, *Inventing Latin Heretics*, especially ch. 3, *The Patriarch, the Pope, and the Barbarians* 49–56.

¹⁰²¹ Latin sources for the contacts between Photius and Pope Nicholas include: *Annales Bertiniani*, ed. Waitz; Pope Nicholas's letters: *Epistolae*, ed. Perels; *Epistolae ad Res Orientales Pertinentes*, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 601–609; Photius, *Epistolae*, ed. Migne: Ep. 1, to Pope Nicholas 585–594; Ep. 2 to Pope Nicholas: 594–618; To Michael the Bulgarian ruler: Ep. 8, 627–696.

marked the 9th century would be too comprehensive and exhaustive for this work. Therefore, the current study does not deal with each and every one of them in detail. This section instead is focused upon only some of those theological quarrels, judged important for the scope of the present research.

The 9th-century contacts between Francia and Byzantium occurred on various bases – and could be seen in terms of exchange. These include diplomatic contacts and exchange (mainly on questions related to heresy, concord and Christian faith), and textual contacts and exchange (through correspondence and translations of the texts).

Important figures involved in the 9th-century contacts between the East and West, who could be understood as mediators and carriers of exchange include: Michael II, Louis the Pious, Charles the Bald, Pope Leo III, Pope Nicholas I, Theodore the Studite, Photius, Anastasius Bibliothecarius, John Scottus Eriugena (c. 815 – c. 877), the Bulgars and their conversion¹⁰²², as well as their oscillation between Francia and Byzantium – as a central, meeting point for the interference and intertwining between the two empires¹⁰²³.

In the 9th century, the translators and interpreters had, in fact, played significant roles as mediators and in-betweeners, who thereby helped to circulate the important ideas from East to West and vice versa. Furthermore, it was the Pope who provided the Latin translations for the Frankish rulers, thereby acting as a philosophical tutor of a kind¹⁰²⁴.

As much has already been written on ecclesiastical and theological disputes, I shall not delve more deeply into that field¹⁰²⁵. Instead, I wish here to try to summarize and outline who the principal mediators (actual or conceptual) were, between East and West in the 9th century, and to examine the extent to which the issues relating to the semantic fields of true faith and heresy provoked these contacts, and how these were used for political purposes. Mediators have sometimes occupied a role of translators and interpreters, as well as those who commissioned the translation work: Eriugena, Anastasius Bibliothecarius, Charles the Bald.

The most pronounced contacts between East and West in the Middle Ages – which applies to the 9th century as well – were related to ecclesiastical disputes. Or, more subtly expressed, it could be observed that one of the most important contacts between East and West in the 9th

¹⁰²² Cf. Dvornik, *Slaves, Byzance et Rome* 184–195.

¹⁰²³ Cf. D. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios* 30.

¹⁰²⁴ Cf. Chadwick, *East and West* 85.

¹⁰²⁵ See, among others, Chadwick, *East and West*; Id., *Heresy and Orthodoxy*; Meyendorff, *Byzantine Theology*; Dvornik, *Slaves, Byzance et Rome*; Id., *Byzantium and the Roman Primacy* (New York 1966); Id., *Photian Schism*.

century was represented by the echo of the Iconoclast crisis and the debates which it provoked, as already elaborated above. The sway of the Iconoclast crisis in the Latin West was discussed at the synods in Frankfurt and Paris in 825¹⁰²⁶. The Iconoclast crisis reached the Frankish West and provoked heated debates¹⁰²⁷.

*Spirituali fratri nostro et pacifico amico*¹⁰²⁸: *Epistle of Michael II to Louis the Pious*

Likewise, the entire letter composed by Michael II and addressed to Louis the Pious on the rebellion of Thomas the Slav carries, in fact, a strong message of unity. It is namely by depicting the turbulent events which had incited the Christian flock to disintegrate, that the aim of the letter is focused on attaining unity within the Byzantine empire, but also unity of the Christian faith, which connected both Byzantine and Frankish realms.

Michael II addressed the letter in question to Louis the Pious in 824, on his behalf and on behalf of his son Theophilus, who was made co-ruler in 821. This letter is preserved in Latin only¹⁰²⁹. Michael sent gifts to Louis and to the Pope, which Louis's legates brought to Rome soon after¹⁰³⁰. Michael alludes to Louis as to his *spiritalis frater* and *pacificus amicus*¹⁰³¹. The reason which led Michael to compose the letter, is ...*quia (Deus) permisit propter quaedam peccata subjecti populi sui provenire quasdam tribulationes*. The rebellion of Thomas the Slav, already ended by that time, partly represented these troubles which befell Byzantium. Furthermore, the Iconophile opposition to the measures undertaken by the emperor was fierce. Thomas appeared, writes Michael, in the times of his predecessor Leo V the Armenian – as a devil's apprentice and an executor of his work: ...*diaboli discipulus, et eius operum promptus*

¹⁰²⁶The Council of Paris a. 825 m. Novembri (ed. A. Werminghoff, MGH Conc. II,2, Hannover/Leipzig 1908) 473-551, here 473-474; cf. Libellus synodalis Parisiensis a. 825 m. Novembri, ed. Werminghoff 481 sq.

¹⁰²⁷ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians; on the echo of the Iconoclasm in Francia, cf. Libri Carolini, ed. Freeman Prefatio.

¹⁰²⁸ Cf. Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 13-14.

¹⁰²⁹ On this letter, see also Einhard, Annales, Annales et Chronica aevi Carolini MGH SS I (ed. G-H. Pertz, MGH SS I, Hannover 1826) 135-218, here an. 824, 212; cf. Annales Regni Francorum (ed. Kurze, MGH SSSR VI, Hannover 1895) a. 824, 165.

¹⁰³⁰ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 474; C. Mango, The Art of the Byzantine Empire 312-1453: Sources and Documents (Toronto 1986) 157-158; on the historical context of the letter, see: Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 260-263. The contents of the letter are analyzed in C. Sode, Der Brief der Kaiser Michael II und Theophilus an Ludwig den Frommen, in: Zwischen Polis, Provinz und Peripherie. Beiträge zur byzantinischen Geschichte und Kultur, Festschrift für Günther Prinzing, ed. L. Hoffmann (Wiesbaden 2005) 138-154.

¹⁰³¹ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 9, 13-14.

*perpetrator*¹⁰³². Thomas firstly committed an illicit union with a spouse of a renowned man, and then fled to Persia. He renounced his Christian faith and thus betrayed it: ...*fidem Christi abnegans et hoc modo proditor fidei Christianae fuit*¹⁰³³ – so that he could easier gather together the Saracens and other barbarians: ...*quo facilius potuisset multos infideles et Sarracenorum et ceterarum aliarum gentium ad suam perducere voluntatem*¹⁰³⁴. He won the barbarian adherents over by lying – having said that he was the Empress Irene’s son. Thomas managed to unite an impressive squad comprised of Armenians, Persians, Saracens and other barbarians, with whom he launched his campaign with the aim of conquering the distant Euro-Asian parts of the Empire. In the turmoil, which befell the Empire, Leo the Emperor was assassinated in a conjuration. The Christians found themselves divided. The chain of these turbulent events has thus provoked the disunion and disintegration in the Christian flock: ...*invenimus Christianos divisos et discordantes*¹⁰³⁵, whereas Thomas is referred to as *impius tyrannus*¹⁰³⁶. Thomas’s military units grew through time – encompassing forces from Thrace, Macedonia, Thessaloniki and from the Slavic bordering regions – and sieged Constantinople for a year¹⁰³⁷. Finally, the rebellion led by Thomas, the “devil and seducer of Christians”, and supported by his followers, pagans and foreigners, *pagani et alienigenae*¹⁰³⁸ – got suppressed. From that time, unity and concord spread again in the Christian Empire, by the merit of God, who united his people in faith: ...*ex eo tempore omnes Christiani imperii nostri ad unitatem pacis et pristinam concordiam redierunt, glorificantes et magnificantes propugnatorem nostrum dominum Iesum Christum, qui ad unitatem fidei coadunare populum suum dignatus est*¹⁰³⁹. With these words, Michael reinforced his relations with Louis the Pious, underlying adherence to the one and the same faith binding the Eastern and Western empires together, and referring to both as guardians of one and the same faith and religion - *unius eiusdemque fidei et religionis*¹⁰⁴⁰. Furthermore, he indirectly explained the incapacity of his predecessor to put an end to the civil war and his own enthronement in terms of Thomas’s rebellion¹⁰⁴¹.

On more than one occasion, Michael underlines the connection with the West: he addresses Louis as *spiritali fratri nostro et pacifico amico*, and insists upon the reinforcement of their

¹⁰³² Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 476, l. 8.

¹⁰³³ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 476, l. 13

¹⁰³⁴ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 476, l. 14–15.

¹⁰³⁵ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 476, l. 38.

¹⁰³⁶ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 476, l. 39.

¹⁰³⁷ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 477, l. 2–12.

¹⁰³⁸ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 477, l. 21.

¹⁰³⁹ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 5–7.

¹⁰⁴⁰ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 11.

¹⁰⁴¹ Lemerle, Thomas le Slave 258.

sound relationship: ...*par has nostras veras et fideles syllabas corroboramus et confirmamus priorem pacem et amicitiam inter vos et nos constitutam*¹⁰⁴².

In support of the true, genuine Christian faith which allied both Eastern and Western Empires, Michael alludes to the foundations on which it was based, testified and sealed by the six Ecumenical councils, Trinity and Christology: ...*trinitatem in tribus personis divisam colimus, unitatem unius divinitatis naturam confitentes....divinitatis et humanitatis duas voluntates et operationes gloriamur*¹⁰⁴³.

Michael closes his letter with the expression of sympathy and bonds (*caritas*) between Eastern and Western Empires¹⁰⁴⁴, as well as of reverence for the Pope Eugenius II (824-827), in the form of gifts that the ambassadors carried to the Holy See – founded by the first apostle, the blessed Peter, who *intercedat pro nobis et vobis*¹⁰⁴⁵. After having discussed Thomas's rebellion, peace and unity which had been regained in the realm, Michael concludes with an admonition to those who attempted to bring this unity in jeopardy. Thus, speaking of the *seductores pseudochristiani, ecclesiae calumniatores*¹⁰⁴⁶, if they appear, they should be ejected: *Eicite malum de medio vestri* (Deut. 21:21) – and not only from the state, but also from the *ecclesia*, which was held responsible for their spiritual well-being¹⁰⁴⁷.

Corpus Areopagiticum

One important document deemed to be of great significance for the 9th-century textual tradition is certainly the *Corpus Areopagiticum*, or, *Corpus Dionysiacum*¹⁰⁴⁸. Additionally, it may have borne a highly significant message of the urge for unity and concord. As such, it would be instructive to include a short analysis of the historical contexts in which it reached Francia in the frame of this work.

¹⁰⁴² Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 478, l. 13–14; 27–28.

¹⁰⁴³ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 479, l. 28–30.

¹⁰⁴⁴ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 479, l. 43.

¹⁰⁴⁵ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 479, l. 40.

¹⁰⁴⁶ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 480, l. 1.

¹⁰⁴⁷ Michael, Epistola, ed. Werminghoff 480, l. 2–5.

¹⁰⁴⁸ The *Corpus* was already known in the Christian world by the beginning of the sixth century, whereas its author apparently lived in the first century AD: cf. A. Louth, *Denys the Areopagite* (London/New York 2001) 1.

The *Corpus Areopagiticum* indirectly connected Byzantium with Francia on the issue of the Iconoclast crisis likewise¹⁰⁴⁹. Some of the questions related to the appearance of the *Corpus* in Francia the in 820's still await for the answer¹⁰⁵⁰. The *Corpus* conveyed the writings of Pseudo-Dionysius to the West, and became widespread thanks to the second translation, produced by Eriugena. The role of Anastasius Bibliothecarius is judged to be important, since he read and verified Eriugena's translation. It was namely thanks to Maximus the Confessor that the works of Pseudo-Dionysius were made accessible to the Byzantine scholars¹⁰⁵¹.

The *Corpus Areopagiticum* has been known to the Latin West from, probably, the end of the 6th century, and certainly from the second half of the 8th century¹⁰⁵²: Pope Gregory the Great cited one passage from the *Hierarchia Caelestis* in his 34th Homily on the Gospels¹⁰⁵³. In the 8th century (758 - 763) Pope Paul I (757 – 767) sent some Greek manuscripts to Pepin the Short (king of the Franks from 751 to 768), in which Pseudo-Dionysius's writings were mentioned, among others, and more precisely - a copy of the Greek text of the *Corpus Areopagiticum*¹⁰⁵⁴. It is certain that a manuscript of Pseudo-Dionysius's texts was kept in Rome: Pope Hadrian I (772 – 795) cited in 791, some passages in his letter addressed to Angilbert of St. Riquier¹⁰⁵⁵ – to provide a moderate defence of the seventh Ecumenical council¹⁰⁵⁶. The same passages were read at the Council of Paris in 825, at the encounter between the envoys of

¹⁰⁴⁹ Lemerle, *Le premier humanisme byzantin* 12–13, on the Carolingian renaissance and the *Corpus*; the first translation, originated between 832 and 835.

¹⁰⁵⁰ Some of which are the following: why was this *Corpus* sent to Francia in this particular time? What was the role of the monks from Rome, who helped in producing the first unofficial translation of the *Corpus*?

¹⁰⁵¹ Cf. R. Roques, *L'univers dionysien. Structure hiérarchique du monde selon le Pseudo-Denys* (Paris 1983); P. Rorem, *The Early Latin Dionysius: Eriugena and Hugh of St. Victor*, in: *Modern Theology*, 24, 4 (2008) 601–614; A. Louth, *The Reception of Dionysius in the Byzantine World: Maximus to Palamas*, in: *Re-thinking Dionysius the Areopagite*, ed. S. Coakley/C. M. Stang (Oxford 2009) 55–70; C. M. Stang, *Dionysius, Paul, and the Significance of the Pseudonym*, in: *Re-thinking Dionysius the Areopagite*, ed. S. Coakley/C. M. Stang (Oxford 2009) 11–26; R. Forrai, *The Notes of Anastasius on Eriugena's Translation on the Corpus Dionysiacum*, in: *The Journal of Medieval Latin*, 18 (2008) 74–100.

¹⁰⁵² J. Irigoin, *Les Manuscrits Grecs de Denys L'Aréopagite en Occident, les empereurs Byzantins et l'abbaye royale de Saint-Denis en France*, in: *Denys L' Aréopagite et sa postérité en Orient et en Occident*, ed. Y. De Andia (Paris 1997) 19–29; A. Louth, *St. Denys the Areopagite and the Iconoclast Controversy*, in: *Denys L' Aréopagite et sa postérité en Orient et en Occident*, ed. Y. De Andia (Paris 1997) 329–339, here 335.

¹⁰⁵³ Gregory the Great, *Homiliarum in Evangelia Libri Duo* (ed. Migne PL 76) 1075–1312C, here 1254b.

¹⁰⁵⁴ *Codex Carolinus* (ed. W. Gundlach, MGH Epp. III, Berlin 1892) 469-657, here ch. 24, 529, l. 19–22.

¹⁰⁵⁵ Louth, *St. Denys* 333, 335.

¹⁰⁵⁶ The first passage (already cited from Damascene, in Louth, *St. Denys* 335) comes from Pseudo-Denys's 10th epistle: in truth and manifestly visible things are images of the invisible (*imagines sunt visibiles invisibilia*), and the second from *Caelestis Hierarchia* I.3, on the prerequisite of using sensible images to ascend to the invisible: "...c'est par les images sensibles qu'il a représenté les esprits supra-célestes, dans les compositions sacrées que nous offrent les Dits, afin de nous élever, par l'entremise des sensibles, jusqu'aux intelligibles et, à partir des symbols qui figurent le sacré, jusqu'aux simples cimes des hiérarchies célestes", R. Roques/Heil, G./M. de Gandillac ed., *Denys l'Aréopagite. La hiérarchie céleste* (Paris 1970) 73. The Seven Ecumenical Council, held in 787 in Nicaea, re-habilitated the veneration of the icons, which was suppressed during the reign of Leo III (717-741) and his son Constantine V (741-775).

Michael II and the Latin theologians (Hildouin, abbot of St. Denys, first of all)¹⁰⁵⁷. The texts of Pseudo-Dionysius were also cited there¹⁰⁵⁸.

The first translation of Pseudo-Dionysius in Latin was completed by 835, by the abbot and archchaplain of Louis the Pious, Hildouin of St Denis. Nevertheless, this first translation did not have a wide circulation¹⁰⁵⁹. It was only in, approximately, 862 that John Scottus Eriugena finished the first official translation of Pseudo-Dionysius' writings in Latin, on the request of Charles the Bald (the translation was begun in 858). It is certainly also due to Charles' support, that Eriugena's translation had such a wide success¹⁰⁶⁰. Charles the Bald nourished a deep esteem towards Byzantine culture.

The Greek diplomatic mission reached Rome and the Frankish court during the fragile times marked by the Iconoclastic crisis in Byzantium¹⁰⁶¹. The Byzantine emperor, Michael II, a moderate Iconoclast, sought support from the Frankish realm: the mission with the letter to Michael II asking him to support Iconoclasm arrived in 824; Pope Pascal I (817 – 824) was an Iconodule, and Michael II, wishing to undermine the importance of the Pope's position, reinforced his relationships with Aachen and the Frankish empire, and sought their support; the synod in Paris was held in 825 under the leadership of Hildouin, and Michael II and moderate Iconoclasm were approved and a couple of passages from the *Corpus* were cited in support of the moderate stance on the icon worship¹⁰⁶². In 827, royal Byzantine ambassadors came from Rome to Aachen and brought a copy of the *Corpus* as a gift to Louis the Pious, residing in Compiègne. Louis the Pious had Hildouin, abbot of St. Denis and his archchaplain produce the

¹⁰⁵⁷Cf. Council of Rome, a. 769 (ed. A. Werminghoff, MGH Conc. II, 1, Hannover/Leipzig 1906) 74–92, here 91, 1.27–30 and 30–36.

¹⁰⁵⁸Ibid., 1.32–35 and 35–41.

¹⁰⁵⁹P. Théry, *Études dionysiennes. II Hilduin traducteur de Denys. Édition de sa traduction* (Paris 1937); P. C. Jakobsen, *Il secolo IX*, in: *Letteratura Latina Medievale*, ed. C. Leonardi (Firenze 2012) 75–159, here 109.

¹⁰⁶⁰E. Jeuneau, *L'abbaye de Saint-Denis introductrice de Denys en occident*, in: *Denys L' Aréopagite et sa postérité en Orient et en Occident*, ed. Y. De Andia (Paris 1997) 363–378, here 366; J. Vezin, *Les relations entre Saint Denis et d'autres scriptoria*, in: *The role of the book in medieval culture*, ed. P. Ganz. *Bibliologia. Elementa ad librorum studium pertinentia* 3 (Turnhout 1986) 17–40; Id., *Les manuscrits copiés à Saint Denis en France pendant l'époque carolingienne*, in: *Paris et Ile de France, Memoires publiés par la Fédération des sociétés historiques et archeologiques de Paris et l'Ile de France* 32 (1981) 273–287.

¹⁰⁶¹ At the time, still marked by heated debates revolving around the icon veneration, the Byzantine ruler was Michael II, and the Patriarch Ignatius.

¹⁰⁶²The *Corpus* was cited in order to support an anti-Iconodule stance, cf. Louth, *St. Denys* 330, 335–336. This, together with the passages cited in 791 (as shown above), might indicate the possibility that those, quoted excerpts from the *Corpus* were used with the aim of supporting the middle-line position, between the Iconodule and Iconoclast faction. Apparently, the *Corpus* offered an ambiguous view on the icon veneration, as has already been demonstrated: Louth, *St. Denys* 329; Roques/Heil/Gandillac, *Denys l'Aréopagite* 74.

first translation of the *Corpus*, started in 832 and finished around 835¹⁰⁶³. The choice reflected the initiative of Hildouin¹⁰⁶⁴, who was at that time the abbot of St. Denys, as already mentioned above¹⁰⁶⁵. He was then restored, after having joined other rebels against Louis the Pious in 830.

Eriugena based his own translation on the older translation of the text¹⁰⁶⁶, but although he demonstrably worked with, and corrected the older version, he in fact made no mention of it. Anastasius Bibliothecarius was a counselor of the Pope Nicholas I who asked for the translation effectuated by Eriugena for Charles the Bald to be sent to Rome, examined and approved. Anastasius was charged with this task in 875, when Charles came to Rome to be coronated emperor¹⁰⁶⁷.

According to Pascal Boulhol, the gift of Michael II was highly political in nature: it was used for obtaining the support of the Franks for Michael's moderate Iconoclasm. However, it was also supposed to ensure the leading position and supremacy of the abbey of St. Denis in the Frankish kingdom, as well as to secure Hildouin's ambitions¹⁰⁶⁸. Thus, one may assume that Charles's decision to have the *Corpus* translated for the second time by Eriugena did not intervene in that particular moment for no apparent reason: it may well have been that the need for unification and peace in the Realm was somehow reflected in the message which stemmed directly from the *Corpus* - as Charles may have interpreted it. Another important observation to add, is that Charles's aim with this second translation – doubtlessly intended for the courtly circles - may have been to highlight his authority in relation to that of Louis the Pious. And last but not least, Charles may have desired to spread a message that his realm was ecumenical –

¹⁰⁶³Including Celestial Hierarchy, ecclesiastical hierarchy, on divine names, mystical theology and ten letters. The manuscript is kept today at the BNF in Paris, Cod. Gr. 437.

¹⁰⁶⁴Cf. Irigoien, *Manuscrits grecs*.

¹⁰⁶⁵In 830 Hildouin joined the rebels against Louis the Pious, as he supported Lothair; consequently Louis the Pious sent him to Paderborn or to the abbey of Corvey, cf. P. Boulhol, *La connaissance de la langue grecque dans la France medievale Vie-XVe s.* (Aix-en-Provence 2008) 29–48. Hildouin was in Corvey, daughter monastery of Corbey, around 830's. Gottschalk was, from 829 to 835 in the diocese of Soissons, archdiocese of Reims (where Orbais, Corbie and Hautvillers lay) – i.e. he left Fulda in 829 due to the conflict with Hrabanus Maurus. Before his arrival to Orbais he visited Corbey where he met Gislemar and Ratramn. Is it likely that he was at the time in contact with Corvey and Hildouin? Cf. Genke/Gumerlock, *Gottschalk and a Medieval Predestination Controversy* 22–23; Cf. Bulhol, *Langue grecque* 36.

¹⁰⁶⁶Irigoien, *Manuscrits grecs*.

¹⁰⁶⁷Cf. Jakobsen, *Il secolo IX*, 130–131.

¹⁰⁶⁸Bulhol, *Langue grecque* 35–37.

since the translation of one of the most important theological treatises from the East might have proved his (Charles's) authority stretching towards the Old Rome, as well as to the New one.

As it has already been mentioned, much has been written on the importance the *Corpus Areopagiticum* played in the Christian history. Furthermore, it may well have left its trace upon the conceptual universe of Carolingian authors as well – and mainly that of the poets; this, nevertheless, represents a topic which awaits for its more comprehensive elaboration¹⁰⁶⁹.

¹⁰⁶⁹ Cf. my article in preparation on the potential influence the Pseudo-Dionysius's *Hierarchia Caelestis* could have left upon Gottschalk and perhaps some other Carolingian poets (for example, Heiric of Auxerre).

II. 11. REPENTANCE – in order to prevent severance¹⁰⁷⁰

This chapter is designed as to demonstrate and summarily analyze the importance of repentance in the anti-heretical textual procedures of the chosen Greek and Latin texts, starting with disobedience, and ending most likely in exile. The stage of repentance represents a stepping-stone and a penultimate point, upon which the execution of penance – which often included exile – depended.

The Theodosian Code clearly underlines the fact that the heretics are absolved from their guilt if they confess the Catholic faith and adhere to the Catholic religious rites, through confession, and by condemning their false doctrine. The heretical doctrine is referred to as a “sect”. Penalty is imposed upon those who perform anything that is “contrary and opposed to the Catholic sect”¹⁰⁷¹. Furthermore, the Donatists, Manichaeans and Priscilians are equated with the pagans before the law.

*Donatistarum haereticorum iudaeorum nova adque inusitata detexit audacia, quod catholicae fidei velint sacramenta turbare. Quae pestis cave contagione latius emanet ac profluat. In eos igitur, qui aliquid, quod sit catholicae sectae contrarium adversumque, temptaverint, supplicium iustae animadversionis expromi praecipimus*¹⁰⁷².

In view of the legal procedures applied by the State in cases of sin – including those of the heretics - the Theodosian Code brings precious information on the second baptism and punishment for the heretics as well. Speaking of baptism, it has been stressed that it is conceded only once by God; any heretical actions against such practice are considered criminal; the

¹⁰⁷⁰ On the exhaustive topic of medieval repentance, much has been written, so here it will be tackled only summarily. Some of the bibliography include: C. Rapp, *Spiritual guarantors at penance, baptism and ordination in the Late Antique East*, in: *A New History of Penance*, ed. A. Firey (Leiden 2008) 121–148; R. Meeds, *The historiography of Early Medieval penance*, in: *A New History of Penance*, ed. A. Firey (Leiden 2008) 73–96; M. De Jong, *Transformations of Penance*, in: *Rituals of Power: From Late Antiquity to the Early Middle Ages*, ed. F. Theuvs/J. L. Nelson, *The Transformation of the Roman World 8* (Leiden 2000) 185–224; Id., *Power and Humility in Carolingian Society: The Public Penance of Louis the Pious*, *EME 1* (1992) 29–52; Id., *What was ‘Public’ about Public Penance? Paenitentia publica and justice in the Carolingian world*, in: *La Giustizia nell’alto medioevo II (secoli IX–XI)*, *Settimane di Studio del centro Italiano di studi sull’alto medioevo 44* (Spoleto 1997) 864–65; R. Kottje, *Die Bussbücher Halitgars von Cambrai und des Hrabanus Maurus. Ihre Überlieferung und ihre Quellen, Beiträge zur Geschichte und Quellenkunde des Mittelalters 8* (Berlin/New York 1980); C. Vogel, *Les “Libri Paenitentiales”*, *Typologie des sources du moyen âge occidental 27* (Turnhout 1978).

¹⁰⁷¹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri 870*; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.44, 458.

¹⁰⁷² Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri 868–869*; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.41, 457.

penalty is exile or deportation. Legal sanctions are particularly aimed against the Eunomians, stating that they should not hold assemblies in the City:

Quod facinus ne etiam a ceteris haereticis perpetretur, commonemus, similem expectaturis poenam etiam aliis clericis haereticis, si divinum baptismum nefarie crediderint iterandum:

Ne eo quoque extra poenam relegationis futuro, qui sponte adque ultro passus fuerit ad secundum se baptismum et geminata semel indultae fidei mysteria inbui temere vel perperam devocari:

Pari poena deportationis absque alicuius intercessione in eunomianos clericos processura, si conventus exercere vel in hac incluta urbe vel in provinciis, civitatibus ac territoriis vel creare ausi fuerint clericos pestiferi dogmatis vel creari¹⁰⁷³.

Similarly to the Theodosian Code, the Justinian Code suggest that he, who commits a crime against religion, brings detriment to all and is committing a public crime:

Ac primum quidem volumus esse publicum crimen, quia, quod in religione divina committitur, in omnium fertur iniuriam. quos bonorum etiam publicatione persequimur: quae tamen cedere iubemus proximis quibusque personis, ita ut ascendentium vel descendentium vel venientium ex latere cognatorum usque ad secundum gradum velut in successione ordo servetur. quibus ita demum ad capiendas facultates esse ius patimur, si non et ipsi pari conscientia polluuntur¹⁰⁷⁴.

In Francia, during the turmoil of the 820's, Wala, Benedictine abbot of Corbie (c. 755 – 836) and Einhard composed a *correction*, due to the disbalanced situation both inside and beyond Frankish realm. The year 827 was a very turbulent one, which brought some undesired troubles into the Carolingian realm (incursions of the Bulgarian and Slavonic tribes in Pannonia). The act of repentance composed by Wala and Einhard based on extracts from the Bible and the Fathers - as required from the emperor¹⁰⁷⁵. The episcopal negligence was also a pillar stone leading to scandal: the second section of the conciliar acts included Pseudo-

¹⁰⁷³ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 875–876; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.58, 1–3, 461.

¹⁰⁷⁴ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.4.1; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 51.

¹⁰⁷⁵ De Jong, *Penitential State* 171–174.

Cyprian's passage on the unjust ruler¹⁰⁷⁶. The correction and penance, negligence of the office and scandal were the "key-words" of the Council of Paris, held in 829. God was offended, and the correction of sins was desperately needed¹⁰⁷⁷. Negligence was once again uttered as the key criterion leading to sin in the accusations held against Louis the Pious in 833. The Biblical contexts of *Admonitio*, *Correctio*, *Increpatio* and *Exhortatio* were frequently employed in the 8th- and 9th-century Frankish narratives¹⁰⁷⁸.

In the mind-set of the Byzantines, the sin of heresy represented one of the greatest sins on the ladder of sins. One could deduce that judging by certain accounts contained in the apocalyptic literature as well, since, according to Jane Baun, this literary genre has been written for and about people in the first place, reflecting the populace's fears, hopes and strivings¹⁰⁷⁹. In the Gospel of Anastasia, a separate punishment zone is reserved for elite sinners, coming from the ranks of high ecclesiastics and emperors¹⁰⁸⁰. Additionally, in the apocryphal gospel according to the Mother of God, the first aggrupation of sinners to be met on a voyage to the afterworld, once a boundary separating this world from the afterworld has been crossed, are the heretics. This offers insight into how heavy was the sin of heresy in the Byzantine consciousness¹⁰⁸¹. Apart from this document, other authors supported this view¹⁰⁸².

After having cleansed our hearts, Photius says, we have "reaped the fruit of repentance" - ...ἐπὶ τῇ μετανοίᾳ καρποὺς ἐτρυγήσαμεν¹⁰⁸³. While repentance prevent destruction, negligence (ἡ ἀμέλεια), however, could represent an obstacle to repentance¹⁰⁸⁴.

Particular set of rituals and regulations prescribed the re-entry of the "lapsed sheep" to the Mother Church. Apparently, this penitential phase took up an important share of life of the ecclesiastic and spiritual community. Important scholarly work has covered the topic and semantic field related to the concept of *μετάνοια*¹⁰⁸⁵, as well as the particular repentance

¹⁰⁷⁶ Cf. The Council of Paris, a. 829, m. Iunio, ed. A. Werminghoff 650–651; Ps. Cyprian, *De duodecim abusioibus Saeculi Tractatus* (ed. Migne, PL 4) 869–882B, here (on *rex iniquus*) c. 9, 877–878; cf. De Jong, *Penitential State* 181, note 156.

¹⁰⁷⁷ De Jong, *Penitential State* 40.

¹⁰⁷⁸ De Jong, *Penitential State* 118.

¹⁰⁷⁹ J. Baun, *Tales from Another Byzantium. Celestial Journey and Local Community in the Medieval Greek Apocrypha* (Cambridge 2007) 1–9.

¹⁰⁸⁰ Baun, *Another Byzantium, Anastasia*, 15.

¹⁰⁸¹ Baun, *Another Byzantium, Theotokos*, 11.

¹⁰⁸² Pargoire, *Église byzantine* 347.

¹⁰⁸³ Mango, *Homilies*, 4th homily 104; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 47, l. 5–6.

¹⁰⁸⁴ Mango, *Homilies*, 4th homily 105–106; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 48, l. 17–18.

¹⁰⁸⁵ A. de Vogüé, *Histoire Littéraire du mouvement monastique de l'antiquité. Deuxième partie: le monachisme grec. Vol. 2: De l'Histoire Lausiaque aux premiers acémètes (Ve-VIIe siècles)* (Roma 2015) 177.

rituals¹⁰⁸⁶. Additionally, the practice of public penance of the bishops has also been attested in Byzantium¹⁰⁸⁷.

A canon ascribed to the Second Ecumenical Council decreed on various heretical groups: Arians, Macedonians, Novatians, Apollinarians, Tessaeskaidekatitai. Persons belonging to these heretical groups should not be re-baptized, but only anointed. The abjuration formulas were an obligatory part of the prescribed rituals.

Photius writes exhaustively on repentance, penance, and the danger of scandal¹⁰⁸⁸. In his account on Arius, Photius informs us that the heretic has not been accepted back into the church even after his repentance¹⁰⁸⁹. Namely, he had been accepted back by the archbishops of Alexandria and Achillas, as well as Alexander; nevertheless, Athanasius, after Alexander's death, refused to acknowledge his recantation¹⁰⁹⁰. This points to the conclusion that each and every case of repentance was particular indeed, with the outcome depending on human elements as well. Furthermore, according to Photius, the "law of pardon" - *ἡ τῆς συγγώμης τάξις*¹⁰⁹¹ - forbids, in most cases, the taking of recurrent repentants back into the Church¹⁰⁹². To reject the person from the church who had erred once, but repented, would be inhuman, argues Photius; still, to accept the repentance of a recurrent sinner would signify that no difference was made between being impious and pious¹⁰⁹³.

Photius focuses also on the former heretics, adherents to the Tessaeskaidekatitai (Quartodecimans), who came dressed in white robes to St. Sophia on Holy Saturday and were allowed to join the congregation¹⁰⁹⁴. On the previous day, the Good Friday, they abjured their errors. This particular ceremony of their re-entrance to the Church and to the body of Christ was apparently performed in the baptistery.

¹⁰⁸⁶ cf. Photius, *Les formules d'abjuration*, in: Photius, *Contra Manichaeos*, ed. Astruc et al. 190f.; cf. A. Torrance, *Repentance in Late Antiquity: Eastern Asceticism and the Framing of the Christian Life c. 400 – 650 CE* (Oxford 2013).

¹⁰⁸⁷ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the World* 137–138; cf. P. Alexander, *Church Councils and Patristic Authority*, in: *Harvard Studies in Classical Philology* 63 (1958) 493–505, at 49, as cited from Parry, *Depicting the World* 138, note 29.

¹⁰⁸⁸ Photius, *Amphilochia*, *Ad Amphilochium Questio XX*, ed. Migne 145–148

¹⁰⁸⁹ Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily 244–245; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 139–140.

¹⁰⁹⁰ for more information on this particular issue, see Mango, *Homilies* 245, fn 7.

¹⁰⁹¹ Mango, *Homilies* 246; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 140, l. 17–18.

¹⁰⁹² Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily 246; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 140–141.

¹⁰⁹³ Mango, *Homilies*, 15th homily 246; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 140, l. 6–15.

¹⁰⁹⁴ Mango, *Homilies*, 17th homily 279, 288, 289; cf. Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 166, l. 1–5.

In his 15th and 16th homilies, Photius tells of a Patriarch John the Grammarian, whom he compares with Arius. Namely, John was Patriarch of Constantinople from 837 to 843; he was an Iconodule, who later joined the heretics, but then repented, and the Patriarch Nicephorus took him back to the body of believers. Nevertheless, when he joined the heretic ranks once more, even with pretensions to become their leader, the patriarch refused to pardon him and number him again among the flock (apparently in the 810's)¹⁰⁹⁵. Similar to John the Patriarch, Arius, head of the heresy, once held a priestly rank. After having repented from his heresy and relapsed into his heretical doctrine several times, he was also refused pardon, since he was charged with having simulated repentance¹⁰⁹⁶. In this case, Photius speaks of a “mask of repentance” – *μετανοίας προσωπεῖον*¹⁰⁹⁷.

By the end of the 9th century, at the Council of Nicaea in 787 and upon the restoration of image worship, the Iconoclast bishops were permitted to return to their episcopal functions after having repented. Some Studite monks (apparently led by Theodore the Studite) were against these practices¹⁰⁹⁸. Later, during the conflict with Patriarch Methodius regarding the treatment of the repented Iconoclasts, the patriarch accepted only those, who, upon their repentance, had been ordained by Patriarchs Tarasius and Nicephorus¹⁰⁹⁹.

Theodore the Studite writes on the topic of repentance on numerous occasions. For example, in his 40th letter, he insists upon the fact that schismatics have to anathematize their heresy and to be anointed or re-baptized¹¹⁰⁰.

Moreover, at the end of the second decade of the 9th century, Theodore consecrates his letters 302, 433 and 538, to a Studite monk called Clement, who lapsed into heretic belief and left his community. Later, he was brought back to Orthodoxy and rehabilitated in his monastery¹¹⁰¹.

¹⁰⁹⁵ Mango, *Homilies*, 240–243f.; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 140–141; on the details of John's monastic repentance and his dispute with Nicephorus, see: Mango, *Homilies* 243, note 41: PG 95, 372B.

¹⁰⁹⁶ Mango, *Homilies* 245–247; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 139–141.

¹⁰⁹⁷ Mango, *Homilies* 246–7; Photius, *Homilies*, ed. Laourda 141, l. 5.

¹⁰⁹⁸ Dvornik, *Photian schism* 8.

¹⁰⁹⁹ Dvornik, *Photian schism* 15; V. Grumel, *La Politique Religieuse du Patriarche St. Methode*, in *Echos d'Orient* 34 (1935) 385–401.

¹¹⁰⁰ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, I, Ep. 40, ed. Migne 1049D–1057D.

¹¹⁰¹ cf. Efthymiadis, *Correspondence of Theodore the Studite* 148–149.

II. 12. SEVERANCE FROM THE BODY OF CHURCH

This chapter opens the final stages of this exposition – that, on the severance of religious dissenters in the first place. In this section, the severance in the form of an interdiction to participate in the Eucharist – the body of the Church – has been presented, in the appropriate examples from the selected textual evidence.

*Bene: propter incredulitatem fracti sunt. Tu autem fide stas: noli altum sapere, sed time. Si enim Deus naturalibus ramis non pepercit: ne forte nec tibi parcat. Vide ergo bonitatem, et severitatem Dei: in eos quidem qui ceciderunt, severitatem: in te autem bonitatem Dei, si permanseris in bonitate, alioquin et tu excideris*¹¹⁰² - “Well; because of unbelief they were broken off, and thou standest by faith. Be not highminded, but fear: For if God spared not the natural branches, take heed lest he also spare not thee. Behold therefore the goodness and severity of God: on them which fell, severity; but toward thee, goodness, if thou continue in his goodness: otherwise thou also shalt be cut off”¹¹⁰³.

The enemies of the Church are to be punished, according to the Theodosian Code:

*Omnes haereses omnesque perfidias, omnia schismata superstitionesque gentilium, omnes catholicae legi inimicos insectamur errores*¹¹⁰⁴.

The Theodosian Code compels the monks to inhabit desert places, because they were originally hermits; additionally, it is stated that numerous fanatics incited seditions:

*Quicumque sub professione monachi reperiuntur, deserta loca et vastas solitudines sequi adque habitare iubeantur*¹¹⁰⁵.

The municipalities were forbidden to certain monks:

*Monachos, quibus interdictae fuerant civitates, dum iudiciariis aluntur iniuriis, in pristinum statum submota hac lege esse praecipimus...*¹¹⁰⁶

¹¹⁰² Rom. 11:20–22, Vulgata.

¹¹⁰³ Rom. 11:20–22, King James Version.

¹¹⁰⁴ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 877; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.63, 462.

¹¹⁰⁵ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 853; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.3.1, 449.

¹¹⁰⁶ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 853; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.3.2, 449

Disturbers of peace of the Church are treated as traitors. Namely, those who attempt to undertake any agitation against the regulations, are seen as “authors of sedition and as disturbers of the peace of the Church”, and “they shall pay the penalty of high treason with their lives and blood”:

*His, qui sibi tantummodo existimant colligendi copiam contributam, si turbulentum quippiam contra nostrae tranquillitatis praeceptum faciendum esse temptaverint, ut seditionis auctores pacisque turbatae ecclesiae, maiestatis capite ac sanguine sint supplicia luituri*¹¹⁰⁷.

*Nulli egresso ad publicum vel disceptandi de religione vel tractandi vel consilii aliquid deferendi patescat occasio. Et si quis posthac ausu gravi adque damnabili contra huiusmodi legem veniendum esse crediderit vel insistere motu pestiferae perseverationis audebit, competenti poena et digno supplicio coherceatur*¹¹⁰⁸.

In the Theodosian Code, the heretics are portrayed as alienated, from the perspective of the Catholic Church. Furthermore, The religious privileges are reserved for the adherents of the Catholic creed only, whereas the heretics and schismatics are considered excluded from these privileges:

*Privilegia, quae contemplatione religionis indulta sunt, catholicae tantum legis observatoribus prodesse oportet. Haereticos autem atque schismaticos non solum ab his privilegiis alienos esse volumus, sed etiam diversis muneribus constringi et subici*¹¹⁰⁹.

The status of the Eunomian heretics is equated with that of the foreigners, regarding their property and testament:

*Eunomianis poenam adimendae testamenti factionis peregrinorumque mutandae condicionis remittimus. Patimur eos et donandi e suis facultatibus, ut velint, et dono rursus ab aliis accipiendi habere liberam potestatem*¹¹¹⁰.

The state unmistakably aims at protecting itself from the heretics, through the economic/fiscal disinheritance and the confiscation of their goods. Besides, the heretics are unambiguously marked as outcasts and their heresy is ascribed to the rank of public crime:

¹¹⁰⁷ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 853; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.4.1, 449.

¹¹⁰⁸ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 853–854; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.4.2, 449.

¹¹⁰⁹ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 855; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.1, 450.

¹¹¹⁰ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 855; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.36, 456.

...Praecipue tamen manichaeos vel frygas sive priscillianistas meritissima severitate persequimur. Huic itaque hominum generi nihil ex moribus, nihil ex legibus sit commune cum ceteris. Ac primum quidem volumus esse publicum crimen, quia quod in religionem divinam committitur, in omnium fertur iniuriam.

Quos bonorum etiam publicatione persequimur, quae tamen cedere iubemus proximis quibusque personis, ita ut ascendentium vel descendentium vel venientium ex latere cognatorum usque ad secundum gradum velut in successione ordo servetur. Quibus ita demum ad capiendas facultates esse ius patimur, si non et ipsi pari conscientia polluuntur¹¹¹¹.

The message of the Justinian Code is equally significant, as of the Theodosian Code: he, who is opposed to the *vera fides* is to be alienated from the communion and from the catholic Church:

Haec est igitur vestra vera fides, haec certa religio, hoc beatae recordationis, ut diximus, patres omnes praesulesque romanae ecclesiae, quos in omnibus sequimur, hoc sedes apostolica praedicavit hactenus et inconvulse custodivit: huic confessioni, huic fidei quisquis contradictor extiterit, alienum a sancta communione, alienum se ipse ab ecclesia iudicavit esse catholica.¹¹¹²

Similarly, according to Hincmar's *De Una et non Trina Deitate*, the ecclesiastics should strive towards exclusion of the "ill sheep" from the flock: *Pastoralis tamen necessitas habet, ne per plures serpant dira contagia, separare ab ovibus sanis morbidam, ab illo cui nihil est impossibile ipsa forsitan separatione sanandam....ut omnes velimus salvos fieri...*¹¹¹³

Moreover, he, who is excluded from the Catholic Church, is, by this very crime, disjoint from the unity in Christ. He will not have a life, but, according to Hincmar, the wrath of God shall stay upon him. He, who eats and drinks in the church undeservingly the body of Christ, shall be judged: *Quisquis autem a catholica Ecclesia fuerit separatus, quantumlibet laudabiliter se vivere existimet, hoc solo scelere, quod a Christi unitate disjunctus est, non habebit vitam, sed ira Dei manet super eum...et quicumque in ea corpus Christi manducavit ac biberit sanguinem indigne, iudicium sibi manducat et bibit¹¹¹⁴.*

¹¹¹¹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri*, cf. 855; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.40, 1, 2, 457.

¹¹¹² Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.1.8.30.

¹¹¹³ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 483A.

¹¹¹⁴ Hincmar, *De Una*, ed. Migne 483B.

Additionally, the basis of the afore-presented warning of severance from the body of the Church, lies in the following lines: the Catholics should not act against authority, unless they wish to be cut off from the body of Christ, as schismatics and non-Catholics. Namely, it is of the utter importance to sever the roots, in order for the crooked branches to dry out: *Nemo igitur catholicus contra auctoritatem, nemo pacificus contra Ecclesiae pacem certare audeat, ne schismaticus, et non catholicus, inveniatur, et a Christi corpore separetur....per quod salubriter abscindere sauciata debuerunt....Si enim radix elationis abscinditur, consequenter rami pravae assertionis arefiunt*¹¹¹⁵.

It is important, stresses Hincmar, for all the Catholics to recognize what is right, and not to step beyond one's position in the given (ecclesiastical) order. Everything within the Church is arranged according to the suitable disposition of the higher and lower limbs which constitute Christ's body: *...ut omnes Ecclesiae filii quae recta et sana sunt sapient, non tamen permittendum est ut quisquam extra sacerdotalem ordinem constitutus gradum sibi praedicatoris assumet, cum in Ecclesia Dei omnia ordinata esse conveniat, ut in uno Christi corpore, et excellentiora membra suum officium impleant, et inferiora superioribus non resultant*¹¹¹⁶.

Furthermore, the severance of the body of the church in the form of excommunication is foreseen as well, amid other forms of punishment for which include exile and/or imprisonment, for having acted against the regulations and without any discipline: *...et cum gradus privatione, atque a corporis et sanguinis Christi separatione, ut Gothescalcus pertinacissimus damnatus est, condemnabitur exsilii vel ergastuli relegatione: quatenus sicut apostolicae sedis statuta decernunt, qui contra statuta tenere tentaverit, et prohibita fuerit ausus admittere, a suo se noverit officio submovendum, nec communionis nostrae futurum esse consortem qui socius esse noluit disciplinae...*¹¹¹⁷. The duty and obligation of ecclesiastics is to separate the sick from the sane body parts: *Quae pastoralis necessitas habet per plures serpent dira contagia, separare ab sanis morbidam, ab illo cui nihil impossibile forsitan separatione sanandam*¹¹¹⁸. Hincmar, with this intention, quotes Pope Celestine's exposition on the religious souls who represent the limbs of the church: *Nefas est haec pati religiosas animas, quarum afflictione, quia membra nostra sunt, nos quoque convenit macerari...*¹¹¹⁹. Furthermore, Hincmar refers to Gregory the Great while underlying the importance of the unity of faith,

¹¹¹⁵ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 501CD.

¹¹¹⁶ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 503AB.

¹¹¹⁷ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 506AB.

¹¹¹⁸ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 508AB.

¹¹¹⁹ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 509AB.

ascertained under the aegis of the Church, and accomplished through the participation in the Eucharist: *Sed et pia mater Ecclesia pro omnibus in Christo, id est in unitate catholicae pacis ac fidei, et in communione corporis ac sanguinis Redemptoris ac Salvatoris nostri quiescentibus*. He, who is separated from the unity of the Church, due to heresy or schism, remains deprived of its *charitas*: *Quisquis ergo ab hac unitate matris Ecclesiae suae, per haeresim de Deo perversa sentiendo, seu errore schismatis proximum non diligendo dividitur, charitatis hujus gratia privatur*¹¹²⁰.

Arguing on the importance of unity among the body of believers, their respective emplacements and on the imperative in remaining in the body of Christ, Hincmar quotes Augustine: *Petrus in corpore oculus est, ille in corpore digitus est, in eo tamen corpore est in quo Petrus, et si minus valet digitus quam oculus, non est tamen praecisus a corpore. Melius est esse digitum et esse in corpore, quam esse oculum et evelli de corpore*. He then continues his narrative on Gottschalk, who was cut off from the body of Christ: *Deo gratias, qualescunque sacerdotes et in Ecclesiastico regimine positi, catholicam fidem servantes in Christi corpore, de quo evulsus est Gothescalcus*¹¹²¹.

In order to underline the importance of the concept of unity of the body of Christ, Hincmar refers to Augustine in quoting Biblical passage: *Ego in eis et tu in me. Ego in eis sicut caput in membris, et tu in me sicut Pater in Filio; ut sint consummati in unum, id est perfecti, quod perficiet qui nos voluit unum esse in se et per se*¹¹²². He continues his exposition on Christ as the head of the body of believers, joined in union, and quotes Augustine: *Nullum majus donum praestare posset Deus hominibus, quam ut Verbum suum per quod condidit omnia, faceret illis caput, et illos ei tamquam membra coaptaret, ut esset Filius Dei, et filius hominis, et unus Deus cum Patre, unus homo cum hominibus...et quando precatur corpus Filius, non a se separet caput suum, sitque unus ipse Salvator corporis sui Dominus noster Jesus Christus Filius Dei...orat in nobis ut caput nostrum*¹¹²³. Gottschalk, having acted against the sacred canons, is to be expelled from the Eucharist. He should be punished, as should every impious, obstinate, insolent, or disobedient monk be, according to St. Benedict: *Qui talia contra canones sacros praesumit...eo privari vel ab ecclesiastica communione separari est digne. Secundum regulam autem sancti Benedicti, improbus, durus, et superbus, vel inobediens...castigatione...est coercendus*¹¹²⁴. Gottschalk, as every disobedient monk, should

¹¹²⁰ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 562AB.

¹¹²¹ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 579CD.

¹¹²² Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 596AB.

¹¹²³ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 607AC.

¹¹²⁴ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 615BC.

be segregated from the healthy limbs of the body of Christ, in order to be prevented from harming the rest of the body. Hincmar compares him to a sheep suffering from an incurable illness which should not be permitted to contaminate the entire flock: *...a sanis Christi membris censura ecclesiastica segregandus, ne una ovis incurabili morbo languida totum gregem contaminet*¹¹²⁵.

In the following section of the narrative, Hincmar expounds on the reasons for which he judged Gottschalk guilty of his doctrine of double predestination, segregated him from the participation in the body and blood of Christ, and excommunicated him¹¹²⁶. On the other hand, sinners represent the limbs on the Devil's body, and the Devil attempts to violate the body of Christ: *Ille enim...in exemplum Iudae filium nominis tradit – non quidem Iudaeis peccatoribus, sed tamen peccatoribus, membris videlicet suis – qui illud inaestimabile Domini corpus violare praesumit*¹¹²⁷. Hincmar proceeds with instructions for the Christian flock, and by presenting desirable Christian precepts. Therefore, it is an imperative for a Christian not to live without communion with God and intermission of sins. Consequently, those who enter into communion with “the Prostitute”, become one body with her, differently to those who enter in communion and unity with God: *Quoniam sicut “qui adhaeret meretrici, unum corpus efficitur”, ita qui digne communicat, de ista communione unus spiritus est cum Domino, et in quo Deus habitat et ipse in Deo*¹¹²⁸.

After having compared Gottschalk to Simon the Magician, being equally *spiritu furioso exagitatus*¹¹²⁹, Hincmar addresses the core issue of the double predestination, and of the condemnation of Gottschalk. He, who evangelizes aside the (benediction of) Holy Spirit and six ecclesiastical councils, is to be anathematized. Furthermore, he, who acts outside the frame of the scriptural tradition and the tradition of the fathers, is to be condemned and separated from the community by exile or imprisonment, so that he does not endanger the others: *Si quis, inquam, aliter evangelizaverit praeter id quod evangelizatum est a sancto Spiritu per ora supradictorum doctorum et sanctorum episcoporum in sex praefatis conciliis, de unitate deitatis, quae est unitas trinitatis, et de omnibus capitulis ad orthodoxam fidem specialiter pertinentibus, quae catholica et apostolica praedicat et tenet Ecclesia, anathema sit. Et de his quae secundum tramitem Scripturarum traditionemque majorum diffinita sunt, contra*

¹¹²⁵ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 615BC.

¹¹²⁶ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 616AD.

¹¹²⁷ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 127, ed. Perels, 66–67, here 66, l. 27–29.

¹¹²⁸ Hincmar, Epistolae, Ep. 125, ed. Perels 60–62, here 62, l. 2.

¹¹²⁹ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 495BC.

*Gothescalcum, vel contra quemcunque alium, in quamcunque disputationem intrare nemo debet praesumere, sed damnatus, ut spuria vitulamina in ipsa radice amaritudinis, vel exsilio, vel ergastulo, separatus a consortio fidelium...*¹¹³⁰

In his narrative on Gottschalk, and the accusations of heresy held against him, Hincmar recurs to the actions undertaken by the Ecumenical synods which condemned heresies in the past and served as a bastion for any future heresy that might emerge. The spreading of another faith is not allowed. Hincmar has thus, through his *modus operandi*, positioned Gottschalk to the line of earlier heresies, which had been condemned by the Ecumenical Synods: *Et Constantinopolitanum concilium, fidem non violandam Patrum trecentorum decem et octo, qui apud Nicaeam Bythyniae convenerant, et manere eam firmam et stabilem, et anathematizandam omnem haeresim*¹¹³¹. Hincmar quotes the acta of the synod of Chalcedon which has also condemned heresies: “*Statuit sancta et universalis synodus alteram fidem nulli licere proferre, vel conscribere, aut componere, aut sentire, aut docere aliter eos autem qui ausi sint componere fidem alteram, aut proferre, aut docere, aut tradere alterum symbolum volenti vel converti, vel ex gentilibus ad cognitionem veritatis venire, vel ex Judaeis, vel haeresi quacunq[ue], eos, si episcopi fuerint aut clerici, alienos esse episcopos ab episcopatu et clericos a clero, si vero monachi aut laici fuerint, anathematizari.*”¹¹³² Consequently, Hincmar finishes, by referring to Gottschalk and his heretical doctrine and the consequences it induced: *Et haec omnia venerunt super Gothescalci caput...*

Hincmar quotes the 18th act of the Sixth Ecumenical Synod (680/1), to which Gottschalk had also alluded to, in presenting his interpretation of the Trinitarian issue. In this act, the concept of anathema is clearly stated and defined. Namely, those who accept and teach a doctrine of faith, other than the one proclaimed by the Ecumenical councils, and those who alter the symbol of faith, are to be expelled from the church, and anathematized: *Qui vero praesumpserint fidem alteram componere vel proferre vel docere vel tradere aliud symbolum volentibus converti ad agnitionem veritatis ex gentilitate vel Iudaismo aut ex qualibet haeresi; hos...alienos esse...anathematizari eos*¹¹³³.

¹¹³⁰ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 495CD.

¹¹³¹ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 498AB.

¹¹³² Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 498BC.

¹¹³³ Hincmar, De Una, ed. Migne 528AB.

Narratives accentuating the importance of the Eucharist and the excommunication from it, have frequently been present in the Byzantine authors likewise, writing on the relevant topic of religious dissent.

In a long letter written during his first exile, Photius mentions “members/limbs of Christ...with which we are united...being both torn asunder and utterly destroyed” while quoting I Cor. 12:12-27¹¹³⁴. He is not referring explicitly to heretics here, but rather alludes to the members of the Church. Discord in the Church results in “the scattering of her members and the dissolution of harmony which attends piety” - *Οὕτως αἱ πρὸς ἀλλήλους στάσεις καὶ φιλονεικίαι τὸν βίον ἀνέτρεψαν καὶ τὴν πίστιν διεσπάραξαν στάσις γὰρ ἐν μὲν ζώου σώματι λύσιν καὶ θάνατον ἀπεργάζεται, ἐν ἐκκλησίᾳ δὲ διασπορὰν τῶν μελῶν καὶ τῆς κατὰ τὴν εὐσέβειαν ἀρμονίας ἔκλυσιν καὶ τὸν ψυχικὸν παραγαμὸν καὶ τὸν ὄλεθρον*¹¹³⁵. The heretics are torn away from the Lord’s body, the Church, and take the side of the enemy; their members are no longer members of the body of the Church, but become the members of the “harlot conventicle” instead: *...τὰ μέλη αὐτοῦ τῆς νύμφης ἐκκλησίας ἀποσπαράζας μέλη τῆς πόρνης παρασυναγωγῆς ἀπεργάζεται*¹¹³⁶. Those taken by the most impious heresy or by the schismatic madness – *εἴτε δυσσεβεστάτης αἰρέσεως ἔρωτι, εἴτε σχισματικῆς μανίας φουσήματι* - are no longer in union with God, but are torn away from the Lord’s body – the Church: *...τοῦ κυριακοῦ σώματος τῆς ἐκκλησίας διασπώμενος*¹¹³⁷.

Therefore, the Eucharistic communion provides an exact reflection, as a *pars pro toto*, of the more amply understood communion between the members of the body of the Church themselves, and the head of the Church and its believers. The severance of the members of the body of the Church could have led to exile, but also to excommunication from the Eucharist. Excommunication was a frequent penance in the Early Middle Ages – both in the West, as in the East.

If a person nourished contacts with heretics, or obtained their benediction, or was simply in friendly relations with them¹¹³⁸, according to Theodore the Studite - he or she was forbidden the Eucharistic service, for a more or less long period, sometimes even until their death¹¹³⁹. “Until when will the penance last?” – asks Theodore in his letter; “Until the peace of

¹¹³⁴ Cf. Stratoudaki White, Patriarch Photios 149, Epistola 8.

¹¹³⁵ Photius’s 16th homily, Mango 275; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 161, l. 9–13.

¹¹³⁶ Photius 16th homily, Mango 277; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 162, l. 21–22.

¹¹³⁷ Photius 16th homily, Mango 277; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 162, l. 16–17, 19–20; cf. 1 Cor. 6:16.

¹¹³⁸ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 32, ed. Migne 1205AB, referring to John Chrysostom.

¹¹³⁹ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 11, ed. Migne 1148C; Ibid., Ep. 95, 1348C.

the orthodox faith returns” – he answers: *Quoad orthodoxae fidei tranquillitas redeat – ἕως ἂν ἀναλάμψη ἡ τῆς ὀρθοδοξίας αἰθρία*¹¹⁴⁰.

Adherence to heresies thus implied excommunication. The schism resulted in the same measures being taken¹¹⁴¹. In this realm we approach other issues which were not directly relevant to heresies – the practice of second marriage, for example. Nonetheless, almost every sin had excommunication as a consequential punishment¹¹⁴².

The course of the narrative of Theodore’s epistle addressed to young Athanasius follows the exposition of the events related to the upsurge and the continuation of the Moechian controversy. Theodore stresses the reason why transgressors of the ecclesiastical canons and supporters of the second marriage of the ruler should be called heretics: those who approve of the adulterine union, and thus infract the divine canons, should be anathematized¹¹⁴³. The crucial precept, by which Theodore is led, is that the Church should stay stainless¹¹⁴⁴. For that reason, the infracting of the ecclesiastical canons results in the impurity of the Church. The line from the opening section of the epistle is put forward, with the aim of offering an explanation after having exposed the grounds for qualifying the Moechian heresy as the heaviest one - *...χαλεπωτάτη οὖν αἴρεσις αὕτη*¹¹⁴⁵. The Moechian heresy is thus elevated to the upper level – or, upgraded – by having transferred the infraction of the ecclesiastical canons to the disrespect towards God: *...λαλεῖν πρὸς τὸν Θεὸν πλάνησιν*¹¹⁴⁶. Consequently, the cleric who performed this illicit union should be excommunicated¹¹⁴⁷.

As already shown above, allusion to the same Biblical passage, but in another context, can be observed in Pope Nicholas’s letter addressed to Photius, in referring to *meretrix*.

¹¹⁴⁰ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 11, ed. Migne 1148C.

¹¹⁴¹ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, II, Ep. 49, Ep. 215, ed. Migne 1260A, 1648; Ibid., II, Ep. 219, 1665.

¹¹⁴² Pargoire, *Église byzantine* 344–347.

¹¹⁴³ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1076D.

¹¹⁴⁴ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1080A, cf. Ephes. 5:25–27.

¹¹⁴⁵ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1080B.

¹¹⁴⁶ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1080B, cf. Isa., 32:6.

¹¹⁴⁷ Theodore the Studite, Epistolae, I, Ep. 48, ed. Migne 1080D.

II. 13. SEVERANCE IN THE FORM OF EXILE

In the last chapter, the topic of severance from the body of Christians in the form of exile in relation to religious dissent will be researched, as contained in the relevant narratives and source material. Hence, this closing chapter presents the last stage of the sequences, enumerated at the opening of the second segment of this thesis. The rather exhaustive semantic field of exile will summarily encompass some pivotal forms of it – namely political, poetical, and allegorical exile.

The topic of Medieval exile was quite well represented in Medieval Latin, Greek and vernacular texts¹¹⁴⁸. Nevertheless, this theme remains insufficiently explored - especially in relation to the Early Medieval exile. Exile in the Middle Ages took different forms. Exile could be observed as a literary theme, as voluntary/involuntary, factual/metaphysical. Recent research on medieval exiled authors has mainly focused upon the Late Medieval period¹¹⁴⁹, or has dealt with some of the echoes of the Late Antiquity and Classical tradition¹¹⁵⁰ among early Christian and Carolingian authors. On the other hand, numerous studies have tackled some aspects of the exiled authors' writings in the scope of other research topics¹¹⁵¹. Nevertheless, the comparative perspective of the 9th-century Carolingian and Byzantine exiled authors has not thoroughly been given.

The Theodosian Code clearly demonstrates that the heretics and heresies, forms of religious dissent (the “delinquents” - *delinquentes*) were regulated by the law and often sentenced to exile¹¹⁵².

¹¹⁴⁸ E. M. C. van Houts ed., *Exile in the Middle Ages* (Turnhout 2004).

¹¹⁴⁹ L. Napran/E. van Houts ed, *Exile in the Middle Ages: Selected Proceedings from the International Medieval Congress, University of Leeds, 8-11 July 2002* (Turnhout 2004).

¹¹⁵⁰ J.-F. Gaertner, *Writing Exile: The Discourse of Displacement in Greco-Roman Antiquity and Beyond* (Leiden 2007); Dunning, *Aliens and Sojourners*; S. Viarre, *Exil ovidien, exil médiéval*, in: *Colloque Présence d'Ovide*, ed. R. Chevallier (Paris 1982) 261–271; L. Harf-Lancner/L. M.Maille-Szkilnik ed, *Ovide métamorphosé: les lecteurs médiévaux d'Ovide* (Paris 2009).

¹¹⁵¹ A. L. Taylor, *Epic lives and Monasticism in the Middle Ages, 800 – 1050* (Cambridge 2013).

¹¹⁵² Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri 863–864*; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.25, 454.

Book XVI of the Theodosian Code is dedicated to the heresies. It instructs on how to deal with heretics, and throughout the entire book, the narrative is threaded with the examples of proscribed exile as the form of punishment for heretics.

If the former bishop “should be apprehended in making any attempts either against the public security or against the public peace, or in seeking again the priesthood from which he appears to have been expelled, he shall, according to the law of Gratian of sainted memory, spend his life a hundred miles away from that city which he has corrupted”:

*Quicumque residentibus sacerdotibus fuerit episcopali loco detrusus et nomine, si aliquid vel contra custodiam vel contra quietem publicam moliri fuerit deprehensus, rursusque sacerdotium petere, a quo videtur expulsus, procul ab ea urbe, quam infecit, secundum legem divae memoriae Gratiani, centum milibus vitam agat*¹¹⁵³.

According to the Theodosian Code, he, who disarrays faith and people and does not heed the law, should be exiled. Namely, if someone disturbs “both the Catholic faith and the people and if he has failed to heed the admonition of the general law...he is deserving of deportation”:

*Deportatione dignus est, qui nec generali lege admonitus nec competenti sententia emendatus et fidem catholicam turbat et populum*¹¹⁵⁴.

The Theodosian Code thus insists upon the fact that the heretics should be entirely secluded:

*Apollinarianos ceterosque diversarum haeresum sectatores ab omnibus locis iubemus inhiberi, a moenibus urbium, a congressu honestorum, a communione sanctorum; instituendorum clericorum non habeant potestatem colligendarum congregationum vel in publicis vel in privatis ecclesiis careant facultate...*¹¹⁵⁵

Those who pollute the divine (Catholic) teaching by the sacrilegious rite, as it is furtherly explained by the Theodosian Code, shall be sent into exile (also to solitary islands):

Clerici vero ministrique eorum ac perniciosissimi sacerdotes, ablati de Africano solo, quod ritu sacrilego polluerunt, in exilium viritim ad singulas quasque regiones sub idonea prosecutione mittantur, ecclesiis eorum vel conventiculis praediisque, si qua in eorum ecclesias

¹¹⁵³ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 847; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.2.35, 446.

¹¹⁵⁴ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 854; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.4.3, 449.

¹¹⁵⁵ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 860; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.14, 453.

*haereticorum largitas prava contulit, proprietati potestatique catholicae, sicut iam dudum statuimus, vindicatis*¹¹⁵⁶.

The Manichaeans, for example, are to be segregated from the community. Furthermore, the teachers of the Manichaean (“profane”) doctrine will be severely punished – and those who participate in their assemblies shall be “segregated from the company of men as infamous and ignominious”. If the Manichaeans bring disturbance into the world, they should be expelled:

Quicumque sub nomine manichaeorum mundum sollicitant, ex omni quidem orbe terrarum, sed quam maxime de hac urbe pellantur sub interminatione iudicii.

*Voluntates autem eorundem, quin immo ipsae etiam facultates populo publicatae nec vim testamentorum teneant nec derelinqui per eos aut isdem fas sit. Nihil ad summum his sit commune cum mundo*¹¹⁵⁷.

The Theodosian Code clearly states that the heretics shall be expelled beyond the city boundary:

*...Quoscumque autem deprehenderit culpaе huius adfines, cum ipsis, quibus et in legum nostrarum et in religionum excidium coniventiam praestiterunt, non solum militia eximi, verum etiam extra moenia urbis huiusce iubebis arceri*¹¹⁵⁸.

The heretics are to be “kept outside the walls of this city” as well; they shall be expelled and are not allowed to convene within the city walls:

*Praeterea omnes clerici haereticorum ex sacratissima urbe pellantur neque his finibus liceat convenire*¹¹⁵⁹.

The teachers of the “crime of the Eunomians” shall be exiled from the municipalities; the Montanists likewise:

Auctores doctoresque eunomianorum facinoris investigati clericique maxime, quorum furor tantum suasit errorem, e civitatibus pellantur extorres.

¹¹⁵⁶ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 872–873; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.52, 5, 459.

¹¹⁵⁷ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 855; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.3, p. 450; cf. 16.5.18, 1, 453–4.

¹¹⁵⁸ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 864–865; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.29, 455.

¹¹⁵⁹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 865; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.30, 1, 455.

*Eunomianae superstitionis clerici seu montanistae consortio vel conversatione civitatum universarum adque urbium expellantur*¹¹⁶⁰.

Furthermore, the Theodosian Code underlines that the punishment of exile is foreseen for the pagans as well, who offer sacrifices to the demons:

*...paganos qui supersunt, si aliquando in execrandis daemonum sacrificiis fuerint comprehensi, quamvis capitali poena subdi debuerint, bonorum proscriptione ac exilium cohercebit*¹¹⁶¹.

Thereby, the insanity of the heretics and exile are aligned in a graded sequence:

*Post alia: manichaeos illosque, quos peyzitas vocant, nec non et eos, qui omnibus haereticis hac una sunt persuasione peiores, quod in venerabili die paschae ab omnibus dissentiunt, si in eadem amentia perseverant, eadem poena multamus, bonorum proscriptione atque exilio*¹¹⁶².

As in the *Codex Theodosianus*, the heretics are to be expelled beyond the city walls, according to the Justinian Code as well:

*...cum omnes haereticos illicitas agere intra oppida congregationes vetemus. ac si quid eruptio factiosa temptaverit, ab ipsis etiam urbium moenibus exterminato furore propelli iubemus...*¹¹⁶³

The Manichaeans are also among those heretics to be expelled from the cities: *Manichaeis etiam de civitatibus expellendis et ultimo supplicio tradendis...*¹¹⁶⁴

Nonappliance to the interdiction to heretics to establish their own priests is punished with exile. Additionally, it has been emphasized that the heretics bear different names, but perform the equivalent sacrilege and are therefore mutually connected by their wrongdoings:

Idcirco apollinaristae, hoc est eutylianistae (quibus etsi est in appellatione diversitas, tamen in haeresis pravitate coniunctio, et dispar quidem nomen, sed idem sacrilegium) sive in hac alma urbe diversisque provinciis sive in alexandrina civitate...episcopos vel presbyteros

¹¹⁶⁰ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 865–856; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.5.31, 455; *Ibid.*, 16.5.34, 455.

¹¹⁶¹ Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 904; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.10.21, 475–476.

¹¹⁶² Mommsen, *Theodosiani Libri* 904–905; Pharr, *The Theodosian Code*, 16.10.24, 476.

¹¹⁶³ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.1.2.2, also in 1.1.4.3; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 5

¹¹⁶⁴ *Codex Justinianus*, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.5.1; Krueger, *Codex Justinianus* 51.

*aliosque clericos creare et habere prohibemus...poenam exilii cum facultatum suarum amissione se subituros*¹¹⁶⁵.

Besides, not only heretics are sentenced to exile; the Justinian Code equally mentions the punishment of perpetual exile. In this case precisely, it is reserved for the Jews, if they circumcise a Christian:

*Iudaei et bonorum proscriptione et perpetuo exilio damnabuntur, si nostrae fidei hominem circumcidisse eos vel circumcidendum mandasse constiterit*¹¹⁶⁶.

Pagan rites are equaled to crime; the corporeal punishment, followed by that of perpetual exile is imposed to the owners of the houses, in which the pagan rites have been performed:

*In tantum autem huiusmodi facinora volumus esse resecauda, ut, etiamsi in alieno praedio vel domo aliquid tale perpetratur, scientibus videlicet dominis, praedium quidem vel domus sacratissimi viribus aerarii addicetur, domini vero pro hoc solo, quod scientes consenserint sua loca talibus contaminari sceleribus...post cruciatus corporis operibus metallorum perpetuo deputabuntur exilio*¹¹⁶⁷.

The examples shown above unambiguously demonstrate the urge to delimitate the heretics from the inhabitants of the Ecumene, in the physical, geographical sense as well. The sentences on the deportation are also contained in the Theodosian Code.¹¹⁶⁸

II.13.1. Political exile

The Latin Early Middle Ages did not observe a sharp distinction between the public and secret sins¹¹⁶⁹. The exclusion from the communion followed the public acknowledgment of sin.

¹¹⁶⁵ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.5.8.2; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 52.

¹¹⁶⁶ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.9.16; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 62.

¹¹⁶⁷ Codex Justinianus, <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/justinian/codex1.shtml>, 14/08/2017, 22/08/2017, 1.11.8.1; Krueger, Codex Justinianus 63.

¹¹⁶⁸ Mommsen, Theodosiani Libri 875; Pharr, The Theodosian Code, 16.5.57, 461.

¹¹⁶⁹ De Jong, Penitential State 232–234; For more information on the transformations of penance, see: Ibid., 202–217.

Public penance was applied by Louis the Pious in the form of monastic exile, as a demonstration of the principle of royal discipline¹¹⁷⁰. In cases of internal exile, the culprits were also sent to monasteries – for example, during Bernard’s rebellion against Louis the Pious in 818¹¹⁷¹, or in the case of Adalhard, after having contested Benedict in respect to the interpretation of the *Regula Benedicti*¹¹⁷². As a consequence, monasteries became endowed with the added function, as places for public penance of internal *exilés*, that is, for political *exilés*¹¹⁷³.

During the reign of Louis the Pious, many political opponents were banished: for example Wala of Corbie, who suffered exile twice: in 814, together with Adalhard, and who was rehabilitated in 822, and the second time, in 830¹¹⁷⁴.

In Francia, Paschasius Radbert (c. 785 – c. 860) made allusions to Ovid who was sent to exile during the reign of Augustus¹¹⁷⁵.

Exile is alluded to as a sort of penance, as stated in a letter of Pope Nicholas, written on the occasion of the conversion of the Bulgars: ...*sufficeret ad poenam illi repulsio a patria vestra, quam cum detruncatione membrorum iudicantibus vobis expertus est*¹¹⁷⁶. Exile as penance is compared to the severance of the limbs, resulting in the culprit’s exile – since he will be placed outside of the society (implying - outside of hierarchy as well) which banished him. The entirety of chapter XX is written on different forms of exile: by quoting scriptural verses (Gen. 12:1,4), the Pope distinguishes between *exilium* and *fuga*, with obedience as the main differentiating criterion – leading to the conclusion that obedience excludes the possibility of sin. Thus, voluntary exile was likewise explained: Namely, ...*quod quia fecit oboediens, nemine iudicante poenam quamlibet protulit*¹¹⁷⁷.

Dedicated to the growth of the seed of *fides recta* among the newly-baptized Bulgars – as a counterbalance to idolatry¹¹⁷⁸, and hoping to prevent their potential return to paganism, the Pope Nicholas advises them, by referring to St. Paul’s epistle¹¹⁷⁹, and reminds them that those

¹¹⁷⁰ De Jong, Penitential State 232–234; Id., Power and humility in Carolingian society; Id., What was *public* about public penance? Paenitentia publica and justice in the Carolingian world, in: La giustizia nell’alto medioevo (secolo ix-xi), Settimane 44 (1997) 863–904; Id., Transformations of Penance.

¹¹⁷¹ Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 29.

¹¹⁷² De Jong, Penitential State 23.

¹¹⁷³ Cf. De Jong, Penitential State 29.

¹¹⁷⁴ On Adalhard’s exile: Cf. Vita Adalhardi, Paschasius Radbertus, according to De Jong, Penitential State 127, note 56 and 58.

¹¹⁷⁵ De Jong, Penitential State 109, note 260.

¹¹⁷⁶ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 576, l. 40–41.

¹¹⁷⁷ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 579, l. 10–11.

¹¹⁷⁸ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 582, l. 40.

¹¹⁷⁹ Cf. 1 Cor. 5:12,13.

who are “outside”, do not represent St. Paul’s concern: *Nam eos, qui foris sunt, Deus iudicabit...De his, qui extra religionem nostram sunt, nihil ego iudico, sed eos Dei iudicio reservo, qui iudicaturus est omnem carnem*¹¹⁸⁰. Furthermore, the pagans and idolaters are expressly indicated as those who fall outside the society and the official hierarchical grades – those who consider their sect more trustworthy and more sacred than Christianity: *...per hoc veratiorem et sanctiorem suam sectam quam nostram existimet religionem*¹¹⁸¹. Additionally, the alliance with pagans is desirable only to the degree to which it pertains to the Christian cult - *ad cultum veri Dei* - since believers and non-believers do not have anything in common¹¹⁸²: *Inveniuntur autem nonnulli sanctorum et fidelium cum alienigenis et infidelibus pacta et amicitiae foedere contraxisse diversa*¹¹⁸³. Returning to the afore-mentioned, these foreigners, or *alienigeni*, might be semantically related to those who had fallen outside of society – referred to as the severed limbs – and thus picturesquely portrayed as severed members of society¹¹⁸⁴. The term *alienus* is similarly applied to Photius, as he had started his career firstly as a layman: in another letter, the Pope inserts in his condemnation of Photius’s election the narrative of the lay and clerical ranks. Namely, Photius has thus ascended from a lay rank, argues Pope Nicholas, and reached the patriarchal office too swiftly: *ac per hoc fit, ut alienus comedat ipsorum fructus laborum et stipendia meritorum extraneus hostis insperatus subripiat, ita ut nihil proficiat clericis in castris dominicis militasse vel gradatim per singulos ecclesiasticos ordines ascendisse, dum alter saltu hos omnes transcendit*¹¹⁸⁵. With these words, the Pope implies the status of foreigner to the layman, in affairs pertaining to the ecclesiastical cursus.

Theodore the Studite was thrice banished: first, between 795/6 and 798 to Thessalonica; then in 809 on canonical grounds upon the decisions of the so-called Moechian Synod to the Princes’ Islands, and lastly, in 815-821, on doctrinal grounds (during the second Iconoclast period) – to Bythina and Smyrna. Thus, it is important to underline the fact that Theodore was, generally speaking, banished by the official ecclesiastical policy of Byzantium in a twofold respect: in regard to the Moechian Synod, and in regard to the upsurge of the Iconoclast crisis.

During his time spent in exile, Theodore, who was already an accomplished and renowned figure – an abbot of the well-known and respected Studite monastery - attempted to preserve

¹¹⁸⁰ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 583, l. 20–22.

¹¹⁸¹ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 583, l. 24–25.

¹¹⁸² Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 594, l. 38–41.

¹¹⁸³ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 595, l. 2–3.

¹¹⁸⁴ Cf. above, Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 576, l. 40–41.

¹¹⁸⁵ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 98, ed. Perels 564, l. 8–11.

the Christian flock from the official position of the Church which he considered erroneous. His attitude towards the official ecclesiastical climate of those days could indeed be perceived as dissenting¹¹⁸⁶. Hence, the struggle of a long date for truth, correct interpretation and delimitation of dissens – has continued. In numerous letters which he composed during his exiles, Theodore acted in a sort of propagandistic way – trying to spread his opinion and address pivotal divergent issues to the key ecclesiastics of his time. Theodore strongly objected to the breaking of the ecclesiastical canons in the case of Moechian Synod, which banished him in 809¹¹⁸⁷. In his letter to Makarios¹¹⁸⁸, focused upon the Moechian issue, Theodore overtly identifies priests in line with Joseph who performed the second marriage of Constantine VI as heretics, as already elaborated above.

The Studite monks rebelled against the patriarch; Theodore's numerous letters have thus discussed the heretical synod regarding the priest Joseph – which falls into the case of the heresies inherent to the inner structures of the Christian dogma. Other letters regarding the Joseph issue were also written by him. It is important to mention Theodore's letter in which he accuses the emperor Nicephorus of Moechian heresy¹¹⁸⁹. It would be of interest to note, that many monks and abbots from the urban area joined the ranks of the Iconoclasts¹¹⁹⁰.

II.13.2. Allegorical/poetical exile

*...Carissimi obsecro tamquam advenas et peregrinos abstinere vos a carnalibus desideriis quae militant adversus animam... Ergo jam non estis hospites, et advenæ : sed estis cives sanctorum, et domestici Dei.*¹¹⁹¹

¹¹⁸⁶ Cf. V. Baranov, Constructing the Underground Community: The Letters of Theodore the Studite and the Letter of Emperors Michael II and Theophilus to Louis the Pious, in: *Scrinium VI* (2010) 230–259, here 236.

¹¹⁸⁷ For more detail on the Moechian Synod, see above, chapter II.9.

¹¹⁸⁸ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 294, ed. Fatouros 294, 433–434.

¹¹⁸⁹ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 31, ed. Migne 1204; Cf. Efthymiadis, *Correspondence of Theodore the Studite* 161.

¹¹⁹⁰ Cf. more in detail on the social strata and urban versus rural areas in relation to heresies: K. Ringrose, *Monks and society in iconoclastic Byzantium*, in: *Byzantine Studies* 6 (1979) 130–151, here 147; Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 9, ed. Migne 1140B–1141B.

¹¹⁹¹ 1 Petr. 2:11; Ephes. 2:19 Vulgata/King James Version: “Dearly beloved, I beseech you as strangers and pilgrims, abstain from fleshly lusts, which war against the soul”...“Now therefore ye are no more strangers and foreigners, but fellow citizens with the saints, and of the household of God”.

In this sub-chapter, pivotal research questions have taken two directions and have been designed, in the first instance, in order to examine how the textual procedure tracing severance from the body of the Church was influenced by political events, and secondly, to frame the contours of the semantic field of allegorical exile in 9th-century Greek and Latin narratives. Furthermore, it is important to underline the fact that this sub-chapter represents only a draft, and a sketch of a much more exhaustive topic, which will be duly elaborated in the future.

Early Christians saw themselves as outsiders and foreigners: *...et confitentes quia peregrini et hospites sunt super terram* - "...and confessed that they were strangers and pilgrims on the earth"¹¹⁹². Nevertheless, the difficulty of defining the term "exile" in its ancient context remains (Greek *φυγή, ἐξορία*; lat. *fuga; exilium*). The term has somewhat different meaning today, since it spread to encompass both the expulsion and the individual exile in the ancient times. In addition, the classical authors did not always make a precise difference between exile and other forms of displacement¹¹⁹³.

The question of adopting the suitable methodology for demarcating the "in-" from the "outsiders" in the Early Middle Ages pertains to a broader cultural discourse of exile. Namely, a lot has been written on the notion of "otherness" in the field of philosophy of science.¹¹⁹⁴

The discourse of insiders and others in the ancient Roman time, brought in connection to early Christian literary history, was recently presented by Dunning; the definition of "foreigner" in the Early Christian period was given in relation to its Classical heritage in the first place¹¹⁹⁵.

The approach to "otherness" in the Early Medieval times is first of all given in respect to and on the example as to how the particular authors, together with the official church, related to heretics and heresies of those days.

¹¹⁹² Epistle to Hebrews, 13:11, Vulgata and King James Version, to note only some.

¹¹⁹³ B. H. Dunning, *Aliens and Sojourners: Self as Other in Early Christianity* (Philadelphia-PA 2009), esp. sub-chapter "Exile and its Discursive Possibilities", 37–40; furthermore, the shift of meaning occurred in modern languages, where the term "refuge" has replaced the former "exile").

¹¹⁹⁴ Cf., for example: M. Foucault, *Madness and Civilization: A History of Insanity in the Age of Reason* (New York 1965); S. Mills, *Michel Foucault* (London 2003) 120–122 (Foucault on historical analysis), 116–119 (Implication of Foucault's work in Literary Analysis); cf. F. Jameson, *Marxism and Historicism, The Ideologies of Theory*, 2 (1988) 148–77, who argues that our understanding of history is always dialectic, oscillating between Identity and Difference; cf. P. Cartledge, *The Greeks: A Portrait of Self and Others* (Oxford 1993) precisely on the concept of 'otherness' as an instrument for definition or self-definition (although referring to the Ancient Greece); cf. P. Veyne, *L'inventaire des différences* (Paris 1976).

¹¹⁹⁵ Dunning, *Aliens and Sojourners*, esp. chapter 1, *Citizens and Aliens*, 25–45.

More precisely, the procedures according to which Carolingian authors depicted and differentiated the faithful from the unfaithful, could be observed on multiple examples, some of which are to be found in the freshly-published collected volume speaking, among other, on otherness in the Carolingian time. Categorizations of the kind, with the aim of producing such classifications, are to be found in several more recent works¹¹⁹⁶.

The Christian exilic tradition unquestionably grew out of soil that was already impregnated with Late Antique pagan archetype – that soil, sufficiently fertile to provide nutritive elements for the growth and development of the Christian Medieval exilic tradition. Thus, it would be instructive to place the concept of the Early Medieval exile within this wider scope, through the attempt to detect the earlier, preceding models¹¹⁹⁷.

Not all of the Early Medieval authors who spoke of exile actually suffered exile in the physical sense: sometimes, they were just feeding upon the exilic traditions. Allegorical and poetical exile were often intertwined; furthermore, both have frequently been interrelated with actual, suffered and induced exile, as demonstrated in numerous examples.

It may nevertheless be equally important to consider which events/semantic fields the author physically actualized in his life and work, and which traditions/semantic fields he was imbued within. Language, words, message: the semantic field of a given author is a key-word, a crucial determinant underlying the cloth of his narration and literary sense and style, constituted not only by the works which he studied and the sentences he heard and uttered, but also by every spoken or written element, which he was impregnated with.

However, leaving the factual (involuntary, or, imposed) exile aside, a huge field of voluntary exile also existed. Linked to the early Christian ascetic tradition in its various expression styles, another *facette* of literary exile took shape – metaphorical exile, encompassing the poetical and allegorical one, which often intertwine and are not so easily

¹¹⁹⁶ R. Broome, Pagans, rebels and Merovingians: otherness in the early Carolingian world, in: *The Resources of the Past in Early Middle Ages*, ed. C. Gantner/R. McKitterick/S. Meeder (Cambridge 2015) 155–171; R. Flierman, *Gens perfida or populus Christianus? Saxon (in)fidelity in Frankish historical writing*, in: *The Resources of the Past in Early Middle Ages*, ed. C. Gantner/R. McKitterick/S. Meeder (Cambridge 2015) 188–205; T. Barnwell, *Fragmented identities: otherness and authority in Adam of Bremen's History of the Archbishops of Hamburg-Bremen*, in: *The Resources of the Past in Early Middle Ages*, ed. C. Gantner/R. McKitterick/S. Meeder (Cambridge 2015) 206–224.

¹¹⁹⁷ This is an extensive topic, which exceeds the scope of the present thesis, and I plan to dedicate some future segment of my research to it. Cf. M. Esposito, *An Apocryphal Book of Enoch and Elias as a Possible Source of the Navigatio Brendani*, in: *Celtica*, V (1960) 196–206, re-ed. dans Wooding J. ed., *The Otherworld Voyage in Early Irish Literature: An Anthology of Criticism* (Dublin 2000) 27–41.

discernable. Heremitic exilic tradition, which emerged in the deserts, could, for example, be perfectly transposed to the medieval tradition of *navigatio*. Other typologies of exile include secular and sacred. Exile could also embrace the semantic fields of pilgrimage and monasticism, enveloping the form of the spiritual exile from the world, whereas the secular forms of exile encompassed political and social banishment. Exile could be observed in two senses: as a proscription, since heretics have frequently been exiled, or as a search for the divine realm on earth – bearing in mind the Scriptures and Augustine’s words, according to which we are all foreigners and pilgrims on earth¹¹⁹⁸: *...peregrini sumus*¹¹⁹⁹ *...omnis eruditus in sancta Ecclesia nosse debet unde cives simus, et ubi peregrinemur et peregrinationis nostrae causam esse peccatum*¹²⁰⁰.

Extreme ascetics were not welcome in every century of Christian history, as has also been the case of hermits and stylites in the 9th-century Byzantium¹²⁰¹.

Exul sum in mare: tradition of navigatio

The *navigatio* and the sea journey with all its “tempests” represents a particular form of the ascetic practice¹²⁰². Further West in the Christian *Oikoumene*, the Irish *Peregrini* navigated in search of the Otherworld, with the sea reflecting desert of the Byzantine ascetics¹²⁰³. The legend of St. Brendan brings account of a pious monk who abandoned his everyday life, in order to embark on a sea-journey. He later become abbot, and enjoyed the company of

¹¹⁹⁸ Augustine recurred numerous times to the terms *peregrinatio* and *peregrini* in his *De Civitate Dei*, cf: M. A. Claussen, ‘*Peregrinatio*’ and ‘*Peregrini*’ in Augustine’s ‘*City of God*’, in: *Traditio* 46 (1991) 33–75; cf. P. Brown, *Augustine of Hippo: A Biography* (Berkeley/Los Angeles 1975) 312–329, esp. 314.

¹¹⁹⁹ Augustine, *Sermo XX, de Verbis psalmi XXXVIII, Sancti Aurelii Augustiniani Opera Omnia, post Lovaniensium theologorum recensionem* 10 (ed. Monachorum ordinis Sancti Benedicti, Paris 1841) 908.

¹²⁰⁰ Cf. Augustine, *Enarrationes in Psalmos, 136:1* (ed. Migne, PL 37) 1033–1967, here 1761.

¹²⁰¹ C. Carozzi, *Le Voyage de l’âme dans l’Audela d’après la littérature latine v-xiii s.* (Roma 1994).

¹²⁰² S. I. Sobecki, *The Sea and Medieval English Literature* (Cambridge 2008) 21–22, 25–33, 34–40, 48–55; J. S. Mackley, *The Legend of St. Brendan: A Comparative Study of the Latin and Anglo-Norman Versions* (Leiden/Boston 2008).

¹²⁰³ Cf. Sobecki, *The Sea and Medieval English Literature* 21–22, 25–30, 34–40, 48–55.

numerous followers - at the aftermath of his voyage, which had allowed him to see the Otherworld: Paradise, but also Hell¹²⁰⁴.

The metaphor of the sea was also present in some apocryphal texts. In *Visio Pauli* – to mention only some – St. Paul finds himself on a ship, on his journey to Rome. God’s symbolism is hereby indirectly linked to the image of the sea¹²⁰⁵.

In Byzantium, even prose authors like Photius employ the well-known metaphor of the stormy sea, symbolising troubles of life – which apparently reached the prose world directly from its poetical and allegorical demeanor. In his 4th homily, Photius also employs the metaphor of the turbulent sea as the allusion to the strifes of life, the harbor of salvation and the heavenly glory: ...ἵνα τῆς προσδοκίας μὴ παρασφαλῶμεν, ἵνα σάλου καὶ κυμάτων καὶ ζάλης τῶν ἐν τῷ βίῳ κακῶν ὑπερاناσχόντες τῆς σωτηρίας ἡμῶν τῷ λιμένι ἐγκαθορμισθῶμεν καὶ τῆς ἐπουρανίου δόξης καταξιωθῶμεν, χάριτι καὶ φιλανθρωπία Χριστοῦ τοῦ ἀληθινοῦ θεοῦ ἡμῶν¹²⁰⁶.

The motif of a sea and sea-journey is present in poems of Theodore the Studite likewise. He compares life to navigation - *εὐπλους βίος*. Theodore opens the poem with his words addressed to the mortals - *Ἄνδρες βροτοί*, and incites them to flee the deceits of this world - *φύγωμεν ἐκ κόσμου πλάνου*. The only concern for a monk is, continues Theodore, to reach a tranquil harbor, where the burdens of pain will cease: *Φροντὶς γὰρ αὕτη τῷ μοναστῇ καὶ μόνον τυχεῖν ἐκείνου τοῦ γαλληνοῦ λιμένος, ἐν ᾧ πέπαιται τῶν λυπηρῶν πᾶς πόνος*¹²⁰⁷.

The Carolingian poets often wrote on the sea: *Exul...in mare sum*, Gottschalk of Orbais would say¹²⁰⁸. Gottschalk was considerably inspired and gifted for poetical expression as well¹²⁰⁹. The themes pertaining to the semantic field of exile are to be found among his verses

¹²⁰⁴ C. Sterckx, Saint Gengoulph, cocu et martyr: Lugus christianisé, in: Héritage indoeuropéen et survivances sélectives – Études offertes à Jacques Michel, ed. G. Nachtergaele, Ludus Magistralis, 22 (1991) 35–59; B. Sergent, Lug et Apollon, Ollodagos, supplément 3 (Bruxelles 1995).

¹²⁰⁵ C. Schmidt, Acta Pauli, nach dem Papyrus der Hamburger Staats- und Universitäts – Bibliothek (Hamburg 1936).

¹²⁰⁶ Mango, Homilies 110; Photius, Homilies, ed. Laourda 52, l. 15–22.

¹²⁰⁷ Cf. P. Speck ed., Theodoros Studites. Jamben, auf verschiedene Gegenstände (Berlin 1968) 116.

¹²⁰⁸ Cf. Gottschalk, Carmina (ed. L. Traube, MGH PLAC III, Berlin 1896) 723–738, here 731–732; N. Staubach, Zwischen Mythenallegorese und Idolatriekritik. Bischof Theodulf von Orléans und die heidnischen Götter, in: Menschen – Heros – Gott: Weltentwürfe und Lebensmodelle im Mythos der Vormoderne, ed. C. Schmitz/A. Bettenworth (Stuttgart 2009) 149–166; cf. Freeman, Theodulf d’Orléans and *Libri Carolini*.

¹²⁰⁹ M-L. Weber, Die Gedichte des Gottschalk von Orbais. Lateinische Sprache und Literatur des Mittelalters 27 (Frankfurt 1992); C. Lambot, Lettre inédite de Godescalc d’Orbais, Revue bénédictine 68 (1958) 40–51; Godescalci Carmina (ed. N. Fickermann, MGH PLAC VI, Weimar 1951) 86–106; N. Fickermann, Wiedererkannte Dichtungen Gottschalks, Revue bénédictine 44 (1932) 314–321; Weber, Gedichte; Gottschalk, Quo ne tu missus (ed. K. Strecker, MGH PLAC IV Berlin 1914) 934–936; Godescalci Carmina, ed. Traube; see also: P. Bourgain, Poésie lyrique latine du moyen âge (Paris 1989) 68–73; P. Godman ed., Poetry of the Carolingian Renaissance (London 1985) 228–246; P. von Moos, Gottschalks Gedicht O mi custos — eine confessio, Frühmittelalterliche

and reflect mainly the metaphorical exile, as observed on these examples from Gottschalk's poesy, written around 850: ...*Nos et in exilio esse doles / Ad patriamque redire mones*¹²¹⁰; ...*cum sim longe exul valde intra mare.....Exul ego discipule / Hoc in mare sum, domine*¹²¹¹; *Exul uti patriam, ceu terram naufragus imam*¹²¹².

The above-presented segments from Gottschalk's poetry, revealing the nature of his apprehension of the semantic field related to the allegorical exile, fall into a more comprehensive section of Gottschalk's poetical discourse. As already demonstrated, Gottschalk's poetry could be aligned to the repertoire of the Early Medieval exilic poetry¹²¹³. Beside Ovid and Virgil, the influence of Boethius upon Gottschalk's poetry would demand a more thorough analysis. Moreover, Gottschalk quotes Boethius, and his poetical section on power¹²¹⁴. Apparently, this only contributes to Gottschalk's interest in *potestas*, ranging from the worldly powers, to the heavenly ones, as presented in *hierarchia caelestis*. Boethius too, on the other hand, delved in questions encompassing predestination and free will¹²¹⁵; additionally, his poetical aspiration and inclination present in his *De Consolatione Philosophiae* might also be assigned to the conceptual "circle" of the poets who distilled their inspiration from the semantic field of exile¹²¹⁶. *Sophia*, representing personified Wisdom, has drawn both

Studien 4 (1970) 201–30, and 5 (1971) 317–358; B.Bischoff, Gottschalks Lied für den reichenauer Freund, in: *Mittelalterliche Studien: Ausgewählte Aufsätze zur Schriftkunde und Literaturgeschichte II* (1967) 26–34; O. Herding, *Über die Dichtungen Gottschalks von Fulda*, Festschrift Paul Kluckhohn und Hermann Schneider gewidmet zu ihrem 60.Geburtstag (Tübingen 1948); F. Rädle, Gottschalks Gedicht an seinen letzten Freund, in: *Scire litteras: Forschungen zum mittelalterlichen Geistesleben*, ed. S. Krämer/M. Bernhard, Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-historische Klasse Abhandlungen, Neue Folge 99 (München 1988) 315–325, here 316–319; Weber, *Gedichte* 135–188.

¹²¹⁰ Gottschalk, *Carmina*, ed. Traube 728.

¹²¹¹ Gottschalk, *Carmina*, ed. Traube 731–732.

¹²¹² Gottschalk, *Carmina*, ed. Traube 733–737, 734, l.22.

¹²¹³ Cf. my forthcoming article: *L'entremêlement des motifs préchrétiens et chrétiens*.

¹²¹⁴ Cf. Boethius Severinus, *De Consolatione Philosophiae* (ed. Migne, PL 63) 0579–0870A, here 744A, l. 3, m. 5, v. 1–10: *Qui se volet esse potentem, / animos domet ille feroces, / nec victa libidine colla / foedis summittat habenis. / Etenim licet Indica longe / tellus tua iura tremescat, / et serviat ultima Thyle; / tamen atras pellere curas, / miseraque fugare querelas / non posse, potentia non est*. Cf. Gottschalk, *Responsa Gotteschalci de diversis ab ipsomet alicui censori transmissa*, ed. Lambot, 146–158; translation in: Genke/Gumerlock, *Gottschalk and a Medieval Predestination Controversy* 98.

¹²¹⁵ Cf. H. Chadwick, *Boethius: The Consolation of Music, Logic, Theology and Philosophy* (Oxford 1990); V. Watts ed., *Boethius, The Consolation of Philosophy* (London 2000).

¹²¹⁶ Cf. my forthcoming article, *L'entremêlement des motifs préchrétiens*; Cf. Gottschalk, *Carmina*, *Ad Rathramnum*, ed. Traube 733–737, 734, v. 22; R. J. Hexter, *Ovid and Medieval Schooling* (München 1986) 91; P. Dronke, *Integumenta Virgilii*, in: *Lectures médiévales de Virgile*, ed. J.-Y. Tilliette (Roma 1985) 313–328; L. Holtz, *La redécouverte de Virgile aux VIIIème et IXème siècles d'après les manuscrits conservés*, in: *Lectures médiévales de Virgile*, ed. J.-Y. Tilliette (Roma 1985) 9–29; Jakobsen, *Il secolo IX*, 93 ; P. Dronke, *Die Lyrik des Mittelalters. Eine Einführung* (München 1977) 24.

Boethius's and Gottschalk's attention¹²¹⁷. The following impression ensues: it might well be that the conceptual clusters have circulated in the *repertoire* of some authors more than in others', and marked their opus to a certain extent: celestial spheres, *Sophia*, antique models. The recurrence to the *topoi* from the classical heritage has been more frequently attested in Carolingian poetry than in the prose works of those times¹²¹⁸. In this respect, it is also on the usage of and recurrence to the motif of *Sophia* that one can judge on the specific poetic inclination and temperament of a given author: interestingly, it is in Gottschalk's poems that the figure of *Sophia* is endowed with an added, "personified" value, contrary to Hrabanus's, for example.

Gottschalk's recurrence to the *topoi* related to the concept of allegorical exile lead to the widely-attested metaphor of *naufragium*. This potent image could be put in connection with the allegorical representation of a state as a ship, attested in Sedulius Scottus¹²¹⁹. Namely, Sedulius employs the designation *gubernator* for a ruler¹²²⁰. Gottschalk, too, employs the same metaphor for Christ: *...sis gubernator*¹²²¹. Analogously, the state was alluded to as a ship. This terminology represents the reminiscence of classical tradition, which was present in the Carolingian epoch, as exhaustively demonstrated by Anton Scharer¹²²². Bearing in mind the doublet king-God, the image of Christ as a helmsman is therein easily implied¹²²³. Moreover, the *Specula principum* in the 9th century, destined to the heirs of Charlemagne, aimed at reinforcing the dualistic principle and at underlining the role and reach of the worldly rulers

¹²¹⁷ Cf. my forthcoming article, L'entremêlement des motifs préchrétiens, as well as the recently-published one: Gottschalk of Orbais, Eberhard of Friuli and Alfred the Great; for the outlook of the more exhaustive topic regarding the differentiation between *sapientia divina* and *sapientia humana*, see: M. T. Gibson, Boethius in the Carolingian Schools, Transactions of the Royal Historical Society, 5th series, 32 (1982) 43–56; P. Dronke, Fabula. Explorations Into the Uses of Myth in Medieval Platonism (Leiden/Köln 1974) 116; Id., Verse with Prose, from Petronius to Dante (London 1994) 38–39, 50; cf. P. Courcelle, La Consolation de Philosophie dans la tradition littéraire (Paris 1967); M. I. Ros, Cultural Terms in King Alfred's Translation of the *Consolatio Philosophiae* (València 2003) 1, 4, 15–18, 33–37, 52.

¹²¹⁸ Cf. my forthcoming article, L'entremêlement des motifs préchrétiens et chrétiens.

¹²¹⁹ Cf. A. Scharer, Herrschaft und Repräsentation. Habilitationsschrift an der Geisteswissenschaftlichen Fakultät der Universität Wien (Wien 1998) 171–175; Sedulius Scottus, Liber de rectoribus Christianis, in: S. Hellmann ed., Sedulius Scottus, Quellen und Untersuchungen zur lateinischen Philologie des Mittelalters 1/1 (München 1906); R. W. Dyson ed., Sedulius Scottus, De Rectoribus Christianis (Woodbridge 2010).

¹²²⁰ Cf. Hellmann, Sedulius Scottus, c. 9, 47.

¹²²¹ Cf. Gottschalk, Carmina, Christe rex regum, 728.

¹²²² Cf. Scharer, Herrschaft und Repräsentation, 171–174; on the prevalent influence of Cicero in Sedulius's texts, but also in Einhard, see especially notes 335 and 336 on the page 171.

¹²²³ Cf. Scharer, Herrschaft und Repräsentation, 173, note 345; cf. H. Beumann, Zur Entwicklung transpersonaler Staatsvorstellungen, in: Das Königtum. Seine geistigen und rechtlichen Grundlagen, ed. Th. Mayer, Vorträge und Forschungen 3 (Konstanz 1956) 185–224, quoted from: Scharer, Herrschaft und Repräsentation, 174, note 346.

under the auspices of Church's authority¹²²⁴, due to the concept according to which the kings have been ordained by God.

If observed in this key, the picture of allegorical exile, which emanates from Gottschalk's verses – and which might well have been provoked by a factual exile - could be the one of an outcast, situated far from the security of the solid ground, or shipwrecked (*naufragus*). In this case, a figure of a ship serves as a metaphor for a state, which actually expelled him from its inner circles into the periphery. Another research segment, pointing to the more ancient Late Antique models which have certainly impacted the Carolingian thinkers and writers, and which would also be proven beneficial to the further research related to this thesis, is the one centered upon the influence of Martianus Capella and his *De nuptiis Philologiae et Mercurii*. The focus of this work is upon the cosmological harmony and hierarchy, which undoubtedly came to prominence in Carolingian times thanks to Eriugena's commentary¹²²⁵.

Eriugena represented one of those important mediators which helped circulate the earlier works: his *De divina praedestinatione*, which is an evaluation of Gottschalk's deterministic theology, assigned by Hincmar and Eriugena's translation of the texts of Pseudo-Dionysius Areopagita, including *De caelesti hierarchia* and *De ecclesiastica hierarchia*¹²²⁶.

According to the above-presented, the metaphorical language was highly important in depiction and self-portrayal of the dissenters. The other interesting and important observation to add is the one on different *modi* and types of artistic expression. For example, the poetical language of Gottschalk was different to that of Hrabanus, judging by the employed stylistic

¹²²⁴ Cf. Dyson, Sedulius Scottus 38; on more detailed information on the concept of secular and sacred authority in the Carolingian time, see: M. Wallace-Hadrill, *The Via Regia of the Carolingian Age*, in: *Trends in Medieval Political Thought*, ed. B. Smalley (New York 1965) 22–41.

¹²²⁵ On the influence of Martianus Capella in the Middle Ages, see: W. H. Stahl, *Martianus Capella and the Seven Liberal Arts: 1. The Quadrivium of Martianus Capella*. *Latin Tradition in the Mathematical Sciences* (New York 1971) 56–65; I. Ramelli, *Eriugena's Commentary on Martianus in the Framework of his Thought and the Philosophical Debate of his Time*, in: *Carolingian Scholarship and Martianus Capella. Ninth-Century Commentary Traditions on 'De nuptiis' in Context*, ed. M. Teeuwen/S. O'Sullivan (Turnhout 2011) 245–272; M. Godden/R. Jayatilaka, *Counting the Heads of the Hydra: The Development of the Early Medieval Commentary on Boethius's Consolation of Philosophy*, in: *Carolingian Scholarship and Martianus Capella. Ninth-Century Commentary Traditions on 'De nuptiis' in Context*, ed. M. Teeuwen/S. O'Sullivan (Turnhout 2011) 363–376.

¹²²⁶ For more detailed information on Eriugena's work, see: J. Marenbon, *John Scottus and Carolingian Theology: From the De praedestinatione, Its Background and Its Critiques, to Periphyseon*, in: *Charles the Bald: Court and Kingdom*, ed. M. T. Gibson/J. L. Nelson (Brookfield-VT 1990²) 303–325; Th. O'Loughlin, *Biblical Contradiction in the Periphyseon and the Development of Eriugena's Method*, in: *Iohannes Scottus Eriugena. The Bible and Hermeneutics. Proceedings of the 9th Colloquium of the SPES, Leuven and Louvan-la-Neuve, June 7-10 1995*, ed. G. Van Riel/C. Steel/J. McEvoy (Leuven 1996) 103–120.

means and figures. This can lead to our comprehension of Gottschalk as an author very much inclined to poetical expression¹²²⁷; or, as Gottschalk himself would put it: *Cum mihi gratuito data sunt subito metra dono celsithroni regis*¹²²⁸.

¹²²⁷ Cf. “Poetic images can sometimes show what is beyond the power of prose statements to express”, in: Dronke, *Verse with Prose* 43.

¹²²⁸ *Godescalci Carmina, Ad Rathramnum*, ed. Traube 733–737, 733, v. 15–16.

CONCLUSION

I have judged the most appropriate method in building up this thesis as here presented, in the exposed manner and structure. Hence, I have applied the following methodological and procedural path: firstly, I have presented the relevant problematic and texts preceding the 9th century (which predominantly constitute the first part of the thesis), and secondly, in the second segment of the thesis, I have analyzed more minutely, point per point, the sequences which were laid out in the first part. One of my objectives was to demonstrate that these sequences relevant to the 9th-century language of heresy in Byzantium, Rome and Francia had already been present in the preceding periods; the semantic fields analyzed in the second part of the thesis have therefore, in a way, only aligned with the already-existing and earlier patterns.

➤ **Metaphorical language**

The significance of the metaphorical “language of heresy” has been stressed throughout several segments of this thesis (especially in chapters I.3 and II.3), through a thorough scrutiny of, primarily, the metaphorical vocabulary and terminology employed by the early Christian and Early Medieval Greek and Latin authors (Irenaeus, Hippolytus, Augustine of Hippo, Isidore of Seville, Joseph, Epiphanius of Salamis, Justin the Martyr; Gottschalk of Orbais, Hincmar of Reims, Hrabanus Maurus, Amolo of Lyon, to mention only some). Namely, heresy was thus defined by means of metaphorical linguistic tools. The heretics and pagans are frequently related to the semantic fields of insanity/madness, contagious illness, serpent (which was the case in other scrutinized texts here presented). Apart from this relation between the semantic fields of heresy and insanity, another related point has been indicating the relationship between heresies and contagious illnesses, as has been observed on numerous occasions in the history of heresiologies (cf. chapters I.2 and I.3). The serpentine symbolic aligns to the afore-mentioned metaphors of illness/contagion.

On the importance of words in disseminating the desired message

Metaphorical language was highly important for the self-portrayal of the dissenters. The other interesting and important observation to add is on different *modi* and types of artistic expression. The example of Gottschalk has demonstrated the importance of language: his recurrence to metaphorical language, above all, in his poetry referring to allegorical exile; in his statement that correct language represents a basis for correct doctrine, and his insistence on the importance of grammar, too, in proving the soundness of his doctrinal views (on *Trina Deitas*); but also in the employment of specific terms for heretics (Hincmar in this particular case of *hirtus*). Gottschalk was a creator of particular messages and meanings he wished to convey, through his careful selection and arrangement of words. Generally, transposed to the larger picture, the key to the heretical representations lies in the language, terminology, expressions. Therefore, the self-portrayal of the heretics represents the protruding feature in the discourse knitted around religious dissent and heresy. The bottom line is, that dissenters, as well as the authorities that attacked them both agreed on the importance of correct words.

Photius, in his homily against the Iconoclasts, expressed his opinion of the importance of words. Namely, by embracing the importance of the Icons, Photius recurs to their symbolic importance in the absence of words - as if the depicted representations become the carriers of meaning in the absence of words - similarly to Walahfridus's interpretation (*pittura muta poema*). This attitude enhances the stance of the pivotal importance of words, which can be noticed the most when judging by their absence, when they are lacking. In this way, the authorities of East and West Christianity involved in some of the most prominent of the 9th-century theological debates (Photius and Walahfridus) took language as the criterion of defense, or, as a first line of defense against the enemies of the tradition.

On the importance of poetic language

In chapter II.13, the analysis of poetic language in relation to the section on allegorical exile, revealed connections with classical models, and has proven valuable, due to another type of insight it offers. Through the example of Gottschalk's poetry, the importance of poetic expression in general can be seen, but also in the relationships with the representations of allegorical exile in these particular cases and times.

His models and precursors have linked Gottschalk to the following circles: 1) to the group of the major Carolingian intellectuals (Heiric of Auxerre, Florus of Lyon, Walahfridus Strabo, but also to the descending line stretching from Theodulf of Orléans and reaching John Scottus Eriugena); 2) to the group of the “exilic” authors, upon which classical tradition (Ovid, Virgil, Boethius) left a decisive stamp (Walahfridus Strabo, Theodulf of Orléans, Ermold the Black); 3) to the Carolingian authors strongly inspired by the sapiential tradition; 4) to the authors who employed more or less accentuated knowledge of Greek in their Latin texts.

For instance, the poetical language of Gottschalk was different to that of Hrabanus, judging by the stylistic means and figures he employed. This can lead to our comprehension of Gottschalk as an author very much inclined to poetical expression¹²²⁹; or, as Gottschalk himself would put it: *Cum mihi gratuito data sunt subito metra dono celsithroni regis*¹²³⁰.

➤ Textual procedure of dissent

As elaborated in chapter I.3, the ascending sequence leading from “disobedient”, to “severed from God”, “foreign” (*alienus*), and “serpentine”, is to be found among images and metaphors in Irenaeus’s treatise against heresies, portraying sinners, falling out of union with God, which are equally the ones employed in describing heretics. According to textual examples from Irenaeus’s text, those who do not believe in God, do not obey him either; they are angels and sons of the Devil: *Qui Deo non credunt, ipsique non obediunt, angeli et filii diaboli sunt*¹²³¹. Namely, Irenaeus gradually constructs the scheme in an ascending line – commencing with disobedience and ending with alienating from God.

Namely, those who do not obey God, as Irenaeus states, become alien to him. They no longer belong to God, and they, serpentine offspring alike, injure others: *...qui non obediunt ei (Deo), abdicati ab eo, desierunt illi ejus esse. Unde nec haereditatem ejus percipere possunt, quemadmodum David ait: ‘Alienati sunt peccatores ab utero: ira eis secundum similitudinem serpentis’. Et propter hoc Dominus quod sciebat hominum esse progeniem, dixit sic progeniem viperarum, secundum similitudinem horum animalium in varietate ambulantes, et laedentes*

¹²²⁹ Cf. “Poetic images can sometimes show what is beyond the power of prose statements to express”, in: Dronke, *Verse with Prose* 43.

¹²³⁰ Gottschalk, *Carmina*, Ad Rathramnum, ed. Traube 733-737, 733, v. 15-16.

¹²³¹ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, IV, 41, 1115.

*reliquos*¹²³². In this manner, the sinners have also been portrayed as a „race of vipers“, as was also the case with the heretics. Those who perform the works of the Devil are his children, after having been cut off (through their sins) from God – and heretics fall within this category of sinners likewise: *Verum quando credunt, et subjecti esse Deo perseverant, et doctrinam ejus custodiunt, filii sunt Dei: cum autem abscesserint, et transgressi fuerint, diabolo ascribuntur principi, ei qui primo sibi, tunc et reliquis causa abscessionis sit factus*¹²³³.

➤ **Disobedience**

Furthermore, as discussed in chapter II.9, the two events in Byzantium and in Francia, related to the second marriage of Lothar II in Francia and Constantine VI in Byzantium, fall into the narratives of (dis)obedience. In these cases, they reflect disobedience to the ecclesiastical canons and Church tradition. The significant difference between the above-presented textual treatments of these two remarriage cases, is that unlike in Francia, the remarriage of Constantine VI in Byzantium has been labeled a heresy. On the other hand, judging by the textual analysis of the relevant source material, there is no hint indicating that the Pope labelled Lothar II a heretic. That also represents one of the important differences between the divorce cases in Francia and in Byzantium.

On the other hand, the similarity between these two cases of remarriage lies in the following: in both cases we witness the requests for the excommunication of the priests who presided over the second marital unions in question. The rulers who performed the second marriages against the canonical practices did not suffer consequences in person; however, the priests involved in these cases were excommunicated. May we, therefore, speak here of a sort of the “transferral” of sin of disobedience from the rulers who actually were the ones disobedient to the ecclesiastics who presided over the *secundae nuptiae*? The important observation is that in the accounts on the remarriages of the two rulers, the same pattern prevails: disobedience, reflected in these factual practices of remarriage leads to scandal and to the severance of the limbs of the church. Thus, the consequences of remarriage here presented in Byzantium, as well in Francia, trace a similar procedure as to that for the cases of heresy: they can lead to scandal and excommunication. The pivotal feature of both these case-studies of dissent lies in disobedience. Therefore, we can conclude that the phenomenon of disobedience *per se* is the

¹²³² Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, IV, 41, 1116, 3.

¹²³³ Irenaeus, *Contra Haereses*, IV, 41, 1117.

common denominator, either in the case of a heretic, or in the royal remarriage. Consequently, we may assume, that the cases of disobedience fall into the broader spectrum of the semantic field of dissent and constitute the “mental maps” of dissent. The consequently-obtained analogies in textual presentation of a heretic and disobedient ruler who was disrespectful to ecclesiastical canons convincingly demonstrate the interconnection and interrelation between political and theological discourses. Namely, the semantic field of dissent with its terminology (encompassing terms such as heresy, hierarchy, obedience, authority) can be ascribed to the highly political narratives.

➤ **Insiders versus outsiders**

The discourse on heretics and dissent falls into a wider *ensemble* of the discourse on “otherness”, which was interknitted throughout the entire thesis, and particularly, with the relationship between discourse and social control.

In the field of discourses, Foucault has developed the concept of a discourse of social control. In exposing his opinion on the semantic field of "otherness", Foucault dwelled upon the elaboration of such terms as “dividing practice”, “construction of alternatives”, and “cultural truths”.¹²³⁴

Apart from Foucault, several other studies have addressed the notion of “otherness” in the field of philosophy of science. Pierre Bourdieu spoke of the “social body”, and the embodied experience of social life, of *dialectic of the internalization of externality and the externalization of internality*, or, more simply, of incorporation and objectification,¹²³⁵ within the hierarchical organization and the differentiation of social fields.

¹²³⁴ Cf. Foucault, *Madness and Civilization*; cf. Mills, Michel Foucault 120–122; 116–119; Cartledge, *The Greeks*; Veyne, *L’inventaire des différences*.

¹²³⁵ Bourdieu, *Outline of a Theory of Practice* 72.

Closely connected to the concept of the socialized body of Bourdieu, is the re-actualized notion of *habitus*, rooted in Aristotle's notion of bodily *hexis*¹²³⁶, which has been transmitted by Thomas Aquinas, and employed by modern authors.¹²³⁷

Concerning medieval Europe, the approach to "otherness" was firstly given in respect to how the Christian church and its heralds (the leading theological authors of those times) related to heretics and heresies.¹²³⁸

Additionally, the ways in which the Carolingian authors described and differentiated the faithful from the unfaithful - within the underlying necessity to exercise the control over the social body - have been analyzed and presented in a recently-published collected volume on *The Resources of the Past in Early Middle Ages*, which deals, among others, of the concept of "otherness" in the Carolingian time.¹²³⁹

➤ Pagan versus heretic

Related in its conceptual core with the notion of "otherness", the new trajectory of research has been announced in chapter I.4. The border-lines in presenting "ento-" and "exo-" heresies, and paganism have undoubtedly been blurred, and not strictly delimited and defined. Nevertheless, one of the assumptions we can reach from the case-studies presented in this chapter of the thesis, is that there were not many unsurmountable differences in textual depictions and descriptions of pagans and heretics, and of the textual means therein employed. On the other hand, diverse heresies have also often been equated with each other or at least described in a closely analogous manner.

¹²³⁶ Original term in Greek is ἕξις, deriving from the verbe ἔχω, „to have“, and implying “stature”, “tenure”, “state”; the Latin morphology follows the Greek example with *habitus* directly deriving from the analogous verb *habere*.

¹²³⁷ On *hexis* and *habitus*, cf. Bourdieu, *Pascalian Meditations* 131–146; 208–237; but also: Carlisle, *The Question of Habit*.

¹²³⁸ Cf. Dunning, *Aliens and Sojourners*; De Jong, *Penitential State*; Bihrer/Limbeck/Schidt ed., *Exil, Fremdheit und Ausgrenzung im Mittelalter*.

¹²³⁹ Broome, *Pagans, rebels and Merovingians*; Flierman, *Gens perfida or populus Christianus?*; Barnwell, *Fragmented Identities*; Pohl, *Social Language, Identities and the Control of Discourse*.

One of the aims of this work has been to show that heretics and representatives of other faiths have often been treated similarly. The concept of the “other” and “otherness”, which presents one of the pivotal axes of this work, is more clearly observable in the examples of how Christians saw and understood those belonging to other religious groups. It is not so evident as in the cases when “main-stream” Christians contrasted themselves with the Christian heretics.

➤ **Outsiders and *alieni***

One of the most poignant textual examples confirming the spectrum and scale of the employment of the term *alieni* and its impact is to be seen in the letter of Pope Nicholas. Concerned with implementing the seed of *fides recta* among the newly-baptized Bulgars¹²⁴⁰, and hoping to prevent their potential return to paganism, the Pope advises them, referring to St. Paul’s epistle¹²⁴¹ and reminds them that those who are “outside”, do not represent St. Paul’s concern: *Nam eos, qui foris sunt, Deus iudicabit...De his, qui extra religionem nostram sunt, nihil ego iudico, sed eos Dei iudicio reservo, qui iudicaturus est omnem carnem*¹²⁴². Furthermore, the pagans and idolaters are designated by the Pope as those who fall outside of society and its hierarchy: *...per hoc veratiorem et sanctiorem suam sectam quam nostram existimet religionem*¹²⁴³. Additionally, the alliance with the pagans is not even considered to be desirable, since believers and non-believers have nothing in common¹²⁴⁴; *Inveniuntur autem nonnulli sanctorum et fidelium cum alienigenis et infidelibus pacta et amicitiae foedere contraxisse diversa*¹²⁴⁵. Returning to the afore-mentioned, these foreigners, or *alienigeni* (as in the letter of Michael II to Louis the Pious, on description of the rebellion of Thomas the Slav) might be semantically related to those who have fallen outside of society – referred to as the severed limbs – thus metaphorically alluding to them as severed members of society¹²⁴⁶.

After exposing relevant examples, the underlying semantic field of the “foreign” is highlighted as predominant in similar narratives, whether on pagans, or on the heretics. Consequently, the concept of “foreign” – *alienus* – was the bearer of meaning, or the key-word, in theological

¹²⁴⁰Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. E.Perels 582, l. 40.

¹²⁴¹ Cf. 1 Cor. 5:12,13.

¹²⁴² Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 583, l. 20-22.

¹²⁴³Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 583, l. 24-25.

¹²⁴⁴Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 594, l. 38-41.

¹²⁴⁵Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 595, l. 2-3.

¹²⁴⁶ Nicholas, Epistolae, Ep. 99, ed. Perels 576, l. 40-41.

positioning and self-representation in respect to other groups and/or individuals who were designed as “others”, pertaining to a much wider discourse, encompassing a broader religious and chronological frame.

➤ **Nuptial symbolic**

One of the key semantic fields, which could also be observed as contained within a wider concept of the body and its symbolism, is the one presented and analyzed in the II.10. It encompasses the nuptial symbolic and is related to the theme of adultery, of the Church as a Bride (*nubia*), of the limbs, and of the Prostitute (*meretrix*).

The Church was symbolically considered one body, whose head was Christ¹²⁴⁷. The secular and clerical spheres were not distinctly differentiated in 9th-century Francia; the orders were intended to function towards a cohesive goal. Therefore, the policy was designed according to the Church – Christ was the head of the body of believers, just as the emperor (Louis the Pious in this particular case) was the head of different orders of the polity, which represented the limbs of society.

In opposition to those numerous heresies is the one and only doctrine of Truth, and the holy maid which represents Christ’s Church, as Epiphanius puts it: *...μία δὲ μετὰ τὰς ὀγδοήκοντα» ἡ τῆς ἀληθείας βᾶσις ἅμα καὶ διδασκαλία καὶ σωτήριος πραγματεία καὶ Χριστοῦ «νύμφη ἁγία» ἐκκλησία...*¹²⁴⁸ Thus the Church is portrayed as a *fiancée* of Christ; while on the other hand, the heresies represent concubines; this metaphor comes from the Song of Songs, where the concubines amount in number to eighty¹²⁴⁹.

➤ **Adultery**

All of these semantic fields, analyzed throughout the thesis, constitute and knit the broad sphere of body and bodily symbolism: nuptial symbolic, limbs of the body (*membra*), the adulterer (forger) of the word of God (*adulterator*), disobedience, the process of the

¹²⁴⁷ Cf. Noble, Images, Iconoclasm, and the Carolingians 358.

¹²⁴⁸ Panarion, Prooemium I, I, 1-4, ed. Holl (1015) 155, 6 – 156, 5.

¹²⁴⁹ Vulgata, Song of Songs, 6: 8-9.

embodiment of sin through disease, plague, contagion – as an embodiment of sinfulness and thus disobedience. Every sequence enlisted here leads to the construction of the body: constructing and solidifying the body of believers. This is the aim of the 9th-century (theological) semantic fields as exposed here, when we take a generalized look. All of the presented procedures are put in place in the aim of repressing sin and sinners, by means of the ligature – that is, obedience.

The concept of adulterating the word of God is present in the New Testament as well: *Non enim sumus sicut plurimi, adulterantes verbum Dei, sed ex sinceritate, sed sicut ex Deo, coram Deo, in Christo loquimur*¹²⁵⁰ - “For we are not as many, which “adulterate” the word of God: but as of sincerity, but as of God, in the sight of God speak we in Christ”. Furthermore, it spread in the authors’ narratives presented here, and is connected to the nuptial symbolic.

➤ **Bodily symbolic: the *Leitmotiv* in the discourse of heresy**

The bodily symbolic pertains to wider universe of the textual procedures focusing upon heresies and religious dissent, as presented and elaborated in this thesis, but not only: it also encompasses the image of “others” who do not make part of it.

The powerful image of the body and its limbs symbolizes also unity and/or disunity of the state, church and individual on the micro- and a macro- level. King and bishop, God as the king of kings, all of these represent a long line of ancient motifs, inherent to Christianity, but other belief systems as well (for example, as shown, the metaphor of the measurements of God is likewise to be found in Jewish mysticism, amongst other sources). As Frank Riess observes, the description of the change from Christianity to Judaism was, in the account of Bodo’s conversion, connected to changes in the bodily and outer image – with the aim of portraying Bodo as alienated¹²⁵¹. This event is brought into connection with sins having befallen the empire, similarly to the interpretation of the rebellion of Thomas the Slav, in the letter of Michael II to Louis the Pious¹²⁵². Thus is the thread linking the (declined) body of the state to the altered bodily image of Bodo brought forward¹²⁵³.

¹²⁵⁰ Cf. 2. Cor. 2:17, King James Version.

¹²⁵¹ Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus 137.

¹²⁵² Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus 137.

¹²⁵³ Riess, From Aachen to Al-Andalus 137-138.

One of the research objectives presented in this thesis is to demonstrate the interconnectedness of several stages, sequences and textual procedures, which constitute a whole: one of the base motifs is that of a body, which contains several smaller ones.

According to Augustine, one must choose between the limbs of Christ or the limbs of a prostitute, since one cannot participate in both. He, who partakes of Christ's flesh and his blood, remains in him. Therefore, those who prefer the limbs of the prostitute, are not limbs of Christ, unless they repent: *Ut enim alia taceam, non possunt simul esse et membra Christi et membra meretricis (1 Cor. 6:15). Denique ipse dicit: Qui manducat carnem meam et bibit sanguinem meum, in me manet, et ego in eo (John 6:51).... Non itaque manent in Christo, qui non sunt membra eius. Non sunt autem membra Christi, qui se faciunt membra meretricis, nisi malum illud paenitendo esse destiterint et ad hoc bonum reconciliatione redierint*¹²⁵⁴.

The Eucharist represents the eternal food and drink and the community constituted by the head and its limbs: *...aeternam societatem capitis membrorumque suorum significat...*¹²⁵⁵ Whoever participates in it, will represent a limb of Christ the head, in the heavenly kingdom: *Quicumque enim ejus particeps fuerit, id est, Christo capiti membrum associatus fuerit in regno coelesti*¹²⁵⁶...

In other words, it is in the sacraments that all the limbs become fused and attached to the head. We become transformed in the body of Christ, adds Hrabanus, if we live in piety and obedience: *In virtute enim sacramenti omnia membra capiti suo conjuncta et coadunata...nos in corpus Christi convertimur dum oboedienter et pie vivimus*¹²⁵⁷. The principle of obedience is shown as a ligature, attaching the limbs of the body of the Church together in unity.

Namely, according to Foucault and the discourses, the change always appears firstly in one segment, from which it then expands to all other segments. This can be applied to one of the conclusions of this thesis, too, especially bearing in mind the afore-said regarding the concept of disobedience. Hence, for example, in the chapter on the bodily symbolic, it is through symbols which are highly laden with meanings of the body and the semantic field of terms designating flow, such as *effudit, infudit* – that the metaphor of the propagation of sin through

¹²⁵⁴ Augustine, *De Civitate Dei*, XXI, ed. Migne 0742-0743; *Ibid.*, ed. Dombart/Kalb 795-797.

¹²⁵⁵ Hrabanus, *De Clericorum Institutione*, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, *De sacramento corporis* 317AB; cf. Hrabanus, *De Institutione clericorum: Über die Unterweisung der Geistlichen I*, ed. D. Zimpel (Turnhout 2006).

¹²⁵⁶ Hrabanus, *De Clericorum Institutione*, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, *De sacramento corporis* 317D.

¹²⁵⁷ Hrabanus, *De Clericorum Institutione*, ed. Migne, l. 1, c. 31, *De sacramento corporis*, 318A.

the image of contagion is disseminated. Hereby we attest to the notion of illness being transposed from bodily imagery to the embodiment of sin, plastically depicted through the image of bodily contagion and illness.

Embodiment of sin

Smoothly aligning to the notion of the socialized body, as developed in Bourdieu, disease (including madness) can thus be seen as related to sin (heresy as well), which thus becomes transposed on the corporeal level and described with the terms related to the semantic field of contagion. Thus, sin becomes observable and palpable. The medicine is to sever the diseased limb.

- **Excommunication as severance from the body:** Eucharist as a *pars pro toto* in textual treatment of the bodily symbolism

The Eucharistic communion provides an exact reflection, as a *pars pro toto*, of the more amply understood communion between the limbs of the body of the Church, and between the head of the Church and its believers. The severance of the limbs of the body of the Church could have led to exile, but also to excommunication from the Eucharist. Excommunication represented a frequent punishment in the Early Middle Ages – both in the West, as in the East. Adherence to heresies thus implied excommunication. The schism resulted in the same measures¹²⁵⁸. In this realm we approach other issues which were not directly relevant to the heresies – the practice of second marriage, for example. Nevertheless, almost every sin had excommunication as a consequence¹²⁵⁹.

- **Allegorical exile**

The topic of Medieval exile was a prominent one in Medieval Latin, Greek and vernacular texts¹²⁶⁰. Nevertheless, this theme remains insufficiently explored - especially in relation to the Early Medieval exile. Exile in the Middle Ages might be observed as

¹²⁵⁸ Theodore the Studite, *Epistolae*, II, Ep. 215, ed. Migne 1260A, 1648; *Ibid.*, II, Ep. 219, 1665.

¹²⁵⁹ Pargoire, *Église byzantine* 344-347.

¹²⁶⁰ E. M. C. van Houts ed., *Exile in the Middle Ages* (Turnhout 2004).

voluntary/involuntary, factual/metaphysical. This exhaustive topic has been opened and elaborated to some extent in the last chapter on exile (II.13).

Exile represented a recurrent punishment for heretics, already attested in the Theodosian Code. In the Early Middle Ages, involuntary exile frequently occurred on political grounds – as, for example, during the reign of Louis the Pious. Public penance was applied by Louis the Pious in the form of monastic exile, as well¹²⁶¹. Furthermore, many political opponents were banished: for example Wala of Corbie, who suffered exile twice¹²⁶². In Byzantium, Theodore the Studite, including other monks from the Studite monastery, were sent to exile; Photius as well, some decades later.

Besides, another form of voluntary exile existed as well – the allegorical exile. Contrary to the involuntary exile, the concept of voluntary exile was not at all times seen as erroneous. For example, according to Augustine, and his concept of *Peregrinatio*, not every exile is seen as a consequence of offenses to God. Exile could be observed as a proscription, since heretics have frequently been exiled, or as a search for the divine realm on earth – according to the Scriptures and Augustine’s words, accentuating that we are all foreigners and pilgrims on earth¹²⁶³: *...peregrini sumus*¹²⁶⁴ *...omnis eruditus in sancta Ecclesia nosse debet unde cives simus, et ubi peregrinemur et peregrinationis nostrae causam esse peccatum*¹²⁶⁵. Namely, it is important to stress the importance of allegorical exile for tracing the process of mental mapping.

¹²⁶¹ De Jong, Penitential State 232–234; Id., Power and humility in Carolingian society; Id., What was *public* about public penance? Paenitentia publica and justice in the Carolingian world, in: *La giustizia nell’alto medioevo* (secolo ix-xi), *Settimane* 44 (1997) 863–904; Id., Transformations of Penance.

¹²⁶² On Adalhard’s exile: Cf. *Vita Adalhardi*, Paschasius Radbertus, according to De Jong, Penitential State 127, note 56 and 58.

¹²⁶³ Augustine recurred numerous times to the terms *peregrinatio* and *peregrini* in his *De Civitate Dei*, cf: M. A. Claussen, ‘*Peregrinatio*’ and ‘*Peregrini*’ in Augustine’s ‘*City of God*’, in: *Traditio* 46 (1991) 33–75; cf. P. Brown, *Augustine of Hippo: A Biography* (Berkeley/Los Angeles 1975) 312–329, esp. 314.

¹²⁶⁴ Augustine, *Sermo XX*, de Verbis psalmi XXXVIII, *Sancti Aurelii Augustiniani Opera Omnia*, post Lovaniensium theologorum recensionem 10 (ed. Monachorum ordinis Sancti Benedicti, Paris 1841) 908.

¹²⁶⁵ Cf. Augustine, *Enarrationes in Psalmos*, 136:1 (ed. Migne, PL 37) 1033–1967, here 1761.

➤ Mediators

The question of mediators imposes itself automatically as an important one throughout this entire thesis. It is difficult to imagine the circulation, exchange and contact between East and West without the authors who served as bridges, linking the two.

Important figures involved in the 9th-century contacts between East and West, who could be understood as mediators and carriers of exchange include: Michael II, Louis the Pious, Charles the Bald, Pope Leo III, Pope Nicholas I, Theodore the Studite, Photius, Anastasius the Librarian, Eriugena, but also Gottschalk, who helped circulate his ideas during his Balkan journey, and was probably imbued by traditions other than the Frankish one. The situation which allowed intensive contacts between Byzantium, Francia and Rome was the conversion of the Bulgars¹²⁶⁶, enhanced even more by their oscillation on doctrinal grounds between Francia and Byzantium. The land of the Bulgars is seen, in this case, as a central meeting point for the interference between and intertwining of two empires¹²⁶⁷.

Additionally, translators and interpreters played significant roles as mediators, who thereby helped to circulate important ideas from East to West and vice versa.

It has already been observed that Eriugena attempted, in effect, to pacify East and West on the *Filioque* issue (which was debated in his *Periphyseon*) – during the years marked by this controversy creating a hiatus between the Latin and Greek dogmatic concepts and practices. Namely, Eriugena acted accordingly by means of his translation of Maximus the Confessor who opted for a “diplomatic” formula according to which the Holy Spirit proceeded from the Father “through the Son”. Furthermore, Eriugena could be seen as a mediator between East and West due to his translations of Maximus the Confessor and the *Corpus Dionysiacum*. Thus, Eriugena represented one of those important mediators who helped to circulate the earlier works.

And Maximus’s writings could in reality represent a common denominator for both Eriugena and Anastasius the Librarian¹²⁶⁸. Additionally, both of these scholars were mediators *par excellence* and Ecumenists. We could thus speak also of direct and indirect mediators; the above-enumerated would be those who vividly supported the exchange between East and West, but also throughout different regions of Europe. On the other hand, conceptual, indirect

¹²⁶⁶ Cf. Dvornik, *Slaves, Byzance et Rome* 184-195.

¹²⁶⁷ Cf. D. Stratoudaki White, *Patriarch Photios* 30.

¹²⁶⁸ On Eriugena’s translation of Maximus’s writings, cf. Geanakoplos, *Maximos the Confessor* 153-156, 160.

mediators would include authors whose works stimulated contacts between the two realms – such as Augustine in the first place, but also Maximus the Confessor, Pseudo-Dionysius, or even Boethius, through the impact his *De Consolatione Philosophiae* had on Frankish and Anglo-Saxon writers of the 9th-century.

➤ **The role of tradition and danger of innovation**

The role of tradition, conveyed through textual authorities, is clearly observable in all of the 9th-century narratives focused on divergent religious thought. The recurrence to textual tradition and its importance therefore underlines and represents the main thread in all the sequences presented here, acting as an engine, propelling the theological debates and reinforcing the much-needed stronghold. For example, as has already been shown, the Iconodules often ascribed their adversaries, the Iconoclasts, to the ranks of earlier heresies: the aim was to show that they, as the orthodox, had tradition on their side, as well as to enhance their point of view according to which the Iconoclasts were guilty of innovation¹²⁶⁹. Analogously, in his first *Antirrheticos*, Theodore the Studite refers to earlier heresies when condemning iconoclasm¹²⁷⁰.

One of the research goals of this thesis is to pinpoint the ascending chronological line and interconnectedness of the earlier forms of religious dissent with the later ones, since heresies and divergences in religious concepts and dogmas which appeared in the 9th century frequently represented the continuation of earlier threads, or, they have often been referred to as the survival of earlier heretical doctrines.

It is exactly in this line – of presenting preceding heresies as being connected to the posterior ones – that the 9th-century authors who supported the officially-accepted Christian dogma saw the imminent danger of innovation and novelties brought into tradition, deemed to be noxious for the cultivation of tradition, transmitted from the earliest Christian theologians and the Church Fathers, in spite of the inherent paradox: abhorring novelties while stating that the newly-arisen heresies were connected with the survival of the earlier ones.

¹²⁶⁹ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the world* 142.

¹²⁷⁰ Cf. Parry, *Depicting the world* 142-144.

Consequently, the innovations and novelties have been seen as a danger to the traditions of the fathers. For example, during the theological disputes between Byzantines and the Latins pertaining to the *Filioque* controversy in the mid-860's, the Greek accusations were particularly ponderous, since they pertained to the old tradition of the Fathers, according to Pope Nicholas: *...ridiculum est enim et satis abominabile dedecus, ut...eas traditiones, quas antiquitus a patribus nostris suscepimus, pro libitu semper errantium infringere patiamur*¹²⁷¹.

Towards a different concept of heresy?

The question of different concepts of heresy and religious dissent has imposed itself throughout the entire thesis. One of the most prominent examples of this difference may be observed during the Iconoclast strife, and especially upon the reactions to the sway it had in Francia. This debate which arose in respect to icon worship and which stirred up Byzantium was labelled a heresy in the East, "as they put it", according to Walahfridus: *Huius rei questio apud Graecos saepe tantas contentiones excitavit, ut sub Gregorio papa iuniore Constantinus imperator*¹²⁷² *apud Constantinopolim omnes imagines deposuerit et sub Gregorio tertio Romae synodus sit facta contra supradictam, ut dixerunt, heresim, in qua firmatum est, ut sanctorum imagines secundum priscum catholicae ecclesiae usum restituerentur*¹²⁷³. Henceforth, we can only hypothesize on the extent to which these two Christian world-views were similar or different; nevertheless, judging by the examples shown above in this thesis, there are some hints which may serve as a more or less subtle indication of the unequally nuanced view of heresy and religious dissent in Byzantium and Francia, Constantinople and Rome.

As has been shown in the chapter II.7, the Byzantine Iconoclast controversy was described by Walahfridus as *ipsa querela Graecorum*. Namely, this controversy reached Francia during the reign of Louis the Pious and was discussed at the Council of Paris held in 825. The echo of Iconoclasm in the Francia was reflected by a conflict arisen between Claudius of Turin and Jonas of Orléans, among others¹²⁷⁴.

¹²⁷¹Nicholas, *Epistolae*, Ep. 100, ed. Perels 604, l. 14-16.

¹²⁷²Constantinus V (741-775).

¹²⁷³The Synod held in Rome, in 731; cf. Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause, notes 79-82, 482, l. 34-38; 483, l. 1.

¹²⁷⁴Walahfridus, *Libellus*, ed. Boretius/Krause 483, l. 1-9.

Additionally, as has been mentioned above and more in detail in chapter II.9, the Moechian controversy was perceived as heresy in the Greek texts, differently to the situation in the Latin West, provoked by the remarriage of Lothar II. In other words, the divorce case of Constantine VI was in Byzantium labelled a heresy, unlike the divorce of Lothar II in Francia and Rome. Apart from the glimpses insufficiently dealt with in this thesis due to its scope and content, the topic of different approaches/concepts of heresy in Byzantium, Rome and Francia is a significantly complex one, and would nevertheless meritoriously deserve a more detailed analysis.

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- CCCM Corpus Christianorum, Continuatio Mediaevalis
- CCL CCSL
- CCSL Corpus Christianorum, Series Latina (Turnhout 1953 sq.)
- CSEL Corpus Scriptorum Ecclesiasticorum Latinorum (Vienna 1866 sq.)
- EME Early Medieval Europe
- GCS Die griechischen christlichen Schriftsteller der ersten drei Jahrhunderte (Leipzig/Berlin 1897 sq.)
- MGH Capit. Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Capitularia regum Francorum, Legum Sectio II: I, ed. A. Boretius (Hannover 1883); II, ed. id./ V. Krause (Hannover 1890)
- MGH Conc. Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Concilia: II, 1 (742-817), ed. A. Werminghoff (Hannover/Leipzig 1906); II, 2, (819-842), ed. A. Werminghoff (Hannover/Leipzig 1908); III, ed. W. Hartmann (Hannover 1984); IV, ed. W. Hartmann (Hannover 1998)
- MGH Epp. Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Epistolae (in Quart): V, ed. E. Dümmler (Berlin 1928); VI, ed. E. Dümmler (Berlin 1925); VIII, ed. E. Perels (Berlin 1939)
- MGH PLAC Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Poetae Latini Aevi Carolini: I, ed. E. Dümmler (Berlin 1881); II, ed. id. (Berlin 1884); III, ed. L. Traube (Berlin 1896); IV, ed. K. Strecker (Berlin 1914); VI, ed. K. Strecker (Weimar 1951)
- MGH SS Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Scriptores in Folio
- MGH SSRG Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Scriptores rerum Germanicarum in usum scholarum separatim editi
- PG Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Graeca (ed. J.-P. Migne, Paris 1857-1866)
- PL Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Latina (ed. J.-P. Migne, Paris 1844-1855)
- SC Sources chrétiennes (ed. De Lubac, H./J. Daniélou, Paris 1941 sq.)

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ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Die Sprache des religiösen Dissenses: Eine Komparatistische Perspektive (die Fränkische und Byzantinische Autoren des 9. Jh)

Die Dissertation fokussiert die Fragestellungen von religiösem Dissens mithilfe eines komparatistischen Ansatzes auf der Basis von ausgewählten Texten griechischer und lateinischer christlicher Autoren des 9. Jahrhunderts. Im Zentrum der Untersuchung stehen dabei die Versuche der Autoren, religiöse Konflikte im Allgemeinen und Häresien im Besonderen durch Definitionen und Terminologie zu strukturieren und in verschiedene metaphorische Narrative einzuordnen. Diese Terminologie und die metaphorische Sprache werden analysiert und in ihre jeweiligen historischen Kontexte einzubetten versucht. Dadurch lassen sich in einem weiteren Abschnitt der Arbeit Zusammenhänge, gegenseitige Einflüsse, aber auch Unterschiede, Fehlinterpretationen und Missverständnisse zwischen den untersuchten Texten bzw. religiösen Diskursen in Byzanz, Rom und im fränkischen Imperium herausfiltern. Dabei werden vor allem die theologischen Kontroversen, wie etwa der Bilderstreit, die *Filioque*-Debatte oder der Prädestinationsstreit analysiert.

Der zweite Teil der Dissertation konzentriert sich auf die spezifischen Erzählungen religiöser Konflikte und untersucht mit einer semantischen Umfeldanalyse die vielfältigen Sprachpartikel und Wahrnehmungsformen von Häresie anhand zentraler Begriffe wie *hierarchia*, *oboedientia*, *disoboediantia*, *heresis*, *schisma*, *pestilentia*, *epidemia* etc. Diese semantischen Einheiten werden systematisch und detailliert analysiert, um schließlich ein deskriptives Modell religiösen Dissens zu erhalten und Mechanismen häretischer Narrative herauszuarbeiten, wie etwa Häresien als eine kontinuierliche Geschichte zu interpretieren, die neue Abweichungen als bloße Erneuerung älterer und als eine permanente Gefahr für die Einheit der Kirche formulieren. Insgesamt zielt die Dissertation auf eine Neubewertung religiöser Konflikte im 9. Jahrhundert als ein diskursives Phänomen, das mithilfe metaphorischer Sprache soziale Ordnung durchsetzen versuchte.

SUMMARY

The Language of Religious Dissent: Comparative Perspective (9th-Century Frankish and Byzantine Authors)

This thesis focuses upon the questions of religious dissent in the selected 9th-century Greek and Latin texts, by positioning them in a comparative approach. In the first section of the thesis, the basis for the study has been laid, established upon the writings of the early Christian writers and Church Fathers. This includes the early heresiologies, and the attempt of structuring the narrative of heresies according to the language of religious dissent, encompassing specific terminology and its metaphorical import.

The aim of here-presented structure of the thesis was designed in order to demonstrate the interconnectedness of the selected and most representative 9th-century Frankish and Byzantine narratives knitted around the semantic field of religious dissent, on the examples related to the pivotal theological controversies of the period – the Iconoclast, *Filioque* and Predestination controversy in the first place. The chapters in the second section of the thesis trace a sort of a “procedure”, here aligned in an ascending line and sequence, thus demonstrating a development pattern in the narratives threaded around the topics related to the semantic field of religious dissent.

The second section of the thesis is focused upon the particularly selected narratives of religious dissent and language of heresy in the 9th-century Greek and Latin texts. The topics related to the attempts to define religious dissent in the 9th-century Byzantium and Francia are discussed and contained in the second part of the thesis, including a more thorough examination of the sequences, which constitute the construction of narratives of religious dissent, through presenting them in a new manner and within the frame of the metaphorical language of heresy. These include the description models of religious dissent through the concepts of reviving of the old heresies, innovation, scandal, the unity symbolism and the severance from the body of Church.

